

D.3.3 - ANALYSES OF AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TRAINING PROGRAMMES ON GENDER-SENSITIVE ENERGY TRANSITION

WP3 – Development of Concrete Solutions to Advance Women in Energy Transition

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the Deliverable and Linkages across Work Packages

Deliverable D3.3 occupies a central role within Work Package 3 (WP3) of the gEneSys project, which examines how to strengthen women's roles as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and change leaders in the energy transition. The aim of this deliverable is twofold: first, to synthesise the evidence generated across multiple national and institutional contexts; and second, to translate these insights into practical pathways for institutional and training changes.

The deliverable is strongly interlinked with other Work Packages. It draws on the conceptual frameworks of WP1, which developed the theoretical lens of gendered sociotechnical systems, and applies the findings from WP3 on the gendered content of curricula and educational resources. At the same time, D3.3 anticipates the needs of WP4, where recommendations and pilot training programmes will be designed, and connects with WP6 to ensure dissemination and integration of gender-responsive strategies into European and international policy dialogues. In this way, D3.3 acts as a nodal point: turning conceptual analysis (WP1, WP2) into empirical validation and stakeholder visions (WP3), which are then translated into training and policy impact (WP4, WP5).

1.1. Methods used

The work underpinning D3.3 combines qualitative, participatory, and comparative approaches to generate robust evidence across national and institutional settings. The methodology consisted of:

- National Focus Group Interviews (FGIs) conducted in Germany, Italy, the UK, and Poland, engaging students (STEM and SSH), lecturers, and structural staff to reflect on gendered educational and career pathways in the energy field. These FGIs employed storytelling, visual mapping, and timeline exercises to reveal barriers and enablers.
- Participatory Theory of Change (ToC) Workshops in Poland, Germany, and the UK. These workshops moved beyond diagnosis to co-creation, articulating concrete pathways for institutional transformation, from recruitment and mentorship strategies in universities to corporate diversity strategies in energy companies.

Table 1. Focus group interviews and workshops

Type	Country	Participants

FGIs	Germany	Lecturers & structural personnel (9); Students in Technical Communication (37 total across 2 groups)
FGIs	Italy	University lecturers (7); SSH students (8); STEM students (5)
FGIs	UK	Postgraduate STEM & interdisciplinary students (11); Lecturers & academics (online group)
FGIs	Poland	STEM male students (10), STEM female students (8), STEM mix-gender students (7), SSH mix-gender students (8), Academic teachers in SSH and STEM degrees (4 + 2 individual interviews)
Workshop (ToC)	Poland	6 participants (business, public administration, academia)
Workshop (ToC)	Germany (Berlin)	15 participants from large Berlin energy company (network, sales, HR, admin)
Workshop (ToC)	UK	6 academic women in HE (lecturers, researchers)

Cross-analysis between FGIs and workshops, is ensuring that findings are not seen as isolated national phenomena but understood in relation to wider European patterns and challenges. This step highlighted both shared challenges (structural stereotypes, lack of female role models, impermeable career structures) and context-specific nuances (e.g. strong grassroots interest in gender equity in Poland; corporate diversity frameworks in Germany; integration of justice and inclusion into academic research in the UK; challenges in STEM enrolment in Italy). This methodological triangulation guarantees that the deliverable captures both individual trajectories (students, women in academia, professionals) and structural conditions (university curricula, corporate policies, cultural norms).

1.2. Scope of the Deliverable

The scope of D3.3 is to provide an integrated analysis of how women can be more effectively supported in education, research, and professional careers in the energy transition. Specifically, the deliverable focuses on:

- Training programmes in Higher Education: identifying practices and reforms that foster inclusive curricula, mentoring schemes, and equitable recruitment processes.
- Professional development and leadership pathways: highlighting the importance of entrepreneurial and innovation-oriented training that enables women to become agents of change in the energy sector.
- Institutional and corporate reforms: examining how universities and companies can structurally embed diversity and equality into governance, recruitment, and promotion systems.

- Design of enabling environments: linking educational, social, and corporate settings to support women's transition from education to professional leadership roles.

By integrating the evidence from four countries and different institutional contexts, D3.3 provides a comparative lens on the systemic barriers and enabling factors shaping women's participation in the energy transition. The findings are not only descriptive but also prescriptive: they lay the foundation for actionable training modules, policy recommendations, and best practices to be further developed and scaled in WP4 and WP5.

2. CROSS-COUNTRY COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

2.1. Institutional and policy context: energy and gender in higher education and workplace in Germany, Italy, United Kingdom and Poland

Germany

Germany is considered to be one of the 'pace-setters' with regard to its' energy and climate strategies. Decarbonisation is coordinated by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and the Climate Action with an economy-wide and sectoral emissions targets defined through the German Climate Act and the policies and measures needed to meet these targets specified through the 'Climate Action Programme 2030' (Lindberg, Wettestad 2024). The country aims to meet 65% emission reduction target by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, achieve climate neutrality by 2045 and a negative emission balance starting from 2050, it has phased out nuclear power as of 2022 (Renn & Marshall, 2016; Sgarciu et al. 2024).

Germany combines strong federal R&D support with robust vocational education systems and tertiary education gaining significance over the last decades. The vocational education and training model underpinning the energy workforce remains however male-dominated in technical fields (Haasler 2020). Similarly, women comprise only 27.7 percent of STEM tertiary education graduates—the lowest rate among the four countries examined (European Commission, 2024). As a consequence, gender gaps persist in employment: women represent 26 percent of the energy workforce and only 15.5 percent of executives (European Parliament 2019; EUWES 2023). In renewables, representation rises to 32 percent, suggesting that new energy sectors offer more inclusive opportunities (Proka, 2024).

To promote equality in employment, the German government has established a policy framework and introduced a set of measures. An Act for more equal participation in the private sector entered into force in 2015. It contains a gender quota of 30 % for the supervisory boards in stock-listed and equally co-determined companies. Since 2022 these companies are obliged to appoint at least one woman to the executive board if the executive board consists of more than three people. Part of Germany's strategy to work against bias and unequal opportunities is the German Federal Equality Act. It requires federal authorities to draw up a new gender equality plan every four years, including measures to improve the compatibility of professional obligations with family or care responsibilities. The current equality plan stipulates that equal numbers of women and men at all management levels are to be reached by 2025. To continuously increase the number of women holding management positions, the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action sets quotas to be reached by each department and monitors the achievement of its targets by internally publishing statistics. The specific measures implemented

to foster gender equality in the energy sector include a mentoring programme with the Global Women's Network for the Energy Transition (GWNET) and other partners aiming at promoting female energy experts and expanding their participation in bilateral energy partnerships and dialogues. (BMWK 2022)

Italy

Italy's Ministry of Ecological Transition oversees the National Energy and Climate Plan, prioritising renewable expansion, energy efficiency, and reduced energy dependence (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2024). Recent projections estimate that full implementation could generate 1.4 million new jobs and €1.2 trillion in investment (Pastore & de Santoli, 2025).

In higher education Italy's female share among tertiary graduates is high overall, and female participation in some STEM tertiary programmes is increasing (Italy is among EU countries with notable shares of female STEM graduates). Women comprise around 40 percent of STEM tertiary education graduates (European Commission 2024). However, gender segregation across fields and limited progression into senior academic and industrial roles persist.

Italy's labour market exhibits one of the EU's largest gender gaps. Female labour-force participation remains below the European average, and women occupy a limited share of energy-sector leadership positions. In 2022, women comprised 26 % of workers in the Italian energy sector (EIGE 2023). They also held about 30% of full-time jobs in the renewables sector (IRENA 2019). At the same time, however, 'Energy and Resources' is one of the sectors that have reached the highest percentages of women on the boards of directors in Italy. With rapid advancement in the space of a few years, it went from 29,3 percent in 2018 to 45 percent in 2023 (Deloitte 2024). In national ministries dealing with the environment and climate change, 39 % of the senior administrators employed were women (EIGE 2023).

To promote equality in employment, Italy introduced "Gender Equality Certification", to certify the effective implementation of policies and measures aiming to reduce gender gaps in public and private companies with more than 50 employees. To foster gender equality in managerial positions, Italy has passed a law requiring 33 % of positions on boards of directors in publicly listed companies to be filled with women (BMWK 2022).

United Kingdom

The UK's energy transition is governed by the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ), supported by a complex network of regulators and agencies (GOV.UK, 2024). The UK frames energy policy around energy security, affordability and reaching net-zero, with an emphasis on large-scale renewables, grid investment and decarbonisation programmes The Climate Change Act (2008) established legally binding emissions reduction targets—amended to net-zero by 2050—while the Contract for Difference (CfD)

mechanism has successfully mobilised investment in renewables. Offshore wind represents a key comparative advantage, positioning the UK as a global leader in renewable capacity. (UKRI 2021).

Initially showing very low female engagement levels in some fields (in 2014, for example only 3.8 % of engineering apprentices were female), the UK in recent years has been making significant progress in STEM education (BMWK 2022). In 2019 women comprised around 40% of STEM tertiary education graduates (European Commission 2024). Despite progress, the UK energy sector faces critical skills shortages. Gender disparities are particularly acute: In 2024 women accounted for 28% the overall energy & utility workforce in the UK (PfW n.d.). Studies attribute this imbalance to male-dominated networks, limited mentoring, and workplace cultures that deter female retention (PfW 2024).

Women remain also underrepresented in the leadership positions within the energy sector. In 2024 in the top 80 UK energy companies 29% of all board members (executive and nonexecutive) were women and only 16% of executive directors on the board were women. Only three companies (4%) had a female chair of the board, and only four companies (5%) had a female CEO (PfW 2024)

The UK energy industry has established industry-led diversity and inclusion initiatives (e.g., POWERful Women, Energy UK's EDI commitments) and publishes sector progress reports, but these show continuing under-representation of women particularly at senior and technical grades; sector reports and advocacy groups stress that cultural and recruitment practices, not only pipeline issues, sustain disparities. Meanwhile, UK universities have increased investment in equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) infrastructure, and national EDI policy in higher education is well developed (PfW 2024). Among specific measures a joint mentoring programme between France and the UK supporting gender diversity in the nuclear sector has been recently introduced (BMWK 2022).

Poland

Poland's energy transition remains constrained by its historical dependence on coal, which still accounted for 80 percent of electricity generation in 2021 (Swora, 2023). The National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) and Energy Policy of Poland 2040 set a target of 21–23 percent renewable energy by 2030 (Bluszcz et al., 2023). Poland's transition is shaped by legacy dependence on coal, active state intervention in energy prices and a politically salient energy security agenda; these political and institutional constraints condition the speed and modalities of decarbonisation and the shape of new labour demand in the sector (Ministry of Climate and Environment 2021).

Female educational attainment remains high: Poland is among the top EU countries with 41.5 percent of female STEM graduates. However, a reverse tendency has been observed at least since 2016, when women comprised 44%

of STEM graduates (European Commission, 2023). Employment in coal mining is declining in Poland due to EU climate regulations, while renewables—especially offshore wind and solar—are generating new opportunities (Bluszcz et al. 2023). However, the just transition strategy has yet to integrate gender equality objectives systematically (Swora 2023). According to the “Gender Equality Index 2023” report (EIGE 2023a), women accounted for about 14 % of employment in the energy sector in Poland in 2022. Moreover, the OECD (2022) review of Poland’s energy policy highlights that while Poland’s gender pay gap in the energy sector is relatively low (~5.1 %), women are still concentrated in lower-paid, non-decision-making roles.

Women also remain underrepresented in energy leadership. While the specific data for the energy sector are missing, in 2023 in the whole economy only 26% of board seats were held by women and 23% of board chairs were women (Deloitte 2024).

While the Polish government adopted a multi-annual programme to promote equal treatment (including gender equality) across sectors with the 2022-2030 focus on labour, education, awareness building, and data collection/research (EIGE 2024), this framework does not provide any specific activities in the energy sector. Gender equality and inclusion are not yet systematically incorporated in Polish energy-sector policymaking (IEA 2022). However, isolated initiatives aiming at fostering gender equality in the energy sector can be detected. These include for example the Women’s Energy in Transition – Polish Edition program addressed to female students and graduates of energy-related fields. It awards the best diploma theses devoted to energy transformation defended by female students and graduates of Polish universities (Dalkia Polska 2024). With a target to enhance female leadership representation up to 25% through initiatives like the Female Talent Development Program and the Global Women’s Network, Hitachi Energy Poland supports women’s professional growth and encourages their ascension to leadership roles (Hitachi Energy 2024).

2.2. Different perspectives on the gender equality opportunities and barriers

The three reports from workshops in the UK, Germany, and Poland, together with four reports from FGIs conducted in Germany, Italy, the UK, and Poland, each shed light on women’s participation in the energy sector. However, they emerge from different contexts and thus reflect distinct perspectives on the barriers and opportunities for progress. The workshops, inspired by the Theory of Change, adopted a future-oriented and transformative approach, focusing on systemic changes needed to enhance women’s participation in higher education and the energy labour market. The FGIs, in contrast, provided a broader exploration of participants’ experiences at various stages of their education and professional careers. While the TOC workshops identified

structural and cultural barriers, the FGI reports offered more granular insights, including direct quotations and detailed reflections from students and academics.

The Italian report examines gender issues through the lens of educational choices, career pathways, organizational culture, and teaching practices in the energy sector, particularly within STEM and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines. It highlights persistent gender disparities, stereotypes, and the obstacles women face, while also identifying potential enablers and recommendations for change. Gender inequalities in education and career choices are shown to be rooted in cultural norms, family expectations, and early socialization processes that shape perceptions of academic disciplines. These influences contribute to women's underrepresentation in STEM and their overrepresentation in SSH. Engineering fields are often perceived as masculine, and some academics attribute women's limited participation to individual choice rather than structural bias. At the same time, energy-related engineering is sometimes framed as gender-neutral, which obscures subtle yet persistent forms of discrimination.

University communication and recruitment strategies often fail to challenge stereotypes effectively, with promotional materials sometimes reinforcing traditional gender roles. Family influence—particularly in more conservative contexts—also shapes educational aspirations, limiting women's engagement with technical and leadership pathways. Many female STEM students describe entering male-dominated fields as a personal challenge, yet report encountering sexist attitudes, microaggressions, and doubts about their competence. SSH students, meanwhile, note that the social dimensions of sustainability and energy transition are undervalued, discouraging women from pursuing these fields.

In professional contexts, the energy sector remains male-dominated, with hiring and promotion practices often framed in terms of meritocracy that overlook structural inequities. Organizational cultures can disadvantage women through unequal caregiving responsibilities and gender-blind practices. Persistent issues such as the gender pay gap and work environments designed around male norms further reinforce exclusion. Gender perspectives are rarely integrated into STEM curricula, which maintain a narrow technical focus and neglect human and social factors. Although SSH programs show greater awareness of gender issues, approaches often depend on individual lecturers and lack intersectional depth. The report calls for more inclusive communication, early gender-awareness education, the promotion of female role models, and stronger integration of gender perspectives across disciplines and institutions.

In the UK, the discussion is rooted in higher education, portraying universities as spaces where women continue to struggle for representation, particularly in

engineering and senior academic roles. Many of the barriers identified decades ago remain unresolved, reflecting entrenched academic traditions and male-dominated technical cultures. Retention emerges as a central challenge, as women often leave academia for industry, raising questions about how institutions can transform their cultures to sustain women's engagement in research and teaching in the energy field.

The German reports, by contrast, focus on the corporate environment of a large Berlin-based energy company. Rather than emphasizing academia, they examine labour market realities, demographic change, and the company's strategic response to skill shortages. The underrepresentation of women in technical roles is acknowledged as a major issue, framed within a broader commitment to equal opportunities and a goal of achieving gender balance in leadership and the workforce by 2030. The reports also note that gender interacts with intergenerational dynamics, as age discrimination and collaboration across generations pose additional challenges. Compared with the UK's academic focus, the German case highlights how corporate diversity strategies intersect with economic imperatives.

The Polish reports bridge educational and professional perspectives, envisioning systemic transformation in which women's energy literacy is enhanced, young women are encouraged to pursue STEM, and female experts become visible leaders in the sector. Unlike the UK's academic focus or Germany's corporate approach, the Polish perspective situates gender inequality within broader cultural perceptions of energy as a "male domain." It identifies a lack of gender perspective in education and a persistent glass ceiling in professional settings. The emphasis is on shifting social attitudes while simultaneously building pathways for women from classrooms to leadership positions.

Taken together, these reports illustrate how national contexts shape both diagnosis and vision. They provide an empirical foundation enriched with participants' voices, specific examples, and methodological detail that complement the broader insights from the TOC workshops. All four countries face significant challenges regarding gender equality in STEM and the energy sector, yet each reveals distinctive nuances.

Across Germany, Italy, the UK, and Poland, early socialization and persistent stereotypes shape perceptions of technical and social disciplines, often discouraging girls from pursuing engineering or energy-related studies. The lack of visible role models and the burden of family responsibilities further limit women's career trajectories. While Germany and Italy emphasize structural and cultural barriers, the UK discourse focuses on institutional accountability and inclusive recruitment, and Poland highlights women's resilience in navigating male-dominated environments. The debate over meritocracy versus equity measures is particularly visible in Italy, where gender quotas

remain contested, whereas Germany's discussion centres on the weak implementation of equality initiatives. In both the UK and Poland, gender perspectives are sporadically integrated into curricula, depending largely on individual educators. Despite shared challenges—rooted in stereotypes, work-life imbalances, and underrepresentation—national narratives diverge: Italy and Poland reflect stronger cultural conditioning, Germany underscores systemic inertia, and the UK promotes policy-driven approaches to gender equity.

Ultimately, what unites these perspectives is the recognition that women's participation is essential to the future of the energy sector. However, strategies to achieve this participation must be tailored to the specific cultural, institutional, and structural realities of each country—whether through curriculum reform, corporate initiatives, or broader societal transformation.

2.3. Shared barriers and places to be improved

The experiences of women in energy-related academia and industry across Germany, Poland, Italy and the United Kingdom reveal persistent gender inequalities at structural, cultural, and institutional level. While all four countries confront deeply embedded barriers, the nature of these challenges vary according to national contexts and the gender equality discourse within each setting. Rather than examining each country separately, this summary explores key thematic barriers, illustrating how they emerge across different national contexts.

Socio-cultural Norms and Gender Stereotypes

Gendered socialisation processes, beginning in childhood, continue to shape women's educational and professional choices across all countries. Participants described how early stereotypes define technical and STEM-related subjects as "male" domains, discouraging girls from pursuing them and fostering internalised doubt about their competence. In Italy, the impact of gendered roles are visible in secondary education, where boys more often enrol in technical, traditionally male dominated, schools, which facilitates their admission to STEM university programmes, while in the UK a similar pattern was discussed in the context of energy-related postgraduate studies which are typically preceded with completion of degree in comparable fields.

Career Structures and Employment Precarity

Across all four countries, participants noted that the energy sector – both in academia and in public or private companies – remains strongly male-dominated, which prevents women from perceiving this sector as suitable for them. Participants referred to initiatives aimed at increasing the participation of women in technical roles (e.g. Girls' Day, mentoring scheme), admitting that the progress has been modest. The scarcity of women is explained by their experiences of sexism and microaggression as well as persistent stereotypes –

such as the perception of STEM as unsuitable for women – which continue to undermine confidence, contribute to pay gaps, reinforced biased recruitment and promotion practices.

Participants highlighted that career models based on uninterrupted trajectories are incompatible with care giving responsibilities and non-linear life courses, resulting in systemic disadvantage for women. The “care penalty” limits women’s career progression: insufficient childcare support and limited state policies push women toward caregiving and fails to engage men in domestic responsibilities. In the UK, precarious short-term contracts for scholars in academia further reinforce instability and hinder long-term planning.

Disciplinary Cultures

In all countries, STEM disciplines were described as influenced by male-oriented traditions that define excellence through competitiveness, technical dominance, and individual achievement. Such norms marginalise collaborative, feminist, or interdisciplinary approaches and contribute to women’s isolation through weak mentoring and networking opportunities.

Institutional Practices and Tokenistic Interventions

Participants across all countries were sceptical of tokenistic equality measures - such as quotas - implemented without deeper institutional reform. In the UK, such interventions are seen as insufficient to address entrenched hierarchies and biased evaluation criteria. In Poland, gendered divisions of labour within institutions are evident: women are frequently tasked with administrative or reporting duties, while men are assigned technical work, limiting women’s opportunities to develop specialised expertise. In both Poland and the UK, women reported being disproportionately assigned pastoral and organisational roles, often justified through gendered assumptions of care. These responsibilities detract from research output, which is more highly valued in promotion, thereby reinforcing inequality. In contrast, German participants focused primarily on the lack of structured pathways for women to enter technical careers, rather than on institutional cultures themselves.

Information Gaps

Participants in Poland and Italy identified how young people lack knowledge about available opportunities in the energy sector, preventing girls and women from envisioning themselves in energy-related careers and perpetuating gender segregation. This information gap is even bigger in case of students from social science, who rarely come across that the intersection of energy and social science can be an option for their career paths. In the UK participants similarly highlighted how the lack of critical mass in certain disciplines intensifies professional isolation, reducing access to networks, mentorship, and information about career opportunities. German discussions, whilst acknowledging limited awareness among young women about

technical careers, focused primarily on outreach solutions rather than examining systemic information asymmetries.

Intersectionality

Intersectional discrimination was most explicitly discussed in the UK, where women from racial and ethnic minorities face overlapping forms of exclusion not addressed by conventional gender equality measures. Participants observed that gender policies lacking intersectional awareness may inadvertently reinforce other hierarchies of privilege. Some also reflected on competitive dynamics among women in senior positions, underscoring the complexity of power relations in male-dominated environments. These phenomena illustrate various factors, such as the insufficient solidarity and support, to encourage girls to pursue their academic and professional expectation.

Leadership and Systemic Change

Across all contexts, the importance of committed leadership emerged as a prerequisite for systemic change. UK participants stressed that women continue to face obstacles in both accessing and exercising leadership roles. Transformative change, they argued, requires leaders willing to redistribute power, endorse inclusive practices, and value diverse forms of expertise. Polish participants emphasised that institutional measures must be reinforced by state-level policy reform, as isolated initiatives cannot dismantle structural barriers. German participants expressed confidence in existing mechanisms such as mentorship programmes, though they acknowledged that their impact remains limited without a broader cultural shift.

2.4. Inspiring practices

Across three workshops, several inspiring good practices emerged that contribute to the discussion on how women can be more fully included, supported, and empowered in the energy sector. These practices span structural, cultural, and individual interventions, each offering a glimpse into how the sector might be reshaped into a more equitable and innovative space.

One of the most powerful practices identified was the deliberate creation of new, inclusive disciplinary and professional spaces. For example, the development of Systems Transition Engineering was presented as a "clean slate" discipline, consciously designed to attract and retain diverse participants. By weaving together feminist principles, systems thinking, and indigenous perspectives, this approach challenges traditional, narrow paradigms and values plural knowledge systems. Alongside this, inclusive networks were seen as critical to counteract the isolation often experienced by women. These networks provided more than professional linkages—they fostered cultures of

empathy, sustained collaboration, and visible pathways into leadership, rejecting exclusionary traditions and valuing diverse contributions.

A second cluster of practices centered on mentorship and support systems. Structured mentorship programs offered early-career researchers practical guidance on navigating academia, building research portfolios, and advancing professionally. Yet mentorship was not viewed as a one-way process. Instead, it was reframed as a reciprocal exchange: while younger participants gained support and clarity, senior academics also benefited from fresh perspectives and renewed purpose. It seems that this practice can be successfully incorporated into the business environment, but also into the grassroots organisation promoting female leadership. Role models, particularly women in leadership, were highlighted as essential for demonstrating that progression is both possible and supported.

The workshops also underlined the importance of embedding feminist-informed principles into institutional practices. Change at this level required systemic integration—developing curricula that explicitly foreground gender equity and intersectionality, reforming recruitment and promotion processes, and ensuring transparent, fair workload allocation. Leaders were called upon to engage actively through structured dialogues, accountability mechanisms, and equity-focused training. Success itself was redefined: rather than relying only on traditional markers such as publications and grant income, collaborative, community-engaged, and interdisciplinary work was recognized as equally valuable.

Another vital set of practices involved proactive outreach and engagement. Several participants emphasized the importance of reaching girls and young women early, through stronger school–university partnerships and direct outreach by female professionals. Initiatives such as Girls' Day, where women working in technical fields share their stories and experiences, were celebrated as powerful tools for inspiring the next generation. Public campaigns amplifying the contributions of women in energy also helped shift narratives, making women's presence more visible and normalized.

The issue of bias and discrimination was not overlooked. Practical strategies to mitigate unconscious bias included anonymized recruitment processes, gender-awareness training for teachers and leaders, and the consistent use of inclusive language in job advertisements and communications. These measures sought to dismantle structural and cultural barriers that often go unnoticed but significantly affect women's participation and progression.

Finally, the workshops highlighted the importance of cross-sectoral collaboration as a good practice. Embedding gender equity in the energy transition requires partnerships not only within academia but also across industry, government, and civil society. Long-term collaborations with professional bodies and community organizations were identified as vital for turning inclusive principles into real-world strategies. By presenting a unified

voice in policy consultations and technical committees, women's networks and allies could exert greater influence over decision-making processes.

Taken together, these practices illustrate a vision of the energy sector where women are not only included but are central to shaping its future. From creating entirely new academic spaces to reforming institutional policies, from mentorship to public outreach, these initiatives collectively point toward an energy transition that is more equitable, innovative, and responsive to society's needs.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

The transition to sustainable energy systems is not only a technological shift but also a profound social transformation. This process Ensuring that this process is inclusive and gender-equitable is essential to achieving innovation, social justice, and long-term sustainability. It requires new forms of expertise, collaboration, and governance that transcend traditional boundaries between disciplines, sectors, and social roles. Yet, despite increasing awareness of gender equality as a key dimension of sustainability, women remain underrepresented in the energy sector—both in technical and decision-making positions. Evidence gathered through focus group interviews and workshops conducted in Italy, the United Kingdom, Germany, and Poland highlights that barriers to gender equality persist across education, research, and employment in energy-related fields. Persistent gender stereotypes, structural barriers in education and employment, and insufficient policy support continue to constrain women’s participation. Participants highlighted the need for systemic change – through public policy, education, institutional practices, and workplace cultures – to build an energy sector that fully integrates women’s knowledge, leadership, and innovation potential. Based on their insights and suggestions, the recommendations for different stakeholders have been proposed. They are addressed to policy makers, universities and research institutions and companies.

3.2. Recommendations for policy makers

The insights from these focus groups and workshops converge on the view that gender equality in the energy transition cannot be achieved through isolated initiatives. It requires coordinated policy interventions across local, national, and EU levels, targeting both structural reforms and cultural transformation. The recommendations below outline the key actions that policy makers should consider to promote women’s inclusion and leadership in energy systems and energy transformation. National and regional policy makers must address the foundations—education, workplace standards, and community awareness – while EU institutions create the frameworks, funding, and data infrastructure that support the efforts towards equality as a shared European priority.

3.1.1 National and regional policy makers

Reforming Education and Training Pathways

The foundation for gender equality in the energy transition lies in education. Focus group participants in all countries stressed the importance of tackling

gender stereotypes early in life and creating pathways that encourage girls to pursue energy-related subjects. This includes interventions at multiple stages:

- Early exposure to STEM and energy topics should begin in primary and lower-secondary education, where perceptions of gendered careers often take shape.
- Energy themes introduced at different levels of education should be discussed through inclusive narratives that link technology to real-world sustainability challenges, rather than abstract technical problems.
- Teacher training and curriculum reform are crucial to ensure that unconscious biases are not reproduced in classroom interactions. Teachers should be equipped with tools to promote gender-sensitive learning and to highlight women's contributions to science, engineering, and social innovation.
- Career guidance services must be strengthened and modernised. As noted particularly in the Polish and Italian focus groups, counselling is often delivered too late and by poorly prepared staff. Guidance should begin earlier and emphasize both technical and interdisciplinary aspects of energy studies.
- Mentorship and internship programs targeted at girls and young women should be expanded. Partnerships between schools, universities, and energy companies can help bridge the gap between education and employment, offering real-world experience and professional networks.
- Interdisciplinary and socially relevant education is key. Students—particularly women—often find energy studies more engaging when linked to social impact, ethics, and sustainability. Integrating social sciences and humanities perspectives into STEM curricula can therefore enhance inclusivity and relevance.

These interventions require coordination between ministries of education, regional authorities, and energy agencies. Incentive schemes—such as scholarships for women entering energy-related programmes or grants for inclusive teaching innovations—can further accelerate progress.

Ensuring Equality and Inclusion in the Workplace

Once women enter the energy workforce, they often encounter institutional and cultural barriers that limit their progression. National and regional policy makers play a critical role in setting and enforcing equality standards:

- Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) frameworks should be mandatory across the public and private energy sectors. These frameworks must

include clear procedures for reporting discrimination, ensuring pay transparency, and guaranteeing equal access to promotion.

- Gender-balanced recruitment and promotion panels should become a regulatory norm. Evidence from the UK focus groups showed that all-male panels reproduce unconscious bias and discourage female candidates.
- Transparent pay scales and career pathways should be required for all energy organisations receiving public funding. Pay equity audits can be a condition for licensing or procurement eligibility.
- Flexible and family-friendly policies—including generous parental leave for both parents, flexible hours, and teleworking—are vital to retain women in the workforce. Participants across multiple countries highlighted the incompatibility between rigid work structures and care responsibilities as a major barrier to advancement.
- Gender quotas may be introduced or encouraged, particularly in leadership and board positions within state-owned or regulated energy enterprises. Evidence from the focus groups suggests that voluntary quotas can accelerate cultural change when implemented sensitively and accompanied by mentoring and professional development support.
- Inclusive communication practices should be normalised in all professional contexts. In Italy, for example, participants noted the significance of using feminine professional titles (“ingegnera”, “dottoressa”) to symbolically and linguistically affirm women’s expertise.

National labour inspectorates and equality bodies should be empowered to monitor compliance with these standards, while regional development agencies can incentivise good practice through grants and recognition programmes.

Promoting Visibility, Representation, and Cultural Change

Cultural change is essential to dismantling the deep-seated perceptions that energy and engineering are “male” domains. National campaigns and regional initiatives can play a transformative role:

- Highlighting female role models in energy science, innovation, and policy through media campaigns, exhibitions, and awards can challenge stereotypes and inspire young women. Examples mentioned in Italy—such as astronaut Samantha Cristoforetti—illustrate the powerful effect of visible representation.
- Public engagement initiatives—such as “Girls’ Days,” school outreach programmes, and open days at universities and energy companies—

should be institutionalised and professionally supported to ensure consistent quality and impact.

- Community and family engagement is equally important. Awareness-raising efforts targeting parents and teachers can counteract unconscious discouragement of girls' technical ambitions.
- Regional “gender equality hubs” could coordinate mentorship networks, training sessions, and peer-support groups, particularly in regions with low female participation in energy sectors.

Changing social norms requires sustained effort. Policy makers should invest in communication strategies that redefine energy careers as inclusive, creative, and socially valuable, moving away from narrow technical imagery and towards a vision of collaborative innovation.

Building Institutional Accountability and Knowledge

Institutional accountability mechanisms are critical to ensuring that commitments translate into action:

- Ministries and agencies should be required to collect and publish gender-disaggregated data on employment, pay, and promotion in the energy sector.
- Gender impact assessments should accompany all major energy and infrastructure projects at the regional and national levels.
- Governments should support research on gender and energy transitions, funding interdisciplinary studies that evaluate policy effectiveness and identify persistent barriers.
- National equality bodies could establish certification systems or “equality labels” for organisations that demonstrate exemplary gender inclusion practices, thereby promoting competition for excellence.

3.1.2 EU-level policy makers

Mainstreaming Gender in EU Energy and Climate Frameworks

At the European level, gender equality should be embedded as a cross-cutting principle within all energy transition strategies:

- The European Green Deal, REPowerEU, and Fit for 55 packages should include explicit gender equality objectives relating to such areas as energy access, workforce and entrepreneurship development, access to leadership positions and gender-responsive policy-making.
- EU-funded research and innovation programmes, including Horizon Europe and the Innovation Fund, should require gender-balanced consortia and gender impact assessments as part of proposal evaluation.
- Gender mainstreaming guidelines should be developed to support Member States in integrating equality objectives into their National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs).
- The European Commission could issue periodic progress reports on gender equality in the energy transition, identifying gaps and promoting good practices.
- This mainstreaming approach would ensure that gender equality is not treated as a separate social objective but as a core component of effective, sustainable energy policy.

Strengthening Data, Collaboration, and Knowledge Exchange

To enable coordinated action, the EU should invest in data collection, capacity building, and cross-border collaboration:

- Establish an EU Observatory on Gender in Energy and Climate to harmonise data collection, monitor trends, and disseminate evidence-based recommendations.
- Support pan-European mentorship and mobility programmes for women in energy research, governance, and entrepreneurship, modelled on Erasmus+ or Marie Curie initiatives.
- Fund transdisciplinary research networks that bridge technical, social, and policy domains, promoting critical and intersectional approaches to energy transition studies.
- Facilitate exchange of best practices among Member States through thematic platforms, workshops, and policy peer reviews.

Supporting Institutional Transformation and Leadership Development

EU-level policies can catalyse cultural and institutional change by setting incentives for inclusive governance:

- Provide structural funds and technical assistance to help universities and research centres embed gender equality in their governance, hiring, and promotion practices.
- Develop EU training programmes for gender-sensitive energy policy making, aimed at public administrators, regulators, and private-sector leaders.
- Promote the creation of new, transdisciplinary fields—such as Systems Transition Engineering—that model inclusive collaboration, systems thinking, and social responsiveness.
- Encourage cross-sector partnerships involving academia, industry, and civil society to implement equality-focused pilot projects with measurable outcomes.

Such initiatives would institutionalise the cultural change envisioned in the workshops, where collaboration, empathy, and inclusivity were identified as core drivers of transformation.

Promoting Inclusive Innovation and Investment

Economic instruments are powerful levers for change. The EU should ensure that financial support mechanisms actively promote women's participation and leadership:

- Prioritise projects led by women or gender-balanced teams in funding programmes.
- Expand ethical microloan and investment schemes for women entrepreneurs developing sustainable energy solutions, especially in underrepresented regions.
- Integrate gender equality indicators into the evaluation of EU-funded energy projects, linking disbursement to measurable progress in diversity and inclusion.
- Encourage public-private partnerships that invest in inclusive technology design, digitalisation, and automation that reduce gendered barriers in physically demanding energy jobs.

By aligning financial incentives with equality goals, the EU can stimulate both innovation and social justice within the energy transition.

3.3. Recommendations for Universities & Research Institutes

Education is one of the most important areas where the nexus of gender and energy can be fostered.

Addressing Structural Barriers and Early Education

- Collaborate with schools to organise science clubs, field visits, and mentorship activities to cultivate early interest in energy topics.
- Promote female representation in non-academic spaces - such as youth media, events directed to young people - to provide visible professional role models.

Embed gender dimension in teaching

- Review curriculum: Integrate gender perspectives into course objectives, learning outcomes, and assessment criteria.
- Encourage interdisciplinary teaching through collaboration between technical, environmental, and social science departments to offer interdisciplinary modules that explore the intersection of gender, energy, and sustainability.
- Incorporate examples of female leaders, innovators, and researchers into course materials to challenge stereotypes and provide visible role models for students.
- Develop assignments, simulations, and group projects that require students to apply gender-sensitive approaches in energy system design, policy evaluation, or technology innovation.
- Establish mechanisms to monitor and evaluate how gender aspects are represented in teaching content and student outcomes, ensuring that progress translates into tangible institutional change.

Attracting and Retaining Women in Energy-Related Academia

- Promote women's entry and retention in energy-related disciplines through mentorship, advocacy, and inclusive leadership.
- Create spaces for networking and collaboration where women and allies can connect, share ideas, and build professional communities.
- Organise outreach and recruitment initiatives (e.g., "Women in Energy" events, talks by female leaders, and targeted scholarships) to inspire women to pursue studies and research in the sector.
- Use positive female role models in teaching materials, public campaigns, and outreach (including schools and popular media) to challenge stereotypes and normalise women's presence in technical fields.
- Implement gender awareness and anti-bias training for all staff, including senior management and supervisors, to foster inclusive practices and eliminate microaggressions.
- Establish clear procedures and confidential reporting channels for cases of discrimination, harassment, or gender-based misconduct.
- Energy themes should be introduced through inclusive narratives that link technology to real-world sustainability challenges, rather than abstract technical problems

Supporting Women's Academic Progression

- Promote mentoring and sponsorship programmes that guide women through career stages and foster academic confidence.
- Offer flexible and family-friendly working conditions, including remote work and adaptable promotion timelines, to accommodate diverse life courses.
- Introduce continuous assessment and teamwork-based evaluation models to support collaboration and recognise varied strengths.
- Encourage international collaboration and mobility opportunities for women researchers.

Strengthening Institutional and Cultural Support

- Integrate inclusivity into institutional missions, values, and policies, ensuring equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) are core institutional priorities.
- Implement gender-sensitive recruitment, evaluation, and promotion procedures with transparent criteria and fair pay structures.
- Provide leadership training, mentorship frameworks, and professional networks specifically for women in academia.
- Normalise flexible working hours, parental leave, and hybrid arrangements across academic departments.
- Broaden definitions of academic excellence to value mentorship, interdisciplinary collaboration, and social impact alongside publications and grant success.

Expanding Impact Beyond Academia

- Strengthen partnerships with industry, government, and civil society to promote inclusive energy transition practices.
- Support women-led start-ups and innovation projects through grants, incubators, and entrepreneurship programmes.
- Build women's networks (including online communities) to exchange knowledge, mentorship, and advocacy across academic and professional sectors.

3.4. Recommendations for Industry & Entrepreneurs

The comparative evidence from FGIs and Theory of Change workshops across different contexts demonstrates that barriers and opportunities for women in the energy transition are not confined to specific countries but show common patterns. These cut across companies, sectors, and institutional settings. Importantly, the findings highlight that industry perspectives should not remain separate from educational and training initiatives: the skills, practices, and cultures that shape workplaces are directly connected to how women are recruited, retained, and advanced. Training programmes therefore need to integrate industrial realities, drawing on evidence from companies and entrepreneurs to ensure that curricula, mentorship schemes, and leadership development modules reflect actual workplace challenges and opportunities.

Embedding this industrial dimension in training means preparing women not only with technical expertise but also with the tools to navigate organizational structures, leadership pathways, and innovation ecosystems. The following recommendations highlight cross-cutting strategies for industry and entrepreneurs to embed gender inclusion as a driver of competitiveness, resilience, and innovation, while also providing critical input for the design of future training programmes that connect education with labour market transformation at all stages of education and training.

Recognize Gender as a Strategic Advantage

Across workshops, participants stressed that gender inclusion is not a matter of fairness alone but directly tied to competitiveness and future viability. Diversity was consistently framed as a way to attract new talent pools, meet skills shortages, and stimulate innovation.

Practical steps:

- Integrate gender equity targets into business and innovation strategies.
- Monitor progress with KPIs and ESG frameworks.
- Position inclusion as an enabler of competitiveness, adaptability, and resilience in rapidly changing markets.

Reform Recruitment and Promotion Practices

A recurring finding across contexts was that recruitment and career progression replicate structural biases, narrowing opportunities for women. Gender stereotypes shape educational pathways and professional advancement, while opaque HR processes perpetuate gaps.

Practical steps:

- Adopt gender-blind recruitment tools and ensure gender-balanced hiring panels.
- Implement pay transparency and actively address wage disparities.
- Design diverse career progression routes (technical, expert, managerial) to avoid the “one path only” promotion model that often excludes non-traditional profiles.

Invest in Mentorship, Training, and Role Models

The role of mentors and visible role models emerged as a central theme across all focus groups. Women reported that seeing peers and leaders in the sector had a direct impact on their aspirations and confidence.

Practical steps:

- Develop structured mentorship programmes linking experienced professionals with early-career women.
- Actively showcase women's achievements in company communications, industry events, and the media.
- Ensure that training and capacity-building opportunities are embedded in organizational strategies, with startups in particular positioned to establish inclusive cultures from the outset.

Create Inclusive Career Pathways

Participants across different sectors emphasized that career barriers are shaped less by skill deficits and more by structural and cultural obstacles. Women's advancement is often constrained by rigid workplace models that fail to accommodate diverse life trajectories.

Practical steps:

- Offer flexible working arrangements (remote work, job-sharing, adaptable schedules).
- Adopt comprehensive family-friendly policies, including parental leave and childcare support.
- Recognize and reward non-linear career paths, valuing both technical expertise and leadership skills.

Foster Innovation through Diversity

Evidence from FGIs and workshops highlighted that diverse teams consistently generate more creative solutions. Women bring perspectives that broaden product design, service delivery, and market responsiveness, particularly in emerging fields such as renewables and cleantech.

Practical steps:

- Ensure women's representation in R&D and product development teams.
- Promote interdisciplinary collaborations that bring together STEM and SSH expertise.
- Pilot innovations that explicitly integrate gender-sensitive design and user perspectives.

Build Cross-Sector Partnerships

A consistent lesson across workshops was that industry cannot act alone. Real progress requires collaboration between businesses, academia, policymakers, and civil society to create pathways for women and to shift systemic norms.

Practical steps:

- Develop joint internship, training, and scholarship programmes with universities.
- Partner with NGOs and public bodies to support women's entry into STEM and energy-related careers.
- Engage in outreach activities (e.g., mentoring in schools, public campaigns, "Girls Day") to inspire the next generation.

Across contexts, the message is clear: gender inclusion is not peripheral but central to the energy sector's capacity to innovate and adapt. By investing in equitable recruitment, structured mentorship, inclusive career pathways, and cross-sector partnerships, industry and entrepreneurs can both empower women and strengthen their own resilience and competitiveness in the energy transition.

3.5. Recommendations for International Programmes

As the global energy sector undergoes a substantial transformation towards sustainability, it encounters not only technological and economic challenges

but also systemic impediments to equity and inclusion. The transition towards cleaner and more resilient energy systems necessitates the comprehensive participation of all stakeholders; however, women remain underrepresented in leadership, technical roles, and decision-making positions on a global scale. To address these disparities, international programs must adopt a deliberate, principle-driven approach to incorporate gender equality into the design, governance, and implementation of projects.

While existing documentation may not explicitly stipulate models for international collaboration, they collectively propose a series of guiding principles that can establish the foundation for equitable and impactful global initiatives.

- Inclusivity must be integrated into the design process from the inception. International programs should eschew narrow, technology-driven "solutionist" frameworks and instead implement transdisciplinary approaches that incorporate feminist perspectives, systems thinking, and intersectionality. Designing projects from a "clean slate" enables them to circumvent entrenched institutional biases and create environments that inherently welcome diverse voices. By framing energy challenges as social, cultural, environmental, and political as well as technical, projects can promote more innovative solutions while providing opportunities for a broader array of participants to contribute meaningfully.
- The cultivation of inclusive and cross-generational professional networks is vital. Women in the energy sector frequently experience isolation and a scarcity of supportive professional structures, particularly in contexts dominated by males. International programs should, therefore, place a priority on establishing robust networks that transcend national, institutional, and disciplinary boundaries. These networks must purposefully move away from exclusionary, hierarchical models and instead emphasize empathy, solidarity, and openness. Cross-generational engagement—via mentorship, knowledge-sharing, and peer support—ensures continuity of expertise and fortifies women's collective agency in shaping the sector on a global scale.
- Securing high-level leadership commitment and resources is an indispensable condition for success. Without visible and sustained support from institutional and national leaders, international projects risk becoming marginalized or insufficiently resourced. Leadership must not only allocate funding and institutional support but also legitimize innovative approaches, integrate diversity objectives into strategic planning, and establish an enabling environment for women's leadership. Commitment at the highest levels conveys a strong signal of credibility and permanence, anchoring gender equity efforts within broader energy transition agendas.
- Projects must embed gender-informed principles and accountability mechanisms. Merely declaring a commitment to gender equity is insufficient; principles must be operationalized through policies, curricula,

training, and practices that explicitly foreground intersectionality. Accountability tools—such as gender audits of hiring and promotion processes, workload distribution, and leadership pathways—can assist in identifying structural barriers and monitoring progress. In some contexts, institutional and policy mechanisms such as legal quotas, shared parental leave, inclusive language standards, and pay equity may be necessary to drive tangible and lasting change.

- Cross-sectoral collaboration and public engagement should be central to international efforts. Energy transitions cannot succeed if isolated from the broader social fabric. International programs must, therefore, collaborate across sectors—government, industry, academia, civil society, and local communities—to amplify women's voices in shaping policy, practice, and public discourse. Building partnerships with schools, universities, and community organizations can also contribute to nurturing future generations of women in energy, while simultaneously enhancing awareness and solidarity at the grassroots level.
- Ultimately, programs are required to redefine the criteria for success to appropriately value diverse contributions. Conventional metrics of achievement, such as the accumulation of publications or patents, frequently do not adequately reflect the comprehensive array of contributions made by women to the sector. It is imperative for international projects to implement inclusive evaluation frameworks that acknowledge mentorship, community engagement, interdisciplinary collaboration, and institutional leadership as essential forms of impact. By expanding the definition of success, programs not only affirm the contributions of women but also foster organizational cultures that emphasize collaboration, resilience, and social responsibility.

In conclusion, these principles delineate a comprehensive vision for international projects that transcend merely integrating women into pre-existing frameworks. Rather, they propose a strategic blueprint for transforming the global energy ecosystem into a model characterized by inclusiveness, equity, and innovation. By integrating gender equity at all stages, from design to evaluation, international programs can facilitate a transition to sustainable energy systems that are not solely technologically advanced but also socially transformative.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D3.3 of the GeneSys project provides an integrated analysis of how women's participation, leadership, and expertise can be more effectively supported in the energy transition through education, professional development, and institutional reform. The report synthesises empirical findings from four countries—Germany, Italy, the United Kingdom, and Poland—using focus group interviews and participatory Theory of Change (ToC) workshops that engaged students, academics, professionals, and corporate actors across the energy and education sectors.

The study reveals that persistent gender inequalities in the energy transition are sustained by a combination of structural, cultural, and institutional factors. These include entrenched stereotypes about gendered career paths, limited visibility of female role models, and barriers to advancement within male-dominated academic and corporate environments. While national contexts differ, a common thread emerges: women's potential as innovators, researchers, and leaders in the energy transition remains underutilised.

The analyses presented in Deliverable D3.3 demonstrate that achieving a gender-sensitive energy transition requires more than increasing women's participation—it demands a structural rethinking of how education, research, and industry interact to shape opportunities and values. To overcome persistent inequalities, institutions must move from fragmented initiatives toward coherent strategies that embed gender equality in every layer of energy systems. This includes reforming educational pathways, mainstreaming equity within energy-sector policy, and creating enabling environments that value diverse leadership and knowledge systems.

The findings underscore that gender inclusion is not a secondary concern but a strategic imperative: sustainable energy transitions depend on the diversity of perspectives, experiences, and competencies. By translating research evidence into actionable recommendations, D3.3 provides the conceptual and empirical foundation for the development of gender-responsive training frameworks, institutional pilots, and international collaborations that together can transform the European energy landscape into one that is equitable, innovative, and future-oriented.

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6. ANNEXES

6.1. National reports from focus group interviews

6.1.1. Germany

Title: Report from organizing FGIs in Germany

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Institution: IAO

Organization of FGIs

1. Introduction

For a better understanding of the deviating FGIs, especially regarding the FGIs with students, this section will give more information regarding this issue. Since the IAO does not have ties to any university, it was a bigger undertaking than anticipated to find participants. With the possibility of conducting the FGI with lecturers online, it was possible to carry out the FGI. There was the possibility to conduct a FGI with students from a certain study course called “technische Kommunikation” (eng.: technical communication). It was possible in this study course since a lecturer is a project partner of the IAO. They made their lecture in the second week of the semester available to conduct the FGIs. The FGI took place in Munich, so there were only limited resources available to conduct the FGIs as Cerri is based in Berlin. Because of this reasoning the students were split into two groups, as there were no interviewers available.

2. Date, place and form of each FGI. Please list the FGIs, adding code to each FGI.

The focus group interview (FGI) with lecturers and structural personnel, meaning two equal opportunity officers and one program director, was conducted on 25th September 2024. The session was held virtually via Microsoft Teams to accommodate participants residing in various locations across Germany. This logistical approach facilitated the involvement of professionals from diverse regions while ensuring accessibility.

Two FGIs with students were conducted, who studied Technische Kommunikation in Munich. The interviews were conducted in Munich on the 15th of October at the Hochschule Munich in person. Almost all of them were in their first semester.

3. Duration of each FGI

- a. The FGI with lecturers had a duration of 1 hour and 50 minutes.
- b. Both FGIs with students had a duration of 1 hour and 40 minutes.

4. What were the characteristics of the interviewee groups in each FGI, including details on gender, type of program, year of study for students, current place of work and subjects taught for faculty staff or experts, as well as the type of higher education institution (HEI)?

Focus Group with Lecturers and Structural Personnel (FGILEC)

A FGI was conducted with nine participants, all of whom are lecturers or structural personnel involved in courses related to science and energy systems. The group comprised individuals teaching or working in the following areas of study:

- Geotechnology
- Traffic and Machine Systems
- Energy Systems and Energy Technology
- Energy Technology (Energy Industry)
- Sustainable Mobile Drive Systems
- Power Engineering
- Energy Technology
- Energy Process Engineering

The lecturers teach at the following universities:

- Technische Universität Berlin
- Technische Universität München
- Dortmund Universität
- Fachhochschule Aachen
- Technische Universität Darmstadt

Most of them work for a university that is more focused on technologies, only Dortmund Universität and Fachhochschule Aachen are universities without a specific focus.

Among the participants, two women also serve as equal opportunities officers. Additionally, one participant is a full-time member of the Executive Board at an NGO focused on energy but will transition into teaching during the next semester. This focus group is designated as FGILEC for further reference.

Focus Groups with Students (FGISMA and FGIBI)

Two focus group interviews were conducted with students enrolled in the bachelor's program for Technische Kommunikation (eng.: technical communication). The participants were chosen randomly for the two groups.

- FGISMA consisted of 17 participants, including eight women and nine men. All students were in their first semester.
- FGIBI comprised 20 participants, with 11 women and nine men. All participants were in their first semester, except for one individual who was in their third semester.

The participants' current places of work were not discussed during these interviews. The groups are referred to as FGISMA and FGIBI in this report for clarity and distinction.

5. Describe the recruitment process, how it went? What were the difficulties? How might those difficulties influence the results?

The recruitment process for the FGIs posed significant challenges, requiring adaptive strategies to ensure participation.

Recruitment for Lecturer and Structural Personnel FGI

Recruiting participants for the FGI with lecturers and structural personnel proved to be more complex. Due to the geographic dispersion of lecturers across different universities in Germany, it was not feasible to conduct an in-person session in a single location. To address this challenge, the FGI was conducted virtually via Microsoft Teams, allowing participants to join remotely from their respective locations. Participants were recruited through a combination of email invitations and follow-up phone calls. One participant then recruited another person. They were chosen by the field in which they teach or work (like a lecturer working at an institute for sustainability mobile drive systems).

These recruitment methods highlight the logistical challenges inherent in engaging diverse groups for focus group research and underscore the importance of leveraging partnerships and flexible approaches in the recruitment process.

Recruitment for Student FGIs

The recruitment of students for the FGIs was made possible through a contact provided by a research partner. This collaboration facilitated access to a sufficient number of participants for the two focus groups conducted with students from the Technische Kommunikation program.

6. Describe the thematic areas discussed and projective techniques used during each FGI.

Methods Employed

In FGILEC, no projective techniques were utilized. In contrast, FGISMA and FGIBI incorporated the timeline exercise to map the career paths of women. This technique provided a visual and structured approach to understanding gender-specific experiences and challenges within their educational and professional journeys.

Key Themes

All focus groups explored the importance of role models for women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. However, the emphasis and additional topics varied across groups:

- FGILEC: Discussions centered extensively on the role of role models in influencing women's participation in STEM. The group delved deeply into how role models can impact career trajectories and inspire engagement in energy systems and related disciplines.
- FGISMA: This group highlighted strategies currently implemented to involve women in STEM fields, offering insights into practices and initiatives that have proven effective in fostering inclusivity.
- FGIBI: The focus of this group was on the barriers that exist for women in STEM, with participants identifying challenges that disproportionately affect women compared to men. These discussions provided a critical perspective on structural and cultural obstacles within the field.

By examining these themes across the focus groups, the study underscores the varying perceptions and experiences of lecturers, structural personnel, and students regarding gender equity in STEM disciplines.

7. Rational behind the chosen FGIs

The limited number of focus group interviews (FGIs) conducted was primarily attributed to challenges in recruiting participants. As Fraunhofer is not directly affiliated with any university, the recruitment process proved significantly more difficult than anticipated. This lack of institutional linkage limited access to potential participants and required additional effort to identify and motivate individuals to participate.

Despite these constraints, FGIs were successfully conducted with the participants who were available and willing to contribute. The composition of these groups reflects the

Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition

resourcefulness of the recruitment process, though the challenges underscore the importance of institutional connections in facilitating participant engagement in research.

Description of FGI with Mixed-gender Students from STEM

1. Educational Choices

- a) What are the educational choices and pathways (please refer to all programmes and pathways that were raised during the FGI)
 - i) All participants in both focus group interviews (FGISMA and FGIBI) are enrolled in the same university program, Technische Kommunikation (English: Technical Communication).
- b) What were the key factors identified as influencing a decision to pursue a degree in energy-related fields? Please mark the influential moments when the interest in energy-related topic / studies occurred.
 - i) Even though the degree program is not specifically focused on energy, it offers opportunities for specialization and can serve as a solid foundation for a future career in the energy field. Accordingly, we asked participants whether they could imagine pursuing a career in the energy sector. The discussions revealed that some students are tentatively considering careers in the energy sector. (In FGIBI: “I also find it interesting with newer energies that are not yet taking place, such as nuclear fusion. [...] I find it interesting that you can say that you can simply bring people closer to it, when it becomes a bigger thing”; FGISMA: “I can imagine that very well, I'm quite open, so I'm also looking in which direction I want to go, yes.”; “I can definitely imagine it, because I studied something with energy beforehand, or started to study it, better said.”; “I could imagine working [in that field] even though I as a layman might not know much about it [...] but I think that this is an area where a lot of innovation is currently taking place and that interests me.”). However, their levels of interest and certainty regarding this career path vary significantly, indicating a range of engagement with the field. One student in FGIBI said that he had previously worked in a place where energy systems was an important topic; he specifically chose to study something where he'd be a provider of information.
- c) Who was a source of inspiration to follow this pathway? What were the sources of encouragement and support that helped to choose energy-related programmes?
 - i) This was not mentioned by participants.
- d) What were the barriers and obstacles?
 - i) No specific barriers or obstacles to pursuing a study course in energy-related fields were explicitly mentioned by the participants. However, FGISMA participants discussed the potential intimidation of entering a male-dominated sector. They also addressed broader socialization factors, noting how children continue to hold gendered perceptions of work, with certain careers still being coded as either "male" or "female". (“I haven't read up on it, but the first thought I get it, yes, it's more of a male area and if I don't have a specific interest in it, then somehow I won't even consider it for myself.”; “I think especially at this primary school age its always very, it depends a lot on belonging and somehow fitting in and I can imagine that at elementary school the boys think robots are cool and the girls have to play horses and if you don't do that then maybe you're afraid of being different, somehow you don't belong anymore.”; “I believe that children in these early years perhaps don't come into

contact with [diverse career choices], or are rather socialized in such a way, ah ok, women are sweet teacher, but [technicians] they don't come into contact with them too much in the early years [...]."; "In the industries, it's still mainly men, in the job interviews too [...], and not women who conduct job interviews with you, for example. And some of them still prefer men to women in this industry.") In FGIBI, socialization was again a central theme, with a focus on how women and girls are often steered toward careers perceived as more socially oriented, which remains the more typical path for them. ("I would say that through the XXX and leadership skills attributed to women and men tend to be simply related to socialization rather than biological differences. And that the reason why men are often perceived as more competent is simply because they are encouraged to achieve the things they want to achieve and women tend to be encouraged to conform to gender roles. I didn't think this has an actual true origin."; "Simply because you have role models from your parents at school. In elementary school, I only had female teachers. I've also never heard anyone who is a man say they're going to be a primary school teacher." "[...] that in elementary school there are [gendered] role models put into place.))

A student provided the example of how work is still frequently categorized as "male" or "female." ("I also know [female] friends of mine, some of whom are in engineering degree programs, where professors have looked funny because there are girls sitting there or something like that, and in the past [professors] of them have made comments about it."

e) Who / What enables those processes?

- i) The participants frequently discussed the role of socialization in shaping career perceptions. It was highlighted that society at large plays a significant role in reinforcing these influences. Additionally, parents, teachers, and other individuals closely involved in a child's or adolescent's life were identified as key contributors to shaping career choices and expectations. ("What could be changes? Generally speaking, there should be a better distribution of women [...] representation of women in the business areas [...] That you can also run a company as a woman." "Socialization and female representation. On the one hand, if you are taught the basics of education in elementary school and are already introduced to a role model at a time when you are very strongly influenced in your life values by others, this has a very influential role that can definitely have an impact on your self-confidence, what you dare to do, what you choose for jobs, what you choose for an education, on the one hand, but also that many [...] do not have the privilege that even primary school education is offered for all genders, is made possible for all genders, as is the case here in Germany.")

f) Are there differences in educational expectations and opportunities related to different energy sectors?

- i) The participants did not talk about this.

2. *Career pathways*

- a) What are the career pathways for women (please refer to all pathways that were raised during the FGI – also the prospective career paths)

- i) The majority of the female participants expressed uncertainty about their future career paths. Several indicated that they did not plan to pursue a career in the energy sector, while others stated that while they did not currently envision working in the energy sector, they remained open to the possibility of changing their minds in the future. Nearly all participants, but bit more often female participants, noted that they had limited knowledge about what working in the energy sector would entail, further reflecting the ambiguity surrounding the field for many of them. (“And regarding the energy industry. I don’t know yet know, because I don’t now much about that field.” “I have not yet read much about that field so I cannot [see myself working there], but this might change during studying.”)
- b) What were the crucial factors that shaped those pathways?
 - i) The participants of FGISMA emphasized the significant role of role models in shaping individuals' career pathways. They discussed how role models can inspire and influence career choices, particularly in fields like STEM and energy, by providing guidance and representation. Most of them said, that they wouldn’t know enough about the energy sector and couldn’t imagine what a job in the energy sector would entail and thus it is not interesting to them, but for some this was also a reason to say, they might consider it in the future. Others said that it does not interest them in general. (“And for working in the energy sector, I don’t really know what that would mean so I don’t know if I want to work there.” ; “[...] because parents and school are role models. In elementary school I only had female teachers [...] I think this is way many female friends of mine now want to do something in the social sector.”)
- c) Who was a source of inspiration to follow this pathway?
 - i) This was not mentioned by participants.
- d) What were the barriers and obstacles?
 - i) No specific barriers or obstacles to pursuing careers in the energy sector were directly mentioned by the participants. However, in FGISMA, participants noted that entering a male-dominated sector could be intimidating for women. As mentioned before in Section 1, they also discussed these challenges in a broader context of socialization, highlighting how children still often hold gendered perceptions of work, with certain careers being viewed as more suitable for one gender over the other. (“Yes, because of this I think a women’s quota could motivate don’t be afraid and if there is an interview where there are only six men present, I do think that that adds pressure.” “I think that it is cliché, that a lot of women go into social or creative based careers and that men go into engineering.”)

In FGIBI, socialization was also a central theme, with discussions focusing on how women and girls are often steered toward social careers, which are still perceived as the more typical career path for them. (“And that the reason why men are often perceived as more competent is simply because they are encouraged to be self-confident and assertive, to achieve things they want to achieve and women tend to be encouraged to conform to gender roles.”)

Family planning was also talked about as a possible obstacle for women. (“Children also have an impact on women’s careers. Now it is also changing, it has become

normal for men to take parental leave too. But it is still biologically that a woman is pregnant, which means that for a certain period of time she has to leave her work and take a break, and I believe that this is precisely what [leads to] disadvantages.”)

- e) Who / What enables those processes?
 - i) The participants discussed the influence of society on this as well, same as in the case of education
- f) Are there differences in career expectations and opportunities related to different energy sectors?
 - i) In FGIBI it was theorized that the energy sector is a liberal place of work since the majority of the people working there are young. (“In some cases, I have the feeling that it is industry-specific, renewable energies for example, a lot of young people are interested in it and therefore a lot of young people are working in it. And there is already a corresponding change.”)

3. *Organisational climate at university/college*

- a) What is the overall climate/culture regarding the gender equality at the university/department?
 - i) In FGIBI the students perceived the group being quite mixed and balanced gender wise. A female student also said that she doesn’t feel like that someone is being discriminated against and that she doesn’t think that she as a woman has fewer chances learning. Another female student said that she hasn’t noticed any discrimination from lecturers and that she feels like male lecturers are happy to see women participating in their lecturers. Another student expressed that she feels like that the lecturers are surprised by the amount of female students this semester. (“Regarding women, I have not witnessed any discrimination from lecturers. I did notice that they seem to be happy that [...] women show a bigger interest in the field.” “I find the number of female and male lecturers balances.”) In FGISMA a female student also talked about there being a fair number of female lecturers. It was not stated that the university was seeking gender equality or diversity specifically, but the sentiment was that women feel treated fairly. The male participants did not contribute on this topic.
- b) Is gender analysis / gender dimension integrated into participants’ study program / courses? Please provide examples and discuss its impact on the participants’ experiences of their studies and career expectations.
 - i) The students did not know if gender analysis or gender dimension are integrated into participants’ study program or courses. One student from FGIBI thinks that they have seen a poster at the university for events which are specifically for women.
- c) Are there any programs / measures / interventions that help women to pursue their educational path or/and career?
 - i) In FGISMA one measure talked about extensively was the “Girls Day”. Girls’ Day in Germany is an annual day of action where girls from the 5th grade onwards can learn about careers in technology, IT, natural sciences and trades - areas in which women are often underrepresented. Companies, universities and institutions open their doors and offer workshops, guided tours and practical insights. The aim is to get girls

interested in STEM professions and break down clichés when it comes to choosing a career. The experience with this ranged quite a lot. A female student talked about how at her school the Girls Day was not very well planned, and she never participated as planned. But she does not think that a different experience would have changed her career outcome as she still researched different firms and investigated the work they do. But another male student said that at his school the Girls (and Boys) Day was obligatory and thus it worked well.

Recommendations

- d) What are the recommendations for the future to raise woman participation in energy sector?
 - i) The participants did not outright talk about recommendations. Some talked positively about the experience of the “Girls Day”. It has also been discussed, that if not prepared properly, it is not as influential as it could be so it would be necessary for schools to have a better protocol as to how the Girls Day is integrated into the curriculum. In FGISMA and FGIBI internships were discussed as well. Especially in FGISMA one female student talked about how internships would be helpful. Especially a few shorter one in middle school and a longer one in high school to have the possibility to explore different areas of work. Another student said that it was helpful to see female lecturers, so it might be helpful to showcase successful women in the energy sector through media, conferences, and educational programs to provide relatable examples for aspiring female professionals. Also, to foster partnerships between educational institutions and energy companies to create internship and job placement opportunities specifically for women might be useful.

Description of FGI with students from social sciences programme

1. Educational choices and career pathways

- a) Why did the student have chosen energy and environmental as well sustainability [or any other field of study the participants are enrolled in] as a field of study? Please mark the influential moments when the interest in energy-related topic / studies occurred.
 - i) FGISMA

Some students expressed a strong personal interest in sustainability and environmental issues. For instance, one student mentioned their positive experience at a Montessori school, where sustainability was integrated into the curriculum, fostering a genuine interest in environmental topics (“I had a different experience. I went to a Montessori school and the teaching there was quite nice teaching and it was kind of cool at the school to be so sustainable. And to think about nature and I think it's important how such important content is taught to pupils and that the teachers themselves then also have this lifestyle themselves. It wasn't so fake, you have to sort garbage somehow sort rubbish, but they really enjoy it.”). A female student expressed a desire to contribute positively to society and the environment. The notion that their work could have a meaningful impact on sustainability and energy efficiency was a strong motivating factor. One student highlighted the importance of feeling proud of their achievements and making a significant contribution to important causes (“So,

as I already mentioned, it's important to me, for example, that I'm proud of the goal I achieve. And that I, it was always important to me that I do something important because I simply have the opportunity to do so.”).

ii) FGIBI

A male student said that it was important to him to do something sensible meaning to do something good (“I would add something else: I do believe that it played a small part in the fact that you say you definitely want to do something sensible at the end. For example, I worked in film for two years and I realized that it didn't really fulfill me. I want to go in a direction with the degree course where I can say that I have made a sensible contribution to society. I think you can say that sustainability plays a major role in Munich.”).

b) What are the factors shaping the decision to pursue this programme?

i) In FGISMA, many students expressed an interest in pursuing careers related to media or film, with one student specifically mentioning an interest in journalism. However, no participant directly explained why they chose a path connected to energy. While some students indicated that they might consider working in the energy sector in the future, the majority did not see themselves in this field. In FGIBI, many students stated that energy was not a significant factor in their decision to pursue their current course of study. One participant, however, shared their prior experience working in the energy sector and expressed an interest in transitioning to a role focused on informing the public about energy-related topics. Some mentioned an interest in working in a career which benefits the earth, by being for a sustainable brand. Others said that they think it would be interesting to explain technical processes or things.

c) Was the interest in energy a crucial factor?

i) For all but one, no, who worked in the energy sector but wanted to change his careerpath to something less manual.

d) What are the perspectives of work in the energy sector by SSH graduates? Do they consider pursuing a career in this sector? Why?

i) In FGISMA, some students expressed a preference for interdisciplinary roles that combine their social science background with aspects of the energy sector. These students are particularly interested in positions that allow them to engage with both the technical and social dimensions of energy issues, such as roles in policymaking or community engagement. They recognize that their expertise in social studies could contribute meaningfully to energy policy discussions and the public understanding of energy-related topics. However, there is a concern among some students that their social studies background may not provide the technical expertise typically required in energy-related roles. This perceived gap in technical knowledge has led to hesitancy in pursuing careers directly within the energy sector, as they may feel underqualified compared to individuals with engineering or other technical degrees. Additionally, two female students specifically expressed a desire to have a positive influence on the world, highlighting their motivation to pursue careers that align with their values. One of them remarked (“So, as I already mentioned, it would be important to me, for example, that I am proud of the goal, that I am proud of what I achieve.”).

e) What are the factors that can facilitate or limit the career in energy/ sustainability sector? Are there different opportunities in different energy sectors? Are there different options for men and women?

- A workplace culture that promotes diversity, equity, and inclusion is seen as an important factor in facilitating career advancement for both men and women. Organizations that actively support gender equality and provide equal opportunities are more likely to attract a diverse workforce, which can contribute to a more inclusive and dynamic work environment. However, some students expressed the perception that the energy sector is still largely male-dominated. One participant, in contrast, viewed the sector as more liberal and youth-oriented, suggesting that this might result in a different work experience for women, potentially offering more opportunities for gender equality. (“That shows that OK, if I choose this path now, I’m not the first woman to encounter all these problems, that it is normal. That women also feel invited in such areas. I don’t think we’re there yet.” “In the industries it’s mainly still men who are in the job interviews with people [...] and some of them still prefer men to women in this industry.” “In some cases, I have the feeling that it is industry-specific, renewable energies for example, a lot of young people are interested in it and therefore a lot of young people are working in it. And there is already a corresponding change.”)

Key factors that could facilitate careers in the energy sector include:

- Education, which equips individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed. (“I find that in elementary school, too, typical and common professions are presented [...] and children don’t even know that there are other professions.”, “It was the same for me, you could choose between the technical aspect and the linguistic aspect, and there was no differentiation between the social aspect and linguistic aspect.”, “With us, you could decide [at the transition to grammar school] whether you wanted to specialize in MINT or SPRINT or something like that. Therefore decide between more of a linguistic focus or a scientific focus.” “I personally went to a secondary school until sixth grade. They also told you, that you should do an apprenticeship because you had no prospects”
- A supportive work environment, where inclusivity and equal opportunities are prioritized. (“I think it’s important for me that [...] I don’t work in an area that somehow pollutes nature a lot, [...] and I’ll make sure that similar values are represented when choosing a career.”; “That shows that OK, if I choose this path now, I’m not the first woman to encounter all these problems, that it is normal. That women also feel invited in such areas. I don’t think we’re there yet.”; “In the industries it’s mainly still men who are in the job interviews with people [...] and some of them still prefer men to women in this industry.”; “That’s why I think the women’s quota could motivate women more, not to be afraid.”; “[...] that you also create [a bigger] motivation, maybe also form a financial point of view, that you say, there are also good job offers [...]”; “I also think I [want] job security? Simply that I know I have a job now where I don’t have to worry about being out of there.” “Satisfaction at work is first and foremost that other people enjoy it, of course, but above all I think that the environment [where you work] makes

a big difference.” “If I felt uncomfortable in a company or in a job where I don’t know that if I got pregnant or if anything happened, I would keep my job and have financial support and paid parental leave or whatever.”; “For me, it is very important who is above me. Who is my employer, how do they deal with me?”; “In some cases, I have the feeling that it is industry-specific, renewable energies for example, a lot of young people are interested in it and therefore a lot of young people are working in it. And there is already a corresponding change.”)

Conversely, several factors were identified as limiting careers in the energy sector, including:

- Gender stereotypes, which can perpetuate the notion that certain roles are more suited to one gender over another. (“[...]On the one hand, if you are taught the basics of education in elementary school and are already introduced to a role model at a time when you are very strongly influenced in your life values by others, this has a very influential role that can definitely have an impact on your self-confidence, what you dare to do, what you choose for jobs, what you choose for an education [...].”)
- Work-life balance concerns, which may discourage women from pursuing careers in sectors with demanding or inflexible work schedules. (“Pregnancy is a very, very big obstacle in a women’s career. [...] You either have to decide to have a family or a career, and it’s very difficult to combine the two.” “I also see a lot of women who have problems with this or are hardly taken on by jobs because they are married, because they are naturally afraid that they will go on maternity leave.” “The woman simply has to cut back. I can’t have a child now. [...] Of course you have to make sacrifices.”)
- Limited representation, where a lack of visible role models and diversity in the workplace can affect recruitment and retention. This was mentioned generally with technical careers as they are dominated by men who can have biases. (“In the industries it’s mainly still men who are in the job interviews with people [...] and some of them still prefer men to women in this industry.”)

2. *Field of study and organizational culture*

- a) Are there issues related to energy included in the study programme? If yes how? Please refer to different aspects (e.g. social, technological)?
 - i) Not as far as the students know.
- b) Is gender analysis / gender dimension integrated into energy-related courses? Please provide examples and discuss its impact on the participants’ experiences of their studies and career expectations.
 - i) Not as far the students know.
- c) What is the overall climate/culture regarding the gender equality at the university/department?
 - i) In FGIBI the students perceived the group being quite mixed and balanced gender wise. A female student also said that she doesn’t feel like that someone is being discriminated against and that she doesn’t think that she as a woman has fewer chances learning. Another female student said that she hasn’t noticed any discrimination from lecturers and that she feels like male lecturers are happy to see

women participating in their lecturers. In FGISMA a female student also talked about there being a fair number of female lecturers. It was not stated that the university was seeking gender equality or diversity specifically but the sentiment was that women feel treated fairly.

Recommendations

- a) What should change in the SSH programs related to energy/sustainability?
 - i) The participants did not talk about this as they did not have looked at the curriculum thus they weren't sure in what way sustainability and energy was implemented.
- b) What should change to make this field more attractive to woman?
 - i) Addressing societal perceptions of gender roles in technical fields is crucial for promoting gender diversity in the energy sector. Initiatives that challenge traditional stereotypes and highlight the potential for women to succeed in STEM fields, including energy, are essential to shifting cultural attitudes. Educational campaigns can play a significant role in normalizing the presence of women in these fields and encouraging their participation. Energy companies should take proactive steps to create inclusive and supportive work environments. Policies aimed at mitigating gender bias, offering flexible work arrangements, and ensuring equitable career advancement opportunities are pivotal. Flexible working options, in particular, can help accommodate the diverse needs of employees, including women who often balance professional and family responsibilities. Developing interdisciplinary programs that integrate technical training with social sciences could attract a broader demographic of women to the energy sector. Such programs not only bridge the gap between technical knowledge and communication skills but also provide pathways for students with diverse educational backgrounds to enter the field. Increasing the visibility of female role models within the energy sector is another critical strategy. Role models can inspire and motivate young women to pursue careers in energy by demonstrating what is achievable. Mentorship programs connecting female students with accomplished women in the energy industry can offer valuable guidance and encouragement, further supporting their aspirations.

Description of FGI lecturers and experts

1. Women's educational choices – energy sector

- a) What are the factors impacting women's decision to pursue studies in energy system?
 - i) A key theme discussed across the focus group was the significant influence of role models on career decisions. GE-FGILEC-6 shared that she had wished for role models during her school years who could demonstrate that it was possible for women to work as engineers in fields involving physical labor. This sentiment was echoed by other participants, who noted the scarcity of female role models, not only within families but also in schools and universities. The lack of representation in these environments can limit women's career and educational aspirations, particularly in fields traditionally dominated by men, such as engineering and energy. GE-FGILEC-7 further

elaborated on the absence of female role models, pointing out that the energy sector is often framed as masculine and that the way the sector is communicated tends to be gender-insensitive. This framing may make the sector less appealing to women. The importance of gender-sensitive language was also emphasized, particularly in German, where gender distinctions are prominent in text. There is a growing movement, especially among younger people, to use more inclusive language, which reflects a broader societal shift toward gender awareness. The influence of socialization was another recurring theme. As highlighted by GE-FGILEC-5, traditional gender stereotypes often discourage women from pursuing careers which plays a role in choosing the course of one's education, that involve physical labor, as women are often perceived to avoid such jobs, which is also made prevalent during their studies with internships as GE-FGILEC-9 also talked about. This can change their educational trajectory. This stereotype is further reinforced by societal perceptions of what roles women "should" pursue. GE-FGILEC-9 pointed out that women are often not given the same technical explanations or encouragement as men, particularly in childhood. For example, girls are sometimes excluded from learning about technical subjects, or the explanations they receive are less detailed than those provided to boys, in school and by parents. Additionally, GE-FGILEC-2 noted that girls are often given gendered toys, such as receiving Lego sets three to five years later than boys, creating a gap in their technical skills and understanding that they later need to overcome. GE-FGILEC-7 emphasized that many women are motivated by the desire to do meaningful work, wanting to contribute to society in ways that have a positive impact on the world. This desire for purpose is a key driver in their educational decisions. The influence of social media on career aspirations was also discussed, with GE-FGILEC-2 noting that young people, especially those still in school, are increasingly influenced by platforms like Instagram and TikTok. Many now aspire to become social media influencers, a career path that is vastly different from traditional roles like teacher or doctor, which are often the only careers students are aware of.

- b) Are these factors different from those of men? In what way?
 - i) GE-FGILEC-2 noted that in addition to girls receiving toys such as LEGO at a later age, which can lead to a delayed development of interest in technical fields, there are also differences in cognitive processing between boys and girls. Women, for instance, tend to prefer communication-based approaches to learning. Furthermore, women often gravitate towards careers that they perceive as meaningful. This preference was reflected in GE-FGILEC-2's observation that female students are more likely to choose courses with names that sound applied, such as "applied technical sciences." GE-FGILEC-6 highlighted a particular challenge that women face in technical fields: they often feel the need to justify their decision to pursue technical studies, whereas men can simply state that these jobs are lucrative. This reflects broader gender dynamics that shape perceptions of women in male-dominated fields. Finally, GE-FGILEC-4 shared an observation that international students tend to exhibit strong motivation in their studies, potentially driven by different cultural and educational expectations.
- c) Is it difficult to be a woman in the energy field? In what way?

- i) General hindrances for women in the workplace were discussed, particularly issues related to pregnancy and maternity leave, which often disrupt women’s careers. GE-FGILEC-2 highlighted the challenge that universities typically offer few permanent positions, making it difficult for women to find stable career opportunities. Additionally, she pointed out that the majority of women still bear the responsibility for child-rearing, which affects their ability to be flexible with work hours. This added responsibility can limit career progression and work-life balance.

2. *Women’s careers in the energy sector*

- a) What are the factors influencing women to choose energy-related studies and career paths?

- i) GE-FGILEC-6 discussed the support women receive in the workplace but also highlighted the negative comments that sometimes arise when a woman is hired, particularly regarding the assumption that such hires are made to meet a quota. Similarly, GE-FGILEC-9 mentioned that in the research facility where he works, women sometimes face comments questioning their physical capabilities, such as remarks like, “I need three strong men to lift this.” Such microaggressions can discourage women from pursuing careers in energy-related fields, especially if they encounter these attitudes during university or internships. These experiences may lead women to feel unwelcomed or unsupported in technical fields. Additionally, both GE-FGILEC-9 and GE-FGILEC-1 raised concerns about women being overworked, often due to their reluctance to voice when they are overwhelmed with tasks, which are both regarding work related tasks as well as being asked to be in a lot of different committees where there is a quota for women -but not enough women at the universities. Women may take on more responsibilities than they can handle, especially in environments where there are additional expectations related to committee involvement or gender-specific regulations. This overburden can contribute to women exiting the workforce. The impact of family responsibilities was also mentioned by GE-FGILEC-9, GE-FGILEC-2, and GE-FGILEC-6, noting that children can interrupt women’s careers. Balancing family duties with professional responsibilities often creates additional challenges for women, further influencing their career trajectories and decisions within the workplace.

The limited awareness of career options further extends to the energy sector, where students lack a clear understanding of what roles like energy engineers actually entail, often relying on misconceptions—such as the belief that such jobs are incompatible with remote work.

Finally, GE-FGILEC-9 shared an anecdote about women who interned at the research facility where he works, noting that they sometimes endure microaggressions, such as derogatory comments about their ability to perform physical labor. While these comments are not always made with overt hostility, they can still impact women’s perceptions of the workplace and discourage them from pursuing similar roles in the future. Although these decisions may not always be consciously made, they can influence women’s career choices and their decisions about where to work later in life.

- b) Are these factors different from those of men? In what way?

- i) Socialization appears to have the opposite effect on men, leading them to more frequently choose careers in technical fields. Men benefit from a greater abundance of role models, as the majority of the workforce in these sectors is male. Additionally, men typically take on less care work, meaning that family responsibilities, particularly related to children, are not as significant a factor in their career choices compared to women. GE-FGILEC-5 contributed by suggesting that women may also consider family planning more prominently in their career decisions compared to men. GE-FGILEC-2 also pointed out the potential for a glass ceiling in the energy sector, a claim that was disputed by another participant, indicating differing views on the presence of such barriers.
 - c) Is it difficult to be a woman in the energy field? Why is that?
 - i) There is no definitive answer to this question. While women face certain challenges in the energy sector that can make it more difficult for them, GE-FGILEC-6 acknowledged the support systems in place, particularly those aimed at helping women thrive, citing a heightened awareness of gender diversity. However, the effectiveness of some of this support remains questionable, leaving uncertainty about how truly helpful these initiatives are in practice.
 GE-FGILEC-9 also shared his observation that at his workplace, it would be more challenging for a woman to pursue a PhD while pregnant or with young children. This is due to the highly time-sensitive nature of research projects tied to PhD programs, which require significant time and attention, further complicating the situation for women balancing family and academic commitments.
3. *Organisational culture and gender equality*
- a) What are the organisational cultures in relation to gender equality?
 - i) How is gender equality supported?
 - (1) GE-FGILEC-9 indicated that he is unaware of any specific regulations or measures supporting his female colleagues, noting that they are more likely to seek support from women's networks. GE-FGILEC-1 shared that at the university where she works, a women's advancement plan must be submitted every four to five years. The plan outlines strategies to increase the percentage of women in various faculties, aiming for a gender balance closer to 50%. However, she expressed uncertainty about whether the women's advancement plans are effectively implemented, suggesting that the individuals responsible for executing these plans may be overworked and have numerous other responsibilities. Similarly, GE-FGILEC-6 stated that she is unaware of any regulations or measures supporting women at her workplace. GE-FGILEC-8 mentioned that his university once had ambitious measures to support women, but some of these measures were considered overly ambitious and, at times, even absurd. For example, a few years ago, his former male superior was allowed to take a course in order to hold the same position as a woman in a women's advancement commission. Currently, his program has no specific regulations or measures for women, although he does try to employ more women. GE-FGILEC-7 explained that while his team has many women's advancement plans in place, they also face a significant administrative

burden with multiple women's advancement plans to manage. He emphasized that the implementation of these plans is heavily influenced by the study program in question. In his view, all study programs share responsibility for advancing women's initiatives, but there is a lack of awareness in many of these programs about opportunities to empower women. GE-FGILEC-2 reflected that, in her opinion, only about a third of the regulations and measures aimed to support women at her university are effective. She attributed the failure of the remaining two-thirds to the personnel responsible for implementing the women advancement plans, noting that many of these individuals lack the experience or qualifications required to realize these initiatives successfully. GE-FGILEC-3 also expressed concern about the insufficiency of women's advancement programs at his university. He highlighted communication as a key factor in preventing discrimination, which can occur unknowingly and without intent.

ii) Is gender equality a critical issue?

(1) As previously mentioned, many participants described how universities have established commissions or teams responsible for developing strategies to support women. However, it was also noted that many of these strategies and programs are not effectively implemented. This indicates that while universities acknowledge gender equality as an important issue and recognize its significance, it may not be prioritized enough by the management of those institutions to ensure that the plans are carried out successfully.

b) What are the factors influencing the higher number of men than women in the energy study programmes and sector?

i) The participants unanimously agreed that socialization both in the context of families and school, plays a significant role in shaping career choices, as women are often encouraged to prefer traditionally feminine activities that exclude tasks such as getting dirty, building things, or engaging in mathematical work. This socialization process leads many women to overlook careers in fields like the energy sector. Compounding this issue is the clear lack of role models for women and girls within the energy sector, which perpetuates the cycle. Even if women do pursue studies in the energy sector, they may encounter discrimination, as described by GE-FGILEC-6, or face microaggressions, as noted by GE-FGILEC-9.

4. Teaching

a) How is gender integrated into curricula (courses)?

i) Several participants discussed their approaches to gender in their teaching. GE-FGILEC-8 stated that he purposefully avoids discussing gender in his lectures, focusing instead on the technical aspects. He admitted that he does not pay attention to the gender distribution in the images used during his lectures. Similarly, GE-FGILEC-4 mentioned that while he does not focus on gender, he does refer to networking opportunities for women. GE-FGILEC-7 also refrains from using gender-specific notes but makes an effort to include female lecturers and connect female students with female executives during excursions. Additionally, GE-FGILEC-7, as program director, reviews the teaching materials annually, ensuring they remain

gender-neutral. GE-FGILEC-6 acknowledged that she does not use gender-neutral language or both male and female forms. GE-FGILEC-3, on the other hand, does not take measures to address gender in his teaching, arguing that students in an academic setting can understand that the generic masculine form of a word (as it is used in German) includes both genders. GE-FGILEC-2, however, is conscious of her potential role as a female lecturer and strives to incorporate gender and diversity into every lecture she conducts. She begins by discussing the importance of these issues in general, then connects them to technical and product development topics. Additionally, she creates a safe space for female students by teaching them in a monoeducational setting, aiming to counteract existing stereotypes and help students build confidence in technical areas. Some of them explained that they simply didn't really thought of implanting a gender aspect into their lectures. Others said that they thought it best to keep it neutral. The women who participated made it more of a point to outright talk about gender because they thought it necessary.

5. *Good practice*

- a) What are the good practice initiatives that support the increase of women in the energy programmes/ sector?
 - i) This was not talked about.
- b) How can they be scaled up?
- c) What are the barriers?
 - i) The main barrier is the work capacity of the people whose task is to put the women's advancements plans into action. Old stereotypes which still exist and socialisation are barriers as well.

6. *Recommendations*

- a) What are the recommendations for changes that can improve women's participation in the energy sector?
 - i) Actively promote and highlight the achievements of women in the energy sector to provide inspiration and concrete examples of success. Encourage women professionals to participate in guest lectures, mentorship programs, and public discussions, thereby offering guidance and visibility to female students and early-career professionals.
 - ii) Develop actionable and measurable strategies to improve gender diversity within educational institutions and workplaces. Ensure these plans are not just created but also executed, with regular monitoring and evaluation to track progress and identify areas for improvement.
 - iii) Take proactive measures to combat discrimination and microaggressions in both academic and workplace settings. This includes educating employees and students on recognizing and addressing unconscious biases, creating channels for reporting and resolving incidents, and establishing zero-tolerance policies for discriminatory behavior.
 - iv) Promote the use of inclusive language and imagery in educational materials and workplace communications. Ensure that women feel represented and valued in the energy sector through culturally sensitive and gender-aware practices.

Cross cutting analysis

1. Differences between STEM and SSH students
 - a. Are there any differences in the women’s educational and career pathways between SSH and STEM?
 - i. Cannot be answered as the two groups were from the same study course.
 - b. What are the differences in incorporating gender perspective between SSH and STEM?
 - i. Cannot be answered as the two groups were from the same study course. Gender perspective in teaching was also not talked about.
2. Differences between STEM (in general) and energy-related programmes and differences between programmes focusing on different types of energy.
 - a. Cannot be answered as the FGIs were not conducted with a study course which was explicitly about energy nor where there differing energy-related programmes present.
3. Teaching and incorporating gender perspective
 - a. Is gender an integrated part of teaching in energy related fields?
 - i. Students did not talk much about the way that gender was or wasn’t incorporated into the teachings. The general consensus was that gender isn’t a focal point in the lectures. The lecturers had various approaches as to incorporating gender into their teachings from not at all to very explicitly.
4. Overarching theme
 - a. In every FGI the role of socialisation on the choices of education and career was talked about. In this context many participants mentioned how children have a gendered view of thinking and talking about places of work.
5. Enablers and barriers of women’s careers

Name of a barrier	Description	Recommendations to tackle them
Entering a male dominated sector	The participants of FGISMA talked about how the energy sector is dominated by men and how it can be intimidating to enter such a workplace.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive hiring Practices • networking opportunities • mentorship programs
Socialization	The still prevalent categories of male and female careers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness campaigns • Workshops for children in grades three to six
Workload	The people who are tasked with putting the women’s advancements plans into place are overworked with other tasks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hiring more people for the administrative work in universities. • More precise follow ups with the implementation of the women’s advancement plans.
Family Planning	Women often bear the burden of care work, and during pregnancy and after	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better protection of women who are pregnant or want to have children

	<p>childbirth, they frequently need to take time off from their jobs. This can result in career uncertainty and may deter them from pursuing positions in industries characterized by physical labor or rapidly changing environments.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide child-care on-site or subsidies for childcare • Create programs to help women transition back to work after maternity leave • Ensure women have access to leadership training and advancement programs
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Name of a supportive factor	Description
Women's advancement plans	German universities often try to come up with and implement strategies and measures to help women take part in male dominated areas. These could combat the problems that women run into at an educational level or for women working at universities.

Cross Cutting Recommendations

1. Clarification on STEM

- a) Helping students in school to have a better understanding what kinds of careers people who work in STEM can have.
- b) Host Career Fairs that focus on STEM.
- c) Incorporate real-world STEM applications into school subjects.

2. Collaboration between SSH and STEM

- a) Helping students at university understand that a background in SSH can be helpful in STEM generally but also in the energy sector explicitly.
- b) Help the leaders of the energy sector to have a better understanding of the benefits of SSH for the energy sector.

3. Incorporate Gender into Teachings

- a) Renew schoolbooks to have a more human reference and incorporate a diverse narrative.
- b) Have a more direct discussion about gender in lectures.
- c) Give attention to a more diverse way of talking about STEM
- d) Have female presentation in the workspace with guest lecturers or excursions.

Appendix

Appendix 1 – The FGI with lecturers

Number of participants	9
Target interviewee group (students from SSH, students from STEM, Academics...)	Academics and Structural personnel
Place of the interview	Online via Microsoft Teams
Date of the interview	25 th of September
Length of the FGI	1 hour and 50 minutes
Number of interviewees	1
Female (number)	4
Male (number)	5
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	There were no questions that were significantly more difficult to answer

Appendix 2 – FGI with the students

Number of participants	17
Target interviewee group (students from SSH, students from STEM, Academics...)	Students from the study course “technica communication” which links a social sciences with STEM
Place of the interview	Munich
Date of the interview	15 th of October
Length of the FGI	1 hour and 40 minutes
Number of interviewees	1
Female (number)	8
Male (number)	9
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	The question which was the hardest to answer was about the curriculum of their study course and if gender equality is

	imbedded in it; questions about the culture of the university were difficult as well
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Number of participants	20
Target interviewee group (students from SSH, students from STEM, Academics...)	Students from the study course “technica communication” which links a social sciences with STEM
Place of the interview	Munich
Date of the interview	15 th of October
Length of the FGI	1 hour and 40 minutes
Number of interviewees	1
Female (number)	11
Male (number)	9
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	The question which was the hardest to answer was about the curriculum of their study course and if gender equality is imbedded in it; questions about the culture of the university were difficult as well

Appendix 3 – Respondents characteristics

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-1
Gender	female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Technische Universtiät Berlin, Institute for Applied Geosciences
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Lecturer; equal opportunities officer
Scientific title (if applicable)	Phd.

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-2
Gender	female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Technische Universität Berlin, Department for Traffic and machine systems
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Lecturer; equal opportunities officer; leader of a junior lab

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-3
Gender	male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Hochschule Zittau/Görlitz Institute of Process Engineering, Process Automation and Metrology
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor; Director Institute of Process Engineering, Process Automation and Metrology (IPM)
Scientific title (if applicable)	Phd
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	
Research interests	<p>Combined heat and power generation</p> <p>Material and energy balancing of complex energy technology systems</p> <p>Simulation of stationary and transient coupled heat and mass transfer processes</p> <p>Simulation of non-isothermal reactive flows</p> <p>Non-equilibrium states in energy technology</p>

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-4
Gender	male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Technische Universität München
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Program Manager M.Sc. Power Engineering

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-5
Gender	female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Bündnis Bürgerenergie e.V.
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Managing Director and Senior Consultant

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-6
Gender	female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Dortmund Universität Chair of Energy Systems and Energy Economics
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Research Assistant
Research interests	Development and testing of algorithms for short-circuit and earth fault indicators for distribution networks

	Simulation of short-circuits and earth faults for fault direction detection algorithms and relays
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Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-7
Gender	male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Fachhochschule Aachen Institutes - Institute NOWUM-Energy Institute - Institute for Data-based Technologies (IDT)
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor; Program Director
Scientific title (if applicable)	Phd

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-8
Gender	male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Technische Universität München Chair of Sustainable Mobile Drive Systems
Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor;
Scientific title (if applicable)	Phd

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	GE-FGILEC-9
Gender	male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Technische Universität Darmstadt Department of Energy Systems and Energy Technology

Country of work/study	Germany
Position at work (if applicable)	Lecturer; Research group leader
Scientific title (if applicable)	Phd
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	(Bio)fuel synthesis through thermochemical conversion of residual materials Investigation of various gasification technologies, in particular chemical looping gasification

Annotation: It was not possible to generate a participant ID for students.

6.1.2. Italy

Title: Report from organizing FGIs in Italy

Authors: Pisacane Lucio, Fraudatario Maria Camilla, Miranda Cloe

Institution: CNR-IRPPS

Introduction

In Italy, three focus groups were conducted, each designed to engage a specific audience. The first brought together university lecturers, the second involved gender mixed students in political and social sciences with a focus on sustainability, and the third gathered gender mixed students from STEM disciplines related to energy. A total of twenty people participated in the focus groups.

These sessions were held in a hybrid format, allowing most participants to attend in person while also providing the option to join remotely. The majority of those involved came from Sapienza University of Rome, a choice driven by the strong collaboration between CNR-IRPPS and the university, as well as their close geographical proximity, which made participation more convenient. The discussions were led by three researchers from CNR-IRPPS and took place across two CNR locations in Rome

For the STEM focus group, the selection prioritized faculty and students from degree programs related to energy. Meanwhile, in the social sciences, recruitment focused on master's programs that broadly address sustainability and social issues. This research initiative unfolded over a period of seven months. The planning phase began in July 2024, the first focus group was held in November 2024, and the final session concluded in February 2025. The results of each focus group are presented in the chronological order in which they were conducted (see table 1).

Table 1 – Information about focus groups in Italy

FGI	FGI code	Date	Place	Form
FG with universities lecturers	IT_FGI01	5 th November 2024	Central CNR offices, Rome	Hybrid

FG with mixt SSH students	IT_FGI02	10 th December 2024	IRPPS-CNR office, Rome	Hybrid
FG with mixt STEM students	IT_FGI03	10 th February 2025	IRPPS-CNR office, Rome	Hybrid

Organization of IT_FGI01

The focus group with universities lecturers took place at the central CNR premises in Rome on the 5th November 2024. The FG was held in hybrid form with 4 in person participants and 3 online participants. The FG with professor least two hours from 11.00 to 13.00.

The sample was composed by 7 university professors, 5 male and 2 female, recruited mainly at University Sapienza in Rome with different background and career level. 4 were full professor, two associated professors and one researcher. 4 participants were recruited within the Department of Astronautical, Electrical and Energy Engineering (DIAEE) of the University Sapienza in Rome including a full professor delegate to research, one participant was recruited within the Department of Communication and Social Science of the University Sapienza in Rome where she teaches social policies on gender equalities and sustainability. One participant was recruited within the Department of Planning, Design, Architectural Technology of the University Sapienza, where he conducts courses related to energy transition such as energy efficiency of buildings, smart energy systems, and the development of energy scenarios for the decarbonisation. Finally one participant was recruited within the Department of Political and Social Sciences of the Trieste University, where he teaches courses on environmental sociology with a focus on energy transition and socio-spatial inequalities.

Use of renewable energy sources, energy efficiency of buildings and smart energy systems, development of energy scenarios for the decarbonisation

The recruitment process was facilitated by the full professor at DIAEE who Rector's delegate to Research is that supported gEneSys since the beginning of the project. CNR team relationship with SSH departments at La Sapienza helped in recruiting the full professor in Social Science while the other two professor in political science and in architecture were invited without previous relationship in place. The recruitment process was time-consuming, and confirmation of the place and date required several rounds of mail and phone calls. The professor however shown an interest in the FG topics and was supportive in sharing their opinions and vision. The FG was conducted by three researchers from the CNR-IRPPS team using the thematic areas and the guidelines provided by the gEneSys partner responsible for the task.

Organization of IT_FGI02

The focus group with students from Social Sciences and Humanities was held on 10th December 2023 at the CNR-IRPPS venue in Rome. The session lasted two hours and involved eight students, six of whom were present in person and two participated remotely. The gender distribution was three male and five female participants. The students represented various fields of study, including strategic management, innovation and sustainability, social design for sustainability, and gender innovation and inclusion. The participants were primarily from the University of La Sapienza and Guido Carli Luiss University.

The recruitment process was facilitated through personal contacts of the CNR research teams with lecturers at La Sapienza, and the invitation to participate in the focus group was shared within the Sociology Departments through this connection. All students were at the master's level. The selection process successfully ensured the desired number of participants, although there was an overrepresentation of students from a specific master's program focused on gender equality, which may have influenced the results. On the other hand, this overrepresentation contributed to an informed and insightful discussion, benefiting the quality of the collected data.

As planned, the focus group was conducted in accordance with the guidelines. After a common session the FG continued with two separate groups created to discuss the projective techniques. Each group discussed one of the two stories, followed by a shared discussion to consolidate the insights. There was no deviation from the design of the SSH/interdisciplinary students FG.

Organization of IT_FGI03

The focus group with STEM students was held on February 4, 2025, at the IRPPS-CNR, in Rome. It was conducted in a hybrid format to allow the participation of two individuals who could not attend in person. This meeting lasted 2 hours, from 16:30 to 19:30.

There were deviations from the original activity design, as it was not possible to conduct three separate sessions (one with a female group, one with a male group, and one with a mixed group). Instead, only one session with a mixed group was held. The reasons were the limited availability of students, some of whom were busy with their exam session, while others were both working and studying, making their schedules fully occupied.

A total of five people participated in the activity (three females and two males). We did not reach the minimum required number of six participants, as three additional students had confirmed their attendance but did not attend.

The recruitment process was not straightforward, as IRPPS-CNR does not have direct contacts with universities or teaching activities. Without access to stable institutional contacts, we had to rely on connections established through this research process itself. Initially, we reached out to STEM professors who had participated in IT_FGI01, asking for their support in identifying a group of students within their courses.

This approach was unsuccessful, so we sought assistance from students who had participated in IT_FGI02. One of the participants connected us with a mechanical engineering student from La Sapienza University, who became a key figure in organizing this focus group with STEM students. He introduced us to his thesis advisor, who then invited his students to participate in the activity. This channel proved effective, allowing us to gather the necessary confirmations to proceed with the activity.

All participants were from Sapienza University of Rome, enrolled in two programs: Mechanical Engineering and Green Industrial Engineering for Sustainable Development. Four participants were master's students, while one was a bachelor's student (a thesis candidate set to graduate in March 2025).

The difficulty in recruiting participants was influenced by the level of interest in the topic. All participants had a prior critical approach to studying, the university as an institution, and gender disparities. This introduces a bias that may affect the results, as the participants' reflections cannot be considered fully representative of the broader STEM student group.

The thematic areas discussed included educational choices, the factors influencing them, career pathways in the energy sector, enabling factors and barriers, and recommendations. The projective technique used was visual mapping, which we conducted via Whiteboard to ensure that remote participants could also view the content.

Description of FGI lecturers

1. Women's educational choices – energy sector

What are the factors impacting women's decision to pursue studies in energy system?

Reflecting on the factors influencing women's choice of study fields related to energy system, the interviews revealed diverse perspectives. Professors of social science and humanities (SSH) acknowledge that university choices are deeply intertwined with the persistent cultural norms that associate specific disciplines with gender biases. These norms are shaped by family, social contexts, and broader societal influences (IT_FGI01_I06; IT_FGI01_I05; IT_FGI01_I07).

This issue is particularly evident in certain STEM fields, where female enrolment remains a significant challenge. Conversely, other disciplines – such as architecture, humanities, and social sciences – face the opposite concern; an overrepresentation of women compared to the male counterparts. However, this imbalance is not always perceived as problematic, reinforcing a form of gender blindness that affects multiple sectors, including education.

Specifically, an engineering professor denies the existence of gender inequalities in energy-related curricula, arguing that the underrepresentation of women results from free choice rather than cultural conditioning or gender stereotypes. According to this perspective, student make independent decisions unaffected by societal expectations:

«If women prefer studying sociology and men prefer studying engineering, that's totally fine [...]. The important thing is that no one says, 'You shouldn't study engineering because it's not for you,' or, 'Don't go into sociology because that's more of a women's field.' That would be wrong. But as long as there's freedom of choice for everyone, that's what matters—it's great that it can be like that!» (IT_FGI01_I03).

There is broad consensus among professors that gender inequalities in STEM enrolments originate from numerical imbalances at earlier educational stages, particularly in high school and lower secondary school. These differences affect the development of specific skills and limit access to professional opportunities, a pattern also observed in other university settings in northern Italy. One participant referenced 2021 data showing that only 30% STEM students are female. However, this figure aggregates various fields of study and may be skewed by disciplines such as design and architecture. In engineering programs, specifically, female students account for 33.7%, compared to 63.3% male enrolment (IT_FGI01_I07). This trend aligns with data from the University of Rome *La Sapienza*, where the ratio in traditionally male-dominated engineering courses is 10 to 1 (IT_FGI01_I02).

According to interviewees, university departments often struggle to effectively communicate the scope and potential of their academic programs, inadvertently reinforcing reductive and stereotypical perceptions. For instance, electrical engineering is frequently associated with hands-on, technical tasks such as welding or transformer maintenance, while broader aspects like managing complex electrical systems and strategic planning are often overlooked (IT_FGI01_I02; IT_FGI01_I03). Additionally, renaming degree programs—such as using "Energy Engineering" instead of "Electrical Engineering"—could make them more appealing to younger generations (T_FGI01_I03, T_FGI01_I04).

From the perspective of engineering professors, the energy-related engineering sector is perceived as neutral—essentially "asexual" (IT_FGI01_I04)—and free from gender discrimination.

According to this view, the disparities observed at advanced levels (e.g., master's degrees, Ph.D. programs, research, or the energy job market) are simply a natural consequence of an imbalance that begins earlier in the educational pathway. Conversely, the few women who pursue this field tend to demonstrate strong motivation, and their individual choices are seen as a self-correcting factor for the overall gender imbalance in the sector.

Several factors, such as outdated and ineffective institutional communication and the role of families, shape the actual cultural patterns influencing students' choices.

Families play a pivotal role in students' decision-making processes, often shaping their perceptions of educational and career opportunities through a lens that reinforce gender differences. As noted by

interviewees, family attitudes can sometimes be less encouraging for young women choosing among the wide range of university programs. This dynamic is particularly evident *in Southern Europe, including Italy, especially in the southern regions, where, until recently, a woman engineer was seen as an alien* (IT_FGI01_I05). Traditional mindsets assign women roles more consistent with family care responsibilities (IT_FGI01_I05), implicitly limiting their professional aspirations. Ultimately, female university choices are influenced by family attitudes, educational approaches, and cultural norms (IT_FGI01_I03). Added to this is the intergenerational dynamic, as family and education perspectives often reflect values and beliefs rooted in one or two prior generations (IT_FGI01_I06).

Beyond family influence, many students face uncertainty when navigating future opportunities and available professional roles. This confusion, partly due to their young age when making university decisions (IT_FGI01_I05), can also create cumulative barriers to realizing their full potential (IT_FGI01_I02; IT_FGI01_I06). The difficulty in understanding how their interests translate into concrete academic paths is particularly evident in STEM disciplines.

Despite these challenges, younger generations are increasingly drawn to topics such as sustainability, renewable energy, and electric mobility. However, they often struggle to find clear academic pathways that align with these interests.

In conclusion, overcoming these barriers requires an integrated approach involving improved university communication, cultural shifts at the family and societal levels, and concrete guidance to help younger generations align their aspirations with academic choices.

Are these factors different from those of men? In what way?

The gender gap in access to university programs is largely overlooked by many of the interviewees in the focus group. Specifically, discussions centred on the attractiveness of curricula and provided examples where gender imbalances were attributed to cultural patterns or educational background, rather than a deep reflection on the actual gender inequalities at play.

In this context, many engineering fields are perceived as more attractive to men due to their associations with specific sectors, such as Formula 1, automotive engineering, and space exploration (IT_FGI01_I02; IT_FGI01_I04). These fields are linked to collective imaginaries of sports or hobbies that have historically been associated with a predominantly male identity.

However, the most critical factor appears to be the differing educational backgrounds of students. For electrical engineering, most students come from technical schools, which have traditionally been male-dominated. In contrast, high school graduates — with a larger female representation — are more likely to pursue information engineering programs, which include energy engineering. This distinction in initial educational paths seems to have a significant impact on the gender composition of the respective degree programs. As one engineering professor noted:

«From my point of view, the different proportion of men and women in electrical and energy engineering courses is related, rightly or wrongly, to the students' educational background. Electrical engineering students tend to come predominantly from technical schools, which are male-dominated. Meanwhile, in energy engineering programs, there are many more students from high schools, resulting in a more balanced gender representation, though not perfectly equal²» (IT_FGI01_I02).

These differences largely stem from misperceptions or a partial understanding of the programs' objectives. Energy engineering is seen as a broad, multidisciplinary field that integrates various energy domains, while electrical engineering is viewed as a more traditional and specialized discipline. This perception influences high school students, who tend to prefer one engineering field over another based on their educational orientation (IT_FGI01_I03). In contrast, social science curricula exhibited a

greater awareness of gender issues related to energy systems, highlighting how energy professions are often ‘gendered’ or shaped by specific socio-cultural conditions (IT_FGI01_I06I). Overall, the faculty members who participated in the focus group revealed diverse and at times conflicting sensibilities, reflecting the varying approaches within academic programs.

Gender inequalities emerged particularly in initiatives aimed at increasing the appeal of STEM disciplines. These efforts are often guided by marketing logics than by a genuine commitment to structural change required to achieve long-term gender equity.

Engineering lecturers, for example, have expressed concern about how to enhance the attractiveness of energy-related programs. Unlike specializations such as mechanical engineering or aerospace engineering, energy engineering tends not to elicit the same imaginative engagement among prospective students. For many young individuals faced with choosing a field of study, energy-related disciplines lack the symbolic allure capable of inspiring dreams or fostering personal identification (IT_FGI01_I02; IT_FGI01_I03). To address this challenge, some engineering departments have implemented communication strategies aimed at expanding their recruitment pool. These strategies involve the use of social media platforms, youth-oriented language, and influencers who convey brief and engaging messages (IT_FGI01_I04).

However, a social sciences lecturer voiced critical concerns regarding the limitations of these individualized marketing approaches. While acknowledging their good intentions, she warned that such strategies may inadvertently reinforce, rather than challenge, existing gender biases:

«I believe it would be more appropriate to use language that genuinely reflects the cultural dynamics of that generation. Otherwise, we risk perpetuating biases, despite our stated aim of promoting female participation. Young people are not interested in being told that women can do certain things; they want to know what can be done. They engage with a democratized understanding of gender roles, while we—right here, in this very conversation—continue to uphold more traditional conceptions» (IT_FGI01_I06).

This last perspective underscores the importance of moving beyond superficial promotional efforts toward more reflexive and culturally attuned forms of engagement. Achieving meaningful gender equity in STEM requires communication strategies that critically interrogate and transform the gender norms embedded in institutional practices and narratives.

Is it difficult to be a woman in the energy field? Why is that?

Interviewees highlighted various aspects of the difficulties faced by women in the energy field, reflecting on contexts closer to them: scientific research in energy. Although women remain a minority in STEM fields, their presence in research is notable and growing, with increased representation in leadership roles. This progress is not the result of explicit gender policies, but rather of formal recognition of their expertise:

“For example, I want to point out that in my research group and in my scientific field, the national coordinator and the group chair are both women. We have a female president and a female secretary who were elected not because they are women, but because they were judged to be the most suitable candidates for these national coordination roles. This, in my opinion, is a positive sign³” (IT_FGI01_I02).

This positive trend reflects a recent shift in which women are starting to occupy leading positions, although gender parity has yet to be achieved. There are visible areas for improvement that could help reduce the observed gender disparities in university enrolment (IT_FGI01_I04). Another aspect is the strong motivation that characterizes women who choose a career in the energy sector. The awareness of entering a male-dominated environment seems to act as a driving force:

“If I look at the proportion of women at the entry level (in university careers, ed.), for example, the percentage in our department is higher than I observe in the student group. In my opinion, this comes from a stronger motivation among women who decide to pursue these careers, probably because they are aware that they are a minority. So when they choose these careers, it is out of a strong motivation, which naturally tends to stand out⁴” (IT_FGI01_I02).

Being a woman in the energy sector can be a challenge, especially because of the imbalance in numbers in STEM disciplines. However, the increasing presence of women in leadership roles and the inherent motivation that drives many of them to succeed in this field indicate a positive change that deserves further encouragement.

Another issue reported by some participants from STEM fields concerns the relationship between female professors and international students from different cultural backgrounds (primarily referring to students from Asian countries). According to the accounts provided, these students struggle to recognize the authority of female professors.

“There is another fundamental issue: the background of international students. We have many foreign students from Islamic countries, and this poses a significant challenge” (IT_FGI01_I04).

“These difficulties are also noticeable with students from certain countries when they encounter a female professor. There is a clear issue of respect, as they perceive her authority to be lower” (IT_FGI01_I02).

2. Women's careers in the energy sector

What are the factors influencing women to choose energy-related studies and career paths?

Regarding the factors influencing women in pursuing studies and careers in the energy sector, the focus group participants agreed that the energy sector has long been a male-dominated field, both academically and professionally. Gender issues pose a challenge for the sector, affecting both the influx of new personnel from higher education pathways and career progression. However, in the participants' view, the issue should be addressed by making the sector more attractive rather than focusing on equity measures. This perspective is particularly evident in their statements about hiring and career advancement in the energy sector, including research and academia. According to the participants, the only criterion that should matter is meritocracy. Altering the gender imbalance through quotas or reserved positions would violate the rules of public competitions in Italy. Furthermore, all focus group participants firmly believed that recruitment and career advancement should be based solely on merit.

“At Sapienza, we say there are no such issues because in our institution, career advancements are not based on gender but rather on meritocracy. Everything is conducted through public competitions, which, according to our Italian Constitution, cannot impose any constraints—not based on gender, religion, race, or anything else. This is precisely why we face difficulties, for example, with the requirements of the NRRP (National Recovery and Resilience Plan), which state that we must ensure a 40% gender balance in researcher selections. Even after legal consultations, we found that it is impossible to specify in a call for applications that 40% of the winners must belong to one gender rather than another. And it cannot be done differently. Frankly, I wouldn't agree with such an approach—even as a woman. I believe that if someone is to win a position, it should be based on merit, not gender” (IT_FGI01_I01).

3. Organisational culture and gender equality

What are the organisational cultures in relation to gender equality?

Regarding the organizational culture, the participants did not express specific opinions about gender-related dynamics or imbalanced power relations. *“If I look within a department, there is no discrimination in one direction or the other. Fundamentally, it seems to me to be a completely gender-neutral process, in the sense that individuals are evaluated as individuals. However, there is an important initial imbalance: in general, the pool of applicants for research positions is already skewed. So, naturally, the selection process reflects this initial imbalance. But in some ways, it also corrects it. For example, if I look at female representation in our department, it is actually higher than the percentage of female students. In my view, this is likely due to a stronger motivation among the women who choose to pursue this career path, precisely because they are aware that they are a minority. When they choose this career, they do so with a strong sense of purpose, which naturally leads them to stand out”* (IT_FGI01_I02).

In summary, the concept of meritocracy is not questioned, as it is perceived as objective. The interviews did not highlight any merit-related factors that could advantage or disadvantage either gender. Only one testimony raised concerns about the application of merit in selection criteria. This case pertains to the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master’s Degree in Sustainable Transportation and Electrical Power Systems (STEPS), where the admission and selection criteria were revised. Initially, the preselection criteria were strictly quantitative and based on grade averages. However, the selection process was gradually adjusted to encourage greater female participation. Currently, all applications from women are pre-admitted to the interview stage, regardless of their grade point averages, which would otherwise disqualify them from the selection process (a detailed description is available in the best practices section of this report).

One of the participants points out that, beyond the formal aspects of organizational culture, a range of practices persist in carrying out activities that, in fact, are not favorable for women, who still bear disproportionate family workloads compared to men.

“I think of everything related to internationalization or publishing activities, where a specific commitment is required from faculty members that goes beyond a clearly defined timeframe. This is undoubtedly a disadvantage for those individuals—I’m referring to women, but this also increasingly applies to younger generations—who have significant external commitments and heavy workloads. So, I would suggest considering, if the question is about organizational culture, not only the regulatory and normative aspects of our departmental activities but also those practices that are constantly present alongside the regulatory framework and may, in some way, influence participation and presence” (IT_FGI01_I06).

4. Teaching

How is gender integrated into curricula (courses)?

In the master degree programs in Engineering and Architecture, gender is not integrated into the curriculum. At most, the issue of the underrepresentation of women may lead to informal conversations between faculty members and doctoral students, as reported by some participants (IT_FGI01_I04, IT_FGI01_I03, and IT_FGI01_I05). Even when engaging with students about their motivations for choosing their fields of study, the topic is not addressed from a gender perspective. This is exemplified by a professor in Electrical Engineering:

“In the classroom I do not specifically address these topics. I mean, I try to ask all students, both men and women, what motivated them to enroll in Electrical Engineering and what their future

perspectives are. If someone transferred to the master's program from another, I ask them about their reasons for doing so. But specifically addressing the male-female distinction, I don't address that" (IT_FGI01_I03).

In contrast, a professor from the Department of Communication and Social Research reports that attention to gender issues is integrated into the activities of the Equal Opportunity Committee (CUG), a body dedicated to promoting a culture of equal opportunities, combating all forms of violence or discrimination, and fostering organizational well-being.

"In that setting [CUG], we often discuss gender issues. We are somewhat a unique case, sui generis, precisely because, as a play on words, we deal with these topics. However, when reviewing the course monitoring report, which highlights aspects such as dropouts and job placement one, three, and five years after graduation, we often question how significant the gender factor is. As a result, we engage with both male and female students and take their feedback seriously. We generally provide them with opportunities to contribute in a practical and active way" (IT_FGI01_I06).

5. Good practice

What are the good practice initiatives that support the increase of women in the energy programmes/ sector?

A good practice mentioned is the “Open Doors” initiative at Sapienza University of Rome, aimed at guiding prospective students in choosing their degree programs. According to a SSH professor participant (sociology), this initiative is directed not only at prospective students but also, and especially, at their families, with the goal of breaking down the stereotypes that influence the students' choices. The participant reports her experience with this initiative: *"What we observe during orientation processes is that the focus often shifts to the parents and even grandparents, rather than the students themselves, who are often reluctant to engage with us. This highlights how families shape their stereotypes about educational paths and their children's future expectations, placing a predominant emphasis on the economic aspect of education rather than its cultural value. Rarely is the message conveyed: 'Study so that you'll have the broadest options to achieve personal fulfillment.' In this context, if appropriate tools were available, they could be used to emphasize that the job market for energy professions is not gendered and is not determined by specific conditions"* (IT_FGI01_I069).

Another good practice, reported by a STEM professor (engineering), concerns the selection process for student admission to degree programs. The participant highlighted the experience of the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degree Sustainable Transportation and Electrical Power Systems (STEPS), conducted between the University of Sapienza of Rome (Italy), the University of Nottingham (UK), the University of Oviedo (Spain), and the Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra (Portugal). The STEPS program has a limited number of scholarships —about 20 per year—and receives an average of 400 applications annually.

Initially, the selection process involved a preliminary screening based on CVs, followed by selection through an interview. However, the professor noted that, particularly among international applicants, women in certain countries tend to have lower grade point averages than men. As a result, while the preselection criteria were initially rigidly quantitative and based on grade averages, the selection process gradually adapted to allow more women to enroll. Now, all applications from women are pre-admitted to the interview stage, regardless of their grade point averages, which would otherwise disqualify them from the selection process. This experience also allowed the professors to observe that the actual abilities and skills of the women were much higher than what their grades indicated:

"What we've observed—and what has positively surprised us—is that even women with initially lower grade averages demonstrate, during the technical interview, the same competencies as, and sometimes even superior to men who may have higher grades. As a result, they are admitted on merit, based on

their performance in the interview, which evaluates various technical aspects and thoroughly assesses the candidates' preparation. This is a practice we've also highlighted to the European Community, and it has been recognized as a good practice. However, it can only be implemented when a degree program has a limited number of spots and a structured selection process" (IT_FGI01_I02).

6. Recommendations

What are the recommendations for changes that can improve women's participation in the energy sector?

- **Gender blind recommendations**

Linked to the narrative of “departmental gender-neutrality”, even when participants were asked to consider how female participation in energy-related degree programs could be increased, the recommendations offered were gender-blind. For instance, one suggestion to attract more students to the Electrical Engineering program—marked by a significant shortage of enrollments, according to IT_FGI01_I04 - was to adopt the language of “young people” through social media and influencers. The underlying idea is that by using youth-oriented language, both male and female students could be reached automatically, without any reflection on the gender differences within the 'youth' group or on how such language might convey and perpetuate stereotypical gender norms.

“The message must use the language of young people, and we've been told it's a mistake to say 'study this [engineering] because it guarantees a secure job.' You have to make them understand that this is a field where dreams can be fulfilled [...] So the idea was to immediately go to the well-known channels like social media or short video content. Writing articles in newspapers is useless; I've even tried it, but you have to use specific channels. [...] I'm broadening the discussion from gender parity to young people in general because, in my opinion, if the message is conveyed effectively, it automatically goes beyond the gender issue” (IT_FGI01_I04).

- **Targeted educational guidance**

A lecture in SSH emphasizes the importance of directing students toward STEM programs related to the energy sector. In particular, this educational guidance must be designed carefully, considering how young people perceive gender roles today. The goal is to avoid reinforcing outdated cultural biases, especially if the younger generation has already moved past them (IT_FGI01_I06).

“The younger generations have a perception of gender—if you will, a feminine condition—that is somewhat different from ours. Not only from ours, because if I may, except for perhaps IT_FGI01_I07 and a few others, we are one or two generations ahead, but they have been socialized to the idea of gender more recently, at a time when certain achievements have been fully realized. Therefore, despite the continuous influences from social media, textbooks, study materials, elementary school aids, or middle school books, it is difficult to notice a clear separation of gender roles or a predetermined path for women in education and work, as was the case in the past. In orientation processes, we are observing a certain neutralization of these phenomena, which is why it is essential to use appropriate language and work through participatory bottom-up processes. However, I believe it would be advisable—regardless of who the influencer is—to use language that is truly embedded in the cultural dynamics of that generation. Otherwise, we risk perpetuating biases, even those aimed at enhancing the status of women, but in a counterproductive way. They are not interested in being told that women can do certain things; they are interested in understanding what can be done in general, as they experience a democratization of specific gender concepts. This is something that we, even here in this very discussion, are still grappling with today” (IT_FGI01_I069).

- **Socialization and Dissemination of good models**

Participants emphasized the importance of social engagement and promoting positive role models in the energy sector, similar to recent efforts to highlight women's achievements in other traditionally male-dominated fields. Sociology researcher IT_FGI01_I07, for example, mentioned Maria Federica Putti, a referee in Italy's Serie A football league who is also pursuing a PhD in labor studies at the University of Bergamo. Another prominent example is astronaut Samantha Cristoforetti of the Italian Space Agency, whose accomplishments have helped challenge gender norms in her field.

“Astronautical engineering is currently seeing an enormous number of female students, and this is probably also thanks to all that has been done in the last three or four years through the various interventions by Samantha Cristoforetti. [...] We should find something that stimulates the minds of female students” (IT_FGI01_I03).

Other participants emphasized the crucial role of families in guiding young students and the need to overcome gendered perceptions that have historically shaped attitudes toward certain professions. Additionally, the discussion addressed motherhood, which is often seen as a factor that places women at a disadvantage in career advancement, particularly due to the burden of care responsibilities placed upon them.

Description of FGI with students from social sciences

a. Educational choices and career pathways

Why did the student have chosen energy and environmental as well sustainability [or any other field of study the participants are enrolled in] as a field of study?

Among the reasons that led SSH students to pursue degree programs on sustainability-related topics is the desire to conduct studies on sustainability that are not strictly focused on economics or classical economic approaches but instead integrate a broader perspective on sustainability and innovation (IT_FGI02_I01 and IT_FGI02_I02). A female sociologist, enrolled in Master Degree in Social Design for Sustainability, Innovation and Gender inclusion affirms that the course she is enrolled in is one of the few courses in Italy that offer project design and development that does not have an economic focus, but rather focuses on sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion from a social sciences perspective (IT_FGI02_I02). A student with a bachelor's degree in Communication, Technologies, and Digital Cultures explains that she became interested in the topic of social sustainability during her master's program, where she was first introduced to this subject. She later decided to further explore this field through an internship at the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, where she is working on assessing the social impact of the National Innovative Program for Housing Quality (PINQuA), funded by the Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan (IT_FGI02_I03).

Some influential moments that sparked interest in sustainability include internships and volunteering experiences⁵ student (IT_FGI02_I05) reports, her Universal Civil Service experience [international volunteer program] in Spain during her bachelor's degree in International Cooperation and Development led her to develop an interest in social project design within the field of urban regeneration. At the same time, the curricular internship she is currently undertaking during her master's degree at the Equal Opportunities Commission of Rome has further strengthened her academic interests (IT_FGI02_I05). Another participant shared her experience of civil service abroad, which helped her understand the necessary skills and competencies required in the job market. “I did my Civil Service [international volunteer program] in London, focusing on sustainability, but in relation to the inclusion of minors. During my time in London, I noticed some gaps that, in my opinion, exist in many organizations working on international projects. That's why I found this master's program, which could provide me with skills in context research and project design” (IT_FGI02_I06).

What are the perspectives of work in the energy sector by SSH graduates? Do they consider pursuing a career in this sector?

Career perspectives are still undefined and do not directly relate to the energy transition sector. Some participants have not yet decided what type of career to pursue, while others have identified a general area of interest through their studies and internship experiences, such as urban regeneration (IT_FGI02_I05), sustainability outreach or healthy, quality work (IT_FGI02_I07), and sustainability planning for public administrations (IT_FGI02_I08).

What are the factors that can facilitate or limit the career in energy/ sustainability sector?

Participants were asked whether they had previously reflected on gender issues related to the energy transition workforce. This question brought to light some factors that limit careers in this sector. It emerged that there is often a lack of awareness regarding the social aspects of sustainability and energy transition. As a result, STEM graduates—mostly women—do not perceive it as a potential career sector for them. One participant mentioned that she became familiar with the social dimension of these sectors during her master's studies, where guest speakers from NGOs were sometimes invited to courses (IT_FGI02_I05). Before this experience, there had been no prior orientation toward this study and career path, and many other potentially interested individuals might never be exposed to it.

Despite the expansion of the sector, including private initiatives, and the increasing demand for skills beyond the technical-scientific field, a significant barrier remains: the lack of awareness about available opportunities. This issue was also raised by another female participant, who stated: *“I don't know what roles are in demand in this sector specifically, but also from a broader perspective, not necessarily related to the transition”* (IT_FGI02_I02). Although new positions related to sustainability, including its social dimensions, are emerging, education and career guidance seem to be failing in directing young people toward these new professions.

On the other hand, another female participant perceives a higher level of discrimination against social science skills, followed by gender-based discrimination. She shared her experience working in public administration within one of the Mission Units of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan⁶, where she is the only expert in social sciences. When tasks requiring social research skills—such as conducting a survey—need to be carried out, methodological expertise is not recognized, implying that anyone can perform these activities without specific training. However, this is not the case for competencies in non-SSH. This is where discrimination lies (IT_FGI02_I03).

Another factor that can limit career opportunities—one that can be viewed intersectionally as adding to gender and disciplinary discrimination—is the territorial factor. The question arises as to whether innovative and sustainable projects will create new jobs in smaller towns or only in larger cities such as Rome, Milan, Naples, and Florence (IT_FGI02_I01). However, the participant challenges the common perception in Italy that there are no opportunities in smaller cities. While there is room for improvement, the reality is not as dire as often assumed. It was discussed that, in fact, many projects are now being developed in Southern Italy.

A further reflection was made using the projective storytelling technique to explore the obstacles and enabling factors that women may encounter due to gender-related issues, which influence both their educational choices and career pathways. Some participants identified with the protagonist of the story for various reasons. Student IT_FGI02_I05 shared that throughout her studies, she repeatedly received the message that, on her own, without the support of a technical expert in the field, she could achieve very little. This dominant perspective on SSH education can be a barrier. However, she has not internalized this view; instead, she critically engages with it, highlighting the valuable contributions that this type of education can offer (these points are discussed in more detail in the recommendations section).

Among the enabling factors in career pathways, the discussion emphasized the crucial role of a supportive figure who can help counteract stereotypes that push women away from male-dominated sectors.

“This is something I think about especially for women in STEM fields. Since there is such a strong gender stereotype, they are often discouraged from pursuing these careers from the very beginning. So being encouraged and supported in this field helps break down these stereotypes” (IT_FGI02_I05).

This mentor or role model should possess specific qualities to genuinely support women’s careers. For example, a leader should be able to recognize and appreciate an individual’s potential and soft skills, acknowledging the contributions they can bring (IT_FGI02_I07). This also implies that leaders and managers should be educated to make decisions in a different way—one that is more open, yet also cautious and mindful (IT_FGI02_I08). Another enabling factor to counteract the barriers created by gender inequalities in women’s career advancement in the sector is ensuring the protection of individuals—not in terms of favoritism, but in guaranteeing gender equity (IT_FGI02_I02).

b. Field of study and organizational culture

- i. *Are there issues related to energy included in the study programme? If yes how? Please refer to different aspects (e.g. social, technological)?***

Although students come from master’s degree programs related to sustainability science (e.g., *Social Design for Sustainability, Innovation and Gender Inclusion, and Strategic Management, Innovation, and Sustainability*), the energy system—considering both its social and technological dimensions—is not a central focus in their curricula. However, throughout various courses, discussions have emerged regarding gender imbalances in the job market and misogynistic attitudes in the workplace environments. These issues are often linked to the underrepresentation of women in STEM-related master’s degrees, which continue to be shaped by persistent stereotypes. Nevertheless, these discussions do not provide specific insights into the energy sector (IT_FGI02_I07).

When addressing the energy transition, students recognize the valuable contributions of key stakeholders who are invited as guest speakers to share their experiences in applied projects. Only during these specific seminars, the energy transition and the energy system are analyzed in depth, particularly in terms of their social implications:

“I discovered this social aspect of sustainability and the energy transition during my master’s degree. Before that, I also mistakenly tended to associate this type of work with professionals from STEM fields and did not fully grasp the social dimension. Thanks to the contributions of various guest speakers in different courses, I became aware of this aspect. For example, I remember Legambiente, which struck me precisely for the social component embedded in its projects. I do not recall the exact details, but I remember thinking at that moment that this is an entire field that has been emerging in recent years, whereas before, we tended to associate it only with a technical domain” (IT_FGI02_I05).

“If we shift the focus to the consumer, it becomes really interesting [...] I remember that last year, as part of the public policy course, we had the opportunity to hear from one of our former colleagues, who conducted a study on energy communities in a neighborhood of Rome. She explained how, by contributing expertise from our field of study within the company managing the project, it was essential to engage with the communities where the initiative could be implemented. This engagement allowed them to first assess the level of energy poverty among households, then develop solutions, and most importantly, design informational and educational campaigns to raise consumer awareness about energy use. In that case, women played a fundamental role” (IT_FGI02_I07).

More generally, students from both selected study programs acquire knowledge about the energy system primarily through seminars and guest lectures; however, this topic is not properly integrated into their core curriculum. It appears that sustainability is approached as an adaptation to the pre-existing expertise of faculty members, who may lack specific skills or interdisciplinary perspectives in

this field. In this regard, students have expressed concerns that knowledge is conveyed as fragmented pieces of a puzzle, which they are then expected to assemble without being provided with the necessary tools (IT_FGI02_I03, IT_FGI02_I02, IT_FGI02_I01).

Someone else, meanwhile, suggested that this challenge is only a matter of time, due to the fact that they are the first cohorts of these new master's programs. Hence, they believe that in the coming years both course content and teaching methodologies will improve to better fill these gaps (IT_FGI02_I04, IT_FGI02_I01).

ii. Is gender analysis / gender dimension integrated into energy-related courses? Please provide examples and discuss its impact on the participants' experiences of their studies and career expectations.

Students have expressed criticism regarding how the gender dimension is addressed in their courses. Across the broader education system, gender-related topics are largely absent from both bachelor's and master's degree programs (IT_FGI02_I08, IT_FGI02_I01). Even in programs where gender is a key focus – such as *Social Design for Sustainability, Innovation, and Gender Inclusion* – it is treated as a distinct subject rather than being integrated into its intersectional aspects with other social dimensions and disciplines (IT_FGI02_I03).

Three main concerns emerge from students' discussions:

- Gender is approached in an outdated and anachronistic manner (IT_FGI02_I03, IT_FGI02_I02).
- The inclusion of gender topics in courses depends heavily on individual lecturers' sensitivity to the issue (IT_FGI02_I06, IT_FGI02_I05, IT_FGI02_I01).
- No dedicated textbooks—either in Italian or in their original languages (such as English)—are adopted for the courses (IT_FGI02_I08, IT_FGI02_I03).

Regarding the first issue, students argue that gender-related topics are often taught in dedicated courses by focusing on early feminist movements. This approach is considered reductive, as it fails to adequately explore gender implications in other relevant fields (IT_FGI02_I02). Furthermore, senior lecturers are often not update on contemporary gender issues, unlike students who are more exposed to international influences. Generational differences significantly affect the way gender is taught (IT_FGI02_I03).

The second concern pertains to faculty sensitivity to gender issues. Although lecturers are well-qualified in their respective fields (such as economics, public policy, and statistics), they often teach in a gender-blind manner. This issue is particularly evident among male faculty (IT_FGI02_I06, IT_FGI02_I05, IT_FGI02_I01), who are recruited into these new master's programs for their specialized skills but then neglect the broader context of study in which they are placed (IT_FGI02_I05). This lack of awareness is also reflected in the use of less inclusive language when conveying key concepts (IT_FGI02_I06).

The third aspect highlights the need for textbooks that truly integrate gender dimensions into the various subjects. Currently, the textbooks mainly used in courses such as sociology and methodology lack this integration. There are only attempts to adapt this knowledge to fields such as sustainability, the energy system or gender studies, which leaves significant gaps in the curriculum (IT_FGI02_I03).

iii. What is the overall climate/culture regarding the gender equality at the university/department?

From the students' perspective, the departments they attend appear to be characterized by gender equality, at least in terms of faculty composition. Students in the *Social Design for Sustainability*,

Innovation, and Gender Inclusion program noted a more balanced representation, with a higher proportion of women in both teaching and managerial roles. Notably, *the president of their curriculum is a woman* (IT_FGI02_I06). However, despite this apparent balance, students acknowledge that they cannot fully grasp what happens at higher institutional levels. They do not rule out the possibility of underlying gender disparities or challenges to gender equality at the top of the academic hierarchy (IT_FGI02_I05).

Although gender considerations are rarely integrated into the teaching approach of technical courses, students generally recognize that gender equality is valued as a core principle within their department (IT_FGI02_I05, IT_FGI02_I06).

According to student from the *Strategic Management, Innovation, and Sustainability* program, the department's culture regarding gender equality reflects a certain dualism:

Starting with faculty members and then moving into the more "traditional" field of economics—the so-called old-school approach—there is still a slight male predominance. It is not overwhelming, but most professors are men. However, as we shift toward more contemporary fields, there is a stronger female presence in the department (IT_FGI02_I01).

In this sense, the academic climate of the department is perceived to be shaped by the overlap between disciplinary field and gender representation.

c. Recommendations

i. What should change in the SSH programs related to energy/sustainability?

The discussion primarily focused on what should change in how SSH education on sustainability-related topics is perceived. In fact, the contribution that SSH can bring to the sector is still not fully recognized. Among these contributions, were mentioned that SSH experts can add value to the workforce by enriching discussions and fostering a diversity of opinions (IT_FGI02_I04). In addition, they contribute critical thinking, asking different questions that complicate the understanding of reality and how to intervene in it, for example, through social impact actions (IT_FGI02_I03). These professionals can also provide insights into the responsibility and implications of decisions and implemented interventions (IT_FGI02_I02). However, this discussion once again highlights the lack of recognition of these competencies as the result of a structured educational path. Instead, they are often mistaken for mere common sense (IT_FGI02_I02).

ii. What should change to make this field more attractive to woman?

The fact that women are not considered suitable for the sector is seen by one participant as a self-fulfilling prophecy, effectively discouraging them from pursuing careers in the field (IT_FGI02_I05). Therefore, one of the proposed solutions is:

- Change dominant narrative through **different communication strategies and initiatives aimed at encouraging women** to take these career paths.

Other recommendations concern **schools and universities**:

- combating gender-based role stereotypes by revising school textbooks
- providing university guidance that is freer from stereotypes
- using non-sexist language

“Even though there is a lot of discussion about simply changing job titles to their feminine form, I still have a friend who graduated in industrial engineering and had ‘Congratulations, Engineer’ written on her cake in the masculine form. It might seem trivial, but in reality, it unconsciously prevents you from

freely considering certain career paths. Then people say that women are more suited to the humanities and men to STEM fields, but there is a fundamental issue. If the PNRR conditions state that 30% of employees must be women and 30% must be young people, but we don't find women in the sector because they haven't even pursued degrees in these fields, then that's a problem. And there's always debate about whether it's really true that there aren't enough women, but the fact is that many don't even start studying these subjects in the first place” (IT_FGI02_I03).

Another participant recommends **energy consumer education at the household level:**

Drawing from personal experience with her parents—where her mother primarily handled energy consumption for household appliances, while her father managed energy-related expenses—she pointed out that women might have less knowledge about energy consumption and available alternatives (such as renewables), making them more distanced from energy-related topics.

“It has to start at home, because if you don't even know the world you live in—if you are unaware, simply because you haven't been educated about consumption—then, especially for women in this case, you will never be drawn to a sector like this” (IT_FGI02_I05).

Other recommendation concerns the **work environment:**

- Educate leaders to recognize the contribution and potential of experts.

“A leader or manager who has to make decisions must also be educated in decision-making; otherwise, they are inclined to choose the easiest, most familiar option” (IT_FGI02_I08).

Description of FGI with Mixed-gender Students from STEM

a. Educational Choices

i. What Are the Educational Choices and Pathways?

To analyze the students' educational choices and pathways, we started from their background developed through bachelor level studies. All the participants hold a bachelor's degree in different branches of engineering (e.g., Mechanical Engineering, Aerospace Engineering, Engineering with a sustainability or energy focus). Several participants described starting out in a general engineering field (such as Mechanical or Aerospace) and later shifting their focus to energy. They cited motivations such as personal interest, broader societal relevance, and opportunities for positive impact.

One participant, IT_FGI03_I05, was completing a bachelor's degree in Mechanical Engineering but planned to switch to Energy Engineering in his master's studies. He explained that although he initially sought a strong technical foundation in mechanical topics, he discovered that his real passion was in “the world of energy,” where he felt he could contribute more directly to sustainability and the energy transition. IT_FGI03_I04 had begun in Aerospace Engineering, only to realize that it did not align with her long-term interests. She mentioned feeling drawn to sustainability, including energy-related dimensions. She states that the fact that STEM fields are male-dominated actually motivated her to choose this path.

“There was some influence related to gender, honestly, because the STEM field often seems like a glass ceiling for women, especially when I had to choose my undergraduate degree a few years ago. So, I liked the idea—having also studied at a science-oriented high school—of entering a field that is traditionally male-dominated. That's why I was also drawn to STEM subjects” (IT_FGI03_I04).

Ultimately, she considered moving into an Energy Engineering master's program or a more sustainability-focused track bridging industrial engineering and energy.

T_FGI03_I03 initially completed an undergraduate degree in Aerospace Engineering but then enrolled in a program that combined management, governance, and technical aspects related to sustainability and energy. She described discovering her program by chance, via online research. While physically located at a campus in Latina (a city 1 hour south of Rome) the program offered her a way to combine ethical concerns about sustainability with technical competence.

IT_FGI03_I01 after a Mechanical Engineering bachelor's, chose a master's track focusing on energy within the same department. Although he found some of the courses overly technical, he realized that if one digs deeper, the topics connect strongly to environmental and societal goals—though he lamented that universities often fail to highlight these broader purposes.

T_FGI03_I02 came from a high school with a classical curriculum (i.e., little advanced math or science) but decided to pursue Mechanical Engineering. She described discovering sustainability and climate-change topics during an apprenticeship (in Italian “alternanza scuola-lavoro”). That experience sparked her curiosity, leading her ultimately to specialize in energy in her master's.

These diverse pathways demonstrate that educational choices for STEM students, especially those aiming at energy-focused fields, can be nonlinear. Participants often described initial enrollment in broader engineering disciplines (Mechanical, Aerospace) before narrowing their focus to energy and sustainability.

“I want to change from Mechanical Engineering to Energy Engineering, because it fascinates me more—both the plan of studies and the idea that I could do something about the energy transition” (IT_FGI03_I05).

“In my master's, I found a course bridging governance and technical aspects on sustainability. I think it's vital to combine an ethical motivation with engineering tools” (T_FGI03_I03).

ii. What were the key factors identified as influencing a decision to pursue a degree in energy-related fields?

Participants pointed to the factors that influenced them to pursue energy-focused studies. Some of these decisions emerged later in their academic trajectory, often after exposure to hands-on projects or personal experiences.

1. Desire to contribute to society and sustainability: Some female participants mentioned that they valued not only the technical challenges of engineering but also the social and environmental impact. Energy fields, in their view, represent one of the most direct ways to address climate change, resource scarcity, and other global challenges.

“I have an ethical drive linked to sustainability. I feel a duty to listen to that drive” (IT_FGI03_I03).

“I liked the idea of doing something socially useful—something that can really make a difference” (IT_FGI03_I02).

2. **High school projects:** IT_FGI03_I02 spoke about an apprenticeship project called “Green Jobs for a Green Future,” which introduced her to sustainability topics and made her realize that an engineering approach could serve as a powerful tool to combat climate challenges.

3. **Practical experiences and internships:** Even during bachelor's studies there can be influential experiences that reorient or focus the interests of students towards energy and allow them to make choices for future master's studies. A male participant mentioned that an influential moment during his bachelor’s studies was an internship in a private company in Mozambique: “*That direct experience made me realize energy is essential for development and that I wanted to work in that field (IT_FGI03_I05).*” During this experience, he participated in the “African Energy Week” and learned about solutions in renewable energy, off-grid systems, and local development.

iii. Who was a source of inspiration to follow this pathway?

When asked who or what inspired them, participants gave a range of answers, indicating that both individuals and broader experiences played a role.

1. **Role models in the family:** A female participant highlighted the importance of having female role models. Her mother, a physicist working on fusion at ENEA (the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy, and Sustainable Development) has been an example of successful women in STEM field. “*My mother is a physicist [...] so I was definitely interested in energy fields and also interested in this world that was already part of my family's education*” (IT_FGI03_I03).

2. **School Teachers or Professors:** A few participants mentioned specific school teachers (e.g., in high school) who recognized or nurtured their mathematical and scientific potential. A male participant pointed out that certain high school teachers—especially those who taught practical or technical subjects—could spark an interest in engineering. However, he also stated that the orientation was generally poor, with minimal official guidance about energy as a career path (IT_FGI03_I01).

Two other participants explicitly refer to have not had any role models or inspiration. “*I personally did not have a mentor or figure of reference. It was an individual decision.*” (IT_FGI03_I02).

iv. What were the barriers and obstacles?

Participants identified multiple barriers they faced along the educational pathways. These included stereotypical assumptions about women in STEM, biases from faculty members, and the organizational structure of engineering education.

1. **Sexist stereotypes and misogynistic behaviors:** At the school level, participants highlighted issues such as differential treatment of children based on gender (IT_FGI03_I04) and gender stereotypes influencing peer dynamics, which, in extreme cases, could lead to bullying or discriminatory practices (IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I05). Additionally, there was a general tendency to associate STEM subjects with practical skills traditionally deemed more suited to

men (IT_FGI03_I01). At the university level, both in bachelor's and master's degree programs, participants noted that sexist attitudes were more frequently attributed to lecturers than to peers (IT_FGI03_I02, IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I04). Some also reported that women are often perceived as less suited for careers in STEM fields (IT_FGI03_I05).

Misogynistic attitudes of lectures have also been reported which hinder equal experience of engineering education. IT_FGI03_I04 described microaggressions from senior lecturer, who used inappropriate remarks objectifying women and reinforcing assumptions about their presumed lack of competence in engineering: *“I remember examples like: ‘We need to calculate the flow velocity of this river—imagine that on the other side of the bank, there's a beautiful girl you want to reach.’ Aside from the fact that this is an objectification of women (which is already problematic), it also assumes heterosexuality and is clearly directed at a male audience. This means that, regardless of the actual composition of the class, some professors take it for granted that they are speaking to men in an engineering classroom. This is important because, even if these things may seem minor, they reflect a certain mindset and unconscious biases that these people carry with them”* (IT_FGI03_I04).

Additional misogynistic behaviors that may be considered microaggressions have been reported, with requests for details not to be shared.

2. Lack of effective dissemination of engineering study options and applications in the field of sustainability: IT_FGI03_I04 argued that Engineering suffers from a negative image among high school students who care about sustainability. Engineering, unlike fields like Biology, is not perceived as tool to address environmental issues. This common perception may discourage some women from enrolling. Other issue is that engineering programs are not always well-publicized, resulting in very few enrollees. E.g. IT_FGI03_I03 is the only enrolled students of her master's degree program in Green Industrial Engineering for Sustainable Development. She considered it a barrier that affects individuals who do not already have strong awareness of the possibilities in engineering.
3. Little support for working students: Some participants (e.g., IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I01) noted how the system makes it difficult to combine employment with studies. They saw the bureaucracy around “working-student status” as a barrier that discourages, among others, women who may face additional outside responsibilities or financial constraints.

v. What were enablers in those processes in the educational choices?

Participants identified enabling factors that help women enter and persist in engineering and in energy-related pathways.

1. Role models: At both primary and secondary school, role models were identified as crucial for recognizing and appreciating the women in both society and the workforce (IT_FGI03_I01). These role models should be supported by family members and teachers who can promote gender equality and integration (IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I05).

2. Active role of teachers: Regarding secondary school, the active role of teachers in fostering critical thinking among students was underscored, particularly concerning social issues that should be fully integrated into the ministry's study programs (IT_FGI03_I01).
3. Family Encouragement: Family support can be an enabling factor for pursuing scientific careers, for both boys and girls (IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I05).
4. Scholarships and internships: Regarding secondary school, participants emphasized the importance of internships focused on social and environmental issues, which they considered essential for future generations of students (IT_FGI03_I02). At the bachelor's and master's degree levels, enablers included scholarships or internships in energy-related fields and a community-based approach (IT_FGI03_I02, IT_FGI03_I05).
5. Reporting and sanctioning discrimination: establishment of dedicated desks for reporting cases of discrimination or misogyny and receiving support (IT_FGI03_I04).
6. Modify study programs: In terms of contents, participants highlighted the importance of courses that integrate themes of empathy, social responsibility, environmental sustainability, and ethics (IT_FGI03_I03). Furthermore, they suggested that technical curricula should include critical thinking skills that allow professionals to have a positive impact on society (IT_FGI03_I01).
7. Targeted communication and guidance: Participants also suggested improvements in communication channels (IT_FGI03_I01), organizing events and workshops centered on women in STEM careers, and enhancing orientation desks in schools (IT_FGI03_I04).
8. Supportive peers: supportive friendships and peer collaboration formed a buffer against discouraging remarks.

b. Career pathways

i. What are the career pathways for women?

The women participants described a similar career trajectory, beginning with a bachelor's degree in aerospace or mechanical engineering, then a master's degree in nanotechnology or energy engineering. However, as their interests evolved or they gained work experience, many reconsidered their choices, seeking more informed career paths aligned with their aspirations.

“Aerospace engineering itself—well, I chose it because at the time it aligned more with my interests. And then, for my master's, I went with nanotechnology. But next year, I'd like to either switch to energy engineering or follow the path IT_FGI03_I03 is taking, which is somewhere between energy and industrial engineering, with a stronger focus on sustainability” (IT_FGI03_I04)

This pattern was not exclusive to women; in general, most students, regardless of gender, initially faced uncertainty in selecting their field of study and defining their professional goals (IT_FGI03_I05, IT_FGI03_I01). This often led to adjustments during their academic trajectories, with many opting for a master's degree in energy engineering to engage with topics related to sustainability and the energy transition.

ii. What were the crucial factors that shaped those pathways?

Participants identified several factors that shaped their career paths in the energy sector. In addition to personal beliefs and values related to energy transition and sustainability, as well as the pursuit of tangible income, other key experiences—such as securing the first job, completing an internship, participating in an Erasmus program abroad, or writing a thesis—were crucial in shaping these career trajectories.

These experiences helped participants better focus their aspirations. As IT_FGI03_I04 reported, during her Erasmus in Switzerland, she came to understand that her profession could have a technical role in sustainability while also serving a social purpose:

“But by going abroad, you really get a stronger sense that engineering can actually be applied—that is, that the things you study can be used toward something that feels like a mission you truly connect with” (IT_FGI03_I04).

At times, the first job or the opportunity to apply practical skills during an internship also contributed to shaping a clearer understanding of one's role, further consolidating career paths:

“I had regrets about my choice of bachelor's degree because, even though I work in the aerospace field, I don't bite the hand that feeds me when it comes to the area I originally pursued. However, I realized that it is not the right field for me—I feel a strong ethical drive, particularly toward sustainability, which I believe I must follow. As a result, I decided to enroll in Green Industrial Engineering for Sustainable Development” (IT_FGI03_I03).

“I went to Africa for three months, working on smaller energy projects and participating in events such as the African Energy Week [...] In fact, my thesis now focuses on what energy transition means in Africa [...] I realized it is a crucial aspect of the future, one that is moving forward both from an environmental and engineering standpoint. With this kind of expertise, I could be useful not only in the social field but also in technical areas, in technological innovation. This direct experience made me understand that the energy sector and the transition to decarbonization are incredibly interesting, and that's what I want to pursue” (IT_FGI03_I05).

iii. Who was a source of inspiration to follow this pathway?

Regarding the decision to pursue a university and/or professional career (as opposed to the choice of field of study), none of the participants reported having had a formal mentor. Participants primarily emphasized strong personal motivation in achieving their goals (IT_FGI03_I02, IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I04). In some cases, familial role models emerged, with relatives in similar professional roles who inspired participants through their work experiences (IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I05). Only in rare instances were university professors perceived as significant support figures in guiding students' career paths and professional choices (IT_FGI03_I01 and IT_FGI03_I02). However, the prevailing sentiment was that such supportive professors were more of an exception than the norm, and that career guidance was mostly the result of personal initiative.

iv. What are the barriers and obstacles in career pathways for women?

During the projective technique exercise, participants identified multiple barriers and obstacles in women's career pathways:

1. Sexist stereotypes and misogynistic behaviors: during the transition to the job market and career progression, participants expressed that gender stereotypes persist, contributing to disparities such as the gender pay gap and differential treatment based on physical appearance rather than professional expertise (IT_FGI03_I05, IT_FGI03_I04). These stereotypes were also seen as reinforcing additional challenges women may face, including maternity and family care responsibilities (IT_FGI03_I05, IT_FGI03_I04, IT_FGI03_I03).

Some participants highlighted that in professions related to engineering, persist serious forms of sexist stereotypes. These take the form of undermining women's competencies or misogynistic allusions. IT_FGI03_I03 recounted a story from her workplace, though it also reflects on the broader culture, where she was introduced to important collaborators simply as the gender quota (in Italian “quota rosa”), entirely overlooking her expertise and professional role:

“I was introduced as the gender quota—in front of important people from major companies. [...] But the hardest part wasn't just the moment itself—of course, I felt bad—but later, when I talked about it with my two colleagues, my peers, they didn't react at all: ‘Oh well, what difference does it make?’ What difference does it make? It undermines the path I've taken and questions my abilities. Why should I be introduced differently when the person next to me has followed the same path? That's why I believe gender biases and stereotypes exist [...] from as early as elementary school” (IT_FGI03_I03)

It should also be emphasized that, in the mentioned case, the person holds that position not due to gender quotas but solely through a selection process based on competence.

Another challenge highlighted by participants was the dismissive attitude of male counterparts, who often downplayed these incidents. The students emphasized the importance of men actively acknowledging and addressing such occurrences, whether in the classroom or the workplace.

v. Who/What are enablers in these processes in career pathways for women?

Similarly to the barriers, the projective technique exercise was also used to identify the enablers in women's career pathways. For each stage of a hypothetical professional trajectory, participants highlighted various factors that could facilitate women's professional development.

Regarding entry into the workforce, career promotion, and progression, participants proposed that companies implement gender equality initiatives and increase incentives for such programs (IT_FGI03_I05). They also suggested mandatory training for leadership roles to raise awareness of gender equality (IT_FGI03_I04), as well as promoting women's self-determination in career and economic advancement (IT_FGI03_I03).

vi. Differences in Career Expectations and Opportunities Related to Different Energy Sectors

Although not discussed extensively, a few points emphasizing gender differences emerged, particularly in terms of higher pay in fossil fuel industries versus socially oriented energy work, and the distinction between niche and mainstream sectors.

Regarding the first point, a participant noted that while men might be drawn to higher-paying opportunities in traditional fossil-fuel industries, women might prioritize social and environmental impact of renewable energy. This difference in priorities may lead to varying career paths and expectations.

“I think that girls are much more determined to follow a path that is not solely driven by profit, as a boy might perceive it. There's also the issue of the energy transition, even though fossil fuels, coal, and oil still play a role in our energy sources. A boy, when offered the opportunity to work for an oil company where he can earn much more compared to pursuing a socially driven energy transition path, is – in my opinion – more easily convinced than girls, who are generally more focused on social and socio-environmental aspects. Of course, this is just my perspective, and I acknowledge that I could be wrong” (IT_FGI03_I05).

Regarding niche versus mainstream sectors, a woman participant outlined that while earning potential is important, it is not the sole factor guiding her career choices:

“I am also interested in earning money. However, I probably wouldn't give in to multinational corporations that focus on promoting oil [...] I was motivated by the fact that my work could yield results that ultimately benefit society” (IT_FGI03_I02).

c. Organisational climate at university/college

i. What is the overall climate/culture regarding gender equality at the university?

Regarding the climate and culture of gender equality within the university, participants primarily reflected on two key aspects: the composition of classes in specific engineering programs, including faculty members, and interactions with certain professors.

According to IT_FGI03_I01, some engineering fields, such as management and aerospace engineering, appear to have a higher percentage of women than disciplines like mechanical and electronic engineering. In aerospace engineering, for instance, women constituted 20% of the class. This percentage remained relatively stable over time while the percentage of male students declined more significantly (IT_FGI03_I03).

Students highlighted the presence of women among faculty members, including those in leadership roles. In particular, the fact that the Vice-Rector is a woman has contributed to normalizing the visibility of high-profile women figures in leadership roles (IT_FGI03_I03). Women lectures were recognized not only for their authoritative presence but also for their strong scientific expertise (IT_FGI03_I03, IT_FGI03_I01). As a student observed regarding a professor of mechanical engineering:

“In my opinion, she also represents a strong female role model capable of instilling awareness and confidence not only in female students but also in male students. I first saw her in my first year, and I thought: «she is an extraordinary woman who truly knows what she is teaching»” (IT_FGI03_I05).

Other participants emphasized that the real challenge lies not so much in the numerical representation of women within classes and departments but rather in their invisibility in certain academic and professional contexts. Students recalled attitudes from some professors whose comments and examples in class reflected a mindset still influenced by gender biases (IT_FGI03_I04, IT_FGI03_I02).

Gender equality remains limited in the workplace as well, as demonstrated by the lack of inclusivity in the design of laboratories and equipment. A significant example was reported by a student regarding her experience in a laboratory:

“Same in companies! I work as a laboratory technician, and lab coats are only available in M-L sizes, while shoes exist only in large sizes. Some of my male colleagues work with me in the cleanroom and have beards but no hair. However, the only protective equipment provided is a cap. I wonder—why can they work comfortably with a beard while I am required to tie my hair back? Of course, it makes sense as a safety measure, but regarding the protective equipment provided, everything is designed for standard M-L sizes. Since I am only 1.60 meters tall, my lab coat drags on the floor. In a way, it's better because it offers more coverage, but still...” (IT_FGI03_I03).

These observations highlight the persistent structural and cultural barriers that continue to hinder full gender equality in academic and professional settings.

ii. Is gender analysis or gender dimension integrated into participants' study program?

Participants agreed that gender analysis is never integrated into their engineering courses, which instead tend to focus exclusively on highly technical aspects such as mathematics, design, and thermodynamics. The strongly technical approach of the curricula was identified as a critical issue for two main reasons.

First, the absence of a gender perspective prevents understanding how the technologies developed could be used differently by men and women, or how gender inequalities may influence their adoption and dissemination.

“When you talk about technological development, man, woman, humanity is not addressed at all. Engineering is like neutral [...] I mean in content, it is generally absent... but the being human is not really addressed, which is the problem in engineering. Or the human is treated as an object with mass M, at most, or with some other counting category” (IT_FGI03_I01).

Second, technical aspects are often taught in isolation, with limited consideration of real-world application contexts or broader socio-economic dynamics. This disconnection from realities hinders students' ability to fully evaluate the social implications of engineering solutions. Only in a few instances did certain lecturers address the broader systemic aspects of energy systems during the courses (IT_FGI03_I01, IT_FGI03_I02).

iii. Are there any programs, measures, or interventions that help women pursue their educational path or career?

No references were made in the participants' testimonies regarding the existence of programs, measures, or interventions aimed at supporting women in pursuing their education and career.

Recommendations

What are the participants' recommendations for the future to raise women's participation in the energy sector?

Participants provided a series of recommendations, some specifically aimed at increasing women's participation in energy-related curricula, while others offered broader reflections on gender inclusivity in education and the workplace. These recommendations are summarized as follows:

➤ **Promoting Gender Awareness and Respect**

Given the persistence of gender stereotypes in both academia and workplace environments, participants emphasized the importance of fostering gender awareness throughout the entire

educational pathways. Families, teachers, lecturers, and peers all play a crucial role in shaping positive social models.

“In my opinion, another key point is to start not only with university education but also with education at the primary and secondary school levels. This is important because, by the time we reach university, we are already somewhat aware of the challenges, especially in the engineering field, which we have already described as predominantly male. It seems logical to try to propose an education that begins at a younger age, because older generations or those who are more experienced have viewpoints that are understandably different from those of today's young people. I have also seen many young people, starting from children as young as ten years old, who are significantly influenced, especially by social media, dark humor, and everything else out there. This, in turn, leads them to grow up in a toxic environment with a view of women that is not what it should be. So, this is certainly an effort that needs to be made, but who should do it? Professors, and even, in a more basic way, families” (IT_FGI03_I05).

In addition, participants stressed the need to eradicate all forms of gender discrimination within universities and workplaces. In this regard, they pointed to the importance of outreach initiatives aimed at young men, with the expectation that the younger generation will be more likely to embrace an inclusive perspective than their predecessors:

“Our male colleagues should be made more aware of these issues. Because, in many of these situations, there is often a bit of a smirk, a bit of camaraderie, and these things are downplayed, like “oh, I was just joking” or “you're so serious,” and in my opinion, this is the crucial point. An 80-year-old professor may not change their mind, but it is important that this is not overlooked by younger people, as this is misogyny” (IT_FGI03_I04).

➤ **Sanctioning misogynistic behavior and micro-aggressions**

Official channels should be provided to handle discriminatory incidents. Professors who make openly sexist remarks should be called out by the administration; and students should feel safe reporting micro-aggressions, with no fear of retaliation or ridicule (IT_FGI03_I04).

➤ **Encouraging Inclusive Language**

A significant point raised by participants was the importance of using gender-inclusive language when addressing women in professional settings. In Italian, where professional titles and nouns have gendered forms, it is crucial to use the appropriate feminine terms, such as “Dottoressa” (female doctor) or “Ingegnera” (female engineer), to acknowledge women's expertise and professional status.

“It often happens that a man is called 'doctor,' while a female doctor is addressed by her first name [...]. The use of titles and words when addressing women workers in this sector is important – terms like 'doctor,' 'engineer,' or any term that highlights the fact that they didn't just happen to be there because of gender quotas. But reaching that point requires a lot of effort” (IT_FGI03_I03).

➤ **Avoiding genderized subjects and targetizing orientation**

Participants suggest breaking the pervasive association of certain subjects with specific genders, particularly in STEM disciplines such as mathematics, physics, and natural sciences. This perception discourages many individuals from pursuing these fields, reinforcing gender disparities in tertiary education and professional careers (IT_FGI03_I01).

“Then you’re bravo at Italian, you’re bravo at history, you’re bravo at geography, but math, which presents objective difficulties for everyone, changes depending on gender. «Oh, well, don’t worry, it’s just math». Then, when you get to high school, they tell you, «But you got a passing grade in math, you can’t enroll in engineering»” (IT_FGI03_I01).

In academia, subjects continue to maintain a monothematic focus, often far from the interest of female students. Participants explained that in mechanical engineering, course content is often centered around topics such as engines and Formula 1, which may not align with the interests of many female students. To encourage a more diverse student body, they suggested broadening course offerings and integrating subject matter that appeals to a wider range of interests. Such curricular diversification could enhance inclusivity and attract more women to engineering programs, ultimately increasing their enrollment (IT_FGI03_I03).

Cross cutting analysis

a. Differences between STEM and SSH students

- i. *Are there any differences in the women’s educational and career pathways between SSH and STEM?*

A key difference concerns the gender distribution in class composition within SSH and STEM programs. As expected, engineering courses are strongly male dominated, while SSH programs are characterized by a larger share of female students.

In addition to differences in class composition, gender disparities also emerge in educational and career trajectories, particularly for women pursuing studies in engineering and energy-related fields. The main challenges encountered include gender bias and discrimination, both in academia and during early career experiences. In addition, a misconception persists that technical subject, such as mathematics, are inherently more challenging for women than the social sciences and humanities. This stems from cultural stereotypes and an educational legacy that is already rooted in primary and secondary education.

Conversely, in SSH programs, female students reported more attention to gender equality policies at the departmental level. However, a critical issue that emerged related to the perceived lower valuation of SSH study paths, which are often seen as less suitable for specific sectors of the labor market, such as energy.

- ii. *What are the differences in incorporating gender perspective between SSH and STEM?*

While the gender perspective is not addressed in STEM courses, it receives greater attention in SSH programs, where it is also reinforced by the general departmental orientation. Notably, the students who participated in the focus group interview are enrolled in the *Social Design for Sustainability, Innovation, and Gender Inclusion* program. However, according to female students in this program, the approach to gender issues remains limited and does not adequately reflect the evolving societal changes affecting younger generations.

b. Teaching and incorporating gender perspective

i. Is gender an integrated part of teaching in energy related fields?

Students criticize the way gender issues are addressed in their courses, noting a lack of integration in bachelor's and master's programs. Even in courses focused on gender, it is treated separately rather than in an intersectional manner. Their concerns include outdated approaches, dependence on individual lecturers' awareness, and the absence of dedicated textbooks. Gender topics are often taught through historical feminist movements, neglecting contemporary issues.

In engineering courses, gender considerations are completely absent, with curricula emphasizing technical aspects without addressing the social implications of technology. Moreover, textbooks do not adequately integrate gender into various disciplines.

This lack of perspective affects how innovations are designed and implemented in diverse societal contexts. While some informal discussions on gender take place, particularly regarding women's underrepresentation, they are not systematically included in the curriculum. Only in certain departments, such as Communication and Social Research, is gender integrated through initiatives like the Equal Opportunity Committee, which promotes awareness and student engagement.

Many lecturers, particularly male faculty, fail to incorporate gender perspectives due to their technical focus, and inclusive language is rarely used.

c. Enablers and barriers of women's careers

Name of a barrier	Description
Sexist stereotypes and misogynistic behaviors (STEM)	Differential treatment and reinforcement of sexist stereotypes during all phases of the educational process.
Lack of effective dissemination of engineering study options and applications in the field of sustainability (STEM)	Engineering is perceived as a subject disconnected from sustainability due to a lack of effective dissemination of study options in the field.

Little support for working students (STEM)	Administrative barriers that discourage and make it difficult for working students to pursue their studies.
social aspects of sustainability and energy transition (SSH)	Lack of awareness regarding the social aspects of sustainability and energy transition.
Territorial disparities (SSH)	Was mentioned whether innovative and sustainable projects will create new jobs in smaller towns or only in larger cities such as Rome, Milan, Naples, and Florence.
Need for technical competences (SSH)	Without a technical expertise in difficult to progress in the sustainability sector

Name of a supportive factor	Description
Mentorship and supportive figures (SSH and STEM)	Crucial role of a supportive figure who can help counteract stereotypes that push women away from male-dominated sectors.
Soft skills (SSH)	A leader should be able to recognize and appreciate an individual's potential and soft skills, acknowledging the contributions they can bring. This also implies that leaders and managers should be educated to make decisions in a different way—one that is more open, yet also cautious and mindful.
Roles models (STEM)	Role models are crucial for recognizing and appreciating the women in both society and the workforce. These role models should be supported by family members and teachers who can promote gender equality and integration.
Active role of teachers (STEM)	The active role of teachers in fostering critical thinking among students.
Family encouragement (STEM)	Family support can be an enabling factor for pursuing scientific careers, for both boys and girls
Scholarships and internships (STEM and SSH)	Regarding secondary school, participants emphasized the importance of internships focused on social and environmental issues, which they considered essential for future generations of students. At the bachelor's and master's degree levels, enablers included scholarships or internships in energy-related fields and a community-based approach
Reporting and sanctioning discrimination (STEM)	Dedicated desks for reporting cases of discrimination or misogyny and receiving support.
Modify study programs (STEM)	Importance of STEM courses that integrate themes of empathy, social responsibility, environmental

	sustainability, and ethics. Furthermore, they suggested that technical curricula should include critical thinking skills that allow professionals to have a positive impact on society.
Targeted communication and guidance (STEM and SSH)	Improvements in communication channels, organizing events and workshops centred on women in STEM careers, and enhancing orientation desks in schools.
Supportive peers	supportive friendships and peer collaboration formed a buffer against discouraging remarks.

Cross cutting recommendations

1. Enhancing Recognition of SSH Contributions

Ensure that social sciences and humanities (SSH) are acknowledged as key contributors to sustainability and energy discussions.

- Integrate SSH perspectives into STEM curricula to foster interdisciplinary approaches.
- Raise awareness among industry leaders about the value of SSH expertise in decision-making.
- Develop policies that recognize SSH contributions in energy sector job roles.

2. Changing the Narrative Around Gender in Energy & STEM Fields

Eliminate gender biases in education and workplace environments.

- Reform school textbooks
- Use inclusive language in professional and academic settings that support women's expertise.
- Implement mentorship programs featuring female role models in STEM and energy-related fields.
- Launch public awareness campaigns to challenge the perception of STEM as a male-dominated field.

3. Early Intervention in Education

Address gender disparities from an early age by reshaping how energy and STEM subjects are introduced.

- Incorporate energy-related topics in primary and secondary school curricula with gender-neutral narratives.
- Train teachers to recognize and challenge unconscious biases in their teaching methods.

- Promote STEM subjects in a way that appeals to diverse interests (e.g., sustainability, innovation, and social impact).

4. Fostering Inclusive Work and Learning Environments

Create an academic and professional culture that values diversity and equal opportunities.

- Establish university and workplace policies against gender discrimination.
- Educate male colleagues and leaders on gender biases and the importance of inclusivity.
- Develop workplace strategies to support women’s career advancement, including flexibility for work-life balance and parental leave policies.

APPENDIX

Appendix 1 – The FGI

Number of participants	10
Target interviewee group (<i>students from SSH, students from STEM, Academics...</i>)	University professors of both SSH and STEM and the vice-rector for research at Sapienza University of Rome
Place of the interview	CNR headquarters, Rome, Italy
Date of the interview	5 th , November, 2024
Length of the FGI	2 hours
Number of interviewees	7
Female (number)	2
Male (number)	5
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	
Comments about research tool	

Number of participants	11
Target interviewee group	Students from SSH
Place of the interview	IRPPS-CNR, Rome, Italy
Date of the interview	10 th , December, 2024
Length of the FGI	2 hours
Number of interviewees	8 (6 in person, 2 online)
Female (number)	5
Male (number)	3
Other (number)	0

Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition

Questions that were difficult for the respondent	
Comments about research tool	

Number of participants	8
Target interviewee group	Students from STEM
Place of the interview	IRPPS-CNR, Rome, Italy
Date of the interview	10 th , February, 2025
Length of the FGI	2 hours
Number of interviewees	5
Female (number)	3
Male (number)	2
Other (number)	/
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	
Comments about research tool	

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics

Participant ID	IT_FGI01_I01
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Astronautical, Electrical and Energy Engineering Department, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	Full Professor and vice-rector for research at Sapienza University of Rome
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Electrical engineer
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Electromagnetic compatibility, nanotechnologies and nanomaterials for applications in electrical engineering, electronics, aerospace, multifunctional materials and biotechnology.
Research interests	
Other relevant information	She is vice-rector for research at Sapienza University of Rome

Participant ID	IT_FGI01_I02
Gender	Male

Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students))	Astronautical, Electrical and Energy Engineering Department, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	Full professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Electrical engineer
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Permanent magnet machines
Research interests	Permanent magnet motor drives and multiphysics design of electrical machines.
Other relevant information	

Participant ID	IT_FGI01_I03
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students))	Astronautical, Electrical and Energy Engineering Department, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	Associate professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Electrical engineer
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Measurement systems for performing non-destructive tests, creation and characterization of innovative sensors, measurement systems for Power Quality, measurements of electrical quantities in non-sinusoidal regime, methods and systems for the calibration of vehicle speed meters.
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Participant ID	IT_FGI01_I04
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students))	Astronautical, Electrical and Energy Engineering Department, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	Full professor. Coordinator of the PhD School of Engineering and Applied Science for Energy and Industry.
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Electrical engineer

Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition

Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Power systems design, planning, safety, protection and coordination, lighting systems, building automation and energy savings.
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Participant ID	IT_FGI01_I05
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Department of Planning, Design, Architectural Technology, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	Associate professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Electrical engineer
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Use of renewable energy sources, energy efficiency of buildings and smart energy systems, development of energy scenarios for the decarbonisation
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Participant ID	IT_FGI01_I06
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	Associate Professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Sociology of culture and political processes
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social policies, gender equality, sustainability
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	IT_FGI01_I07
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Department of Political and Social Sciences, University of Milan
Country of work/study	Italy

Position at work (if applicable)	Research fellow
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD Urban Planning, Design and Policy
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Renewable Energy communities and energy poverty
Research interests	Territorial dimension of welfare governance, with particular reference to energy transition, and socio-spatial inequalities
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGII-I01)	IT_FGI02_I01
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Master's Degree in the Faculty of Economy, Luiss University, Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor's Degree in Economics and Finance
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Strategic Management, Innovation and Sustainability
Research interests	Economic and management development in the field of sustainable and innovative development
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGII-I01)	IT_FGI02_I02
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor's degree in Sociology
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion
Research interests	Social Housing
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGII-I01)	IT_FGI02_I03
Gender	Female

Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition

Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students))	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion
Research interests	Intersectional approach in the social impact assessment of public policies: the case of the PNRR
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	IT_FGI02_I04
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students))	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor Degree in Political Science
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion
Research interests	Sustainability in sport
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	IT_FGI02_I05
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students))	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor's Degree in Cooperation and Development
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion

Research interests	Urban redevelopment, social inclusion, social research
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	IT_FGI02_I06
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor's Degree in International Security and Cooperation
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion
Research interests	Community welfare in urban contexts, urban sociology and participation
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	IT_FGI02_I07
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor's Degree in Humanities
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion
Research interests	Sustainability and employment
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	IT_FGI02_I08
Gender	Male
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Master's degree at the Department of Communication and Social Research, Sapienza University of Rome

Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Bachelor's Degree in History and Global Society
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Social design for sustainability, innovation and gender inclusion
Research interests	Sustainable mobility and accessibility
Other relevant information	

Name and Surname	IT_FGI03_I01
Gender	Male
Country of study	Italy
Department/institute/university and study level	Mechanical engineering curricula energy University of Rome “La Sapienza”, BA
Study programme	Mechanical engineering
Previous academic qualifications	Scientific high school
Research interests (e.g., you could also indicate a hypothetical thesis topic)	Sustainable energy, social application
Other relevant information	

Participant ID	IT_FGI03_I02
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Mechanical engineering, University of Rome “La Sapienza”
Country of work/study	Italy
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	Mechanical engineering bachelor degree
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Mechanical engineering curricula energy master programme
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Name and Surname	IT_FGI03_I03
Gender	Female
Country of study	Italy
Department/institute/university and study level	Green Industrial Engineering, University of Rome “La Sapienza”, Master Degree
Study programme	Green Industrial Engineering master degree
Position at work (if applicable)	National Institute of Nuclear Physics (Frascati, Rome)
Scientific title (if applicable)	Aerospace engineering bachelor degree

Research interests (<i>e.g., you could also indicate a hypothetical thesis topic</i>)	Green energy
Other relevant information	

Name and Surname	IT_FGI03_I04
Gender	Female
Country of study	Italy
Department/institute/university and study level	Nanotechnology engineering, University of Rome “La Sapienza”, Master Degree
Study programme	Nanotechnology engineering master degree
Previous academic qualifications	Aerospace engineering bachelor degree
Research interests (<i>e.g., you could also indicate a hypothetical thesis topic</i>)	green energy and sustainability
Other relevant information	

Name and Surname	IT_FGI03_I05
Gender	Male
Country of study	Italy
Department/institute/university and study level	Mechanical engineering, BA degree candidate, University of Rome “La Sapienza”
Study programme	Mechanical engineering
Previous academic qualifications	scientific high school
Research interests (<i>e.g., you could also indicate a hypothetical thesis topic</i>)	Thesis: energy transition in Africa
Other relevant information	//

6.1.3. Poland

Title: *Report from organizing FGIs in Poland*

Authors: *Tadeusz Rudek, Paulina Sekuła, Aleksandra Wagner, Marta Warat*

Institution: *Jagiellonian University*

1. Organization of FGIs

Focus group interviews (FGIs) were conducted by the members of the Jagiellonian University team of the gEneSys project between November 2024 and January 2025.

Sample

The study engaged students from diverse academic backgrounds to explore gendered experiences and disciplinary perspectives related to career development and the energy sector. It applied a qualitative methodology, and focus group interviews (FGIs) were selected as the most suitable method to respond to the research questions and capture the dynamics of group interaction.

Two of the FGIs were conducted with students from STEM and technological universities, including participants from both MSc and BSc programs. To create an environment conducive to open and reflexive discussion, and to explore whether gender influences the dynamics and content of the discussion, participants were organized into gender-specific groups: one composed of women (8 participants) and the other of men (10 participants). This arrangement aimed to minimize potential power asymmetries and social pressures that might arise in mixed-gender discussions. The focus group with female STEM students included primarily participants from BSc programs, with only two currently enrolled in MSc programs. Their academic backgrounds were diverse, encompassing fields such as Nuclear Energy Studies (for the MSc students), Offshore Wind Engineering, Renewable Energy Systems (RES), General Engineering, Geography and Environmental Protection. This diversity allowed the discussion to capture a wide range of perspectives on the challenges and opportunities women face in technical fields. Similarly, the focus group with male STEM students was composed mostly of BSc students, with only two participants at the Master's level. Their study programs spanned Mechatronics, Light Engineering, Automation and Robotics, Acoustic Engineering, and Environmental Engineering, including specialized areas such as Automatics and Meteorology. The variety of disciplines represented in the group provided rich insights into the ways how male students perceive women's academic and professional trajectories in Energy system, and broader – in STEM. A third FGI was conducted in a mixed-gender group, gathering 7 participants. These workshops focused on identifying internal (institutional) and external (societal and structural) factors that may impede women's professional advancement and participation in technical and engineering fields. The interviewees were diverse in terms of their study programs, with the majority enrolled in BSc programs and only few in MSc programmes. Their fields of study included

Mechanical Engineering and Robotics, Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, Electrical Engineering, Automation, Computer Science and Biomedical Engineering, as well as Energy and Fuels.

A fourth FGI was held with students from the social sciences and humanities. Eight students participated: seven from the MA program in Sociology and one from the BA program in Sociology. The group was mixed-gender, though reflecting the higher proportion of women in these disciplines, there were six women and two men. This session aimed to explore how students from these fields perceive the energy system, their understanding of its social and environmental dimensions, and the extent to which they envisage themselves pursuing careers within the energy sector.

Together, the four FGIs provided comparative insights into how disciplinary cultures, gender dynamics, and institutional environments shape students' professional aspirations and perceived barriers to participation in energy-related fields. Detailed profiles of participants are presented in the Annexes.

The FGI with faculty members aimed to gather the perspectives of lecturers and academic staff who are actively engaged in institutional bodies focusing on research, career development, and higher education practices. Four participants took part in the FGI, all of whom were female professors representing different disciplines: Sociology, Economics, and Environmental Studies. While their disciplinary backgrounds varied, all participants shared a professional interest in energy topics, approaching the subject from diverse angles—ranging from environmental science and health considerations to social and societal implications of energy systems.

In addition to the FGI, two individual interviews were conducted to complement the faculty perspectives. One was with a male Associate Professor from a technical university, whose research focuses on nuclear energy, and the other with a female professional working as an innovation broker at a technical university. These individual interviews provided additional depth and insight into faculty engagement with energy-related topics, bridging technical, and innovation-focused viewpoints.

Date and duration of each interview:

- 8.11.2024, FGI with STEM women students (FGI1_PL), duration: 2:18:57
- 9.11.2024, FGI with STEM mix-gender students, (FGI2_PL), duration: 2:13:01
- 12.11.2024, FGI with STEM men students (FGI3_PL), duration: 1:57:03
- 28.11.2024, FGI with academic teachers (FGI4_PL), duration: 1:22:57
- 4.12.2024, FGI with SSH mix-gender students (FGI5_PL), duration: 2:02:54
- 10.01.2025, IDI with STEM teacher (IDI6_PL), duration: 1:00:11
- 23.01.2025, IDI with STEM expert/innovation broker (IDI7_PL), duration: 1:10:03

Recruitment Process and Challenges

Participants of FGIs with STEM students were recruited through multiple channels, including snowball sampling, personal contacts, students bodies and advertisement. In addition, lecturers distributed information about the study to students enrolled in their courses. While the study was initially planned include only MSc Students, difficulties in reaching this group necessitated the inclusion of BSc students as well. This change had both limitations and advantages: it restricted the discussion of certain topics, such as career development and advanced professional experiences, but is also allowed for more in-depth exploration of education on energy, providing valuable insights into factors that facilitate or hinder learning in this area.

Students from social sciences and humanities were selected based on their enrolment in the courses addressing energy-related topics. They were approach individually through a course leader who sent the invitation to participate in the FGI. This personalized approach facilitated successful recruitment, enabling the group to be formed as originally planned. Faculty members were identified by the research team and approach individually with a formal request to participate in the study.

All participants were offered a gift for their participation in the study.

Describe the thematic areas discussed and projective techniques used during each FGI.

FGIs with STEM students explored their educational choices, career aspirations and experiences in the energy sector. While in the group with female students the discussion focused mostly on the participants' experiences, in the male and mixed-gender group the personal experiences were supplemented by reflection on educational and professional choices of women in general. To engage the participants in the discussion, FGIs used a combination of discussion and projective techniques. To facilitate the discussion on educational choices, a storytelling technique was used: the participants were asked to imagine a young women choosing a study programme in the energy sector. They reflected on the factors that might influence her decision (e.g. personal motivation, support family and mentors, societal expectations, gender stereotypes). In the second part of FGI, participants examined women's career paths in the energy sector through visual mapping. They used a large sheet depicting a career path to write down obstacles and supporting factors and discuss how they affect students' studies and potential/foreseen careers and strategies of overcoming them. The FGI addressed the integration of gender perspectives in energy education and the workplace. Participants discussed the organizational culture of their institutions, whether gender issues are included in their courses and this inclusion (or their lack) influence experiences and career expectations. Finally, the session concluded with a recommendation part.

A similar scenario was used in FGI with SSH students as participants explored the topics related to educational and professional paths for SSH students in energy sector. They explored the factors influencing their decision to study energy-related topics within their disciplines, reflecting how energy-related topics are integrated into their programmes and how their discipline can contribute to energy transition. The group discussed the potential career paths which would allow them to combine social sciences with energy field. Using a large sheet to visualize ideas, participants explored factors influencing the career choices, opportunities and challenges for women's career in different sectors: public,

private and NGOs. They also focused on the inclusion of gender-based perspective in their programme and courses and the overall of the organizational culture of their institutions regarding gender equality. Finally, participants were invited to provide recommendations, suggesting how to make study programmes related to energy and workplace more inclusive for women.

To supplement the perspectives of students, the opinions of faculty members were gathered through group and individual interviews regarding the similar topics. The participants explored factors influencing women's engagement in energy-related studies and career and organizational culture. Contrary to the FGI with students, no projective technique was used. Faculty members examined the factors affecting women's interest in pursuing education and career in energy system, reflecting on the similarities and differences between women and men's choices. They also shared their perspective on the organizational climate within their institutions, gender dynamic in career progression and perceived importance of gender equality in the energy field. They highlighted promising practices and effective interventions at the institutional level and provided recommendations for improving support for women's education and career in energy sector.

2. Description of FGI with Male Students from STEM (FGI3_PL)

A. Educational Choices

Participants in the study spontaneously recalled high school as the period when their interests began to take shape regarding future study choices. The selection of a class profile or school seemed particularly significant.

“The fact that you already have to choose in high school, when you’re 14 or 15, what you’ll want to study later — that’s such a distant perspective at that age, kind of strange, right? And when you’re in a math-physics class, it’s natural that most people from there will go into some technical field, right?”

Most participants studied either in a technical school with a specialized technical profile or in classes with an extended mathematics curriculum, which influenced their later preferences for higher education. Another important factor in university choice was location (preferably close to home) or the fact that older siblings were already studying in that city.

“I chose my major mainly because earlier in technical school I was in the automation technician profile, so this is a continuation. I know that in my... industry, having an engineering or master’s degree is necessary to be able to sign off on completed systems and projects.”

Within this context, decisions regarding the choice of an engineering field were often made with the involvement of "important people"—either from the family or the school environment. Parents, teachers, or other influential individuals played a key role in shaping participants’ professional identities and, consequently, their study choices.

“As for my interest in electronics, I think I owe that to my uncle. I’ve always been around computers since childhood, and later I got more into electronics. He’s also an IT specialist.”

“I had a great physics teacher who prepared me for the physics Olympiad. I wasn’t that strong in computer science, but I just liked it.”

“I came here, for example, because my high school had a lot of ties with [name of a university] — teachers from [name of university] came to Lublin, where I’m from. And my brother also studied here.”

Additionally, when participants distanced themselves from personal experiences through projection exercises, they began to focus more on perspectives related to the labor market. Many expressed the belief that STEM fields offered better career prospects and higher salaries than artistic or humanities disciplines. Consequently, interest in the latter was often seen as a hobby rather than a professional path. Participants emphasized the reputation of their chosen university and its high position in national rankings.

“I actually tried applying abroad and even got accepted to some universities in Ireland and Denmark, but financial reasons didn’t allow me to go. So I ended

up with my second choice, [name of the university]. As others mentioned, this university ranks quite high, at least in Polish rankings.”

“Secondly, you look at job prospects, salaries, or future opportunities, and that kind of thing.”

Influences on Study Profiles

Study profiles are influenced by societal perceptions, personal interests, social dynamics, and family expectations.

Key points include:

Societal Stereotypes:

Participants noted the persistence of a belief that engineering is unsuitable for women, which affects educational choices, even though they personally reject this stereotype. They assumed that a girl interested in electronics might face discouragement due to the field’s male-dominated image.

“I think there’s still a belief in society that engineering studies aren’t for women. You can see that in technical schools — mechatronics, IT, electronics, automation — girls make up just a fraction of the class, not even close to half. It’s usually a handful, at most.”

Family Influence:

Families might steer children, especially girls, toward fields perceived as more appropriate, even when their interests lie in technical areas.

“A girl who wants to go to a technical school and is interested in, say, electronics might even be discouraged by her parents — told that this isn’t the right kind of school for her, and that she should rather go to a general high school.”

Social Dynamics:

Educational environments can be isolating for minorities in male-dominated fields, affecting social integration.

“When you go into a field where it’s mostly men and you’re the only woman — or the reverse, like a man going into nursing — you know you won’t meet many people of your own gender. And however much we’d like to minimize it, guys usually get along better with other guys, and women with women.”

“In my technical school, there was one girl in a class of 24. I think it required a big adjustment on her part, adapting to a male environment. It’s a skill to get along with 23 boys when there isn’t even one other girl to talk to.”

Gendered Careers:

Career choices may be influenced by gender expectations, sometimes leading to feelings of alienation.

“If a girl consciously decides to become an engineer, she’ll have to consider whether she’ll be able to manage men, show authority — because some still have the attitude that they won’t take orders from a woman.”

“Also, if a young woman decides to study something like energy engineering, she might already be thinking about starting a family, but this kind of work often involves travel — building power plants, for example. It’s much harder to start a family when your job requires frequent travel. That can be a demotivating factor.”

Personal Interests:

People often align with “safe,” gender-normative fields despite personal passions, treating their true interests as hobbies rather than career paths.

“I think that all the factors we discussed as discouraging women from technical fields really depend on personality. For some women, what we see as obstacles could actually be motivating or neutral.”

“If a woman already knows she wants to go into a technical field, then the situation is similar. But if she’s unsure, I think a technical direction won’t be her first choice.”

“From my perspective, choosing a university program really comes down to two main things: first, your own interest, which I think is the most important — most people make their choice based on that.”

In conclusion, the choice of study profile is shaped by a combination of personal interests, societal expectations, gender stereotypes, and the desire for social belonging. These factors create a complex decision-making process that involves both external pressures and internal motivations.

Participants observed the disproportion between male and female students in technical and energy programs and attributed it mainly to societal factors rooted in the past. At the same time, they emphasized their own neutral or modern view of gender issues and expressed a strong belief that personal interests and goals are the primary motivators.

Interestingly, participants rarely noticed the positive influence of school curricula or teachers on their personal interests and choices. Likewise, they did not perceive any discouragement or discrimination against girls in earlier stages of education.

“I think that if there’s a girl and a boy with exactly the same skills, the difference in how often they might hear discouraging comments is negligible.”

“I know her parents supported her. She studies nanomaterials engineering, and she was good at math and physics, just like me. Our exam results were similar — maybe a 2% difference. The recruitment process was practically the same, and gender didn’t play any role at all.”

B. Women Career pathways in participants’ perception

According to the participants, career pathways depend largely on personal interests and motivation. They view childhood as a formative period for developing interests and self-

esteem. When discussing career paths, they generally opposed the idea of enforcing gender parity. However, they strongly emphasized that there should be no pay disparities between men and women — salaries should depend solely on skills and qualifications. At the same time, they considered it unacceptable to use higher pay as an incentive for women to enter a particular profession.

“That could also cause conflicts between employees...”
“Exactly. Because someone might get the job just because we need to keep a 50:50 balance.”

“Encouraging women with higher pay — that they’d earn more than men in the same positions just because they work in the energy sector — that shouldn’t be happening.”

Participants recognized the potential role of schools in shaping students’ interests, as well as the importance of extracurricular clubs. However, they stressed that such activities should be equally accessible to all students. A possible solution to the low representation of women in technical professions, including energy, could be to develop a societal model in which career choices are guided by individual interests — interests that can be freely nurtured from early childhood, starting in preschool.

“Teachers play a huge role here, especially at the primary level. I think that, for example, to increase the percentage of women working in technical fields, there should be better development of extracurricular clubs or career counseling at earlier stages of education. Like having technical clubs in primary school that both girls and boys can attend.”

“I think it’s more about creating a society where we don’t impose quotas but instead let people follow their own passions and what they truly want to do. Then things would balance out naturally — maybe not 50:50, but 40:60, or in some other proportion. Because there will always be some areas where one gender prevails, whether due to biological predispositions or simply different interests — those disparities will exist.”

Participants acknowledged the appeal of flexible working hours but pointed out that it may be difficult to shift the dynamics of sectors traditionally associated with biological or social roles. They observed that sectors aiming to hire more women tend to create favorable working conditions for them, while others are more likely to continue employing men.

“It’s probably a bit of a self-fulfilling prophecy. If you have a field dominated by women, employers will naturally create conditions to attract and retain them. So employers — or even state institutions — will compete to make things easier for women, for example, by offering more flexible schedules, better maternity leave, or financial bonuses for preschools and nurseries. This helps women start families without interrupting their professional careers.”

C. Organisational Climate at University

Participants in the study generally did not perceive discriminatory behavior in their studies. A few examples were mentioned concerning older-generation lecturers, but there was a shared belief that students themselves do not tolerate such behavior. One participant described the process of filing a complaint about inappropriate and discriminatory remarks made by a lecturer. Overall, gender discrimination was seen as a generational issue — a remnant of the past. In their view, their own generation is largely free from such prejudices and stereotypes.

At the same time, they pointed out weaknesses in earlier stages of education, especially in developing students' interests. Schools, they argued, do not provide sufficient stimulation or practical knowledge about potential career paths.

“It seems to me that nowadays it would be hard to come across real sexism — those kinds of jokes and attitudes are basically gone.”

“Speaking of [name of university] and gender discrimination, one leftover from the past is that there aren't women's bathrooms on every floor, for example.”

“You can evaluate lecturers now, so if anyone made sexist jokes, it would definitely come out in the evaluations and be addressed.”

Views on Language and Feminatives

Participants did not speak enthusiastically about the use of feminatives and considered language-related issues secondary.

“Polish can be tricky when it comes to gendered language. Sometimes it's just annoying to always use both forms, and 90% of people won't remember to do it. You can say it once and then just use the word 'students' for everyone. Polish also isn't really adapted for non-binary people. The fact that the language doesn't account for that doesn't mean someone is being discriminated against — it's just inconvenient.”

D. Recommendations

Participants suggested several ways to encourage more women to enter technical education and the energy sector. Key recommendations include:

- Increasing the visibility of women in technical and energy-related professions to inspire others.
- Expanding extracurricular clubs and technical initiatives, which play an important role in engaging students and sparking early interest in STEM fields.
- Improving career counseling, which currently begins too late and is often delivered by inadequately trained professionals.
- Organizing workplace visits, allowing students to observe real work environments and understand the specifics of different professions.

3. FGI with Female Students from STEM (FGI1_PL)

A. Educational Choices

There is a clear mismatch between the educational choices of two groups of female students interested in energy-related fields. On one hand, there are those pursuing renewable energy (RES) and environmental issues, and on the other, those planning careers in the nuclear energy sector. Students in the nuclear energy field perceive it as a significant opportunity and a well-defined research path:

“And nuclear energy is the future, or... well, it’s not just about Poland — we’re talking about a global trend. Whether we like it or not, we have to move away from coal.” (FGI1)

In contrast, students focusing on RES and environmental protection view their field as more closely aligned with sustainability:

“In my case, it wasn’t really an interest in energy as such — it was more about the fact that my studies touch upon many areas related to the natural environment, and... and that makes them quite interesting, because you can learn chemistry, geology, and a bit of everything. And still, it somehow relates to what is important in the context of the future.” (FGI1)

Both career paths—nuclear energy and RES—can be seen as responses to urgent global challenges often highlighted in the media. This makes the energy sector an attractive option for developing a career:

“For me, unlike the girls, I can’t really say it was a passion. It was rather what was happening in the news — the way it was being talked about, that we need to change our energy mix, the way the law was slowly being adjusted — that somehow steered me toward the energy sector, meaning renewable and ecological energy. And since I had always felt comfortable with subjects like mathematics and physics, I knew I could choose that kind of field.” (FGI1)

Some students interested in environmental issues see RES as a way to combine their personal interests with a promising career path:

“Yes, but for me it also came from the fact that, well, I was afraid that... Because I didn’t necessarily want to go into energy — I was more interested in ecology — but I was worried that it might not be such a stable job.” (FGI1)

Inspiration for pursuing careers in energy often comes from parents or primary and secondary school teachers. Parents are typically seen as sources of support and motivation. However, teachers can play dual roles, sometimes discouraging students but also inspiring them to prove themselves:

“And I had this situation with my physics teacher — he just didn’t like me... he picked on me and a classmate, so gender had absolutely nothing to do with it. He simply decided that we weren’t suited for physics and said he wouldn’t give us higher grades. So we told ourselves that when we get our PhDs, we’ll just bring them to him, throw them on his desk, and say: ‘Take a look at that!’” (FGI1)

Conversely, teachers can also inspire students to pursue specific career paths:

“In my case, it was my physics teacher — she actually has a PhD in nuclear physics — who really encouraged us to go into... nuclear energy.” (FGI1)

All participants highlighted that energy as a career path is not clearly presented during primary or secondary education in Poland. This issue is particularly evident for nuclear energy, which is often considered a “taboo” subject:

“That’s exactly the thing... Now that we’re talking about knowledge — as I mentioned earlier — even a teacher who doesn’t really go into these topics can easily imagine how solar or hydro energy works. Even if that image isn’t entirely accurate, it’s still easy to picture. But nuclear energy, on the other hand, is kind of a taboo topic — because if someone hasn’t really looked into it, they don’t quite understand where it comes from or how it actually works. So it’s often easier just not to bring it up, to avoid questions. Because when questions do arise, there might not be any answers.” (FGI1)

Energy education in Poland often focuses on spatial planning, systemic perspectives, and resource distribution, rather than presenting energy as a viable career path for individuals:

“But I can say that I didn’t take advanced physics — I had geography instead — and for us it was a bit different. We talked about all those things like biomass, geo... geography (laughs), nuclear energy, but always in a spatial context — where each type is found, where it’s produced, where certain power plants are located, what percentages in which countries — but not why it’s like that. I mean, we learned why it’s there — for example, that China has many rivers and so on — but not how it actually works.” (FGI1)

An interesting observation was made about perceived gender roles in energy sectors. Conventional (fossil fuel) energy is often associated with men, while RES tends to be seen as more suited for women:

“I’ve actually noticed that nowadays there’s this kind of division — that when it comes to non-renewable energy, the target group tends to be more often young boys, men, mhm... whereas renewable energy is associated more with women. I’m not really sure where that comes from, but... I think it’s rooted in the culture of mining — that men, as a group, have a much bigger stake in it, meaning they care more about not closing the mines, because it’s work done almost exclusively by men — when it comes to non-renewable energy.” (FGI1)

This claim was countered by students in nuclear energy studies, who view their field as distinct from both conventional and RES sectors. They emphasized that Poland’s investment in nuclear power requires a growing workforce trained specifically for this field.

B. Career pathways

The career pathways of STEM female students are closely tied to their personal interests and the opportunity to secure stable, well-paying jobs in both renewable energy (RES) and

nuclear energy sectors. Key elements shaping their career choices include: Personal Interests and Passion, many participants highlighted their intrinsic motivation and enthusiasm for specific energy topics as pivotal in their decision-making:

“My interest in nuclear energy [started] back in middle school.” (FGI1)
“Environmental changes are one of the biggest problems we’re facing.” (FGI1)

Another crucial thing for developing ones successful career is the Exposure to Real-World Issues : Media coverage of energy policies and climate change served as a significant source of inspiration for participants and an indicator that they follow a needed (from the global perspective) pathway. Finally Practicality of Career Choices, where the desire for stable employment and professional development opportunities was a crucial factor

“Passion mattered, but so did the future prospects of the field.” (FGI1)
“So here too... I’m kind of at a crossroads — I could choose a PhD driven by passion, something I really enjoy (ns 01:42:33), but, well, you can’t buy bread with passion, right? Or I could go for another PhD for which I’d get a big grant — so, well, that’s the dilemma...” (FGI1)

High school education in the Polish system plays a critical role in shaping future career choices. During the FGI discussions, participants highlighted the differences in their interests related to specific energy sectors. Those pursuing RES were often motivated by environmental protection, while those in nuclear energy were drawn by a strong affinity for STEM subjects, particularly physics. Despite these differences, the underlying motivation for choosing a career in the energy sector remained consistent: the promise of stable and well-paid employment. A significant enabler for success in the energy job market is institutional support from universities and educational programs. Participants emphasized the importance of practical learning opportunities, internships, and hands-on experience in the energy sector. Access to international workshops and training programs was also seen as critical. This is particularly important for students pursuing careers in nuclear energy, as Poland currently lacks operational nuclear power plants. Consequently, students must seek practical training and internships abroad to gain relevant experience.

Worth noticing is the fact that participants indicate that in energy field frequently stay at the academia – so thus they become scientists and academic teachers, whereas males are taking the jobs in the industry.

“It seems to me that as soon as we started talking about the academic staff and the male–female divide, it became clear that it’s often not so much that women are strongly encouraged to pursue academic positions, but rather that they don’t see themselves in other roles after finishing STEM studies. Quite often, they stay at the university simply because, as my colleague mentioned, they don’t see a future in industry.” (FGI1)

“I’d also like to add — it’s not that these women are being forced into academia. For example, when I chose my internship supervisor, both she and her husband wanted to pursue academic careers. It’s not that the wife didn’t want to — it just turned out that the husband had to move into industry,

because, well, one of them had to. So the academic path is still seen that way — that one of the spouses must go in another direction, because unfortunately, science in Poland isn't really prepared to support both partners in academia, unless, well, there's some grant funding.” (FGI1)

In reference to the career pathways it is worth indicating that some woman might be questions or discourage from pursuing certain roles or sectors by family members

“I've heard from people close to me: ‘You just don't seem like the type to be putting up wind turbines.’

This is especially true as indicated by the participants in case of nuclear energy sector – showcasing the fears related to radiation and potential pregnancy of female employees.

“I was told directly that I wouldn't become an operator, because it's not a job for women.” (FGI1)

“I'd say it's a bit worse with the rest of my family — they just don't know much about it. There's this general lack of knowledge, some myths connected to nuclear energy. I'd actually prefer if the rest of society were like that (laughter), but still, you sometimes hear things like: ‘Oh, once you get pregnant, you'll lose interest.’ (laughter)” (FGI1)

C. Organisational climate at university/college

The overall climate regarding gender equality in the university and its departments appears mixed, with both positive aspects and notable challenges. Several participants observed relatively balanced gender representation in some energy-related programs.

“In Environmental Engineering and Protection, there are definitely more women than men.” (FGI1)

“In Renewable Energy Studies, it's roughly fifty-fifty.” (FGI1)

However, fields such as nuclear energy remain predominantly male-dominated:

“In Nuclear Energy, there was a predominance of men.” (FGI1)

“In practice, I was told that I wouldn't become an operator, because it's not a job for women.” (FGI1)

At the beginning of the discussion, all participants indicated that they did not perceive any signs of discrimination at their higher education institutions. This perception shifted when one participant shared an experience involving an older professor who had made an inappropriate comment, intimidating her in front of the entire study group:

“We have this one older professor, and once a male student drew a line on a technical drawing that he shouldn't have, because it was supposed to be invisible. And the professor said to the whole class: ‘Ladies, please be careful — this gentleman must have a laser in his eyes, he can probably see the color of your underwear.’ So yes, there are such comments — unpleasant ones. And

sometimes he also picks on the girls more than on others, in different ways.”
(FGI1)

Such framed by the participants as unpleasant, rude, and sexist remarks were attributed primarily to older academic staff members. Another challenge mentioned by participants is the "gender blindness" in educational programs, where energy-related topics are taught without acknowledging potential gender differences:

“But I also have the impression that this isn’t just about women — among the teaching staff in general there’s a kind of learned blindness to differences between us. So it often happens that we don’t talk at all about how things affect different social groups differently, or about class divisions either. We just have this kind of education that assumes we’re all equal, and so on.”
(FGI1)

Infrastructure at technical universities may also reflect historical male dominance, as seen in the insufficient provision of women’s facilities:

“I think it’s about the fact that [university name] is a technical university, and now about one-third of the students are women. I’ve had the chance to hear stories from older professors who said that — even today — sometimes, to find a women’s restroom, you really have to walk around different floors, especially in the older buildings.” (FGI1)

On a positive note, participants acknowledged that younger professors tend to adopt a more inclusive and supportive approach toward students. In some cases, such as nuclear studies, potential risks—like radiation exposure for pregnant women—are addressed proactively. Clear rules and safety measures are in place to protect all students:

“And also, if it turned out that a woman was pregnant — well, there’s no obligation to disclose it, because that only applies once you start doing lab work. And during studies, it happens, of course, since we’re all adults, so it’s just... you know...” (FGI1)

D. Recommendations

Based on the discussion in the focus group interviews, several recommendations were made to increase women's participation in the energy sector:

1. Encouraging Women to Focus on Their Passions. One participant emphasized that the decision to pursue a field like energy should be based on passion and personal interest, not just job prospects. This is seen as crucial for long-term success and fulfillment.

“What’s really important here is a certain kind of passion — because if someone hates their profession but only counts on it bringing some income, then they’ll just spend their whole life struggling through it.” (FGI1)

Advising Women to Choose Specializations. It was recommended that women focus on areas where they are good at and where their strengths lie, such as physics, environmental development, or measurements.

“Focus on what you’re good at... and go in the direction where you feel comfortable.” (FGI1)

2. Creating a Supportive Environment for Career Development. Several participants pointed out the importance of a supportive atmosphere, especially within academic environments, where women can grow without facing unnecessary barriers. Participants also indicated that the more younger the academic teachers are the more inclusive and support they are.

“I’d say I’d ten times rather have classes with a PhD student who brings some freshness and treats all of us — women and men alike — equally.” (FGI1)

3. Highlighting the Importance of Career Flexibility and Mobility. Women were advised to consider the possibility of international opportunities or remote work in energy sectors that are more global in nature, such as nuclear energy.

“That for a certain period of time, it might simply be necessary to emigrate to another part of the world.” (FGI1)

4. Addressing Structural Barriers and Gender Bias. It's important to tackle barriers like gender stereotypes and the "glass ceiling" that may limit women's career progression in certain technical fields.

“There are still, especially in the more technical or exact fields, these rather long-established glass ceilings.” (FGI1)

4. Description of FGI with Mixed-gender Students from STEM (FGI2_PL)

A. Educational Choices

The students taking part in this FGI were enrolled at different engineering study programmes at the same technical university in a big Polish city, with only two of them pursuing academic studies directly related to energy. They are both in their MSc/graduate programmes, which were determined by their choices of undergraduate studies.

“I'm studying... actually, I'm in my final year of my master's degree, studying ecological energy sources at (name of a university-PS). Before that, I studied renewable energy.” (woman)

“I am an energy engineer from (name of a university, where the students did his BSc degree-PS). Later, I worked in (name of a city) as a block operator. Then, for six months, I worked on the start-up of a steam and gas power plant, which is a project (ns 00:05:52). Later, I decided that I wanted to finish my master's degree, so I moved to (name of a city) and that's why I'm studying nuclear energy at (name of a university).” (man)

For some of the participants the choice of the study field was somehow obvious, **driven by previous educational decisions** made at the stage of high school:

“This is my adventure with energy; I simply attended a technical high school for renewable energy (...)” (man)

“I graduated from technical high school in automation, and I really enjoyed what I was doing there. So I decided that I would like to continue studying this subject here at [name of the university].” (man)

Other students declared that their study choices were more **coincidental**, driven by the unexpected results of high school final exams or even last-minute decisions.

“For me, the decision was, you could say, almost accidental, because in high school I wanted to study biology and chemistry, but I didn't get in. (...) And it turned out that I did very well on my geography final exam (...), I did better in geography than in math, and I wanted to be sure that I would get into the program I applied for; and that's how the topic of renewable energy came up.” (woman)

“Originally, I also wanted to study cybersecurity, as many members of my family work in this sector. I didn't get in, so I ended up studying intelligent systems.” (man)

Sometimes, the choice of the study field was the **result of meticulous consideration** of the pros and cons of several study options or appeared only after the previous study choices have proved unsatisfactory.

“I had a big problem choosing what to study, because it wasn't a choice between this or that engineering, but between theater school and veterinary medicine, and mechanics and machine construction, and that was everything, so well, it narrowed down so much that I thought it would be better

to make my humanities interests a hobby and my scientific mind a job, rather than the other way around. And I just decided that it would be easier to reconcile these two sides, so to speak, so that's what I chose.” (woman)

“This isn't the first degree program I've started. The first one was international economic relations at [name of a university], but I was there... I almost finished the first year, but I really didn't like the direction it was going in, it was very (ns 00:10:41), which strictly leads to working in a corporation, which I preferred to avoid, so I decided to drop out. Later, I studied applied computer science at [nam of a university] (...)” (woman)

Some participants consulted their educational decisions with other students who had been already enrolled in the programme of their choice and could provide some insider knowledge. Additionally, two women participants indicated that their educational choices were motivated by **good career perspectives**.

“And anyway, just as I got into this program, everyone who studied with me also thought that it was a promising field and that it was something worth developing.” (woman)

“Well, but mainly that it's easy to find a job and that such... typical, let's say, reasons why you might choose these more exact fields, so... I think that's mainly it.” (woman)

From the participants' narratives, it appears that other people, **family members or teachers**, played certain roles in their educational choices, however this influence was indirect and consisted of raising interest in the subject, acting as **role models** or providing external validation of own choices.

“And there I had this woman teacher (...), she was also a doctor of energy, she gave various lectures, that is, she taught us about... all renewable energy sources at the technical high school, and I was fascinated by the fact that she had such extensive knowledge.” (man)

“I've always had engineers in my family, and it was always the case that they had such knowledge, they had such interesting jobs (...)” (woman)

“When I presented my vision to my parents, they were (ns 00:09:14) that it was great, that it was a wonderful idea, very forward-thinking.” (woman).

While none of the interview participants reported giving up their choices because of the family objection, the following excerpt demonstrates the potential negative impact of discouragement from family members based on traditional gender norms on (women's) educational choices

“When I was still considering going to technical high school, my grandmother, for example, was terrified. She said, “No, how can that be? But that's where you'll be the only one there,” and so on, but when I went to college, she didn't make any comments like that at all and... she also completely changed her attitude towards it”. (woman)

Regardless of the particular background of their choice of study, most participants declared being driven by their **personal interests and abilities**.

“I chose one thing from the list that would more or less apply to my interests and skills.” (man)

“I’m pretty good at technical subjects, and, well, solely because of those technical subjects, I’d also like to be a little creative, because I’d like to go more in the area of audio studies. I’ve always been interested in that, for example, in terms of movies or theater, or just dealing with sound.” (woman)

When discussing challenges that they encountered in making the study field choice, participants unanimously pointed to the difficulties in the higher education **application and enrolment process**, due to inaccessible information on the university websites and short deadlines for submitting documents after receiving the results of the high school final examination (matura).

“It was an ordeal: finding a university, where to sign up, where to go, what to fill out, what to bring, what photos to take. It was awful, stressful, and for someone who had just graduated from high school and didn’t know what was going on, it was... it was awful” (man)

“Another problem is that when you take your final exams, the results are announced, say, on Wednesday, and the enrollment period ends on Friday. That gives you two days to enroll after finding out your results, which I think is a very short time (...).” (woman)

One of the women also recalled her first month at the university as very stressful, when she had to adjust quickly to new study conditions, new class formats and longer classes as well as living on her own in a new city. The factor that helped her navigate through these hardships was the possibility to **share challenges** with other first-year students.

“I lived in a dormitory and met a lot of people there who were studying the same thing as me and going through exactly the same thing as me, and I think it gave me a lot of support that they were just as lost as me and didn’t really know what was going on..” (woman)

B. Career pathways for women

When discussing what factors play a role in shaping women’s educational and career choices in energy, the participants indicated good career prospects, family support and knowledge of the field of study. In this context, one of the participants raised an issue of lack of knowledge on the variety energy study programmes, as she for long *“was not aware that you could study energy or something like that, that there are majors, that there is such a wide range of majors related to energy”*. An equally important factor in taking educational and career choices by women is their knowledge on the study culture, including women’s representation in the field, teachers’ attitudes towards women and prevalence of gender discrimination.

“However, I assume that it is more difficult to choose a field of study when there are, say, 5 women and 100 men. So yes, it can definitely be a factor in

the choice. If, for example, a person is more shy and is not the type who can stand up for themselves or file a complaint, or unite with other victims of such discrimination, then they may definitely prefer to choose a field where women are, let's say, more welcome.” (woman)

When specifically discussing barriers and obstacles for women to pursue education in energy related field and career in energy sector, the participants discussed a number of factors. These included traditional gender roles and gender stereotypes transmitted both in families and schools and influencing both women’s self-images and self-selection processes, teachers’ prejudices towards women’s aptitudes and the employers’ reluctance to hire young women, as they may have longer career breaks due to maternity leaves.

“When it comes to pregnancy, it's not just that the employer thinks there's a risk, but also that you're pregnant, so there's pressure not to go to work and take care of your family, right? Let's say it wasn't planned to get pregnant, but it happened, so in that case, let's say I decide that I have to become a mother, let's say, full-time.” (woman)

In this context, women participants stressed the negative long-term influence of teachers and family members who undermine self-confidence of girls and young women, which may result in imposter syndrome and chronic self-doubt. At the same time, however all agreed that primary and secondary school teachers play a decisive role in developing (or inhibiting the development) in girls and young women interest in energy-related subjects.

“If we are talking about a situation where there is a teacher like mine, for example, from elementary school, who, when women answered, said: “You can tell she's a woman because she thinks for a long time.” And this was in elementary school, at a very young age, such comments can cause one group to worry more about their answers than the other. It's not that only people who don't know anything worry, but a person can know a lot, but such a comment can completely throw them off their train of thought and also discourage them for the future, thinking: “Okay, so I think slowly, well, maybe he's right, right? I hear it every day, I hear it many times, I hear it from him, also from my father and so on, so maybe he's right ”. (woman)

Among the factors that facilitate women’s entry into an energy career path the participants discussed the role of mentoring programmes, in which people working in the sector would discuss practical aspects of their jobs with the students who make their career plans.

“I would also add mentoring programs to the advantages, because there are many of them now, both for men and women, some dedicated specifically to women and, of course, joint programs. And I think that for a young person who doesn't really know what they want to do with their career, it would be so... it would be really cool to talk to someone who already works in the energy sector, for example, and they... it could really encourage them.” (woman)

While considering the factors that facilitate taking a decision to develop a career in the energy sector, regardless of the gender of the person, the participants discussed the

advantages of internships. While they generally found the internships an important opportunity and career facilitator, one of the women raised the issue of unpaid internships inaccessible for students and graduates with lower economic status.

“I never had a problem finding internships, but when I found out that they were unpaid, meaning work for nothing, well, I gave up. (...) Some people simply can’t afford it.” (woman)

When considering in which energy sector women have more career opportunities, the respondents agreed that the renewable energy sector with a growing number of jobs, and less rigid structures are more accessible for women (and for men) than both fossil fuels and nuclear energy sectors.

“There are many companies where you can find work, from tiny family businesses where someone simply designs installations and installs panels, to large companies such as PGE, which is now installing 20 gigawatts of renewable energy in the Baltic Sea. (...) there are very few jobs in nuclear energy itself (...) And as for coal, I think that not only is it already being phased out, but the structures are already firmly in place and it is difficult to break into them. It doesn't even matter whether you are a man or a woman, without connections it will be difficult to get into such positions.” (man)

C. Organisational climate at university/college

One of the aspects of the study climate is the gender distribution of the lectures. Interestingly, while other STEM fields at their university were reported by participants as heavily male-dominated, energy-related fields, both renewables and nuclear energy, were argued to have a gender balance among the faculty.

“It was fifty-fifty, both in the first and second degrees. These energy-related subjects were usually taught by women... Yes, fifty-fifty. I mean, I wanted to generalize here, but it varied—mathematics, for example, was taught by a man, but mechanics by a woman, so it was fifty-fifty, completely fifty-fifty.” (woman)

“Nuclear energy is the same, it's also fifty-fifty. I was surprised, but there are a lot of women in this field” (man)

When asked, whether the gender of the teacher influences their attitudes towards women students, the participants disagreed. Some argued that it is an individual's personality rather than gender that is decisive, *“because you can always find a woman, just like a man, who can really knock you down”*. Other interviewees suggested that, based on their own experience, it was rather women or rather men who more often bullied female students.

“In my experience, women who have already achieved something in a given field and who have themselves been oppressed as women tend to oppress women more than men. For example, we had a female mathematician who had a lot of comments only for women.(...) So I think that often the opposite is

true, that people look at whether a woman is teaching a class, because women can actually do much more harm to women than men” (woman)

“I never had a female lecturer who was particularly harsh towards women. I had the opposite situation, where the male lecturers were very... I also had a situation where my friend fainted during class because she was treated so badly by the male lecturer”. (woman)

When directly asked, most participants declared that they had not so far experienced or observed unequal treatment of women during their studies. As one of the participant noticed, it is student engagement and knowledge that matters and is evaluated, not their gender .

“There has never been any discrimination whatsoever. Well, in the entire department, there are practically 50% women and 50% men. I don't even know if there will be more women in total. And I've never had any... Let's say that no one... no one cares whether someone is a woman or a man, or whether any other factor matters, except whether you attend classes and how well you know the material.”

At the same time, however, a few of the interviewees easily recalled some recent incidents during the lectures that can be classified as gender microaggressions, as in the first quote illustrating a hidden insult or as evident gender discrimination, as in the second case:

“We have this one lecturer who comes up with lines during lectures like, “Let's ask one of the ladies now, because ladies are so nice to talk to,” or, “Oh, even a woman knew that!” when one of them volunteers. During lectures, for example, he would only ask girls questions and stuff like that” (woman)

“There were two women in his department, but unfortunately they ended up with a professor who had a very stereotypical attitude and assumed from the outset that women should not study such subjects. And, well, he said that he did everything he could to simply not let those two women pass (...) they had a really hard time because they were simply women.” (woman)

When further discussing the organisational culture of their study fields and the whole university, the most participants agreed that it was rather favourable not only to women, but also to LGBT+ students. At the same time however, a woman participant noticed that, while there operates an equality department at their university which receives students' complaints on unequal treatment, the transgender students miss a separate unit and active policy for their protection.

“ We found that there is some kind of equality office, we found it while looking for where to file this complaint. So, it exists, but it seems to be a bit dusty. And as for... that... the other issue, namely equality for LGBT people, well, there's nothing about that, right? We couldn't find anything like that at [the name of the university] when we were looking. The only thing we found was some document from a few years ago that says [the name of the university] is open to such people. ” (woman)

The participants did not identify any examples of integrating gender dimension neither in their study programs, nor even in individual courses. Similarly, their lecturers did not use gender-sensitive language. Importantly, mostly male participants did not see the necessity of doing so, arguing that energy is impersonal and about engines, vehicles. However, a few participants noticed that unequal representation of women in textbooks and the use of generic masculine linguistic forms may have a detrimental effect on girls and young women's self-identity and motivations to pursue a career in energy sector, through the mechanism of external validation, that STEM and energy fields are only for men.

"In my opinion, this builds a subconscious belief not that, for example, I'll look at a picture and think, "Hmm... a man working on an engine, why not a woman?", but it will still register in my subconscious and add to it, because... well, because our brains look for patterns, right?" (woman)

"You think, "Okay, so they're looking for a man then," but also subconsciously, since this position is called "engineer," since it's called "operator," it builds up this subconscious belief that it's a man". (man)

D. Recommendations

Based on the discussion in the focus group interviews, several recommendations were made to increase women's participation in the energy sector. They mostly refer to activities directed towards two aims: 1. attracting children's and youth's interest in energy education and career and 2. facilitating the process of choosing energy-related academic study field.

As for rising girls' general interest in energy related topics, the participants suggested that:

1. To effectively attract girls' attention to energy topics and careers early enough, the popular culture, and especially children cartoons and youth films, should depict more professional women as role models.

"As for elementary school, I think that play and fairy tales, films for young people (...) simply observing women in high positions, women in specific fields in fairy tales, still play a significant role here".

2. To attract attention to energy topics schools – both primary and secondary – should organise activities like research clubs and trips to technological centres, which would help pupils explore their passions

"Some kind of extracurricular activities that broaden your horizons a little and help you discover new passions. For example, a club related to energy can inspire you to choose a field of study related to energy and pursue that path".

To facilitate the process of choosing by young women the energy-related field of study, the participants focused on:

3. Well prepared open days at universities and visits to high schools with presentations on energy-related study programmes, with a representation of current students (both women and men) who share their insights from their study experience.

“I think that these visits to high schools are definitely very important. I mean, currently it's more like the student decides to visit their old teacher and the teacher asks them to talk about something, but officially organized delegations would be a very good idea. And I also think that a mixed group, with both women and men, would be the best decision.”

4. Establishing forums where prospective students can consult their questions with current students and receive insights on study specificities.

Additionally, to facilitate the process of study enrolment for both women and men for any field of study, the participants opted for:

5. Specific guides and youtube tutorials for enrolment including information on how to get through the application and enrolment process.

5. Description of FGI with students from social sciences programme (FGI5)

A. Educational choices

All participants were enrolled in a Master's programme in social sciences. Some participants reported that their decision to pursue this programme stemmed from unfulfilled expectations in their previous academic studies. For these individuals, social sciences represented a new academic direction - one they perceived as more promising, intellectually stimulating, and aligned with their evolving interests. For some, the decision to study social sciences was initially incidental - they were not fully aware of the programme's content or the career opportunities it could offer. However, they soon realised that it was a suitable choice, as they found the programme engaging and ultimately decided to continue.

(...) to put it bluntly, I tossed a coin. When I realised that I could only study one programme, I was 19, I sat down and cried. I said that I wasn't able to study just one thing, so I chose about six programmes, applied for all of them, and then sent text messages to everyone in my family asking, 'Which programme should I choose now, because they haven't rejected me from any of them and I don't know what to do now.' I was hoping it would be a little easier, and my dad just told me that I might like it [Sociology] the most. And, well, the truth is that I quickly, like in a week or two, decided that there was no other option, I would definitely stay until the end, because it's interesting, and I'm still here. (woman)

Only one participant explicitly stated that their choice of programme was directly linked to an interest in sustainable development.

I was definitely inspired by the fact that these are more social studies, not economic-oriented. I wanted to try something new and I was also interested in sustainable development, so I felt that it might be nice to supplement my education. (woman)

Energy was not the primary factor influencing the participants' choice of this particular programme. They admitted that they lacked role models or individuals working in the energy sector who could encourage or inspire them to pursue energy-related fields. Moreover, energy-related topics were rarely addressed in their school education. However, when reflecting on their experiences and attempting to reconstruct key moments in which they encountered information about energy, some participants identified instances that may have contributed to their awareness in the field. Starting from an early age, they pointed out that children's toys are influential in shaping interest in technical subjects. The participants acknowledged that the range of toys available

today is increasingly diverse, often challenging traditional gender stereotypes and potentially encouraging girls to develop an interest in technology or STEM fields. In this context, they highlighted science kits related to chemistry, biology, and electronics, as well as Barbie dolls representing various professions that girls could identify with as a potential way of introducing the energy-related topics and shaping children's interests in this area. However, despite the growing availability of gender-neutral toys, the participants noted that gender stereotypes still played a significant role in shaping children's interests and career aspirations.

- It also reminds me that when I was little, I had a little chemist's kit, but my brother had something like a physicist's kit or something to do with renewable energy sources or something... a mine was on the box. So maybe (...) there's more of a subconscious division between what's more masculine and what's more feminine.

-But chemist seems so feminine, don't they? I mean, I'm talking about children's toys, for example, like a chemist's set, something like that, because it's associated with... it has to be, yes, because it has to be a very meticulous... I mean, a very meticulous person, somewhere out there. It seems to me that, for example, this stereotype, that meticulousness, that kind of, you know, down to the gram, down to the milligram, especially [fits] women. And if you need to hit it with a hammer, give it to your brother, right? That's the principle. (both women)

Participants recalled their early experiences in kindergarten and primary school, where they were first introduced to ecological activities such as waste sorting and turning off lights. However, these activities were often introduced as strict rules to follow, rather than being framed within a broader context that explains their connection to energy-related issues.

(...) there were lots of posters on the subject and, apart from that, we talked about it in lessons. But I have the impression that it was never, at least that's how I remember it, that it was never stated so clearly, like, 'turn off the light when you leave the room' because, I don't know, you save energy and so on. We were just given clear rules about what to do because it makes life better, but there was no exploration of the consequences of our actions. Maybe so. (man)

But for example, from my primary school, in fact from every school, every level of education, I don't remember any energy topics [to be discussed] at all. I have the impression that there were pictograms saying 'turn off the light' or 'save water', but that's it. (woman)

While referring to their experiences in primary school, the participants mentioned that discussions with some teachers included ecological topics, emphasising individual

responsibilities in protecting the planet. However, explicit discussions about energy were less common: only one participant reported having discussed energy transition during Geography lessons. However, this was perceived not as an integral part of the Geography curriculum but rather as a result of the individual approach taken by the teacher.

I'm from Lublin voivodeship and I remember the narrative at school, I don't remember there being many posters. But we definitely talked about it at school and we also talked in particular about the energy transition itself. I remember it most during geography class. But I think I also had a very wise and knowledgeable, and generally wonderful teacher. But at school, we also had discussions with other teachers about why we should, for example, turn off the water, or why there is actually a 10-minute break or whether it is better or not to leave the light on and when more electricity is consumed. But my first memory of this topic, I remember in kindergarten, there were a practical task to sort rubbish properly. (woman)

Some participants only engaged with the topic in depth during their academic studies and one noted that their interest in energy emerged in the context of their professional work, but this development occurred only after they had already chosen their study programme.

The moment when it started can be a bit difficult, because it actually happened when I was about 18 years old, and I think I started with Instagram, with zero waste approach, which I started somewhere... I started practising. And then... my interest in sustainable development only occurred during my studies. I was in a Students' Circle and there I began to explore the subject of CSR and then ESG, and only later energy. (woman)

I became more interested in energy in my professional life, so I didn't have this interest while studying sociology or management, but now I would really like to explore it from this social perspective. (woman)

Interest in energy-related issues was also fostered through well-designed study trips to locations within the sector. When encouraged to apply a gender-sensitive lens in evaluating study trips, participants noted that, to effectively challenge gender stereotypes, these trips should be designed to highlight the participation of both women and men in the industry, demonstrating the diverse roles they can occupy.

Interviewee (man): Yes, I said study trips, because I remember that we had such a trip in lower secondary school, but I wasn't there, but there was a trip to a sewage treatment plant. To a place that you don't have access to on a daily

basis, which makes it quite an exotic place. Interesting, I think it could be eye-opening for children.

Interviewer: Could... could something else happen there, that might encourage a girl to do it [develop educational and professional path in energy]? Because maybe... it could also be that... that I don't know, she'll see only men there and decide: 'it's not for me'.

Interviewee: I mean, it would be nice if, for example, a female employee gave the tour.

While further discussing the role of school in shaping the interest in energy transformation, the participants emphasized a practice-oriented approach as a crucial factor in both school and university education. Providing hands-on activities, meetings with experts, workshops, and classes led by practitioners not only allows students to apply their knowledge in practice but also enables them to actively engage with real-world challenges and to refer to someone as a role model to follow, which seemed to be especially important for girls.

Personally, I really like those subjects where someone from outside the company, who works in the sector, comes in and gives us a real-life example, tells us what they do, tries to pass on their knowledge to us, but they're not just an employee, a person who works here [at the University], they're from outside and they're really into it. (woman)

It also depends, let's say, if someone who comes to us, someone I can somehow relate to, and I see that they made it, so I can too. That makes a big difference. Not like a guy who just feels that this is naturally his place and it's not big deal. (woman)

One of the examples of such learning-by-doing approach was the participation in "Earth Day" activities at school. While this was recalled by few participants, this event was particularly memorable for one of them due to the involvement of students from a technical university, who conducted workshops on reusing waste materials, such as constructing rockets from recycled materials.

For participants, the human factor plays a crucial role in shaping education aspirations. The participants pointed out to the important role of parents as key actors shaping interests and future career paths, particularly for women. In case of energy-related (or broader technology-related) interests, this influence can act as both a supportive factor and a barrier: when parents are open-minded and actively inspire their children to explore diverse interests, they can nurture curiosity in technical subjects and related activities. Conversely, if parents reinforce gender stereotypes, they may unintentionally restrict

career aspirations, limiting choices to those traditionally deemed appropriate for a child's gender.

Interviewee (woman): I would actually start with my parents.

(...)

- Interviewee (woman): Because there will be parents who will inspire you to be more... I don't know... get more involved in your own... future and that you can do whatever you want. Or there will be ones like my dad, who said that I don't need to learn how to change a car tyre because my husband will do it for me anyway (laughter).

- Interviewee (woman): And I feel that... I'm very grateful to my dad, because I never wanted to do any kind of technical things, but he would take it very calmly and say: 'OK, now try using the drill.' (...) And he taught me things like that. It was only later that I appreciated it.

- Interviewee (woman): The first time I... when I was 20. Before that I wasn't allowed to because I might hurt myself.

- Interviewee (woman): I live alone, and my dad sometimes come over and ask if I need a light bulb changed, so that... because of the electricity, so that nothing happens to me. (...) he recently cleaned my kettle so that I wouldn't get electrocuted, because women shouldn't touch such things. You can hurt yourself there... too delicate, I mean... I mean... too... too weak.

Furthermore, for children and young people, peer opinions hold significant influence. While this factor was discussed in a loose relations to participants' experience, they agreed that social pressure suggesting that certain subjects, courses, or study programmes are not suitable for girls may discourage them from pursuing their interests in these fields. They may feel that they do not belong or do not fit into such spaces. However, negative peer influence can also have a motivating effect, encouraging girls to challenge cultural expectations and demonstrate that they are just as capable as boys in technical disciplines. Such reactions, however, depend on various factors, including parental support, the presence of role models, and individual characteristics.

Personal circumstances sometimes played a role in shaping familiarity with energy-related issues. For instance, living in a neighbourhood with two different energy sources led to routine comparisons of energy bills, making such considerations an integral part of daily life. Being exposed to these discussions from early childhood may have indirectly fostered an interest in energy-related matters.

For me, it was about energy - I mean, on one hand, because I grew up in an area where, at first, everyone had those gas heaters, so energy was already expensive. My whole neighborhood had electric heating, but the one next to ours still had those heaters, and there was always this comparison between, say, our apartment and

my mom's friend's place - like, "Oh my God, they pay so much more in winter," for heating and all that. And I remember, as a child, constantly hearing that I should never live somewhere with those heaters or with, like, gas heating, because I'd never be able to afford it in winter - the bills would be too high. So, in that sense, that definitely influenced me. (woman)

Regional differences were also highlighted. While participants perceived energy as a commonly discussed topic in regions such as Górny Śląsk or Małopolska, they noted that this was not be the case in areas like Warmińsko-Mazurskie, where energy issues may not have been as prominent in everyday conversations.

B. Career pathways

Although all participants acquired new knowledge about energy only during their study programme, they had already identified potential career opportunities within the energy sector. One area they considered was human resources (HR) departments in energy companies. While they recognised a connection to the energy industry through employment in an energy company, they perceived this link as relatively weak, given that HR functions are not significantly influenced by the specific sector in which a company operates.

I think there are, because, for example, if I remember correctly, Hitachi Energy in Krakow definitely offered internships for people with a background in the humanities, so that they could be interns in the HR department or something like that. If it is, say, a job in an energy company, but not entirely related to energy. (woman)

Graduates of social sciences can also pursue a research-oriented and education-oriented career path. They are needed in research centres, universities, and other organisations conducting social research on energy. Given the substantial investment in the energy sector and its ongoing developments, research is crucial for understanding the associated processes, their consequences, and their impact on societies, communities, and the environment. Graduates from social sciences possess the necessary expertise to design and conduct such research, contributing valuable insights into the social dimensions of energy transition. This positions them advantageously compared to graduates of technical disciplines, who primarily focus on the technological aspects of energy.

But it also occurred to me that there is currently a great deal of investment in research in the energy sector, because new forms of energy supply are constantly being developed, and a great deal of research is needed in this area. And sociologists, as we know, are also useful in such research centres. (woman)

All evaluations, even regional ones or... or... or at the lowest possible level, are necessary, and even from the perspective of the education and experience that sociologists have. Even when conducting interviews or... or qualitative research, I think that it would be much more cost-effective to hire a group of educated sociologists than, for example, a group of even very good engineers or people interested in working strictly in the field... in the field of, precisely, the development of the energy sector, who will not, for example, be able to fully convey information during such consultations or evaluations with... with... well, with any person, yes, with Mr. John or Ms. Anne, who are not... are not... do not use such energy jargon, or... or... or simply the entire company dialect.

Not only can the graduates of social sciences organise and conduct social research, but also consultations on issues related to energy, its development, and implementation. Additionally, they can lead training sessions for individuals interested in working in the energy sector, equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge.

Or, for example, if the state plans to build nuclear power plants, this requires some kind of public consultation, and in my opinion, the work of sociologists would be extremely important here.

One area where sociologists could find employment in the energy sector is, I can see it from the example of activists – especially women – who are very active, usually in cities or within various foundations. They are also heavily involved in... creating new jobs in the energy sector for people who will soon no longer have their current jobs and will need to find something else. And at the moment, there is very little public discussion about this. It is clear that this problem exists, but, for example, according to my information, the government is doing very little in this direction. This is where sociologists could be very useful, in terms of ensuring new jobs, retraining employees, providing access, but also in terms of overall energy security, because this is something we will have to deal with. I think that this topic is also slightly overlooked in public discourse, and we as sociologists could also influence this.

Another career path in research and education involves working in interdisciplinary teams within institutions that support energy transformation, such as banks, energy-focused companies, and investors. These organisations offer opportunities for professionals to both inform individuals about financing or technology options, and fulfilling an educational role - raising awareness and knowledge about energy transition, enhancing public understanding of energy transition. Success in this sector requires not only expertise in energy transformation but also the ability to convey specialised knowledge in a clear and accessible manner to non-experts. Experts in social sciences can act here as intermediaries and facilitators of communication between citizens

encountering new technologies and those driving innovation, such as inventors and entrepreneurs. By translating complex scientific and business concepts into accessible language, they help demystify emerging technologies, clarify their benefits and challenges, and promote constructive dialogue between the public and the business and innovation sectors.

I think we can be such an intermediary, so to speak. If we imagine, for example, a bridge, we will be somewhere in the middle of the bridge and we have this community which, as we know, when a new technology comes along, we feel some fear, right, usually aversion. Because it is something new that we do not know. And on the other side, we have these new inventors, right, or these entrepreneurs who want to implement this innovation at all costs. And we should make both sides aware enough to somehow communicate with each other.

According to the participants, there is also significant potential for employment in the policy sector, particularly in the development of energy policies. Given their educational background, graduates from social sciences can analyse the intersection of energy and society, offering a deeper understanding of energy consumption patterns, their underlying rationale, and their societal consequences and finally translate these insights into policy recommendations. Their expertise allows them to contribute both as consultants, providing a more comprehensive understanding of ongoing processes, and as active participants in drafting and formulating policy documents.

I think that this also has an impact on solutions at the state level, that is, I think that sociologists could have a significant influence on the shaping of certain policies introduced by the state in the energy sector.

In conclusion, the energy sector is regarded as an attractive career path for social science graduates. They can pursue opportunities in energy-related companies, business, banking, and finance, as well as in public administration, policymaking, and research institutions.

There are several reasons why participants are interested in pursuing careers in the energy sector. Some perceive it as a financially lucrative field, attracting significant investment and offering substantial economic opportunities.

I associate it with big money, but I don't know.

They highlighted the financial resources provided by the European Union for this sector, as well as "green credits" available through the banking industry, which support the development of this field. Consequently, participants anticipated competitive salaries. Additionally, the energy sector was viewed as a long-term, promising field - not merely a temporary trend - since they believe it will continue to expand and develop in the future.

On the other hand, it is currently undergoing rapid development. I mean, not only is it the energy sector, but it is a sector that, to put it simply, affects practically everyone. The whole of society, even globally. So the demand for it will keep increasing, I think - at least from what I can see with the naked eye, even if that's not necessarily based on solid data - even private, semi-private companies are being established or expanding their activities. So it's constantly growing, and I think that for the next, well, I don't know if I can say decades, but certainly for the next few years and...

Work in the energy sector is also perceived as a social mission, framed through the lens of addressing global challenges, promoting sustainability, and improving current environmental and societal conditions. Many view their potential contributions as part of a broader effort to combat climate change or enhance energy efficiency.

When it comes to renewable energy, there may be a sense of, I don't know, perhaps this is too strong a word, but of saving the world.

The participants are also aware of barriers they may encounter in energy-related sector. Careers in the energy sector can be constrained by the socio-humanities focus of the programme. Participants acknowledge that the role of sociologists and the broader field of sociology are not widely understood in general, and entering the energy sector presents additional challenges in demonstrating how sociology can contribute to organisational development and innovation.

Many people do not fully realise that after studying sociology, one could try to go in this [energy] direction.

- I was just about to say that I think the problem may be that sociologists simply do not see energy sector as a potential place of future employment for themselves, and... especially since I think there is a stereotype about the energy sector that it is technical, that it is rather a male domain, as has already been mentioned, and that the humanities have little application in it. (man)

Furthermore, graduates of social sciences and humanities, who typically obtain a Bachelor of Arts degree, are often perceived - according to the participants - as less competent and less equipped with industry-specific knowledge and labour market-oriented skills compared to graduates of technical programmes.

It is said that an engineer and a bachelor's degree are supposedly on the same level – but they are not. Because, at least from the conversations I have with all my friends, people who graduate with an engineering degree are very often treated as people who already know how to do something, have practical skills, so they can very quickly translate them into skills or just go to work and do something, to put it bluntly. (...) But then a bachelor's or master's graduate comes along, and it's like, "So, what can you actually do — besides writing your thesis?". (woman)

As emphasised by the participants, there remains a prevailing perception that the energy sector is highly technical, which can serve as a barrier for many graduates of social sciences. As a result, they may not even consider the possibility of pursuing a career in this field, despite the potential contributions that social sciences can offer to the sector.

According to the participants, the element of innovation - specifically, the practical knowledge required to transfer a project conducted in school or university into real-life applications – is largely missing in their programme. They highlighted a noticeable gap between technical programmes and those in social sciences and humanities, with the former offering more structured training and internship opportunities. This disparity suggests that students in social sciences and humanities may have fewer chances to gain hands-on experience, which could limit their ability to translate theoretical knowledge into practical skills relevant to the energy sector, and therefore hinders their career opportunities.

- I think I recently met a group of people my age from [nam of university] who studied sustainable energy sources or something like that. We added each other on LinkedIn, and I see that they already have two internships in the energy sector, very different ones, and that they are already very focused, for example, on hydrogen energy or nuclear energy. And it's fascinating that we're the same age, yet we face different entry barriers. (woman)

The participants reflected on gender inequalities in the energy sector. While some individuals argued that gender does not significantly impact career development within the industry, others highlighted it as a potential barrier preventing women from pursuing careers in this field. Notably, some participants emphasized that the energy sector has traditionally been male-dominated and continues to be perceived as a male-oriented industry. As a result, women entering this sector may face additional challenges, including the need to continuously prove their competence and legitimacy in a field where they are underrepresented. The participants also noted that the societal role of motherhood and the expectation that women will take leave to care for children create substantial obstacles, particularly during the recruitment process. Moreover, women often feel less confident on how to negotiate employment conditions, including salary. As a result, they are less likely to apply for positions unless they feel fully confident in their

qualifications and competencies, which makes it difficult to compete in male-dominated sectors.

- *They will ask us if we plan to have children.*
- *Yes.*
- *Yes.*
- *And certainly also that, well, the pay gap, for example, appears very often. I recently read in a study that this is because women do not want to negotiate their rates at the start, that they are less inclined to do so in general, and this then has an impact on... on every pay rise, and that is why this gap is created in the first place. But the second thing... the second thing is that they often don't apply for jobs where they feel they don't meet all the requirements 100%, while men meet 30% of the requirements. I'm generalising now, but it's easier for men to apply because they say, 'OK, let's see,' while women have to meet all the requirements more.*

Microaggressions are also recognized as a significant issue, as the way women are approached and treated in the workplace often reflects underlying gender inequalities, subtly reinforcing barriers to career advancement and inclusion.

For example, at work I am called 'Mrs [diminutive of a name]', literally. On the one hand, it's nice, but on the other hand, it's incredibly infantilising, as I am an adult woman. And I think that this is even more so in this type of environment, where there are, let's say, one or two women for every fifteen or twenty men. The way people talk about her, the way they address her, any comments they make, will also be a make it or... or... or break it when it comes to her position, for example, in this group. Are they even considered as people who have... whose voice counts, or are they just Mrs Aneczka, Mrs Marteczka, who are also there because they will do it, but somewhere there they are also a kind of group mascot in a way. (...)

- But also, for example, we can't really imagine someone saying at work, let's say, Adasieńku, Maciusiu.

- I also think that a woman always has to fight to be an equal partner, let's say, in conversations. A man just walks in and is treated as such, while a woman has to constantly prove herself and show that she is also competent enough to be that... that equal person.

The participants also highlighted overburdening women with administrative tasks - on top of their primary responsibilities - and perceiving them as assistants who are expected to take on additional duties without question as a persistent issue, further reinforcing workplace gender inequalities.

I think that something else that could break this girl, this woman, is that women are often given additional administrative tasks on top of their duties in a particular field of specialisation: 'And maybe you could also book a room for us or arrange catering.' That, well, she is simply given more responsibilities and because of that, I think she may also be overworked or burnt out after some time.

The career opportunities of women depend on work environment: participants noted the importance of supportive team and its leader. In their opinion, working in male-dominated teams – which were assumed to occur more often in technological companies - was considered stressful, competitive, and demanding, requiring women to put in additional effort to demonstrate their competencies and advance their professional careers. Some participants noted that this environment might also pressure women to adapt to a traditionally masculine style of work, such as "being tough" or "showing no emotion".

- I think it would be more stressful if I had to imagine working only with men, or in a place where they dominate. I would be more stressed, I would want to prove my competence more, but I feel that the team I am in now, for example, which is entirely female, is very supportive, despite everything. That... that I don't feel like I have to pretend anything, that I can show my emotions, that I don't have to be tough. Because I've noticed that a lot of women who hold high positions and work in male-dominated environments try to come across as very tough, very emotionless individuals, even in their make-up and appearance, in order to somehow measure up. That emotions are always treated as something bad, empathy, well, 'you can't make decisions, you're not decisive if you're empathetic', so that... that can definitely influence it.

Regarding leadership, the age and gender of a direct supervisor or manager were highlighted as significant factors influencing workplace dynamics. Younger supervisors were generally perceived as more understanding, whereas older women could exhibit either a mothering approach or a highly restrictive attitude. In contrast, older male supervisors were often described as patronising and infantilising.

Both barriers - the field of study and gender inequalities - can independently hinder career opportunities, but their intersection may create new experiences of inequality. The nexus between educational background and gender stereotypes is clearly perceived as a significant obstacle for women seeking careers in the energy sector for graduates from social sciences.

a lack of knowledge even about, like, the whole, the entire path of education and experience combined, well, perhaps, with this image of a woman who

comes in and may give the impression of being, well... not only incompetent, but also unsuited to the environment, somehow too, well, unnecessary in such a space. Perhaps also simply... unaware of what... When a woman comes and says she is a sociologist with a degree. 'And you have no experience in energy?' 'I haven't worked in this sector, nor do I have any education in energy.' So the question might be, 'Well, what do you know about energy, apart from the fact that the lights are on?' This could be a form of infantilisation of the employee.

Importantly, the discussion on barriers and supportive factors extended beyond the energy sector, encompassing gender discrimination in technical fields more broadly, regardless of women's educational backgrounds. This indicates that the energy sector struggles with challenges similar to those in other technological fields and that the promise of creating better opportunities for women in the green energy sector has yet to be realised.

Overcoming the identified barriers requires the presence of more role models – whether a woman who has successfully pursued her interests despite numerous challenges, a passionate teacher who presents her subject in an engaging way, or a female professional in the energy sector sharing her experiences. Positive representations of women in the media, at public events, or as keynote speakers can further empower young women to envision themselves in the energy sector and encourage them to challenge traditional norms.

But she worked in such a team, and there were economists, engineers, and so on. And she said outright that she didn't feel inferior there, that everyone thought she contributed a lot to the team and enriched the project. contributed a lot to the team and enriched the project. It really resonated in her statement, and then, literally a few days later, I was at Open Eyes Economy and she was a speaker there, and I thought to myself, 'God, how cool that she's a speaker.' She was a speaker, the topic was about education and the importance of education, but... . But anyway, you can see some kind of power in all of this. (woman)

C. Field of study and organizational culture

The participants acknowledged that their study programme is not specifically oriented towards energy, as it is not planned to offer a dedicated specialisation in this field. However, energy-related topics are incorporated into certain courses, where students are encouraged to explore the intersection of sociology and technology and even consider technological career paths. They highlighted one course on energy, noting that while it provides a basic introduction to the subject, its primary focus is on technological aspects, with limited attention to the social dimensions of energy transformation. According to the participants, these topics are only briefly covered within their

curriculum. As a result, they often acquire knowledge on the subject from social media platforms, such as Instagram, or from sociologists actively engaged in disseminating information about career opportunities available to sociology graduates.

- And it's like... the course is really cool because it opens up this possibility for us, so we think, 'Oh, maybe there's a place for us somewhere out there.' However, it is, after all, an introductory course, and we learn about the construction of mines, which are renewable or non-renewable, so, as I say, maybe it's not bad, but it's really just the basics. And let's say we needed more development later, this social aspect, or precisely such solutions that we, for example, as sociologists, can contribute there. However, this is not there yet, because it is so new that first we need to have some knowledge about it in order to say anything about it. So I think this aspect is completely missing here, we don't touch on it, and in a way I understand that. It's not there. But I think it would be necessary. It would be cool and very interesting if we had a supplement in the form of such a topic later on.

The gender dimension is not systematically integrated into energy-related courses. In the case of two courses, gender aspects were introduced only as brief digressions or indirectly incorporated through student contributions. For instance, when students were asked to identify and describe a key figure relevant to the topic under discussion, they had the option to select a woman, but this was not a structured component of the curriculum.

D. Recommendations

- The curriculum at different educational levels (secondary school, HEI) should offer more trainings and internship which focus on gaining practical experience and applying knowledge to solve real issues. This could be done in a form of a partnership with energy-oriented institutions from various sectors to make sure that the internship are related to the programme and that pupils / students are involved in activities allowing them to use their knowledge.
- Increasing the number of practices-oriented classes and meetings; inviting people from business, NGOs who can share their experiences.
- Better occupational development course / meeting and career counselling (at all levels). Introducing professional education in the school to inform pupils about the possibilities of different career paths. Promoting career paths related to energy among young girls and students of social sciences.
- Promoting female role models in energy sector to encourage girls and young women to consider this educational and career paths.

6. Description of FGI lecturers and experts (FGI4 + IDI6 + IDI7)

A. Women's educational choices – energy sector

The lectures and experts stated that the factors impacting women's decision to pursue studies in energy systems can be shaped by historical and social perceptions: There is a societal expectation that technical fields like energy systems are more suited for men. This is enabled by the education system where women often feel less prepared for subjects like physics or technical fields. One of the respondents pointed out:

“What just came to my mind is the question of how much it is the children who actually make those educational choices and decisions, and how much it is rather their parents' decision — shaped by their stereotypes, their... well, their kind of historical thinking, just as X said.” (FGI4)

“I would also add some examples here, things I've seen and reflected on, because you, X, talked a lot about how we teach at earlier stages of education. My observation is that in high schools, in those mathematics and physics tracks, there are still more boys than girls. In the Youth Palace, where my children attend extracurricular classes, I can immediately tell what kind of class is taking place just by looking at the gender composition of the kids standing outside the door. If there are boys — it's obviously physics or math; if there are girls — it's probably some artistic activity. And that's true at every level. But what also came to my mind were those educational fairs for secondary schools.” (FGI4)

“I think this is generally connected to the country's social development — in the sense that girls have become more confident and are no longer afraid to enter technical fields. There's a broader social awareness now, something like: ‘Yes, I can do it. Yes, I'll go for it. No, it's not too hard for me. Why should I be treated differently?’ But I think this attitude is already instilled at the level of primary and secondary school. So by the time they get to university, they already come with this strong sense of: ‘Yes, this is where I belong, simply.’” (FGI4)

However, the under-representation of women in energy-related STEM studies is changing. One participant highlighted the increasing number of female students enrolling in STEM-related programmes, including those focused on energy (IDI6): 'The fact that women are under-represented in energy-related STEM studies is changing:

“In general, it seems to me that for some time now there has been a trend at universities for women to start studying technical subjects. This is not mainly related to energy, but to all fields of study, as we can see. At the moment, we have a ratio of about 40-60% in nuclear energy specializations, i.e., in these really advanced studies, where 40% are women, so this is a very, very large percentage compared to what it was before, where the percentage was only 10%, if not less. And this... this can be determined based on the number of students.” (IDI6)

A key factor driving this shift, particularly in the field of nuclear energy, is the perceived novelty and attractiveness of the subject, as well as promising future career prospects. A similar opinion was expressed by another participant regarding a growing women's interest in renewable energy careers as they are seen as less involved with big machinery and installations than the conventional energy industry.

"(...) energy has become fashionable, and renewable energy too. Well, it may also look a little less threatening from the point of view of such mechanization than conventional energy. Because conventional energy is all those huge thermal installations, gigantic, right, some very complicated pipelines, various storage tanks, processes, and so on. Renewable energy is a little simpler here, because everyone has these panels on their roofs and... and it doesn't look so repulsive, I would say, so maybe that's why it has actually lost some of that stigma... ...the kind of bogeyman that mining, for example, certainly still is for women. So I think that trends, politics, and fashion can completely, even unintentionally, influence these choices." (ID17)

Another factor is the visible interest of women in "softer" energy sectors. Women often lean towards fields perceived as softer, such as sustainable development, while men gravitate toward more technical energy roles:

"Well, in renewable energy, interest is generally linked to two things. The first thing, which I think is stronger in women, is a desire... a desire to do something for the environment. Men are more focused on interesting work and financial gain. However, there is a trend among women to say that they care not only about themselves, but also about the environment and their children, right?" (ID16)

A crucial factor highlighted by the FGI participants is also self-perception and confidence. Women tend to rate their technical competencies lower than men do, which impacts their confidence in entering energy fields.

"Women, regardless of age, consistently rate their technical skills significantly lower." (FGI4)

This contrasts with another participant's perspective, who highlighted the growing self-confidence among women and their refusal to be treated differently. They view the energy sector as a space where they belong, and achieve success on equal terms with male students.

"I think it's generally related to the country's social development, in the sense that girls are more courageous and aren't afraid to simply go into technical fields. There's a greater social awareness, along the lines of: 'Yes, I can do it. Yes, I'll go there. No, it's not difficult for me. Why should I be treated differently?' But I think this is already instilled in people at the primary and secondary school level. And they come to college with this very good experience, like, 'Yes, I'm supposed to go here, just like that.'" (ID16)

Changes at the individual level, in the approach and motivation of girls, are also supported by the external factors. There are also international organizations such as Women Nuclear who openly encourage women to pursue studies or additional trainings in nuclear energy. Moreover, to encourage girls to pursue studies and careers in the energy sector, especially in nuclear energy, international institutions provide scholarships and grants which openly state that explicitly prioritize female candidates. Importantly, these initiatives are only undertaken by external institutions and are not developed by the higher education institution where the participant works: there are not internal regulations prioritizing women as candidates for their programmes.

An additional motivator closely related to women in the energy sector is the large number of support programs. In nuclear energy, we have virtually no support programs that are not dedicated to women. Women always have priority, and these are support programs organized primarily by international institutions under the auspices of the European Commission and, for example, the International Atomic Energy Agency. So that... that is the factor that gives women priority." (IDI6)

While discussing the impact of these programmes on women and energy sector, the participant (IDI6) highlighted three key aspects. Firstly, these programs were introduced to improve gender balance, as data collected by the EU clearly indicated the masculinization of the traditional nuclear energy sector. Secondly, having women in the company was perceived as beneficial, as they are often regarded as more accurate and meticulous. Thirdly, the participant emphasized the diversity of roles within the energy sector, stating that “(...) from an employer's point of view, not every position is suitable for a woman, not every position is suitable for a man. Maybe it's politically incorrect, because we shouldn't make that distinction, but in practice, in reality, that's how it works” (IDI6).

“Although young women today choose their field of study much more independently, I'm aware that they are still under considerable pressure from their social environment, which somehow shapes their opinions. They also tend to listen to what older people tell them — those who claim to have more experience — and their parents often give them suggestions as well. So it's not that young people make these decisions entirely on their own. I think that if they did make them 100% independently, they would be much less afraid [to choose energy-related fields].” (IDI7)

However, at the same time, another participant argued that universities are today very well adjusted to the needs of female employees with caring duties. At her organisation acknowledging the needs of women with parenting duties through simple adherence to the Labour code offering plenty of measures, works very well:

“(...) And it's possible. You just have to want it. So I... I really don't see... I don't see... I don't see any obstacles here. You just need to create the right conditions. That is, if she's currently employed at a particular department, right, where she works — or let's say her supervisor — then he or she has to be flexible enough to understand that her availability will be limited for a while, since she's starting a family and having a child. But at the Technical University,

this works very well. (...) The Labour Code now includes so many provisions... so many benefits and facilities for young parents, and for people starting families in general, that it's really enough just to follow the letter of the Labour Code — and the conditions are already quite good. These are genuinely good conditions.” (ID17)

B. Women's careers in the energy sector

The increasing emphasis on gender equality and diversity in companies has contributed to opening the energy sector to women. Gender equality is viewed as a business case, making it beneficial for companies to develop diverse teams and avoid criticism for failing to meet established standards. Such approach affects not only women graduating from energy-programmes, but also from social sciences, which reflects a more general tendency to work in interdisciplinary teams as the energy sector clearly needs non-technological experts. They can be engaged in research but also play an important role in social consultations, communication and dissemination, conveying findings and activities to the public.

It is one of the trends, I mentioned that we have what is rather unattractively called “nuclearization,” which is teaching nuclear energy to students of other disciplines, but we also have a lot of projects aimed at teaching students, including soft skills. It's a very interesting idea in general, but the implementation of this part is very controversial, because I don't know if you also see it, there are many external entities that have no idea how to teach these soft skills. There are some charlatans who have seen something somewhere. And the problem is that (ns 38:04) they can harm students. It has to be prepared personally. But opening students up to soft skills, as you said: sociology, social sciences, some law, or things like that, they are open to it.” (ID16)

One of the participants claimed that there is a significant difference in women’s and men’s career options—while men tend to consider a career in industry by default, women more often choose an academic career path. However, interview ID6 provided a contrasting view, suggesting that women prefer careers in business over academia due to higher salaries, a more practical orientation toward creating tangible products, and a stronger emphasis on implementation, aspects perceived as less prominent in academia. Given these contrasting perspectives, this study does not allow for definitive conclusions but rather points toward areas requiring further exploration.

Women's careers as indicated by the FGI participants tend to choose a **supportive and flexible work environments**: Women are more likely to choose energy-related careers when the sector offers flexibility and work-life balance. Where the workplace culture allows them to feel fully empowered and equal to the male colleagues. Women's career choices are often influenced by the desire for work-life balance and family life, whereas men may prioritize career advancement and technical challenges. One participant mentioned:

“So indeed, they tend to drop out more quickly — if they choose that kind of profession, it often turns out that, for example, it’s their first job, and then their next job is already in a different sector.” (FG14)

Another participant referred to the same issue of work-life balance, when explaining gender differences in research interest. According to her, whereas men are eager to develop implementation projects, women researchers in the energy field more often engage in theoretical issues.

Explaining gender imbalances in the energy sector through individual women’s choices was also present in another participant’s statement:

“The women who deal with energy-related issues — because they work in research — always declare that they approach these topics more from a theoretical perspective. The men, on the other hand, tend to focus on more applied solutions — the kind they would like to see actually implemented. They produce solutions written with a specific practical application in mind, and that’s something I notice in the energy field. (...) This may result from the fact that applied issues and applied activities carry greater responsibility. And this responsibility — it’s not that women avoid responsibility — but it requires deeper engagement with the subject. So, if a woman has her priorities set in such a way that she needs to fulfill several roles at once — like having a family, children, and at the same time her professional work — then in such a situation, she might, even subconsciously, think about not getting too deeply involved, so that it doesn’t require her to limit her availability for the sake of her family.” (IDI7)

Another participant, while noticing the growth of female employees in the energy sector, also underlined that they are underrepresented among leaders and, once they hold management positions, they tend to be in less prominent positions.

“I suspect that if we reviewed the major energy companies and their positions, we would probably find quite a few women there. However, so far — traditionally, in all industrial companies, at least everywhere I check (and I check quite often) — for instance, when we start negotiations with a company, I always look up the composition of the management board. And yes, there is a woman, but in 99% of cases she occupies just one position. (...) The accountant, yes, exactly. The company’s management board typically looks like this: president, vice-president, president for strategy, for development, for operations — and then one board member, the lady accountant.” (FG14)

However, one of the participants (IDI6) in our study argued that the energy sector – regardless of its type – is becoming more accessible to women in managerial positions, while significant barriers persist for women in more physical demanding roles in this sector. Importantly, these leadership positions are usually associated with "soft" aspects, such as organizational and administrative matters, while technology-focused management remains male-dominated (IDI6). According to the participant, this may be a result of the previous organizational culture, in which women educated in energy-related

fields pursued careers in this direction, leading them to these particular "soft" managerial positions. However, the participant anticipates a shift in the near future, already observing its first signs, driven by changes in the educational system and evolving expectations among women..

“Yes, I think the distinction is perhaps not so much between sectors — like nuclear, conventional, or renewable energy — but rather between different positions within the energy sector. Usually, women hold positions that require more intellectual work than physical work, one could say — such as supervisory roles. And I don’t mean positions like accountant, HR officer, or someone handling paperwork at a desk, but rather managerial roles, involving oversight and coordination. Naturally, some field positions would be difficult to perform with a predominantly female workforce, since they require very demanding physical effort, right? Because it really is tough work. But at the management level, there are more and more women — and we can clearly see that.” (IDI6)

Additionally, workplace discrimination and microaggressions, such as inappropriate comments, contribute to an uncomfortable environment for women, as illustrated by the remark,

“The kinds of jokes where certain things can supposedly be said to women — they’re meant to be funny, sarcastic, even sweet, but in reality, they’re really not.”

“People our age and younger are, in a way, aware of what they can and can’t say — there’s this boundary, right? A boundary against stupid jokes, silly insinuations, or those childish diminutives like ‘Kasiunia’ or something similar, you know? Because being called by such a [diminutive name] — nobody really likes that. So yes, we know where that line is, but unfortunately, older people are often unaware of it.” (IDI6)

Moreover, women often encounter barriers to career advancement, feeling the need to constantly prove their competence in a male-dominated field:

“In the workplace, when it comes to technical professions where there are many men around, it’s not easy, right? The question is — these women always have to, so to speak, prove that they are just as competent.”

Specific in the nuclear energy sector, there is an argument related to security and safety of pregnant women due to radiation. On the one hand, this argument is presented as a barrier at the institutional level or even at the level of national law in some countries. On the other, there is an argument related to women being not willing to take risk.

“Nuclear energy is quite specific, because the risk is always higher due to radiation — and women are generally more afraid of radiation than men. It’s already been proven, in a way, that they face a greater risk and therefore don’t want to take it. But still, they enter this industry. So that’s how it looks.” (IDI6)

These factors collectively create significant obstacles that make it difficult for women to thrive in the energy sector.

C. Organisational culture and gender equality

The organisational cultures in the energy-related Higher Education sector in Poland are a blend of efforts to support gender equality, but also indicate significant barriers. Gender equality in participants institutions is supported in various ways, particularly through awareness and initiatives that aim to balance opportunities between men and women. For example, some institutions, as pointed out by one participant, promote inclusivity and sensitivity to gender issues by fostering open, supportive environments.

“In our institute, there’s a strong sensitivity to various kinds of, well... politeness, I’d say. We really try to be open, tolerant, and to approach every person with respect.”

“The importance of this issue comes from the top — once it’s adopted by the rector and the Senate, and once certain decisions are made and the bodies responsible for overseeing this equality are established to ensure it’s actually upheld, then this example, so to speak, spreads across the individual units. This cascading process takes some time, but I can see that it’s much better now than it was eight or nine years ago, when I first started working at the Technical University. I can simply see how things are changing.” (IDI7)

The change in organizational culture is also driven by external EU initiatives, which set gender equality standards in projects and establish GEP eligibility criteria. This suggests that some organisations do make a conscious effort to encourage tolerance, respect, and openness. They also established units responsible for equality and diversity policies (including Gender Equality Plan) and initiatives. However, the knowledge about these policies and initiatives as well as the implementation of gender equality practices may be insufficient or uneven across different institutions, with older, more traditional structures not always being as aware of gender-related challenges. As one participant noted, indicating that younger staff may be more attuned to gender issues compared to their older counterparts.

“Among the younger teaching staff, I think yes. But among the older ones, definitely not.” (FGI4)

“So that’s what I notice — the problem is that people with high academic titles, not positions but titles, usually don’t take criticism well. They believe they can do anything, because that’s how they were brought up in the previous era. That’s where the problem lies. I’d say that up to the age of forty, even fifty nowadays, it’s not an issue — people know the boundaries and understand general rules of behavior, right?” (IDI6)

Another argument relates to the principle of meritocracy, emphasizing that the primary priority for higher education institutions is the competence, knowledge, and skills of employees, while gender equality is not perceived as a significant factor influencing these attributes. Such an approach also impacts the perception of initiatives prioritizing women (such as the aforementioned training programs), leading to a negative view that women are included solely based on their gender rather than their qualifications.

“But generally speaking, forcing — to put it bluntly — forcing women into management bodies or other positions just because there has to be a woman,

because it's written somewhere, is a negative thing. It should be about competence, not about gender.” (IDI6)

As one participant acknowledged, while the number of female academics with a PhD is increasing, becoming closer to the number of male academics, only a few women attain the rank of full professor (IDI6). Female students and early-career researchers are also more frequently assigned academic housekeeping tasks, but with the generational change, they are more often refusing to undertake them if they are not listed as their responsibilities.

The prevalence of microaggressions and gender biases in the workplace also indicates that gender equality is far from fully realised. This issue is particularly evident in sectors that are predominantly male, where women must often prove their competence repeatedly, as highlighted by the comment (FGI4). Participants point several times the problem caused by the lack of balance between man and woman working in the energy sector. Several factors contribute to the higher number of men than women in energy study programmes and the sector at large. The perception that technical roles require physical strength or specific male-oriented competencies continues to deter many women. As one participant noted,

“For example, at the Faculty of Energy and Fuels, there are mostly man (FGI4) pointing out the dominance of men in the more technically focused areas of energy studies.

Moreover, women are often steered away from pursuing energy studies and careers due to a lack of early exposure and role models in these fields. Educational guidance and career advice for young girls still tend to focus on traditionally female roles, while technical fields like energy are often presented as male-dominated.

Teaching

In the discussion during FGI it became clear that gender is not integrated into curricula, but there are some efforts to make energy-related studies more inclusive.

“I mean yes, yes, in that respect — absolutely. It's about, for example, energy consumption profiles — how women use energy in the household, or when someone's cooking on the stove, when the washing machine is running, or whether it's a woman or a man who turns the lights off or leaves them on, right? These are definitely social behaviors. They are discussed, but not in terms of being good or bad — rather just in terms of how things actually look.” (IDI6)

The participant continued by stating that incorporating gender aspects in terms of knowledge is important, but without emphasizing gender as a crucial factor.

“I think we shouldn't address this in such a way — it's something that exists, yes, but we shouldn't try to forcefully bring it into education. It should be talked about, of course, but not in a way that... There's this tendency, I feel, to overemphasize the role of women and to push, somewhat forcefully, their inclusion into certain areas — and that shouldn't be happening.” (IDI6)

For others, this question even raises a significant objection from one of the participants. Indicating that observing the differences between man and woman in the energy sector is useless.

“But what difference does it make? I’m sorry, really, truly. Let me put it differently — women use hair dryers, right? And men use them less often, or use something else. I just don’t quite understand why gender should matter so much here, you know? It’s just that women might be, well... our research showed quite clearly that they tend to be more sensitive to issues of energy saving.” (FGI4)

However, the integration of gender into the curriculum is not the case in technical courses. In more traditional technical programmes, such as those focusing on energy engineering or electrical energy, the emphasis tends to be on the technical skills required for these roles. This argument is also visible in the participants' vision of how gender policing should be in the claims of one of the partners, who emphasises that gender issues are less relevant because the crucial things are competences - which should not be biased by any gender issues.

“For me, what matters are competencies — competencies are key. That should be the main criterion when thinking about working in a given position or profession. All barriers should be removed. And we should also eliminate those earlier stages that lead to certain choices being made the way they are — not necessarily in the most optimal way, right?” (FGI4)

Good practices

Several good practice initiatives have been identified that support the increase of women in energy-related study programmes and careers. One example is the creation of mentorship and role models within the sector, where women are encouraged by those already established in the field. This highlights how mentorship programs, particularly those that focus on empowering young women by providing role models, are crucial for increasing female participation. Additionally, initiatives such as the *"Ambasadorzy Transformacji Energetycznej"* program provide opportunities for younger individuals to engage with the energy transition, thus offering them exposure to the sector early on. These kinds of programs, along with specific courses that include social sustainability and environmental energy studies, tend to attract more women due to their focus on "softer" and socially impactful aspects of energy. To scale up these initiatives, it is essential to integrate gender equality more systematically into curricula and organizational structures. As mentioned in the transcript, greater awareness and training are needed to address gender biases, both in educational institutions and in the workplace. For instance, incorporating specific gender-focused modules into energy programs could ensure that women feel more confident pursuing these careers. Furthermore, fostering partnerships between educational institutions, industries, and NGOs would enhance these initiatives' visibility and expand their reach to a broader audience. Encouragingly, young staff and academics are more aware of gender issues, as seen in the transcript where a younger generation of educators seems more attuned to supporting gender equality, which can be leveraged to accelerate these efforts. The barriers to increasing the number of women in the energy sector are multifaceted. A

significant challenge is the deeply rooted gender stereotypes about technical fields, which continue to frame energy studies as male-dominated and physically demanding. This discourages many women from even considering energy as a career path.

One participant referred to a good practice of systematic encouraging women to study engineering fields that was introduced at her university and brought a growth in the proportion of female students:

“The Technical University has taken — and I know it has taken — such actions, including promotional campaigns aimed specifically at women and girls, encouraging them to apply to the university. In fact, I myself took part in such a campaign about ten years ago, called ‘Engineer in High Heels’. I really liked it, and I think it was a very good initiative. This kind of thing should definitely be done, because there’s absolutely no reason for girls to be afraid. Absolutely not. They just need good examples. I think it’s really about breaking through certain mindsets and stereotypes. If, in their surroundings, there are women saying things like, ‘No, don’t do that. Why would you bother? You’ll end up among those guys — they’ll crush you, they’ll overwhelm you,’ there should also be a woman who says, ‘What are you talking about? Give it a try — it’s great, it’s completely different.’ You just have to try. So yes, the Technical University has carried out and continues to carry out such initiatives. And I think that’s one of the reasons why we now have more and more girls.” (ID7)

D. Recommendations

The recommendations for improving women's participation in the energy sector focus on both structural changes and cultural shifts within education and industry. Crucial recommendation is the implementation of mentorship programs and the promotion of female role models in the sector. Providing mentorship opportunities can help women navigate the challenges of the energy field and gain the confidence they need to pursue leadership roles. These initiatives can be scaled up by fostering stronger connections between educational institutions and industry, ensuring that women are introduced to role models and mentors early in their academic careers. Encouraging companies to create more inclusive, flexible work environments with policies that support work-life balance and career progression for women can also help retain female talent in the sector.

Finally, addressing gender biases and stereotypes within the workplace is essential. This can be done by implementing unconscious bias training for employers, awareness raising initiatives and promoting policies that ensure equal pay and equal opportunities for advancement for women in the energy sector. To overcome these barriers, industries should create supportive networks and safe spaces where women feel empowered to contribute and lead, ensuring they are not marginalized or overlooked in the decision-making processes.

7. Cross cutting analysis

A. Differences between STEM and SSH students

Are there any differences in the women's educational and career pathways between SSH and STEM?

The focus group discussions revealed notable differences in the educational trajectories and experiences of students from STEM and social sciences and humanities programmes, as well as distinct gender dynamics within STEM fields. The study suggests that STEM students' educational paths – especially in case of men - are strongly shaped by prior technical preparation, often shaped by attendance at technical schools or classes with an extended mathematics curriculum, while female STEM students, by contrast, often cited global challenges, such as sustainability and energy transition, as motivating factors for pursuing careers in renewable energy systems (RES) or nuclear energy. Moreover, in case of male students the argument of better career prospects and salary is mentioned more often. Social sciences students, on the contrary, often viewed their studies as a more intellectually stimulating academic direction. For many, the choice of program was initially incidental, and energy-related topics were not a primary consideration in selecting their field. What makes the energy topics interesting for them is the practice-oriented learning, including hands-on workshops and interactions with role models. This motivation is especially important for women, but in general social science students admit that they develop their interest in energy more gradually due to lack of role models, individuals working in the energy sector who could encourage or inspire them to pursue energy-related fields or addressing energy topics at school. Moreover, contrary to male STEM students, their motivation to choose education paths with energy-related topics was not linked to the career opportunities it could offer. For them, energy was rather related with ecological approach from the early (pre-)school time, which explains their broader vision of energy and its linking with societal issues.

While in case of both groups significant others – parents, teachers or peers – play significant role in taking the decision about education, their role seems to be more often mentioned by the female STEM and SSH students. They are often presented in their narrations as sources of inspiration and support, those who foster their curiosity and interested in non-traditional fields. However, the study also points to the possible negative attitude of parents and teachers, who can undermine girls' confidence in their STEM-related abilities.

Finally, the study shows that gender stereotypes shape educational trajectories from the early ages, encouraging and leading diverse paths. Male participants recognized persistent stereotypes that engineering is unsuitable for women but generally rejected these personally, though they noted that such beliefs could affect female peers. Female participants from STEM programmes also highlighted the gendered perception of energy sectors, with conventional energy often associated with men and RES seen as more suitable for women. Social science students highlighted the role of socialization, pointing to the gender stereotypes and expectation as formative experiences for children which is rarely challenged by education at the primary and secondary level. As a result, gender stereotypes may shape the career aspiration of women, discouraging them from pursuing education and career path in this area.

The differences are also observed regarding the career paths. While STEM students focus on potential career in jobs related to technology, SSH students pointed out to the potential paths linking sociology and energy, emphasising the social aspect of energy. While STEM pathways emphasize technical training and early exposure, SSH pathways highlight interdisciplinary skills, societal relevance, and communicative competence as central to career development. Their career paths are typically oriented towards research, education, policy, consulting and advisory roles in energy-related sectors.

Within STEM, differences between male and female students are evident. For male students career in energy sector is related to meritocracy and personal interests. While they recognize gender stereotypes, men rarely perceive them as personally limiting. Women, on the other hand, must navigate both the same societal and family pressures and additional barriers tied to gendered perceptions of technical competence. They face more direct structural and cultural barriers, requiring external support and personal resilience to navigate male-dominated pathways. Interestingly, renewable energy is perceived as more flexible and accessible for women, while fossil fuel is view as male dominated and less inclusive. At the same time, similarly to STEM male students, energy sector is for them linked with stable employment, professional development and good salary. SSH students point to the perceptions of the energy sector as highly technical and male-oriented, which may discourage engagement despite the sector's growing need for social, policy, and research expertise.

B. Differences between STEM (in general) and energy-related programmes and differences between programmes focusing on different types of energy.

The FGIs indicate clear contrasts between general STEM and energy-related study programmes in terms of students' motivations, cultural perceptions, and gender representation. In general STEM programmes, both male and female students tend to make educational decisions based on continuity with previous schooling and pragmatic career considerations. Others cited family influence or school prestige as determining factors. By contrast, the choices of students in energy-related fields were shaped by ecological awareness, global energy transition discourse, and the perceived societal relevance of their studies. Energy-related programmes, therefore, appear to link scientific curiosity with civic and environmental responsibility.

As for gender representation, in the STEM FGIs, participants repeatedly observed that engineering and technical fields remain "strongly masculinized". Women's underrepresentation is understood as a cultural legacy rather than a reflection of aptitude. Male participants often referred to social stereotypes that "*engineering studies are not for women,*" while insisting that ability, not gender, should determine participation.

"I think there's still a belief in society that engineering studies aren't for women... in technical profiles girls are a fraction of the class" (FGI3_PL).

Socialisation processes in adolescence, family expectations, and the fear of social isolation in male-dominated environments further constrain women's educational

choices. One male student noted that *“a girl who wants to go to technical school may be even stopped by her parents... because it’s not a direction for her to study”* (FGI3_PL).

In contrast, energy-related fields seem to present a more complex gender pattern. Certain subfields—particularly renewable energy and environmental protection studies are portrayed as interdisciplinary, progressive, and aligned with global climate goals. They provide women with a legitimate entry point into technical fields and display relatively balanced gender representation. Nuclear Energy is associated with stability, prestige, and scientific challenge, but remains hierarchical and male-dominated, often accompanied by gendered concerns about safety and motherhood. As female students noted:

“In environmental engineering there are definitely more women than men. (...) On nuclear energy, there was a predominance of men.” (FGI1_PL)

Fossil fuels are viewed as technologically outdated and socially conservative, offering limited space for new entrants regardless of gender. Participants also identified gendered symbolic divisions: non-renewable energy is culturally associated with men and physical labour, whereas renewable energy is perceived as more compatible with feminine-coded values such as care and sustainability:

“If energy is non-renewable, the recipients are usually men... and if renewable, then women. (...) It seems to come from the mining culture” (FGI1_PL).

This perception suggests that the process of energy transition coincides with a symbolic reconfiguration of gender roles, allowing women to enter new technological domains under the banner of environmental responsibility. Women’s career trajectories in both STEM and energy fields are however marked by ambivalence. On one hand, participants express strong commitment to competence and meritocracy; on the other, they recognise enduring structural and cultural obstacles. In the male-dominated nuclear sector, women reported being explicitly discouraged from certain positions:

“I was told directly that I will not become an operator, because it’s not a job for women” (FGI1_PL).

Such experiences contrast with the renewable energy and environmental sectors, where the culture is perceived as more inclusive and modern. Students viewed these industries as expanding, innovative, and flexible, compared with the declining and rigid structures of fossil fuel sectors.

At the university level, organisational climates vary. Some participants described equitable and supportive environments, particularly where younger professors treat women and men equally. Others, however, reported instances of sexist remarks by older lecturers, revealing generational gaps in attitudes.

Interestingly, female students in energy-related fields often indicated a preference for academic careers, partly because they perceive industry as less welcoming or accommodating to women. As one participant noted, *“women often stay at the university, because they do not see themselves in industry”* (FGI1_PL).

To conclude, the FGIs reveal that while STEM education in general remains structured by traditional gender hierarchies, energy-related studies—particularly in renewables—create more inclusive spaces for women by connecting technical expertise with ethical and ecological narratives. However, nuclear and fossil sectors continue to reproduce masculine norms and exclusionary practices.

C. Teaching and incorporating gender perspective

Across all FGIs, participants agreed that gender is rarely addressed in curricula. Both male and female students described technical and energy education as “gender-blind”—focused on mechanics, systems, and efficiency rather than on human or social dimensions. As one female participant observed:

“We have a kind of blindness to differences between us (...) we learn purely technically, as if we are all equal” (FGI1_PL).

Nevertheless, students recognised subtle gender effects in teaching materials, especially the absence of female figures in textbooks and the exclusive use of masculine linguistic forms:

“It builds the subconscious feeling that ‘a man at the engine’ is normal. Our brains look for patterns” (FGI2_PL).

While explicit integration of gender studies is lacking, participants offered practical recommendations: inviting female professionals as guest lecturers, incorporating examples of women engineers, establishing mentoring programmes, and ensuring visibility of women in energy-related outreach and media (compare chapter 7c).

D. Enablers and barriers of women’s careers

Name of a barrier	Description	Recommendations to tackle them
Early Educational Decisions	Students must choose their educational paths at an early age, often before they fully understand their career interests, and environment that doesn’t presents them energy as a field of successful career.	Introduce flexible pathways in secondary education allowing students to explore different fields before making a final decision. Present energy as a field for successful career in the future during the high school.
Gender Stereotypes in STEM	Perceptions during the educational periods that energy, engineering and technical fields are male dominated discourage women from pursuing them.	Increase visibility of female role models in STEM related handbooks and materials, implement mentorship programs, and introduce inclusive career guidance.
Family and Societal Expectations	Parents and society often push girls away from technical fields, favoring more traditional career choices. This might also relate to nuclear energy, which is seen as dangerous for woman that have parenting plans.	Awareness campaigns targeting parents and teachers to encourage them to support woman to peruse carriers in energy related fields.
Lack of Career Guidance in Schools	Many students, especially women, are not exposed to energy and technical fields due to insufficient career counseling.	Improve career counseling in schools, provide industry visits, and create educational materials showcasing career opportunities.

Organizational Climate at Universities	Gender biases, microaggressions, and outdated infrastructure (e.g., lack of female restrooms in technical buildings) discourage women.	Introduce gender sensitivity training, ensure equal infrastructure, and establish clear reporting mechanisms for discrimination.
Workplace Discrimination	Employers sometimes hesitate to hire women in energy and engineering due to concerns about maternity leave and career breaks.	Implement policies that promote gender equality in hiring and career advancement, including flexible work arrangements.
Lack of relevant gender roles in the sectors	Weak visibility of successful women working in the different sectors related to the energy field	Mentoring, more visibility of female professionals in the public sphere,
Lack of Representation in Study Materials	Educational materials often reinforce male-dominated images in STEM, which may discourage women from entering these fields.	Ensure gender-balanced representation in textbooks and promote female achievements in STEM fields.
Rigid Hiring Practices in Energy Sector	Traditional energy sectors (nuclear, fossil fuels) have historically and culturally determined rigid hiring structures that limit opportunities for women.	Encourage flexible hiring policies and create targeted recruitment campaigns for women in the energy sector.
Limited Awareness of Energy Careers	Many students are unaware of the opportunities in the energy sector, particularly in emerging fields like renewables.	Increase outreach through school visits, social media campaigns, and partnerships with universities.

Name of the supportive factor	Description
Early Exposure to Energy Topics	Introducing girls to energy-related subjects from an early age through school curricula, extracurricular activities, and media can foster interest in the field. Crucial thing is to promote also energy sector as a field for successful career.
Role Models and Mentorship Programs	The presence of successful women in energy careers serves as an inspiration and motivation for young women considering entering the sector.
Inclusive Career Counseling	Providing career guidance that highlights diverse opportunities in the energy sector and challenges gender stereotypes (i.e. presenting only male – inventors) encourages more women to join the field.
University/ High-School and Industry Collaboration	Partnerships between universities/ high schools and energy companies offer practical experiences, internships, and networking opportunities that support career development.
Gender-Balanced Study Programs	Creating an inclusive environment in energy-related education, including a balanced gender representation among faculty and students, supports women's participation.
Flexible Work Conditions in the Energy Sector	Offering flexible working hours, remote work options, and family-friendly policies makes energy careers more accessible for women.
Recognition of Women's Contributions	Highlighting achievements of women in the energy sector through awards, media coverage, and academic recognition increases their visibility and encourages new talent.

Increased Representation in Study Materials	Ensuring that textbooks and educational content include diverse examples of female professionals in energy encourages young women to consider these careers.
Supportive Organizational Culture	Universities and workplaces that promote gender equity, address discrimination, and provide mentorship foster an inclusive environment for women in energy.
Availability of Scholarships and Grants	Financial support programs aimed at women in STEM and energy-related fields reduce economic barriers to entry and encourage more women to pursue these careers.

E. Cross cutting recommendations

To increase women's participation in the energy sector across both STEM and SSH), it is essential to integrate and promote interdisciplinary career pathways at all stages of education and create inclusive educational environments that promote energy as a prospective job sector both for young woman and man. STEM students should be encouraged to view energy as a multidimensional sector that requires not only technical expertise but also policy analysis, social impact assessments, and ethical considerations. On the other hand, SSH students should have access to technical knowledge and practical applications of energy policies through interdisciplinary courses and hands-on experiences, such as energy transition case studies, sustainable development projects, and policy-making simulations. Energy should be taught as a less abstract – systemic endeavour but as a crucial thing for everyday life and practices.

Mentorship programs and industry-academic collaborations should be strengthened to provide female students with exposure to real-world career opportunities in the energy sector. Universities and high schools should establish formal mentorship initiatives where experienced professionals—both men and women—guide students through career development, research opportunities, and industry networking. Additionally, internships and apprenticeships in energy companies, regulatory agencies, and research institutions should be made more accessible to women from both SSH and STEM backgrounds. Providing financial support for these opportunities, especially for students from underrepresented groups, will help bridge gender gaps in energy careers.

Another crucial recommendation is to address gender biases and structural barriers in education and the workplace. Universities and all educational institutions should actively promote an inclusive culture by ensuring gender-sensitive curricula, diverse representation in teaching staff, and the elimination of stereotypes in course materials. In STEM fields, where women are often underrepresented, proactive strategies—such as outreach campaigns and scholarships targeted at female students—should be employed to increase their participation. SSH disciplines should emphasize the crucial role women can play in energy governance, policymaking, and social innovation, fostering confidence in pursuing leadership roles in the sector.

Finally, the visibility of women in the energy sector should be enhanced through storytelling, media representation, and leadership opportunities. Female professionals

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in both STEM and SSH should be invited to speak at conferences, participate in university events, and contribute to knowledge-sharing initiatives. The creation of platforms where students can exchange experiences, collaborate on interdisciplinary projects, and advocate for gender equity in energy transitions will also play a key role in fostering a more diverse and inclusive energy sector.

APPENDIX

Appendix 1 – The FGI with female STEM students

Number of participants	11 (3 researchers + 9 interviewees)
Target interviewee group	Female students from STEM
Place of the interview	Institute of Sociology, Jagiellonian University
Date of the interview	8.11.2024
Length of the FGI	2h18min
Number of interviewees	9
Female (number)	9
Male (number)	0
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	Not applicable
Comments about research tool	Not applicable

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FGI1-I01
Gender	F
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	MS
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Student
Scientific title (if applicable)	Not applicable
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Nuclear studies
Research interests	Nuclear energy

Other relevant information	N/a
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Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FGI1-I04
Gender	F
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Student
Scientific title (if applicable)	Not applicable
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Environmental protection
Research interests	RES
Other relevant information	N/a

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FGI1-I05
Gender	F
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Student
Scientific title (if applicable)	Not applicable
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	RES
Research interests	RES
Other relevant information	N/a

Appendix 2. The FGI 2 (mix-gender STEM)

Number of participants	11 (3 interviewers, 8 interviewees)
Target interviewee group (students from SSH, students from STEM, Academics...)	Students from STEM
Place of the interview	Institute of Sociology, Jagiellonian University
Date of the interview	9.11.2024
Length of the FGI	133 minutes
Number of interviewees	8
Female (number)	3
Male (number)	5
Other (number)	-
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	<p>Question on the role of the university/faculty to support women's self-confidence (whether questioning women students' abilities, challenging them more than men students is a factor that strengthens self-confidence or undermines it and shapes an imposter syndrome)</p> <p>Question on introducing gender dimension in their studies (students referred to textbooks from primary and secondary schools, or claimed that energy studies are neutral and there is no space for introducing gender dimension)</p>
Comments about research tool	

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics at the FGI 2 (mix-gender STEM)

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I01
Gender	woman
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics, 2 nd year of BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-

Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Mechanics and Mechanical Engineering
Research interests	-
Other relevant information	-
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I02
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics, 1 st year of BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Acoustic engineering
Research interests	-
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I03
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics, 1 st year of BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-

Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	automatyka przemysłowa i robotyka/ industrial automation and robotics
Research interests	-
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I04
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, 1 st year of BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Engineering and data analysis
Research interests	-
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I05
Gender	Woman
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics, 1 st year of BSc, 1 st year of BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Acoustic engineering

study programme for students)	
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I06
Gender	Woman
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, 2 nd year of MSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Ecological energy sources
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I07
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Energy and Fuels, MSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	nuclear power engineering

Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG2-I08
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Automatics, Computer Science, and Biomedical Engineering, 1 st year BSc
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	-
Scientific title (if applicable)	-
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Computer science and intelligent systems
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Appendix 3. The IDI7

Number of participants	2
Target interviewee group	Academics and Experts
Place of the interview	MS Teams
Date of the interview	23.01.25
Length of the FGI	70 minutes
Number of interviewees	1
Female (number)	1
Male (number)	0
Other (number)	-
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	A question on recommendations for enhancing studying environment at universities to better facilitate women's access to energy related study fields. The respondent suggested that she does not have enough data to answer this question
Comments about research tool	The FGI scenario was easy to adjust to the needs of an individual interview

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-IDI7
Gender	Woman
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Innovation centre at technical university
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Innovation broker at technical university
Scientific title (if applicable)	MSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Energy

Research interests	Research application
Other relevant information	

Appendix 4. The FGI 3 with male STEM students

Number of participants	12 (2 researchers and 10 interviewees)
Target interviewee group	Male students from STEM
Place of the interview	Kraków- Institute of Sociology
Date of the interview	12.11.2024
Length of the FGI	1:57:03
Number of interviewees	10
Female (number)	0
Male (number)	10
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	Not applicable
Comments about research tool	Not applicable

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_02
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Light Engineering
Country of work/study	Poland

Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	BSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	Not specified
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FG11-I01)	PL-FG3_04
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Mechatronics
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	MSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FG11-I01)	PL-FG3_03
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	IT
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	BSc

Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_05
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Automatics and Robotics
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	BSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_06
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	IT
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	BSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-

Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_07
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Environmental Engineering
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if aplicable)	BSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_08
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Acoustic Engineering
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if aplicable)	BSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_09
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute /IT study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	BSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	-
Research interests	
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG3_10
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute /Automatic and Metheorology study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	
Scientific title (if applicable)	MSc
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	
Research interests	
Other relevant information	

Appendix 5 – The FGI with Teachers

Number of participants	6 (2 researchers + 4 interviewees)
Target interviewee group	Female teachers from HE institutions
Place of the interview	Online- MS Teams
Date of the interview	16.12.2024
Length of the FGI	1h22min
Number of interviewees	4
Female (number)	4
Male (number)	0
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	Not applicable
Comments about research tool	Not applicable

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG4_1
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HE
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	Professor
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Sociology
Research interests	Energy
Other relevant information	

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG4_2
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HE
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	Professor
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Economy
Research interests	Energy
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG4_3
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HE
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	Professor
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Environmental sciences
Research interests	Energy & Environment
Other relevant information	
Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-FG4_4
Gender	Female
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HE

Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	Professor
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Sociology
Research interests	Energy & Health
Other relevant information	

Appendix 6 – The FGI with SSH students

Number of participants	10 (2 researchers + 8 interviewees)
Target interviewee group	Students from SSH
Place of the interview	Institute of Sociology, Jagiellonian University
Date of the interview	4.12.2024
Length of the FGI	124min
Number of interviewees	8
Female (number)	6
Male (number)	2
Other (number)	0
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	Not applicable
Comments about research tool	Not applicable

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics

Participant ID	PL-FGI5-I01
Gender	M
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Sociology, MA

Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Student
Scientific title (if applicable)	Not applicable
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Sociology
Research interests	Not applicable
Other relevant information	Not applicable

Participant ID	PL-FGI5-I02
Gender	F
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute / study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	HEI, Sociology, BA
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Student
Scientific title (if applicable)	Not applicable
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Sociology
Research interests	Not applicable
Other relevant information	Not applicable

Appendix 7. The IDI

Number of participants	2
Target interviewee group	Academics and Experts
Place of the interview	MS Teams
Date of the interview	
Length of the FGI	60 min
Number of interviewees	1

Female (number)	0
Male (number)	1
Other (number)	-
Questions that were difficult for the respondent	Not applicable
Comments about research tool	Not applicable

Section II. Each respondent's characteristics

Participant ID (code of country_number of participant e.g. PL-FGI1-I01)	PL-IDI6-I01
Gender	Man
Place of work/ study (HEI, department/institute/ study level (BSc, MSc, BA, MA, etc.for students)	Technical University, Nuclear Energy Studies
Country of work/study	Poland
Position at work (if applicable)	Associate Professor
Scientific title (if applicable)	PhD
Research field (for faculty members/ study programme for students)	Nuclear Energy
Research interests	Nuclear Energy
Other relevant information	Not applicable

6.1.4. United Kingdom

UK Report on Focus Groups (Task 3.2)

Authors: Yara Evans and Rocio Diaz-Chavez - Institution: Imperial, UK

Introduction

This document reports on the activities undertaken by Imperial partners (UK) for gEneSys T3.2: *Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems.*

The task required carrying out a number of Focus Groups with postgraduate students and lecturers at UK universities. The aim was to explore how Higher Education Institutions support women pursuing an education and a career in energy sector, across different stages, from recruitment, teaching methods and programmes, and outside-class activities, through to mentoring programmes. The activity also aimed at identifying interventions that can help enhance and develop careers pathways in the energy sector.

The Focus Group aimed at helping address the following research questions:

- What factors impact on women's interest in the energy transition, in particular in relation to their educational and career progression?
- What factors hinder and facilitate the inclusion of women in renewable and fossil fuel energy sectors?
- What practices and interventions are most promising/effective in increasing the proportion of women in energy system, both in Higher Education Institutions and in the labour market?
- What gender-based analysis is integrated Higher Education teaching and research to increase the proportion of women in studies related to energy sector, to obtain their active participation whilst studying, and to ensure retention of women students in careers in the energy sector?
- How may a gender perspective be applied to Higher Education Institutions organizational culture?

Methodology

The team of two staff at Imperial (Dr Diaz-Chavez and Dr Evans) carried out all the tasks related to the Focus Group activity. This required, first of all, obtaining ethics clearance from Imperial, a process that took an inordinate amount of time due to internal bureaucracy, which delayed the start of proceedings. Once ethics clearance was obtained, recruitment began in earnest for recruiting for the Focus Groups.

The Focus Group activity entailed recruiting postgraduate students enrolled at current Master's courses in the UK (2024 intake) as well as current lecturers and academic experts based at UK universities. The Imperial team carried out two student Focus Groups, and one Focus Group with

academics. This is a deviation from the original number of Focus Groups required by Task3.2 organisers, which required a total of five Focus Groups: four with students, and one with academics. The shortfall was due to limited resources at Imperial (e.g. largely time allocation to the two staff within the gEneSys project, the limited number of staff to carry out the task, there being only two staff at Imperial, and financial resources to help enlist support, such as, for instance, offering incentives for extra staff or students to help take down detailed notes from each participant at the Focus Group). These limitations were discussed with the task leaders and the project coordinator at an online meeting, with final agreement by the project coordinator.

For the student Focus Groups, recruitment focused on students enrolled at Master's courses run at Imperial where energy figures either as central or complementary topic in Master's course programmes, namely: *Sustainable Energy Futures*; *Environmental Technology*; *Future Power Networks*; *Geotechnical Engineering with Offshore Renewables*; *Green Chemistry, Energy and the Environment*. Focusing on student intake at Imperial was meant to enhance the chances of securing participation within the time available for this task. Course directors at Imperial helped decide on the most appropriate dates/times for student availability, circulating the recruitment call to their students. Nevertheless, interest was always very low, and it took a few more attempts to recruit a minimum number of students to run the Focus Group.

The first student Focus Group was carried out on the 18th of November 2024, with five students (three women, two men) from a STEM background who were enrolled on *MSc Sustainable Energy Futures (SEF)*, run by the Mechanical Engineering Department (code FGA). The second student Focus Group was carried out on the 20th of November 2024, with six students (four women and two men) from an interdisciplinary background (Including Social Sciences) who were enrolled on *MSc Environmental Technology (ET)*, offered by the Centre for Environmental Policy at the Faculty of Natural Sciences (code FGB). Specific details about each focus group composition and students research interests are shown below in Table 1.

Table 1: Participants Interests - Imperial MSc Students	
FGA: MSc Sustainable Energy Futures	FGB: MSc Environmental Technology
Student 1 (FGAS1M): economics and policy, renewable natural gas, electricity and energy market, gas market	Student 1 (FGBS1W): water and energy
Student 2 (FGAS2W): renewables, engineering consulting	Student 2 (FGBSW2): energy and food systems
Student 3 (FGAS3W): hydrogen seasonal storage; CCUS	Student 3 (FGBS3M): energy poverty
Student 4 (FGAS4W): energy systems sustainability	Student4 (FGBS4M): environmental assessment and management
Student 5 (FGAS5M): renewable energy, energy policy	Student 5 (FGBS5W): sustainability
	Student 6 (FGBS6W): energy, climate, finance
Source: Focus Groups (18th and 20th November 2024)	
Key: M=Man; W=woman	

The gEneSys partners at Imperial facilitated the two Focus Group sessions, which were held face-to-face in rooms at Imperial's premises in central London and lasted around 1:30 hours. The two partners took summary notes of activities (it was not possible for them to take detailed notes since they were both facilitating the activity so this would have required extra staff). The student themselves wrote most of their contributions on 'post-it' notes which they affixed to flip chart sheet for each of the discussions or wrote them directly onto these sheets. The meetings were also audio-recorded using the Teams platform, from which a transcript was obtained.

The steps followed in each of the Focus Groups were broadly the same. At the start, the facilitators introduced gEneSys project, asked students to introduce themselves, and then explained and led each of the activities set out in the guidance prepared by the task leaders. The dynamics of the activity followed a general pattern for a focus group, that is, the group were asked specific questions which participants could answer individually in turn, and were given specific tasks (e.g. identifying issues relating to a specific topic) that they would then carry out as a whole group, or also, in subgroups, reporting to the whole group at the end of the task.

For FGA, the first main activity was an exploration of students educational choices and careers aspirations, oriented by Storytelling as the projective technique, where students considered the most important factors weighing in the decision of an imaginary young woman choosing a Master's programme where energy is a main or major component (e.g. the MSc Energy Futures). This was followed by the exercise centres on identifying factors bearing on a woman's career progression, which used the Visual Mapping projective technique, which involved students working on a flipchart sheet to trace the barriers and enablers on women's career progression in the energy sector from education through to employment. In the next activity the students examined the integration of gender in energy education, both in their own MSc, department and university, as well as more generally in education, and in the energy labour market too. In the final segment of the session, students put forward recommendations for addressing the barriers they had identified to women's involvement in education and careers on energy-related issues.

For FGB, the first main activity was also an exploration of students educational choices and careers aspirations, entailing discussion on a range of issues, from their decisions to elect energy as a topic of study, given their background in non-energy undergraduate degree disciplines, through to whether their courses integrated a gender perspective, and to how this may contribute to the energy transition. In the next activity, students identified the barriers and enablers in women's education and career progression in energy, tracing them in a flipchart sheet. The final main activity entailed students making recommendations for adapting the Master's course programme to make it more relevant to the energy sector and more relevant to young women/women. No project technique was used in FGB, as the proposed contrasting narratives did not seem the most effective way to engage students into discussing the topics. The Focus Groups data was analysed thematically, following the general order of themes discussed during the activities conducted in each session, as prompted by the set of guiding questions set up by T3.2 leaders.

With agreement from the task leaders, the focus group with academics was to be carried out online, again, due to time and resources constraint at Imperial. Recruitment for participation in the

lecturers focus group was made through direct e-mail invitation by the Imperial researchers using their professional networks in the UK, which included professionals within and outside Imperial. The selection criteria was lecturers based at UK universities whose teaching and research include topics on energy. Recruitment was difficult, with many turning the invitation down due to prior engagements, with only a few committing initially but dropping out at the last minute. As a result, the focus group had to be rescheduled twice and was eventually held online on the 16th of January 2025. Key details about participants are shown in Table 2. The meeting was video-recorded, and a transcript obtained to enable extracting the contributions by participants. The audio and video recordings from all focus groups were destroyed and the transcripts anonymised to comply with the research ethical clearance requirements.

Table 2: UK Academics Profile				
Participant	Position and University	Faculty/School	Modules taught	Research Interests
FGLR1M	Assistant Professor Coventry University	Centre for Agroecology, Water and Resilience	Principles and Practice of Low-carbon building; RE engineering	enabling the use/consumption of energy, moving to use of more renewables and low carbon materials
FGLR2W	Lecturer University College London	Energy Institute	Introduction to smart energy data and statistics; Smart Energy Solutions in the Built Environment	the operational performance of buildings; implementation of data-driven options and smart solutions in the built environment
FGLR3M	Professor University of Leeds	Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences and Faculty (School of Chemical and Process Engineering of Environment) and Sustainability Research Institute (School of Earth and Environment)	Strategic Energy Issues; three modules on techno-economic issues	industrial decarbonisation (modelling activities and governance issues)
FGLR4M	Emeritus Professor University of Surrey and Consultant Loughborough University		Transitions to low carbon energy systems Introduction to electricity systems	Modern energy cooking services (clean cooking); carbon credits

	(Modern Energy Cooking Services)			
FGLR5W	Research Fellow (with teaching duties) Imperial College	Chemical Engineering Department	Energy decarbonisation (RE, nuclear energy)	Development of models used for energy systems transition (e.g. industrial decarbonisation; RE and fossil fuels)
Source: Focus Groups (16th January 2025)				
Key: M=Man; W=woman				

Results of FGA (MSc Sustainable Energy Futures- SEF)

Educational choices and career pathways

The students who took part on FGA were from diverse nationalities, reflecting the reputation of the university for attracting overseas students (Indonesia, Germany, Mexico). Some had already been working in the energy sector in their home countries had purposefully come to the UK to study the MSc, whilst others had been working in the UK, and some had just finished their undergraduate degree, with no work experience. All participants had signed up for the 2024 MSc Sustainable Energy Futures (SEF), a taught course. Some of the modules in programme were named during the activity (e.g. on leadership). Students mostly had an educational background in Engineering. Table 3 shows their background and reasons for choosing an energy pathway to study.

Table 3 FGA Participants Reasons for Choosing an MSc in Energy

'I want to learn actually about the renewable natural gas that will be injected into the pipeline, natural gas. And I read into the website that there is Green Gas Certification system in the UK ... and I am interested' (FGAS1M)
'My background in general Engineering allowed me to explore [pathways] renewable energy aligned the closest as it addresses global warming ... one of the largest crisis ... and Engineers want solutions' (FGAS2W)
'I want to deepen my understanding in sustainable energy ... my background in Chemical Engineering gave me a broad view of the energy challenge and sparked my interest ... and seeing news on climate change and pollution' (FGAS3W)
'For me it was more my background, so I did general Engineering, which was like, it was a bit different to the other Engineering disciplines in a way that it let me explore a lot of areas, and as Engineers, you tend to be looking more for solutions compared to business ... I've particularly enjoyed modules like Power Systems. And we did do a module on energy as a whole. So, I realised that my interests weren't [only] renewable energy because it had this wider purpose ... solving one of the largest crisis we are facing right now ... [so] I wanted to diversify my energy knowledge with policy and engineering' (FGAS4W)
'I have an Engineering background, and I realised that there are so many aspects, while deciding: the policy, the social aspect, the environmental aspect, the legal aspect ... this program will teach all ... the multidisciplinary aspect ...' (FGAS5M)

As can be seen in Table 3, students identified a range of reasons for pursuing an MSc in energy related-fields, based on their own experiences and aspirations, which often included an interest in interdisciplinarity or multidisciplinary. These included: an interest in helping address global

warming and the climate crisis, diversifying their knowledge, and extending their knowledge on sustainability. Students further discussed the factors that influenced their own decision to study for an MSc on energy at Imperial, and specifically the SEF, which is driven by a focus on sustainability and derived from their own motives for studying an MSc degree more generally. These factors are noted in Table 4. Again, they highlight an interest in developing skills to help solve the climate crisis, including a broader and multidisciplinary understanding of sustainability.

Table 4: FGA Participants Reasons for Studying the MSc SEF

'I am Interested in energy development ... want to learn broader aspects of sustainability, not only technical [such as] design policy and planning to achieve Net Zero [with a focus on] energy power and renewable energy'(FGAS1M)

'I chose the masters because I wanted to have an active role in solving the challenge of climate change and energy, a challenge particularly in sustaining the energy transition. And I thought this, the MSc in SEF was a programme that gave an analytical, a holistic view ... on the challenge, on the problem and on the opportunities, we have to address the challenge'(FGAS4W)

'[to develop] variety of knowledge, from Economics, Technical, Engineering (electric, mechanical, chemical) ... To leverage my knowledge particularly in new renewable energy. To enhance my career. To have an experience studying high level degree abroad. To learn from the UK... And because there is a Sustainable Gas Institute [at Imperial] (FGAS5M)

Importantly, gender as a factor in helping choose the MSc on SEF was noted by two students:

'I'm getting to do this is because of my passion for energy and sustainability. I want to learn more about policy aspects and become a generalist towards the energy transitions. And then I want to prove that a woman can also contribute' (FGAS2W)

'A course that explores a take on leadership in energy sectors, it is an immense issue for women, and SEF offered this ... [alongside] reputation of energy degree to accelerate admission into energy sector which traditionally male-dominated ... So, we have quite an element on leadership in our course. And I think it's really important because women don't tend to be in the leadership roles in the energy sector (FGAS3w)

As can be seen, these quotes highlight perceptions about gender in energy as field of education and as a career. Whilst they saw the field as being male-dominated, they thought women also have an important role to play but are lacking opportunities that enable their progression into leadership roles.

Students also considered the sources of inspiration and encouragement for taking on the energy pathway in education and specifically the MSc in SEF. These included the reputation of the MSc and of the university and recommendations by women who had taken the course. Yet, again, though, some women students noted the male domination of the field which, at the same time, drove them to seek to challenge gender preconceptions and misconceptions, as illustrated in the following quotes:

'[women are] a minority. STEM is mostly dominated by men ... [MSc an opportunity to] engage women to have a voice towards what they want ... and prove the stereotype [about] women wrong' (FGAS2W)

‘Other peers who chose to pursue a similar masters [were the inspiration] ... the reputation of the energy degree ... [but it] is a very Engineering field. So, it's very male dominated. So, the better the reputation of the degree, like the one at Imperial, the more likely you are to get into an energy sector that's filled with men ... then you [women] become the minority’ (FGAS3W)

‘[The] reputation of the energy degree, that's quite important ... a senior colleague from Engineering went on this course and recommended. She had just finished this course when I started it ... during my undergraduate [studies] there weren't that many energy careers fairs, energy information, sessions, nothing like that because it was Engineering based (FGAS4W)

As the quotes suggest, the women students had signed up to the MSc on SFE following recommendation from female peers who provided an incentive that was lacking from other means of recruitment (e.g. career fairs), and who took it as a personal challenge to demonstrate that a woman may succeed in a male-dominated field.

In terms of educational expectations about gender in energy sectors, some students thought that men dominate the field of nuclear energy, whereas others thought that women were increasing their participation in wind energy. Whilst other types of energy were mentioned throughout the focus group activity (e.g. renewable energy, gas and electricity) none of these elicited any further discussion about a gender dimension in the MSc in terms of its role in preparing students for embarking or progressing on a career in energy.

Gender issues in career pathways

In terms of career pathways, students envisage women mostly taking up employment in private companies or public agencies [state-owned] in the energy sector, entailing diverse types of jobs, including research, but this was seen as being largely conditioned by a woman's own background and career aspirations, although combining motherhood with a career loomed large. As one student observed *‘I think it depends on her background and on whether the job opportunities will align with the type of life she would like to have. After the master she chooses because of the flexibility these type of jobs will give her ... for example, if she wants to have a family later, she would like to have a job that has more flexibility so that she can take care of the children’ (FGAS4W).*

One central activity in the focus group was for students to consider the factors that operate to hinder or enable young women to embark and progress in a career on the energy sector. Students identified a variety of barriers, some of which hinged explicitly on gender (that is, their condition of being a woman), which often intersected with other characteristics (e.g. age) and combined to hold women back.

Chief amongst the barriers was the perception that recruiters and company bosses made what were seen as making ‘stereotypical assumptions’ about women's careers aspirations that would operate to thwart progression. One key assumption was that all women want to have children at some stage in their careers, which would predispose employers against such women, giving rise to a stigma around women seeking to exercise their right to maternity leave, which could also lead to disparagement in the workplace by male colleagues. A further assumption was that women might

not be inclined to do certain types of jobs and employers, would therefore, not offer them. The quotes in Table 5 illustrate some students views on these issues.

Table 5: FGA Employers Barriers to Women’s Career Progression in Energy

‘I was at a workshop recently for women in Engineering and they were saying that ... recently, a lot of things that were happening is with projects. So, like, if you get an Engineering project, women start like reaching the age of 25 to 35, they start discriminating because they start thinking you're going to have a child soon. So that I found very shocking ... Even if you don't want a child, like, not every woman wants a child, but they start instructing you, putting you in little, mini projects [because] you're going to go and get pregnant’ ... So, you're stereotyping’ (FGAS2W)

‘A barrier would be like a recruiter assuming that you don’t want to do that job, not giving it you an option’ (FGAS3W)

‘Maternity leave, that was also in the leadership programme that I did recently. They said that women coming back from maternity leave felt bullied in the work environment. So, Engineering roles in energy, especially like, when they come back after however long they want to take, it's like, ‘Oh yeah, she just got her time off’ ... like a holiday, when it's not’ (FGAS4W)

Yet, students were aware that legislation in many countries guaranteed the right to maternity leave, and in some, paternity leave as well, with varying lengths of leave. But, as one student reasoned, the stigma from maternity leave could be addressed by *‘giving men paternity leave as well, so that they're less sour ... Maybe that's why men are always so angry about maternity leave’* (FGAS2W).

Some students also reasoned that the energy sector limits the scope of work for women, specifically, jobs that had to be undertaken on the field, making it less attractive for women, although others were actually keen to undertake them but thought they might not be offered the opportunity, whilst others thought that women had more opportunities in specific areas. The quotes in Table 6 illustrate the arguments.

Table 6: FGA Women’s Jobs in the Energy Sector

In my experience, in policy, the jobs for women are more dominant, the percentage of women working in policy is higher than the men ... around 60% or 70% of the workers are women (FGAS1M)

If you see that there is both office and site jobs where there is enough women, you'd want to go there (FGASW2)

‘Many women would not like to really work on the field, even in the energy sector ... Women don't want to be in this type of job ... unless it is on site and doesn't require a physical strength ... you know, the types, in the energy sector. So, they are trying to seek ... different types of jobs and functions within that ... the jobs that are women’s, maybe, or sectors, you know, that they can get more readily or easily than men? (FGAS3W)

‘If you think about types of jobs, I’d love to work in the wind [sector] and on site as well, like go on site. I just think you wouldn’t be expected, I don’t know. I just think people might not expect that. I want to go on site’ (FGASW4).

Regarding career progression, one view that emerged was that decision-making often took place outside the remit of formal work. For instance, one student related how she had learned at a recent event on leadership that men tended to be involved in informal male social networks operating outside working hours and the workplace that enabled decision-making favouring men’s progression. She reported that

‘[at the event] They said that (which made a lot of sense) as well doing like, job promotion and stuff, men tend to go out with the managers to have a drink or go out, like tennis, or anything that they will

not do with a female colleague. And that's where usually job progressions are decided, they're not decided in the workplace. They're usually decided in these hobbies, outside. Women, they're not usually invited to that scene, because that's usually like a bond time with your male colleague, and it's like opportunities you miss out on' (SFAS4W)

Nevertheless, views were mixed as to whether men or women were more likely to be in decision-making positions regarding progression and whether they would favour men or women. For instance, one of the male students thought that women would be chosen for being less of risk takers than man (FGAS1M), whereas the other male student reported that in a previous company he had worked in, the policy was to seek a gender balance when vacancies came up (FGAS5M). By contrast, a female student thought that women who were directors or managers would favour men for promotion (*'they promote them more easily than a woman'* FGAS2W). Another female student also thought that the progression path for women in general (i.e., not just in the energy sector) was thwarted by a recruiter bias towards physical appearance rather than by valuing skills:

'In my experience, sometimes people like, value women from their physical, you know, like it's important in judgement. They judge their career in their life, in the appearance. Some people, like, don't pay for ... intelligence. They're more about appearance. Just like for a type of joke, like for a secretary' (FGAS4W)

Students also considered the factors that might enable young women to embark and progress successfully in careers in the energy sector. They thought that placing women in leadership positions within companies was important (with some thinking that women working in recruitment could be very powerful) as was prioritising the participation of women in the design and enforcement of company policies in the energy sector.

Gender issues and practices at the university

Further issues that students examined during the focus group were the extent to which gender was incorporated into their MSc programme as well as how gender was addressed more widely in terms of academic and institutional practices at the university hosting their master's degree.

In terms of the gender balance of lecturers teaching their modules, student noted that of a total of 10 staff, six were men, and four were women. But a general perception was that gender was not incorporated in any meaningful way in the course programme. Regarding the integration of gender analysis into the taught modules, one student observed that *'they don't have any concern about that. They're gender blind. Let's say, they are general. Or gender neutral?'*(FGAS3W). But students noted that one female lecturer had mentioned gender in her lecture, even if only very briefly, and she was only a guest lecture in the programme, rather than the convener of the module. One student commented:

'Today there was a lecture about energy justice... And the lecturer kept talking about it, the first time I heard about gender ... So, this was one lecturer teaching on the economics and policy course. But it was she was only a guest lecture. And it wasn't just gender, gender was mentioned, but it was more energy justice as a whole' (FGAS2W).

Another student explained how the lecturer had discussed how energy companies in the UK, which are all privatised, never took into account the impacts on people of putting up energy prices in winter, and how this needed to change, citing the example of a single mother, the impacts on her. In the student's words, the lecturer had gone on to argue that:

'there should be some sort of like public element to it because a lot of communities, especially women in underdeveloped regions of the UK, are affected by these prices changing' (FGAS3).

No student reported seeing any guidance targeted specifically at women students during the recruitment process for the MSc on SEF. As seen previously, students were aware of the likelihood of there being gender imbalances in the take up of such courses which could impact the dynamics of work in the classroom, replicating earlier experiences in their university education. The following quotes illustrate this perception:

'In my undergraduate [degree], in group projects, in the beginning, men tend to make stereotypical assumptions [about women]. Like, 'Maybe I'm more qualified in that technical Engineering assignment than that person', and they'd be telling me 'Here's your book. And here's your pen'... At the beginning of this course someone said [to me] 'You're going to take the notes'. Yeah. I mean, it's like, my whole seven years [for this] ... menial task is important too ... But, you know, secretary? Difficult! They want a woman to be a secretary (FGAS3W).

'It did cross my mind a few times because I'd just come fresh from my undergraduate straight here. So, I did think it's probably going to be male dominated, and I wasn't particularly happy about it. In my undergraduate [degree], we did a lot of teamwork. It can get interesting, the dynamics can get a bit interesting if you know the team you're in, but not if there is more men than women ... I did think of that!' (FGAS5W)

Similarly, no students reported receiving any information on careers on energy yet, although this might yet happen at a later stage in the course. But one female student related that she had accessed information about jobs in the university's webpage after actively searching on her own. She found out about an event being hosted for women interested in careers on energy which she attend. She reported that *'the women working there said that the gender statistics are horrible'* and thought that promoting such events does not seriously help address gender disparities in the sector (*'they are just covering it up with these events'*, FGAS4W).

Students considered whether and which measures could be taken to incorporate gender into master courses on energy such as the MSc SEF to make it more appealing to women. Some thought there was scope for incorporating gender in the research project module, whilst others thought it could be integrated into modules focusing on energy system analysis, low carbon technologies, economics, policy and regulations, workplace safety (on site and in the field) and leadership. Students also thought more women lecturers should convene such modules. Yet, one female student noted how proposing a module on gender and energy might not be as attractive to students than one without an explicit reference to gender. She reasoned:

'I said a module on energy justice instead of just one guest lecture. I did not say gender just because ... there's a mental difficulty ... how is it going to appeal to them? So just because of that ... I would have

said gender and the energy transition, I would have had that as a module, but I think I am going to go with energy justice ... with a bit of, like, part of it on policy issues (FGAS3W).

Some students also proposed that women should be placed in leadership positions in academic activities to help attract more female students into the MSc programmes on energy, although one view was that this would probably require starting at a much earlier stage of education, whereas another view indicated that creating networks of alumni women would also be effective. The following quotes support these views:

'But also like for more women to be this type of person [a leader], I think it all starts back, like, primary school ... because women have to be interested in Mathematics and all those things to go first into engineering. So maybe it starts back there' (FGAS2W)

'If we go to careers fairs ... it tends to be younger, like graduates, recent graduates. So, I guess if the university, because they have a very wide network of ... students from 17 years ago, so some of them are in leadership positions. So maybe like ... women in energy leadership panel, specific women in these positions, [that] would give us a good network, and it would be appealing (FGAS3W).

Further measures students thought should be implemented to help attract more women students into MSc programmes on energy are:

- Promote careers events for women in energy and encourage women to lead such events
- Promote recruitment events targeting women where women leaders speak
- Giving women scholarships
- Building women's networks and support communities

Recommendations

Students suggested a variety of actions that should be taken by policy makers and employers to help raise women's participation in energy jobs and careers. These are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: FGA Improving Women's Participation and Progression in the Energy Sector
Women to have the same opportunities as men (gender equality); ensure transparency in the designation of hours and tasks; ensure same pay for the same roles independent of gender and divulge pay scales; divulge pay for all positions (transparency)
Increase awareness of gender inequality and address it
Design and enforce Equality, Diversity and Inclusion policy (workplace ethics)
Company policy to have a minimum percentage of women in top management; ensure promotion of this policy (quotas)
National voluntary quotas for women
Clear regulations on maternity leave
National policy to enforce gender equality at local level
Company policies and regulations to spell out opportunities for career/path progression
Diverse recruitment panel (i.e., not just made up of men)
Women in leadership panels: place women in the spheres of power (company board of directors; managers)
Flexible hours
Attractive company statistics on gender (both office and site jobs)

Results of FGB (MSc in Environmental Technology - ET)

Educational choices and career pathways

As with students in FGA, most students who participated in FGB had come to the UK to do the masters' course (e.g. from China, Thailand, the Middle East). All participants were enrolled in the 2024 MSc on Environmental Technology (ET), also a taught course. They had pursued undergraduate degrees in various interdisciplinary fields (e.g. *International Business Management, Geography, Economics and Finance, Economics and Business*) and some had already had some work experience (UK government; business journalism; teaching). Students mentioned the module options they were studying in the MSc ET, which included: *Energy Policy, Water Management, Environmental Economics and Policy, Environmental Assessment and Management and Integrated Management, Business and e-Learning*. Table 8 shows their reasons shaping their decision to pursue the MSc ET.

Table 8: FGB Reasons for Choosing the MSc ET

'We cannot function as a modern society without energy. So, solving the energy crisis element, which is at the core of things, can have a positive chain reaction to everything else. I also think it's crucial in supporting and also being supported by sustainability initiatives. So, it kind of comes full circle where energy both fuels and gives a way for sustainable development to occur, but then also that contributes to renewable energy and extraction of certain types of energy' (FGBS1W)

'My reason is not very related to energy, I think. I got interested in this topic just mainly because one thing that I guide my students to participate in the business competition and all of the topics are about sustainability. They all get deep or dive deep into the topics, into the food system and other areas. So, I got really interested in this topic because I think all we teach or learn in the class actually is about marketing and production and profit and how to maximize shareholders' interest. But the area should be shaped from the profit and shareholders to the well-being of the humanity of the population. But I'm lacking a lot of scientific knowledge ... about sustainability. So, I think I should learn first and then see what I can help to do' (FGBS2W)

'My number one reason was that technically all of our problems or the most pressing challenges of the world can all be solved by addressing one issue, which is the energy crisis. How do we get affordable, clean and cheap energy to all? I think it's the most important question we have to answer, because if you solve the energy problem, solve the water problem, solve the hunger problem, you can solve the poverty problem. You can solve any other problem as long as you have abundant, clean and affordable energy' (FGBS3M)

'Thailand is on its way to decarbonise the economy. Like, one of our most polluting is manufacturing and agricultural industry, which use a lot of energy, of course. So, to be able to achieve that, we need more green talent. I want to help the country. But apart from just the decarbonisation process itself, I think it needs a lot of assessment to make it valuable, someone to validate those processes. So, I think this area is kind of interesting to be in' (FGBS4M)

'I didn't choose the energy option. So, I'm not that interested in energy question, but after hearing everybody ... I think that's an important issue. But I'm more interested in, for example, on things related to human well-being. And also ... biodiversity. Because I think that's interesting, and I also want to maybe do something for the society and the world' (FGBS5W)

'It's such a big topic in the media, seeing Russia's invasion of the Ukraine, like, it's dominating the media and politics. What it's been drawn to my attention how much energy the world actually has access to. So, for example, in Venezuela, they still have blackouts, in South Africa. And I would love to, you know, change that. And I'm seeking a career in international development' (FGBS6W)

As the quotations show, energy was a relatively important consideration in most students' decision to pursue the MSc ET. This was because of concern with issues around sustainability and an interest in playing a part in helping address impacts associated with energy access and use and their impacts. Students further considered the importance and implications of having an energy component in their MSc programme, with some noting that Economics is fundamental for modelling energy scenarios, and that energy is also essential for resolving other environmental

crises (e.g., the water crisis by powering desalination plants sustainably through use of ‘green hydrogen’). Table 9 illustrate the arguments.

Table 9: FGB Participants Views on the Incorporation of Energy into the MSc ET

When you solve the energy problem, you solve other problems (FGBS2W)

‘If you are looking at business ... I think a lot of people ... believe that engineering and finance are the most important decisions. However, I do think that diplomacy and more of an international relations approach is even more important, because at the end of the day, a lot of states have energy needs, and they have national interests, and they have national security interests. So, they always play games when it comes to energy. So, if we have more diplomacy, more willingness to work together, it makes it a bit easier to solve the energy crisis’ (FGBS3M)

‘My option is business, and energy is fundamental to business’ (FGBS5W)

As in FGA, students in FGBA were asked to think through the factors that constrain and enable young women’s education that incorporates energy and then career advancement in the energy sector. Some students noted that *lack of money* was a limiting factor in getting an education or getting specific training. Yet some students thought that this was not as relevant as focusing on career progression. For instance, one student asserted that *‘I think we have to consider the context here, that women have got a good education already’* (FGBS5W), whilst another wondered *‘Isn’t this highly specific to where she lives, what family she comes from, and what her education is?’* (FGBS1W). But lack of economic resources was also seen as a barrier to progression, for, as one student reasoned *‘I guess some people stay in their job because they need that money [wages] immediately rather than pursuing their goal passionately that is going to bring a big transformation’* (FGBS6W).

The barriers students identified to career progression largely turned on pressures and impacts of socio-cultural norms and expectations about marriage, family planning and motherhood, and childcare on women’s rights, including reproductive rights. Students spoke of constrains by cultural gender norms (e.g. *‘women stay at home and men go out to work’*), family pressure (*‘marry young and start your career later’*), and partner’s expectations (*‘your partner may not agree that you will go out to work’*). The quotes shown in Table 10 further illustrate these issues.

Table 10: FGB Participants’ Views on Gender Barriers to Progression in Careers in Energy

‘A parent who has a child and decides to leave the job and decides to leave the job ... It is just that parents don’t want that ... but they will need to leave their job for some time to take care of their children ... timeout for childcare’ (FGBS2W)

‘It’s an example from my friend. She’s performed very well in Chemistry. She can get to go to both the Faculty of Chemistry and the Faculty of Chemical Engineering. At the last minute she decided to go to the Science Faculty. Because I think her family might be worried about her, it is hard work, it is male-dominated’ (FGBS4M)

‘There have been so many reports all-around of women who take time off to have children ... and once they come back to the office, they might never catch up. Especially in quickly changing industry, like computer science, and frankly, energy. If women lose about two years’ experience, it’s going to be a big job to compete ... Some companies are even worried about ... women who haven’t got married [yet]. For example, if she’s single, then in the foreseeable future, she might get married and have a child. If she just got married, then the recruiters might worry about her getting pregnant’ (FGBS5W)

Other types of barriers were also identified relating to specific types of work in the energy sector. Explanations for these are shown in Table 11.

Table 11: FGB Barriers to Women’s Progression in Careers in Energy

'Traditional oil and gas energy industries are typically not very woman-friendly. It's like very labour, heavy job. It's quite dirty. It's quite disgusting. It's male-dominated. It's not something a woman would be particularly interested in'(FGBSa3M)

'I think if it's related to some remote area, let's say, like oil rig in the sea or some solar farm in some rural area, I think safety is the main concern here... this is why you tend to have men out there instead of women. I think if we have a well secured facility, that wouldn't be a problem' (FGBS4M)

'Is the energy sector a good place for women to work in? I don't know about the energy sector, but I think basically every sector a woman can do. Because if you do not let others, like the media, like culture, like everything else, deceive you, and try to change your mind, then I think it's not a gender issue. It's what you believed' (FGBS5W)

In a further task in the focus group activity, students identified factors they thought may enable women to progress in careers in the energy sector. These ranged from national government policy interventions, through measures and initiative adopted by businesses, to socio-cultural norms and personal drive, as shown in Table 12.

Table 12: FGB Enablers of Women's Progression in Careers in Energy

Business initiatives (funds)

Business laws (for equality/gender balance, e.g. quotas)

Company policy for pregnant women: maternity leave

Culture

Employment transparency

Equality, Diversity, Inclusion (EDI)

Government policy to incentivise women's progression

Religion

Personal Motivation

Support from husband and family

Working from home

The quotes in Table 13 illustrate some of the students' thinking on factors that enable women to progress in the energy sector.

Table13: FGB Measures to Help Women Progress in Careers in Energy

'I don't know for sure. I don't study laws. But from what I know, business have to pay attention to the balance of gender ... hand have to pay attention to diversity and equality, and I think because some part is because of the law, some part because of social pressure' (FGBS2W)

'If you don't really have a strong faith in your religion or you don't really adhere to your religion, it's a bit easier to just leave [behind] those perceived gender norms. It's a bit easier to just be a bit more free, liberal'(FGBS3M)

'More and more, at least I see from the financial sector they have specific... Some funds are created to incentivise women in STEM or some business that are led by women. I think it is good for the company's PR' (FGBS4M)

Some friends of mine ... some men ... they have children, they can work from home, they can take care of their children at the same time. They can work. It's very practical'(FGBS5W)

'If you think you are a disadvantaged woman and you ... behave like you are a disadvantaged woman, then you shouldn't do it. I think it's some psychology thing. If you are not confident you can do it well, and you might try, you will fail. But if you are confident ... you have more possibilities to get a job' (FGBS5W)

'I was thinking about myself, that my family is supporting me. Maybe, like, going one generation back, I wouldn't have been encouraged to travel for work' (FGBS6W)

Students undertook a final task related world of work (in the energy sector or other sectors related to their own degree fields), putting forward measures for improving women’s progression. Again, these combine measures that should be undertaken by businesses (company level) with more diffuse initiatives led by wider society. Such measures are listed in Table 14 and illustrated in Table 15 by students’ rationale for their recommendations.

Table14: FGB Recommendations for Improving Women’s Progression in the Energy Sector
Strong Role Models to Empower Women; encouragement
Digitalisation, robotics, automation
Sustainable and ethical microloans
Recruitment/Employment transparency
Work Safety
Gender awareness in the workplace
Schemes specifically for women to accelerate career
Social trends (social media)
Generous company policy (e.g. letting women work from home when their children are very young)

Table 15: FGB Participants’ Recommendations for Improving Women’s Progression
‘Obviously, microloans is super tested, but especially in the ... Global South, I think microloans, although they’re contested, they’ve helped out a lot of women to be more independent. So, if we push that a bit further, as long as it’s sustainable and ethical, we can definitely help out more women’ (FGBS1W)
‘In the employment, it can be more transparent. So, we can know how many women they hire. Yeah. Or about the process that they hire people ... the recruitment process, how they select people for their jobs. So, we can see if they hire people according to their availability and everything else’ (FGBS2W)
‘Focusing on just the energy industry, I think it makes it a bit more accessible if we have certain help when it comes to more labour-intensive jobs. So of course, if you have automation/robotics, ... it’s a super silly example, but it can help you transfer solar panels more easily, or help you take out the boilerplate, the pipe, and the digitalisation is just about ... like working from home, having that freedom of location’ (FGBS3M)
‘Currently the major social media in China most women use is called the Red Book ... most of the content are related to women ... I think the majority of users are empowering women or encouraging women ... I see the things that need to take courage, but maybe back to 10 years women didn’t have. It might be related to ambition, related to job position, related to the relationship of their marriage, this kind of things. So, I think there is a trend in China that women are trying to fight for their own places in society. And rights, women’s rights. And you can find support in that’ (FGBS5W).
‘My second manager was a woman and as soon as I came up ... she said, ‘You’re doing so well, you can be a director’. I was like, I’ve never been raised to think that I can actually get to that level and do that, but just somebody telling you that you can do it and that they see your capability’ (FGBS6W)
‘Safe work environment, the physical environment as such. Because it is dangerous. But also, in terms of respect, isn’t it? How many places? How many platforms? Because it’s too many men there. Even in an office. You can have a different type of behaviour also in an office. That can be also applied, awareness about that’ (FGBS6W)

Gender issues and practices in the MSc programme and at the university

Students discussed whether and to what extent gender had been incorporated into their MSc programme or could be incorporated into it, and their perspectives on it. But some students also considered their experiences in earlier education. For instance, one student stated that gender had actually been addressed when studying for the undergraduate degree, noting how positive that was in terms of challenging gender preconceptions. As the student related

'We had a case study in Africa where women were actually pioneering being entrepreneurs because they had access to cleaner energy. So, they were able to set up street food stores, street food market stores, and some of the markets, and make a living for themselves or support the family ... So, having a more maybe feministic point of view when it comes to solving our challenges, maybe a gender-neutral point of view? ... It revealed some interesting things about how we run the world and how we might find solutions to it. So, gender can play a nice role or an important role if we decide to deconstruct our current thinking and find new solutions to our problem' (FGBS3M)

Students also noted that gender had been addressed in some of their lectures in the MSc ET programme in relation to other topics (e.g., Sustainable Development Goals, food, just transition). It had also been addressed in relation to climate change. As one student put it:

'We had a session during the meeting, and the topic was climate change and gender inequality. I think it's one of the PhD students' topics, so we use it as a practice for them ... I'm surprised that climate change has a relationship with gender ... but after some thinking, we realised that natural resources and natural disasters have different impact on men and women, and women are more vulnerable to those changes and to disasters, and that's the key takeaway I got from the session' (FGBS1W)

However, the general impression was that gender was not a main concern in the MSc programme, which was intimated in a comment by a student who noted that although gender inequality had been addressed in some lectures *'it's not the main topic to focus on' (FGBS4M)*. Indeed, one student thought that gender was addressed rather narrowly, whether alone or in relation to energy or inequality, observing that

'I feel like gender gets mentioned a lot, energy access, it always comes down to cooking. That's something that just hit me now ... when we have renewable energy sectors, and we talk about gender ... I guess there's still some biases there' (FGBS6W)

This perceived 'narrow' approach to gender and energy in the study programme was reiterated by a comment by another student, who noted that a lecture was scheduled for the next day where

'We're looking at cooking stoves and the African Development Bank and how women are really pioneering the technology of cooking stoves and reducing the need for biofuels'(FGBS1W).

Students also reflected on the gender balance of lecturers who were teaching their MSc module options, although there was some disagreement. Students did not spell out the number of lecturers that were men or women teaching their modules, although it was noted that, in the classroom *'they talk about the stats a lot ... about both the lecturers and the students' (FGBS4M)*. Regarding the gender balance of lecturers, one student thought that *'that they are quite balanced; of course there is more men, but it is not an overwhelming majority FGBS4M'* which was swiftly refuted by another student who stated *'I'd disagree! I think it is still quite male-dominated' (FGBSW6)*. In terms of the gender balance of students enrolled in the MSc ET, again, there was a perception that in the past it had been more 'women-dominated' and but that this year intake was more balanced (51% women 49% men), which may be related to interdisciplinary nature of the MSc itself, both because of the degree requirements for enrolment and the content of the module options itself.

Students were asked to reflect on how the MSc ET programme (which incorporates energy and sustainability to an extent) could be improved to make it more attractive for women study, but this did not elicit much in the way of explicit suggestions. As one student reflected

‘gender could be tied up into maybe ... our essential readings ... what we find a lot in class is that gender is, especially like female, is tied into well-being, education, which is kind of complex on its own... but things mentioned [here], like culture, I find ... interesting, but I am not sure how to include that’ (FGBS4M)

Nevertheless, it could be surmised from some of the previous discussions, that a better gender balance in terms of the teaching staff, and the incorporation of more gender-oriented content (e.g., women working in energy fields as role models, cases studies on women’s experiences of access to energy, discussions around the concept of gender, challenges women face working in different energy sectors) could prove effective.

Cross-Cutting Analysis of the Findings from FGA and FGB

The results from FGA and FGB activities reveal that gender is not a major consideration in the design, content and delivery of the MSc programmes represent in the focus groups. These clearly attracted women, who were a majority in each of the focus groups (3:2 in FGA; 4:2 in FGB), although the gender balance in the overall intake for the MSc ET (INTER) seemed more even than that for the overall intake for the MSc SEF (STEM). At any rate, the general perception was that the educational background required for admission into an MSc focused on energy comprised disciplines that are seen to be ‘male-dominated’. Thus, most students in FGA reported to have a background in Engineering, in contrast to students in FGB, whose first degrees were from a wider range of academic disciplines, yet energy was a relatively important consideration in most students’ decision for signing up to MSc degree, often linked to issues around sustainability. In FGA, recommendations from former women students were acted as an incentive for women to sign up for the MSc SEF, driven by a desire to prove that women can take on the challenge of developing skills to pursue a career the energy sector. No students in FGB reported having been influenced by women to pursue the degree. Career pathways in the energy sector were also seen to be dominated by men, although in FGA, for example, in a discussion of renewables, men were seen to dominate in nuclear energy, whereas women were seen as raising in wind energy and also having a strong presence in jobs on energy policy.

Regarding barriers to and enablers of women’s educational and professional development in careers in energy, the results reveal some similarities as well as differences between the focus groups. For instance, lack of economic resources was noted in FGB as preventing women from studying for a degree covering energy content as well as progressing into the energy labour market, a factor that was not identified in FGA. Table 16 shows the key factors identified by students.

Table 16: Factors Affecting Women’s Educational and Professional Development in Energy			
FGA (MSc SEF)		FGB (MSc ET)	
Barriers	Enablers	Barriers	Enablers
Maternity/maternity leave (stigma)	National voluntary gender quotas	Lack of money to study/train	Business initiatives (funding)

Recruiter bias (assumptions and stereotypes)	Stereotypes (women careful; not risk takers)	Marriage/Marrying young	Business laws (for equality/gender balance, e.g. quotas)
Type of job (tasks/location)	Women in leadership positions (boards; managers)	Socio-cultural norms/expectations	Company policy for pregnant women: maternity leave
Discrimination (men/women favouring men for progression)	Awareness of gender inequality; promotion of EDI	Pressure from family	Employment transparency (recruitment policy/data)
	National policy to enforce gender equality (local)		Government policy to incentivise women's progression
			Support from husband and family
			Personal Motivation
			Working from home

Students in the two focus groups identified a few common and intersecting barriers to women's professional advancement in the energy sector rooted in perceptions about a gender division of labour and women's roles that are also informed by stereotypes and socio-cultural norms and expectations. One first major barrier revolved around women's aspirations to develop a professional career (e.g. insertion in the labour market) that could be thwarted by taking maternity leave to have children and raise a family. Students spoke of employers assuming that all women want to have children, likely early in their careers; of employers' antipathy to maternity leave (a stigma); and of maternity leave holding women back (a loss of two years in progression).

A second barrier comprised socio-cultural norms and expectations that operate to put pressure on women to prioritise family life over pursuing a career, so that delaying entry into the labour market may also have a detrimental effect on career advancement.

A third barrier hinged on the specificities of jobs in the energy sector itself (i.e., male-dominated, physically demanding, located in remote locations, thereby raising issues about personal safety), which could prevent employers from offering jobs to women on the assumption that they would not suit or appeal to them, even though, in fact, some women might welcome the opportunity to take them.

One further barrier was identified in FGA only, comprising male networks of socialisation outside the workplace that excluded women and seemed to operate to inform decision-making about career progression that favoured the promotion of men over women (i.e., male-biased decision-making), although it was also thought that women in position of power could often themselves promote men over women (i.e., gender inequality in so far as women in similar career stages and with similar skills as men were passed up for promotion).

Common factors were also identified in both focus groups as enablers of women's progression in careers in the energy sector, entailing enforcement of measures inscribed in national policies, and actions and initiatives undertaken by companies. A common enabler was the local (i.e., business

level) enforcement of national voluntary quotas to help obtain gender equality alongside other government policy to incentivise women’s progression (i.e., addressing gender inequality through implementation of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion measures).

However, the two focus groups also identified distinct enabling factors. Thus, in FGA, ‘positive’ stereotyping was seen to help advance women (i.e., women seen as generally more careful or guarded in terms of decision-makers; ‘no risk-taker’), as well encouraging women to move into leadership positions (director’s board; management) and thus act as role models for other women (i.e., those in early/lower career stages). In FGB, enablers comprised business initiatives (including funded training), business enforcement of women’s legal rights (e.g., maternity leave), business transparency in employment practices (recruitment and progression policy) and data (statistics on employment according to gender) and flexible practices (e.g., allowing working from home). Additional enabling factors comprise supportive actions by family and partners, as well as own initiative (personal drive).

In terms of incorporating a gender perspective into the MSc programme and into the teaching of the MSc programme, students in FGA had more to say than students in FGB. In FGA, students noted a gender balance in terms of the number of lecturers teaching the MSc options, although women were usually guest lecturers, and so students suggested that women should themselves convene and lead modules containing energy topics. Overall, students thought that gender was not incorporated in any meaningful way in the MSc programme, with modules being largely ‘gender blind’ or ‘gender neutral’, being only narrowly addressed alongside topics such as energy justice. Students also suggested that women should occupy positions of leadership in academic activities to help attract women into the MSc programmes on energy, whilst the university should undertake a range of activities to the same end (e.g., promote careers events for women in energy, engaging professional women speakers; grant women scholarships; help build women networks and support communities). In FGB, students noted that gender had been addressed in some of the lectures on energy or sustainability, but, again, it was never the main topic and was addressed narrowly (e.g., women and renewable technologies for cooking), whereas the gender balance of the teaching staff was seen to be heavily skewed towards men. Students were relatively muted in terms of spelling out measures to increase the rates of women signing up for MSc programme, but their discussions suggest that this could be achieved by incorporating more gender attentive content (e.g., case studies of women working in energy fields, women speakers in seminars) and increasing the number of women lecturers.

Results of FGLR (Academics Teaching and/or Researching on Energy Topics)

Factors Influencing women’s educational choices

In the FGLR, participants identified the factors that impact women’s interest and choices in deciding to pursue an education in energy topics/systems, and the extent that these may differ from those for men. The quotes in Table 17 shows the main factors they identified, which largely relate to the entry requirements and the extent of interdisciplinarity in the study programme.

Table 17: FGLR Factors Influencing Women’s Decision to Pursue an Education in Energy

'We used to run a course on Structural Engineering with Architecture, called Environmental Engineering. I think when it's sort of dry civil engineering, our ratio is probably 80% to 20% [students] 80% male ... But when we had these different flavours of courses, then the gender balance was a lot closer to 50-50' ... I've always thought that it might be that there is something that aligns itself more with female interests when it gets to go beyond just the seemingly very arid field of Civil Engineering. And once they feel that there is a sustainability aspect, a novel aspect, a more humanitarian aspect, then the interest seems to grow' (FGLR1M)

'Often the more interdisciplinary courses attract more women ... At the undergraduate level, we have an image in Engineering and Architectural Design, which is very strongly applied for and attended by young women, which is good' (FGLR2W)

'In terms of the mix of women on our courses, you know, how much that is also to do with the A levels that we require them to have [for entry] ... for Chemical Engineering, you have to have Maths, and you have to have either Chemistry or Physics. So immediately. we've got some very stringent requirements there. If you want to go and do one of the sustainability courses, I think you just have to have three decent A levels, I don't think we even care what they're in. So they could be in the Sciences, they could be Geography, they could be Economics, it could be anything. So, we're actually recruiting from a much bigger pool. And my suspicion is that already at A levels, the number of women doing STEM subjects is a lot lower than the number of men' (FGLR3M)

Gender incorporation into teaching and research

The academics in FGLR also considered the extent to which their teaching and research integrated gender aspects or themes and the impacts on female engagement. Table 18 shows the main responses as regards incorporation of a gender dimension in teaching.

Table 18: FGLR Extent of Gender Integration in Teaching and Research

'We do reflect a great deal about the gender imbalance in our courses in Civil Engineering and other Engineering courses that we deliver. But I don't think we have a particularly well-managed strategy. Part of the problem is a lot of the members of staff that deliver in Civil Engineering are male and we've tried to address this gender imbalance, but yesterday a colleague, one of our female colleagues resigned. So, I don't know if we, I could say we have the most successful approach, the fact that we don't have a particularly well-planned strategy, that we're thinking of one, we're formulating one, doesn't impact the number of female students we have in our course' (FGLR1M)

'Gender is not a dimension we look at in my own modules, because of the more technical nature of them. But that's definitely an aspect that colleagues at the university really look at from different angles. I have colleagues, for example, that have been looking at such things, for example, uptake in heat pumps or other technologies where often you have sort of different actors looking at different aspects of the journey. For instance, in the installation of heat pumps: usually male in the household, look after the technology, the technical aspects of installation and do most of the decision making. But then the preferences or the way of operating the building and the experiences are quite different for men and women' (FGLR2W)

'The sustainability students will get a huge amount of material on gender, even if they don't get it on my course ... we have a lot of people there who [teach] gender, other protected characteristics, and the role in sustainability, and particularly a lot of work on intersectionality. At the away day yesterday, I think we had two or three sessions, which touched on those kind of things ... In Engineering, I might be taking it to an extreme if I say it's never mentioned, but it's pretty much never mentioned. There might be one course about sort of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion or something like that, or one lecture. But you know, it's not embedded at all... to be honest, I've never probably even stopped to think about how that impacts the experience of women, of our students' (FGLR3M)

Academics working more on research also considered the extent to which their incorporates gender. One academic, for instance, noted the relevance of empirical research as content for teaching, explaining how his field of interest, clean cooking energy in the Global South, incorporates gender issues, as it examines the impacts on women and young girls of using biomass

for cooking (i.e., time spent fetching wood fuel, time spent in the kitchen and exposure to indoor pollution). However, he was concerned that such research tended to trade on stereotypical victimisation of women and girls as they bear the brunt of the negative impacts, thereby limiting the scope of positive representation of women’s agency for change. He explained

‘It is very easy, I think, to fall into a trap of gender is an important part and women are particularly involved and impacted, but slightly in a victim way, because they’re impacted negatively. So, I think one of the things that we work quite hard to do in the research, but also then reflect that into, into kind of presentations and teaching about this issue, is the potential role, the potential vital role of women in terms of delivering on solutions ... there is a greater opportunity to engage women into helping develop and market and sell and be engaged with and be involved in startups and so on associated with cleaner cooking’ (FGLR4M)

Another academic also considered how their own research and teaching on energy (including in the context of the Global South) incorporates gender and its importance in terms of effecting change

‘In certain modules that I’ve led, related to the climate compatible growth, there is special attention ... to really increase capacity building, especially in energy system modelling, there’s a big need of answering this call for energy system [transition]. Especially the younger, they are targeted to learn more about energy systems modelling, because that would be a way for them to change their lives (FGLR5W).

Overall, then, these results indicate that gender integration into teaching and research is more common in programmes or modules adopting a more interdisciplinary approach (e.g. Sustainability) than in STEM.

Gender institutional practices the university

Participants in the FGLR were asked to discuss their own institution’s culture and practices regarding gender balance in appointments and career progression. The quotes shown in Table 19 illustrate some of the responses, which highlight the importance of practices that create positive role models that may encourage women to seek to study and work at universities that teach and research on energy topics.

Table 19: FGLR Institutional Practices Regarding Gender Balance and Progression

‘EDI [is] at the core of our school ... [there is] a large number of women in research ... positions, but more recently, also at more senior levels, like, Head of Department or at professor’s level. And it’s often nice, because in many cases, these are people who have been in the department or in the school for a while, and perhaps have had different roles here. So, it’s also nice to see that growth and definitely is good as role models for young, more junior colleagues’ (FGLR2W)

‘In Chemical Engineering ... it’s all men ... whereas I counted ... 15 professors in the Sustainability Research Institute, and seven are women ... When I joined ... I was yet another man, and we had a few women. But over the last 13 years, progress has definitely been made there. And if you look at the demographics, more generally, as long as there’s no kind of glass ceiling, you would imagine that very soon, we will have more female professors than we have male ones in Chemical Engineering [where] we’ve got two women at professorial level, amongst about 18 or 20 professors and ... at post level, you can find some women, but I don’t know, 20%, maybe (FGLR3M)

‘I am [in] between kind of hardcore original Engineering and Sustainability and Sustainable Energy ... in our ... Engineering Department, most of the senior leadership are male. Many of the course directors are male. And many of the degree programmes, I think, have that typical kind of rather hard Engineering bias to them ... But on ... the sustainable energy side, I think there’s much more reflection

of the real importance of systems views about sustainability ... one sees a much wider kind of mix of academic staff involved, genders and across the board ... [with] engagement of students of different sorts ... [there] the people who've been most successful in sort of claiming ownership and leadership of theme areas associated with energy have been largely women who are taking a much more holistic, much more systems level and sustainability level view'(FGLR4M)

The academic who teaches at two different faculties at the same university (i.e., Engineering and the Sustainable Institute) contrasted the gender balance and dynamics at each, to illustrate ‘how they are absolutely, completely different culturally, in terms of gender, everything about them is different ... very different ethos’. These differences are shown in Table 20.

Table 20: FGLR Comparison of Practices Regarding Gender Balance and Progression at Different Faculties at one University (FGLR3M)

Engineering	Sustainability Institute
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ ‘I’m 56, probably one of the younger members of staff’ ➤ Staff all nearly male (very, very few women) ➤ 80% of students are male ➤ Decision-making: handed down by senior management; ‘if they say, “Jump”, you jump; if they say, “Jump higher”, you jump higher’ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Most staff are aged 40 or younger ➤ 60% of staff are women ➤ 50% of students are women ➤ Decision-making: ‘endless discussions about what we should do, often with very little outcome if people can’t agree’

On considering such differences, the academic highlighted a fact that might be applicable more widely, that is, other universities in the UK

‘if you are a woman, and you attend [this university], your kind of experience, in terms of the people who are teaching you, so the role models that you see, but also the people that you’re mixing with on a day-to-day basis, would be very different’ (FGLR3M)

Another academic related how the proposed creation of a MSc in Sustainable Energy at the Chemical Engineering Department panned out

‘It was proposed by a small group of entirely male engineers who thought they knew everything about sustainable energy and ... actually ... it was incredibly dry, all technical, it really missed out all of the important kind of Economics, social sort of broader systems level aspects that I think most of us on this call would feel are important. And we’ve worked really hard to try to get them to inject those things. But they just felt that this was what was needed. And that this was what everybody must want to know about, because it was what they thought was important’ (FGLR4M)

Thus, as with the results for gender incorporation into teaching and research discussed in the previous section, the findings here together point to a clear divide in terms of institutional gender practices and dynamics (i.e., gender balance in lectureships and senior roles) between more interdisciplinary programmes and traditional STEM programmes.

Factors Hindering and Enabling Women’s Professional Progression in the Energy Sector

The academics in FGLR discussed factors that may hinder or enable women’s inclusion and progression in the energy sector. Gender imbalances (e.g. male domination) noted previously in academia and research were also observed in the labour market for certain professions and work environments. For instance, one academic considered the situation in his own field of Civil

Engineering as students' progress through the degree programme and then enter the world of work

'the image and the realities of ... construction sites, which are quite intimidating and which I think are still perpetually very male environments ... And there are environments that are not only just male-dominated, but very laddish sort of environments ... even if [students] go into the profession, they still encounter an environment that is, at least in construction sites, very male-dominated. In the consultancy environment ... you see a greater gender balance' (FGLR1M)

Some academics in the FGLR also thought that some attitudinal traits in women may operate to thwart progression in their careers, such as being more guarded than men regarding in jumping at opportunities, lacking in confidence, or being doubtful about their abilities and skills. The excerpts in Table 21 illustrate the argument.

Table 21: FGLR Factors Hindering Women's Progression in Energy Careers

'My wife is an Engineer, and she really works in the field. And I noticed that she tends to doubt herself more than her colleagues. And quite often, I've seen it with my students, sometimes a female student is possibly the one knows the most ... frequently, you have female students who know more than a male student ... and yet, they tend to doubt themselves. And then you have very confident male students who don't know anything, but they somehow, they're forceful and happy, it's all bluff. So, I think there is, there's a psychological dimension to this that both in universities and secondary education, and employers have to better understand and address' (FGLR1M)

'I do think that going into bits of the energy sector ... that often are going to be majority male to start with, that is a challenge ... women often may be more hesitant to put themselves forward or not wanting to put themselves forward for jobs that they don't think they may be 100% equal. Whereas men will happily put themselves forward for anything they fancy. Why not give it a? Give it a try ... I think there's also a kind of slightly related issue about this kind of behavioural and attitudinal approach. That and how it differs in genders ... which is very important to sustainable energy ... I suspect if we looked at startups across the energy sector, you would probably find that there is a bias towards male leadership of startups just because the men think 'Yeah, we'll give it a go. We'll try. It might not work, but we'll try it and fail'. And there's that classic thing that women typically are less willing to try something if they think they might fail, and hence all the efforts to try and get girls and women to be willing to fail' (FGLR4M)

[recruitment adverts] 'They're very much about a bullet list of what you must have ... men look at that and think "Yeah, I could do at least three of those. So, I'll apply". Women go down and say "Oh, number eight, I'm not sure that I can really quite do all that. I won't, that job's probably not for me" (FGLR3M)

'Usually, women have a personality, they tend to be quite risk-averse, but it also depends on the field' (FGLR5W)

Gender discrimination by employers was also noted as major hurdle to women's professional development. One academic related how he had learned about a case of 'blatant' discrimination against women in the offshore energy industry that he found shocking. At a large conference on energy and offshore opportunities that he attended a few years ago, there was a panel discussion around creating a more diverse workforce in the sector. Yet, during a break, he overheard two women chatting who turned out to be from recruitment agencies whose job is to recruit people and place them in the offshore industry. He related his exchange with them

'They said, "Well, it's all very well to have that discussion about diversity, but that's not what the companies want ... if we put forward women to work in the offshore industry, they will be turned down, because they're women". And I said "So what? But do you still put them forward?" They said "No, we don't get our fee, if we put forward people who aren't employable. So, we would only ever

put forward men”. And I said, “Surely that's illegal!”. And they said “Yeah, of course it is. It is an open secret. You know, if you're female, don't try and work offshore”. And they were so blasé about it. It's one of those situations where you don't really know what to say. And I went “Oh, is that widespread?” And they went “Yeah!” (FGLR3M).

Thinking about factors that play a role in enabling women’s insertion and progression in the energy sector, the academics in FGLR highlighted the importance of role models for women, and also reflected on the use of quotas, which could be positive if used judiciously. Table 22 illustrate their thinking.

Table 22 : FGLR Role Models for Women

‘In general, I kind of subscribe to the view that it's difficult to be what you can't see. So, if you have role models that look a bit like you ... whether that be about gender or background, or colour, race, whatever, then I think you can see that people can succeed in that field ... and that gives you some hope that you might be able to ... do it ... I had a conversation with my youngest daughter [when] she was probably seven or eight ... And they had to write a little bit at school about famous scientists ... and I said, “Well, what's your list?” And I looked at it, and there wasn't a single woman on the list. And I said, “Aren't there any women?” And she said to me “Well, I don't think women are scientists”. And I said “Well, they are!” She said “Well, we haven't been told about any”. And I thought “Yeah, we need to change that!”’ (FGLR3M)

‘One knows that in terms of spreading messages around the importance and the opportunities for uptake of cleaner cooking solutions, if you're not kind of tackling the gender differences, if you're not dealing with the different ways in which people are engaged in the cooking system, then you're going to be missing on ... really good opportunities if you don't think actively about ... gender issues, then it's possible that you end up with rather a negative view ... And you need to, I think, in our view, you need to turn that around and, and then look for the kind of positive engagement and the role models ... that's very powerful ... it does help spark the imagination and the engagements of women who are receiving those messages, whether they're engaged in delivery on the ground in developing countries, or whether they're sitting in the classroom ... at Imperial or Surrey, and hearing ... the importance of that’ (FGLR4M)

‘I think what was said previously and emphasised, there's this psychological aspect, for example, that would probably hinder certain women in taking up certain jobs. And I think for that, I think it's quite important to really strengthen the role models that could inspire young women. And so, for example, at Imperial, there is this network of women in Engineering, and they used to run more frequently in the past compared to now, these events around showing these role models. So, women that exceeded in their career that are usually assigned to men. I think it's very useful, especially for young Engineers to learn that you can ask for things, and you can do something to get to this certain position ... I think you really need role models (FGLR5W)

Academics also considered some employers’ measures for supporting women in teaching and working, not only in energy and sustainability fields, but also more widely. Some argued, for instance, for support for young women with young families, and providing flexibility around maternity leave and other needs specific to women during certain periods and tasks that may require it (FGLR2W). Yet, another academic related that some years ago, during an interview for a job, his wife had asked the interviewer whether she could have flexible working and got the reply “What? What's this?”. But he noted that attitudes and practices may have changed, particularly since the 2019 Covid pandemic (FGLR1M).

A further measure discussed to help women advance in their careers was the use of quotas, which some thought could be effective when used judiciously, but others had doubts about. The reasoning is conveyed in the excerpts in Table 23.

Table 23 : FGLR Quotas for Women

'I can get confused about quotas. I mean, bearing in mind what has happened in some parts of the world when they had quotas for employment for ethnic minorities, sometimes you hear quite positive things that have enabled change, and sometimes you hear that they've generated resentment. So ... I don't know if quotas work. Instinctively, I think it's a good idea, but I think it needs evidence because, obviously, you don't want it to be counterproductive' (FGLR1M)

'It's quite a sensitive thing that needs to be well balanced. For example, in our department ... you need to have a certain number of women versus men representatives, for example, in job interviews ... I'm pretty sure that ... it was meant to have a positive impact. But sometimes [you're asked] to be there just because you're a woman ... helping tick the box for the meeting ... to go ahead ... that, I think, is counterproductive ... because you don't feel you're there because you're valued for your skills or for what you bring ... And these kinds of things also often go from one extreme to the other ... but eventually, they, sort of, will find a middle ground' (FGLR2W)

FGLR recommendations for enhancing women's participation in the energy sector

The academics in FGLR considered measures to help increase women's take up of academic studies in programmes incorporating energy and sustainability topics, as well measures to encourage them to pursue careers in the energy sector. They highlighted, for instance, the importance of interventions in the earlier stages of education, such exposing young girls to core disciplines in STEM that will become requirements for entry into higher education degree programmes. As one academic argued:

'It's important to focus on the higher education level, but I think it would be even more important to foster, you know, the, this interest and curiosity of younger women at, I don't know, primary school, secondary school, and just to help them get more and more interest and sort of a can-do attitude, in a sense, towards STEM courses ... and activities ... if you don't invest earlier on, for example, you don't have that Maths background or Physics background, that might prevent you from being accepted in different courses, where actually you may have opportunities then to move to the energy sector. That already sort of cuts a lot of people out, especially because, possibly, of a younger age, it's possibly a bit harder to see all the opportunities you may have. And some professions or some activities within professions may not be as obvious' (FGLR2W)

Another academic concurred:

'Working at the educational level, in schools, it's also important to make students familiar with when they're young, that they can be aware about the deep STEM and all these other fields' (FGLR5W)

A further suggestion was for a change in the methods of assessment and work dynamics in degree programmes, from the conventional assessment by exams at the end of module study to continuous assessment throughout, alongside teamwork, which are seen to address the requirements of evolving dynamics in the workplace. The academic who proposed the measure explained the rationale, as well as noting potential downsides

'I think continuous assessment and group work, and those kinds of approaches to assessment as against exams ... are both better aligned to future career requirements, because an awful lot of work these days is teamwork. And so, there's opportunities for learning how to work in teams, as well as actually the kind of particular energy situations. But there's also ... the opportunity within ... group work and assessment group work for women's ... natural, on average, greater emotional intelligence to engage well in those sorts of groups, to do well compared to very, kind of end point examination type of assessments. Although the risk is that you could potentially get groups which are kind of overly

dominated by male voices ... So, I think there is a caveat to that ... But I do think ... appropriate forms of assessment ... is both good for future career development ... also, potentially, helps women's ... greater capacity for that kind of systemic view and holistic kind of approach to thing is an important part of it' (FGLR4M).

Addressing unconscious bias against women in the workplace was also raised as an important measure, which in the case of women academics, should be addressed very early on. As the academic argued

'I think we also need to work on sort of unconscious biases against women and young women, particular in certain jobs. Like, for example, again, a little bit anecdotally, but we tend to have more student complaints against young lecturers, women lecturers, than for older professors, male professors. And not necessarily ... disparaging the performance on what it is provided to the students. But there seems to be a dimension of bias ... that probably we need to work on well before students get to higher education' (FGLR2W).

Changing the style and content of advertisements recruiting for jobs and posts was also suggested to help women apply for employment in energy and energy-related fields. One academic related how, whilst working for the International Energy Agency, he had attended a training course on recruitment run by the Gender Equality Unit of the OECD which proposed. He explained that

'they had a lot of evidence about how they had changed the way that they had written the adverts and a demonstrable change in the number of females applying for those roles. By moving away from this 'You must have a degree in this, 10 years' experience of that' and all the rest of it to a much more sort of 'Come with us on a journey. Are you committed to protecting the environment? We'll do this'. And that apparently is more appealing to women ... when I joined the university, I was quite shocked to see that ... the adverts, at least at [his university] and probably most other places, belong somewhere in the 1950s. They're very much about a bullet list of what you must have ... So, I think it would be really interesting to ... think about how we describe jobs, maybe even where we advertise them, how flexible they are ... that we could do' (FGLR3M)

A final suggestion was that companies should change the way they promote staff, adapting promotion to reward the different types of profiles associated skills sets, rather focusing on hierarchical approaches. As the proponent of the measure reasoned

'One thing that I've always found that I feel uncomfortable with companies is that management roles are the only way you can progress in a career. So, if you're willing to become a significantly more project manager, you're going to move up the echelons. But if you like to just sit down and resolve technical aspects, you just stagnate in your career. And I have heard, in some companies, they create sort of parallel possibilities. I have a friend who works at a company where that approach exists, where they say, 'Well, actually, you're really good at a technical aspect, and you don't have to be very managerial'... In confrontational spaces ... it's possible that male participants, in these sort of discussions, sort of become very forceful and - I'm probably thinking Alpha males - become very dominant in these spaces ... that might mean that you create a company that helps people that are very forceful in discussions and in meetings, they'll be the people who go to rise to the top' (FGLR1M)

Cross-cutting Recommendations for Increasing Women's Greater Participation in Education and Careers in the Energy Sector

The contributions of students and academics in the focus groups were distilled into the following recommendations to help improve the women's greater uptake in higher education in energy fields, and enhancing their insertion, retention and progression in careers in the diverse energy sector. These are shown in Table 24.

Table 24 Increasing Women's Participation in Education and Careers in the Energy Sector	
Education	Careers
Start teaching STEM to girls earlier (secondary school onwards)	Run recruitment events for women where women leaders speak
Provide interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary higher education courses	Role models
Give women scholarships to pursue degree programs	Use role models to help encourage young women/women move to pursue and progress in careers in the energy sector
Run careers events for women led by women	Company policy to provide adequate support to attend to women's specific needs (e.g. maternity leave; flexible hours; working from home)
Use role models to help encourage young women/women to read for degrees/higher degrees with energy/sustainability components	Enforce EDI: company policy to ensure equality of opportunity (e.g., similar hours and pay scales for similar hours and tasks for men and women, promotion into senior roles, management, directorships,); transparency in recruitment practices and progression; modernise recruitment practices (e.g. ad description for jobs not just a list of skills and abilities)
Build women's networks and support communities (including through use of social media)	Company policy to enforce quotas for women (discretionally and sensitively)
Improve gender balance (ratio) of teaching and research staff	Company policy to strengthen measures on safety at the workplace and work sites (including through greater use of digital technologies and automation)
Incorporate gender aspects into the degree programmes (cases studies on role models, women's experiences on production/consumption of energy)	Greater financial support for women startups
Change method of assessment (continuous rather than end-of-module exams) and promote teamwork	Flexible promotion styles (i.e., progression not necessarily hierarchical)

Overall, the focus groups results make evident that:

- gender as a topic of enquiry is not a major concern in any of the MSc programmes discussed (e.g., very limited or virtual ‘gender-blindness’)
- students are interested in programme interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary
- male lecturers dominate STEM programmes as do male students, but interdisciplinary programmes seem to enable gender balance in terms of teaching staff and students
- opportunities for career progression in the energy sector for women may be thwarted by taking off to have children (maternity leave), lacking support from family or partners, stereotypes and assumptions by employers, being excluded from male informal networks of socialisation that may influence decision-making about progression, the characteristics of certain types of jobs (e.g., hard physical labour, dirty, dangerous, remote sites, male-dominated),

APPENDIX

FGA

Number of participants	5
Target Focus Group	STEM (MSc Sustainable Energy Futures)
Place of the interview	Imperial, Central Campus, London
Date of the interview	18 th November 2024
Length of the FGI	90 minutes
Female (number)	3
Male (number)	2

FGB

Number of participants	6
Target Focus Group	Interdisciplinary (MSc Environmental Technology)
Place of the interview	Imperial, Central Campus, London
Date of the interview	20th November 2024
Length of the FGI	90 minutes
Female (number)	4
Male (number)	2

FGLR

Number of participants	5
Target Focus Group	Lecturers/Researchers
Place of the interview	Online
Date of the interview	16th January 2025
Length of the FGI	90 minutes
Female (number)	2
Male (number)	3

6.2. Reports from the national workshops

6.2.1. Germany

Workshop Report: Theory of Change for a large Berlin energy company

1. Introduction

The workshop held on May 14, 2025, was part of the ongoing European research project, gEneSyS, which is funded by the EU (Grant Agreement No. 101094326). This project focuses on gender aspects in energy production, consumption, and policy regulation, with a particular emphasis on strengthening the representation of women in the energy sector and research. As part of this initiative, Fraunhofer IAO approached a large Berlin energy company, to collaborate on a workshop aimed at addressing these issues. The company was particularly interested in participating due to their current strategic focus on diversity, making the workshop an important step in their efforts to promote equal opportunities within the company.

Led by the Head of Change and Culture at a large Berlin energy company and Dr. Clemens Striebing from Fraunhofer IAO, the purpose of the workshop was to develop a sustainable concept to ensure equal opportunities within the company by 2030. This initiative was driven by the noticeable changes in the labor market, such as the increasing shortage of skilled workers and demographic shifts. The workshop aimed to address how the energy company can effectively engage new target groups, actively promote diversity, and secure the company's future viability. It served as a critical step in developing concrete answers to these challenges.

Participants included representatives from various sectors within the energy company, such as network, sales, commerce, administration, human resources, and different staff departments. The workshop was scientifically supported by the Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Engineering and Organization (IAO), which brought its expertise in organizational change processes. This context provided a rich backdrop for the discussions, emphasizing the importance of gender representation in the energy industry.

The methodological framework of the workshop involved applying the Theory of Change to describe how the energy industry can become more inclusive. Participants engaged in focus groups to identify key challenges and develop strategies to overcome them. The Theory of Change was used to map out the logical sequence of actions needed to achieve the desired change, starting with inputs such as resources and partnerships, followed by specific activities like workshops and mentoring programs. Outputs included increased awareness and improved recruitment processes, leading to outcomes like better gender representation and heightened employee engagement. The long-term impact aimed for a

workplace where diversity is structurally embedded and equal opportunities are the norm.

2. Description of the Workshop Process

The workshop was structured into several sessions, beginning with a welcome and introduction by the Head of Change and Culture from the energy company and Dr. Clemens Striebing from Fraunhofer IAO. The initial session set the stage by explaining the workshop's purpose and the pressing need for the energy company to address workforce diversity and sustainability amid labor market changes. Participants, comprising 15 individuals from various departments, engaged in a brief introduction round to share their roles and perspectives.

The workshop's flow included individual and group work, starting with a session where participants individually reviewed the results of the 2024 "Diversity Compass" survey by the energy company and prioritized key challenges related to equal opportunities using adhesive dots. This led to the formation of three thematic groups focusing on equal opportunity and inclusion, career development and access, and intergenerational collaboration.

Participants then worked in small groups to develop strategies to overcome the identified challenges. Each group defined a target state (impact), necessary resources (inputs), actions to be undertaken (outputs), and the immediate effects of these actions (outcomes). The methods and tools used included change mapping and impact pathways, facilitating a structured approach to applying the Theory of Change. Participants engaged in discussions and collaborative brainstorming to create comprehensive strategies.

The workshop concluded with a discussion on the proportionality and framework conditions of the strategies, emphasizing the importance of leadership support and the need for sustainable, long-term processes rather than short-term interventions. The company's Head of Change and Culture highlighted the importance of integrating the workshop's insights into a cohesive action plan, aiming to develop a realistic and ambitious implementation strategy supported by both leadership and employees.

3. Desired Change / Vision of the Goal

As a result of the topic discussion and prioritization, the topics that were considered essential were grouped into three groups for further processing:

1. **Gender equality and inclusion:** This cluster includes achieving gender equality and overcoming gender bias in recruitment and promotion processes as well as promoting and making visible (female) role models. It focuses on creating an inclusive work environment in which all genders are equal and barriers for women are removed in order to offer them equal opportunities and support.
2. **Career development and access:** This cluster addresses skills barriers and the impermeability of careers. It focuses on the need to identify and remove barriers to career development in order to ensure fair access to career advancement opportunities for all employees, regardless of their demographic affiliation
3. **Intergenerational collaboration:** This cluster addresses issues such as ageism and intergenerational collaboration. It aims to create a harmonious working environment that utilizes the strengths and experiences of all age groups while at the same time prevents age discrimination in order to promote productive and respectful cooperation between the generations.

The participants aim to achieve increased equal opportunities at the energy company by addressing challenges related to age, gender, ethnic origin, and visible and invisible disabilities. The focus for the year 2025 is on age and gender, with the goal of developing a sustainable concept to ensure and structurally anchor equal opportunities by 2030.

The envisioned future is a workplace where diversity is the norm, supported actively by leadership, and where equal opportunities are structurally embedded. The energy company aims for a 50/50 gender distribution in leadership and the workforce by 2030, fostering an inclusive environment free from stereotypes.

The change aims to address key values such as diversity, inclusion, and equality. It seeks to meet the needs for a fair and supportive workplace, where barriers are removed, enabling all employees to have equal access to career development and advancement opportunities, regardless of demographic background. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of intergenerational collaboration and the recognition of diverse competencies across age groups.

4. Assumptions and Context

Participants made several assumptions about the current conditions at the energy company and the conditions necessary for change. They assumed that the company is at a critical juncture due to noticeable shifts in the labor market, such as increasing skill shortages and demographic changes. These conditions necessitate effective engagement with new target groups, active promotion of diversity, and securing the

company's future viability. To achieve change, participants believe the energy company must develop practical and feasible solutions that address these challenges and structurally embed equality by 2030. The focus is on creating an inclusive environment that overcomes barriers related to age and gender, ensuring fair career development and fostering intergenerational collaboration.

During the workshop, several barriers and challenges were identified concerning equality at the energy company, particularly focusing on age discrimination and the lack of female workers in technical jobs.

Participants understood age discrimination as the challenges faced by older employees in adapting to new digital technologies and processes. This discrimination can manifest in a lack of opportunities for older employees to engage in digital innovations, leading to feelings of being "left behind." Conversely, younger employees may face challenges in being recognized for their digital competencies and innovative ideas, especially in environments where traditional experience is highly valued. The workshop highlighted the importance of utilizing the experience of older employees while integrating their skills with the digital competencies of younger staff. Measures such as reverse mentoring, where younger employees guide older colleagues in digital matters, and job-sharing across generations were proposed to foster a respectful and productive intergenerational collaboration.

The scarcity of female workers in technical roles was identified as a barrier to forming diverse teams. To address this, the workshop proposed strategies such as personal outreach in schools by female technical professionals to inspire young girls, participation in career-oriented events like Girls' Day, and mentorship programs for women entering male-dominated fields. These initiatives aim to increase female representation in technical jobs, thereby enriching the diversity and effectiveness of teams at the energy company.

The social and economic context influencing the possibility of change at the energy company is shaped by several factors. Socially, the demographic changes and increasing skill shortages on the labor market necessitate effective engagement with new target groups and active promotion of diversity. Economically, the energy company faces the challenge of ensuring future viability amidst these shifts, requiring strategic planning and resource allocation to address barriers to equality, such as age discrimination and the lack of female workers in technical jobs.

5. Pathway of Change

The logical sequence of actions leading to change at the energy company begins with identifying the necessary inputs to initiate action. These inputs include resources such as training programs, diversity workshops, mentoring schemes, and strategic partnerships

with educational institutions and industry experts. The aim is to create a supportive environment that fosters diversity and equal opportunities.

The specific activities undertaken involve implementing sensitization workshops to address biases, diversifying recruitment panels, conducting targeted surveys among women in technical roles, and promoting diversity within project teams. Additionally, initiatives like reverse mentoring, job sharing across generations, and targeted outreach to schools are designed to engage new demographics and enhance intergenerational collaboration.

As a result of these actions, the outputs will manifest as increased awareness and understanding of diversity issues, a more inclusive recruitment process, and enhanced support structures for women and underrepresented groups. Project teams will become more diverse, and mentoring programs will facilitate knowledge transfer and career development.

The short- and medium-term outcomes include improved gender representation in technical and leadership roles, heightened employee engagement, and a culture that values diversity and inclusion. These outcomes will contribute to a workplace where equal opportunities are structurally embedded.

The long-term impact of these changes will be a sustainable organizational culture at the energy company that embraces diversity as a core value. By 2030, the company aims to achieve a 50/50 gender distribution in leadership and the workforce, ensuring that diversity and inclusion are integral to its operations. This transformation will enhance the energy company's reputation as an employer of choice and increase its competitiveness in the evolving labor market.

6. Indicators of Success

Participants will recognize change through observable shifts in workplace demographics, improved representation of women in technical roles, enhanced intergenerational collaboration, and reduced barriers to career advancement. Additionally, the presence of inclusive practices and policies will serve as indicators of progress.

Quantitative indicators include the percentage increase of women in technical and leadership positions, the number of diversity training sessions conducted, and the reduction in reported gender and age-related bias incidents. Qualitative indicators involve employee feedback through surveys, case studies showcasing successful intergenerational projects, and testimonials regarding career development opportunities.

Potential data sources for tracking these indicators include employee surveys, HR records, feedback from diversity training sessions, incident reports, mentoring program data, and performance reviews. These sources will provide both quantitative metrics and qualitative insights into the effectiveness of the implemented strategies and the overall cultural shift towards inclusivity and equal opportunities at the energy company.

7. Recommendations and Next Steps

After the workshop, participants should focus on developing a comprehensive and actionable Theory of Change that integrates the insights and strategies discussed. This involves creating a detailed roadmap that prioritizes the identified measures and aligns them with the organizational goals and resources available. The workshop highlighted the necessity for a strategic plan that not only addresses diversity and equal opportunities but also structurally embeds these values within the energy company's operations.

To realize the Theory of Change, further actions should include the establishment of a clear implementation framework that outlines responsibilities, timelines, and resource allocation. Collaborations with educational institutions and industry partners can enhance the outreach to new target groups, particularly young women in technical fields. Additionally, fostering partnerships with organizations that specialize in diversity and inclusion can provide valuable support and expertise.

Institutions supporting the process should focus on providing continuous training and development opportunities that promote an inclusive culture. They should also facilitate the exchange of best practices and offer platforms for dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders. The leadership at the energy company is crucial in championing these initiatives and ensuring that diversity goals are integrated into the company's strategic planning. By creating sustainable structures and encouraging a culture of continuous engagement, the energy company can effectively implement the Theory of Change and achieve its 2030 vision for equal opportunities.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the workshop provided valuable insights and strategies for achieving equal opportunity and diversity within the energy company by 2030. It highlighted the importance of leadership support, structural changes, and proactive engagement with diverse groups. The Theory of Change framework offers a roadmap for realizing the envisioned future, emphasizing inclusivity, collaboration, and sustainability.

6.2.2. Poland

Enhancing Women in the Energy Sector in Poland- workshop Theory of Change, Poland

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Summary

Gender imbalance in the energy transition requires not only sectoral reforms but also a shift in societal values, family practices, and public policy priorities that collectively sustain gender inequality. The Theory of Change was applied to facilitate a collaborative process with women pursuing careers in energy sector in business, public administration and higher education. It explored the conditions under which transformations in both educational and professional domains could enhance women's energy literacy and motivate them to pursue career trajectories in energy-related fields.

The workshop was methodically divided into two segments: the first segment involved the introduction of the gEneSys project, as well as the presentation and discussion of its research findings, in particular the analysis of gender dimension in energy education textbooks and insights derived from focus group interviews with both students and teachers on gendered education and career paths in energy. The second segment focused on civic and consumer competencies as foundational to informed participation and decision-making in energy in higher education, taking into account both immediate and future-oriented perspectives.

Participants engaged in an analysis of the prospective inputs and outputs of the proposed initiatives. The short- and medium-term results show that the initiatives are expected to lead to a noticeable increase in the number of women enrolling in energy related higher education programmes and entering the energy sector, including management positions. The desired changes need both the reforms mandating gender equality in organisation and education, and social and cultural change to strengthening the social fabric, which build community awareness and social solidarity around gender equality in the workplace and civil engagement.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the workshop

The 'Enhancing Women in the Energy Sector in Poland' workshop was conducted in line with the Theory of Change methodology. This project-based approach, originating from the field of evaluation (Reinholtz, Andrews 2020) was applied to facilitate a collaborative process with women pursuing careers in the energy sector in business, public administration and higher education. The joint work aimed to reflect on the conditions necessary to foster change that would support the overarching goal of increasing

women's presence in the energy sector. This included advancing their professional careers and strengthening their energy-related competencies, thereby enabling them to make informed decisions as consumers and active citizens.

Theory of Change (ToC) is a widely used approach for designing and evaluating complex initiatives that seek to generate meaningful change. At its core, it involves a collaborative process of defining long-term goals and mapping the pathways through which planned activities can lead to these outcomes (Fell et al. 2023). What distinguishes ToC is its strong emphasis on the *real change* to be achieved in the chosen area of intervention. It considers the broader context, including policies, structural conditions, and cultural meanings. By doing so, it enables participants to critically examine their own assumptions, clarify motivations and aspirations, and anticipate both potential obstacles and unintended consequences.

1.2 Brief presentation of the participants and context (e.g. sector, project, social issue)

The Polish workshop was conducted as part of the Horizon Europe gEneSys project, specifically within the scope of Work Package 3. It represented one of three national workshops, parallel to those convened in Germany and the United Kingdom. While the German report focused on exploring the conditions conducive to enhancing gender equality within organizational settings, and the UK report concentrated on fostering support for women in higher education within the energy sector, the Polish workshop integrated these viewpoints. It explored the conditions under which transformations in both educational and professional domains could enhance women's energy literacy and motivate them to pursue career trajectories in the energy sector.

The workshop was facilitated by three female scholars from Jagiellonian University and convened six participants: two from the business sector, three from public administration, and one tasked with the implementation of a new academic program on leadership in the green transition. It was held in Kraków at Jagiellonian University on 12 September 2025 (10:00–14:00 CET).

The event was methodically divided into two segments: the initial segment involved the introduction of the aims and foundations of the gEneSys project, as well as presentation and discussion of its' research findings, in particular the analysis to gender dimension in energy education textbooks and insights derived from focus group interviews with both students and teachers on gendered education and career paths in energy-. This prompted a critical reflection on the current pedagogical approaches to energy education in Poland and assessed the extent to which these approaches encourage young individuals to align their prospective activities and careers with the energy sector.

During the second segment of the workshop, executed within the framework of the Theory of Change, participants initiated by conceptualizing an aspirational vision for the energy sector as an environment conducive to the advancement of women. Subsequently, they engaged in a discourse on their personal experiences, alongside the political, economic, and socio-cultural determinants influencing their career trajectories, working conditions, and perceptions pertaining to energy practices, the sector at large, and other women operating within it. This iterative process fostered a critical examination of their

foundational assumptions and facilitated the identification of requisite transformations in both the expansive external milieu and the specific internal context necessary to actualize the envisaged changes. Furthermore, participants engaged in an analysis of the prospective inputs and outputs of the proposed initiatives, taking into account both immediate and future-oriented perspectives.

Table 1. Workshop participants

P	Background	Current Position and Work
A	She holds a background in economics and finance, later complemented by studies in agronomy in Poland. She also completed an MBA at a Polish university.	Currently, she works for a leading international company in the fuel sector, where she occupies a senior managerial position responsible for the company's energy transition strategy and reports directly to the board. Her work also includes communication with the Ministries of Energy and Environment on energy legislative improvements. She brings with her over a decade of professional experience in the business.
B	Participant B was trained in information technology (a computer systems programmer) and has over 20 years of experience in senior managerial positions, leading teams in both the finance and energy sectors. In addition to her professional expertise, she is also a coach and mentor.	She currently serves as the head of the technological centre of the Polish branch of an international company producing power technologies, where she manages a team of around 600 people. In her previous job she implemented educational projects aimed at getting young children interested in STEM subjects and at encouraging female high-school students to study STEM disciplines. She is also a certified life crisis mentor
C	Participant C is a habilitated doctor in law with more than 30 years of experience in scientific research and higher education. She has built her academic career within the university sector, combining expertise in teaching and research.	At present, she is responsible for developing and organizing a new study program focused on leadership in the green transition at a leading university in Poland.
D	Participant D holds a STEM background with a degree in Environmental Engineering from a technical university. She has several years of professional experience in	Participant D currently works in the city office of a municipality neighbouring Kraków, where she is responsible for issues related to clean air, the transformation of heating systems, and the broader process of energy transition. She is also a member of the governing board of

	public administration, where she serves in a leadership role responsible for energy transition and climate-related issues.	an energy cooperative. For 7 years she has been responsible for the city energy efficiency programmes. She also co-runs an energy cooperative
E	Participant E holds a degree from the University of Economics in Kraków.	She currently holds a managerial role in the Department of Municipal Economy and Climate at the City Hall of Kraków. In this role, she is responsible for overseeing initiatives related to clean air, the transformation of heating systems, and broader energy transition efforts. Additionally, she is a member of the board of an energy cooperative. Her work is instrumental in advancing the city's climate adaptation strategies and fostering citizen engagement through initiatives like the Kraków Climate Panel. Until recently she had been involved in a programme “A Pact for Climate” aiming at awareness raising and education about climate neutrality. Currently she is engaged in a H2020 project on increasing city energy efficiency.
F	F possesses academic degrees in Polish and Italian Philology from the Jagiellonian University and has an extensive background in literary studies and translation. She also has several years of experience as a lecturer at a Polish university.	F is a Kraków-based public official and activist, currently with a position in the city hall, responsible for advancing gender equality, anti-discrimination initiatives, and inclusive social policies within the city. She is engaged in the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan for the city hall and municipal units with a special focus on women’s recruitment and career development.

2. Methodological framework: how Theory of Change was applied during the workshop

2.1. Description of the Workshop Process

The workshops, although structured according to the principles of the Theory of Change, did not make explicit reference to the theory itself. Participants were apprised of the structure of the discussion, yet remained uninformed about the underlying methodological presuppositions. The process commenced with the formation of an aspirational vision regarding women's participation in the energy sector, delving into

dialogues about the significance of such participation, the participant's perceptions of existing tools that support women, the objectives in question, and their importance. The conversation progressed naturally into an examination of the required alterations in the current system for this vision to materialize. Participants deliberated on who would be impacted by these changes, who could instigate them, and which factors might impede or facilitate their execution. In the subsequent phase, the emphasis transitioned to formulating recommendations on how to enhance women's participation in the energy system, both professionally and as citizens. Participants were segmented into two groups: one concentrated on pathways related to careers and education, while the other addressed civic and consumer competencies as foundational to informed participation and decision-making in the energy field. A notable reflection emerged, indicating that most of the identified barriers and limitations for women extend beyond the energy sector, permeating numerous domains of social life where competition for resources and prestige prevails. The figure 1 illustrates the main steps of the collective workshop, figure 2 main categories used as stimulus during discussion.

Fig. 1 Visualisation of the workshop main steps.

Fig 2 Next steps in a collective discussion.

3. Desired Change / Vision of the Goal

During an intensive and reflective discussion, a shared vision of a gender-just energy transition gradually crystallized among the workshop participants. At the outset, they expressed reservations about defining the goal of gender justice solely in quantitative terms, such as achieving a 50:50 gender balance across all subsectors of the energy industry. Rather than focusing on parity “*at any cost*,” participants emphasized the importance of creating structural and cultural conditions that enable all individuals—irrespective of gender—to pursue their professional interests freely and without constraint. The envisioned transformation was thus not limited to numerical equality but was directed toward the removal of systemic barriers that restrict autonomy and reproduce gendered divisions of labour. As one participant noted,

“I don't mean 50-50, but exactly what you said, that there should be competencies, that girls should feel that they have those competencies... that I can and want to, right? Or, in other words, if I want to, I can, right? I have equal rights.” (Participant B).

In the world imagined by the participants, career choices are genuinely autonomous, shaped by personal motivation and competence rather than by entrenched gender stereotypes or social expectations. Women’s engagement in the energy sector is guided primarily by passion and capability, not by prescriptive notions of appropriate gender roles. The participants’ vision thus foregrounds an egalitarian framework in which both women and men can participate in all domains of the energy transition on equal terms, with confidence derived from equal access to education, training, and opportunity.

However, participants simultaneously acknowledged that realizing such a vision requires deep institutional transformation. Over the course of the discussion, they increasingly recognized that gender equality in the energy transition cannot be achieved without a substantial increase in the representation of women among the sector’s “gatekeepers”—particularly within executive, managerial, and policy-making bodies. A more balanced distribution of decision-making power was regarded as essential not only for ensuring equitable participation but also for reshaping the sector’s culture, priorities, and practices. The presence of women in leadership positions was understood as a precondition for changing organizational philosophies and for inspiring subsequent generations of women to pursue careers in energy-related fields.

For many participants, the principle of gender justice was inseparable from the broader democratization and empowerment of citizens within the energy system. They articulated a vision of an informed and engaged society in which energy awareness, literacy, and competence are widely shared and supported by transparent, accountable, and accessible institutions. In this desired future, citizens—both women and men—possess the knowledge and confidence to understand energy systems, interpret costs and tariffs, and participate meaningfully as consumers, prosumers, and stakeholders in the energy transition.

Ultimately, participants envisaged a just energy transition that enables women to pursue professional success without compromising their personal identities or aspirations. In this scenario, women are visible and valued as experts, entrepreneurs, and leaders within a sector that recognizes and rewards diverse contributions. Decision-making bodies are more gender-balanced, workplace cultures are inclusive, and gender ceases to be a determinant of opportunity or authority. The participants’ collective vision thus extends beyond the energy sector itself, imagining a comprehensive social transformation in which equality, autonomy, and empowerment are integral to both the energy transition and the society it seeks to serve.

Table 2. Vision: Women in Energy Sectors

- Confident women who freely express their opinions on energy-related topics
- Women choose their educational path and subsequently their career based on personal interests
- Equal access to education, employment, career advancement and leadership positions
- Women visible in the public sphere as energy experts
- Laypeople, both women and men, have energy literacy
- The energy system is transparent and user-friendly
- Women feel supported in pursuing their choices
- Acceptance of making mistakes and readiness to take responsibility

4. Assumption and Context

4.1. Assumption

The workshop discussions reveal several key assumptions underpinning participants’ views on how to make the energy transformation gender just. First, participants assumed

that the energy sector possesses some unique characteristics—it is perceived as stable, essential, and resistant to crisis (Participant Hitachi). Energy was described as a “mission critical” sector, one that will always exist because society will always need energy.

“This sector is still there, of course, IT is shrinking, (...), or automotive, you can see that. Energy is a mission-critical sector (...), the worse things get in the world, the more the business grows.” (Participant B)

This perception implies that energy work is not only well-paid and secure, but also highly diverse in terms of competencies—from technical experts to social scientists. Yet, despite this diversity, participants assumed that the sector’s image does not reflect this inclusivity, and that its stability has also contributed to its resistance to change, particularly in gender dynamics and representation.

At the same time, however, the participants came to the conclusion that the gender inequalities observed in the energy sector are not specific, but rather common to those jobs, where money (high salaries) come along with power and responsibility and prestige:

“That is, well, you have to be competent, you have to make decisions, you have to take responsibility for them, but you will also most likely be well rewarded, and most likely this job will still be prestigious.” (Participant C)

A second major assumption concerns women’s participation and influence in the energy transformation. Participants shared the view that gender justice requires more women not only as employees but especially in leadership and decision-making roles. They assumed that simply increasing the number of women in these positions would not be enough—a critical mass is necessary to shift organizational culture and practices. The “30% threshold” was mentioned as a tipping point, beyond which women could begin to influence institutional norms and bring other women along. Implicit here is the assumption that gender equality cannot be achieved through token representation; rather, it requires structural change in power relations and corporate culture:

[If it is] “30%, they will attract more, in the sense that there will no longer be a threshold preventing this woman from joining the board (...) she is already one of several women, so it's a different situation than when I'm alone in a group of men and I have to masculinize myself, because if I don't, they will go for a beer, agree on something among themselves over that beer, and I will be cut off” (Participant F)

“I changed my mind (...) that these quotas, based on what you said about [men] not wanting to share power, could actually be a tool to enforce certain behaviors, regardless of competence. Why? Because do we think that those 90% of men are competent? Well, I'll tell you that they're not (...), there's a lot of cronyism, especially in this sector, the traditional one, the state sector most of all, so these quotas could actually support us when we want to get in.” (Participant A)”

Third, participants assumed that deep social change is a prerequisite for gender justice in the energy sector. They connected gender inequality to broader societal norms and socialization processes that shape women’s self-perceptions and career choices. As one

participant noted, women are not born feeling “worse” or less capable—these beliefs are socially constructed:

“Why do we, as women or girls, (...) assume that we are inferior?” (Participant A) “It doesn't come from nowhere, because no one is born that way. It comes from society.” (Participant C)

This suggests an underlying assumption that transforming the energy sector requires transforming the societal mindset about gender roles and competence, not just implementing internal company policies. Some also recognized that achieving this vision requires the involvement of men as allies and co-creators of a more inclusive sector.

“I believe that we also need men to achieve the kind of society we would like to see in the energy sector, with diversity between women and men and responsibility.” (Participant A)”

Finally, participants assumed that a gender-just energy transformation must also be socially inclusive, involving citizens as active participants rather than passive consumers. They identified low energy literacy as a barrier to this engagement—citizens often do not understand how the energy system works or what their bills mean.

“People do not understand how the energy system works, what is on their bills. But our bills are extremely complicated. That's true. There are 10 pages of different papers.” (Participant F)

“Citizens need motivation; they need to know how knowledge about energy costs can be useful to them” (Participant B).

This reflects a belief that education, transparency, and user-friendly communication are necessary to empower people as energy consumers and prosumers. Thus, gender justice and citizen inclusion were viewed as mutually reinforcing dimensions of a just energy transformation—both requiring cultural, educational, and institutional shifts beyond the technical aspects of the transition itself.

4.2 Challenges

The workshop participants identified a range of structural, cultural, and institutional challenges for the progress toward gender equality in the energy sector. Their reflections reveal that the roots of gender imbalance are deeply embedded in socialization processes, cultural norms, and workplace practices that together create a cycle of exclusion and self-doubt for women and girls.

A first major barrier discussed was the gendered process of socialization, which begins early in childhood and continues through education. Participants observed that girls and boys are taught to occupy different roles, interests, and expectations, which later shape their career trajectories. As one participant explained,

“In fact, it is largely us, as parents or teachers, who instill in them the idea that they are not suited for it, that they do not have the right mindset” (Participant B).

Similarly, *“expectations toward girls and boys are differentiated, boys’ successes are more appreciated, while girls’ merits are overlooked... girls are punished for competing”* (Participant F). These social norms steer girls away from technical or energy-related fields and lead them to internalize notions of inadequacy. As another participant noted, *“in family homes or elsewhere, women are indoctrinated toward certain career paths”* (Participant A).

Participants also emphasized how stereotypes about gender and work reinforce these inequalities, often disguised as benevolent or “soft” biases. As one participant explained,

“These stereotypes sometimes even take the form of supposed privileges for women... boys are told they must earn money, so they’re pushed toward technology or law, while girls are told they can choose something lighter, like philology” (Participant F).

This not only narrows girls’ choices but also contributes to men’s overrepresentation in high-paying and technical fields. The same participant linked this to a broader issue of self-confidence, suggesting that *“men are more self-assured even in areas where they know little, while girls, even when competent, feel uncertain... The technological sector is perceived as highly specialized, which amplifies this insecurity”* (Participant F).

Another challenge identified was the lack of knowledge about opportunities in the energy sector. Young people often do not know what kinds of jobs are available, which roles require technical education, and which do not. As Participant A explained, *“Those choosing their future do not know what professions exist in the energy sector... it’s not only for people with technical backgrounds.”* This information gap prevents girls and women from envisioning themselves in energy-related careers, perpetuating gender segregation.

Within the workplace, participants highlighted gender bias in recruitment and task allocation. One participant shared that women had been screened out during the initial stages of hiring due to perceived lack of competence, but *“when identifying information was removed from applications, women were suddenly invited for interviews and hired”* (Participant C). This example illustrates the persistence of unconscious bias in selection processes. Once hired, women also face gendered divisions of labour, as described by the same participant while reporting a case of an early-career woman colleague: *“When the boss distributes tasks, the guys get all the technical ones, and I get to write the report.”*

A significant structural barrier identified by participants concerns the impact of motherhood and care responsibilities on women’s career progression. The experience of one participant captured this clearly:

“A child means a sudden career slowdown... even if someone returns to work, they don’t get important projects because they might need to take sick leave. I didn’t realize how stressful this was until I experienced it” (Participant F).

In addition, institutional and policy arrangements reinforce this imbalance: *“The state doesn’t support women’s careers—existing mechanisms push them toward caregiving, without strengthening institutional care or men’s engagement”* (Participant A). These gendered expectations create a “care penalty” that discourages women from pursuing leadership roles in the sector.

Finally, some participants pointed to institutional distrust and opacity in the broader energy system, which they viewed as symbolic of exclusionary practices that also affect women’s engagement as citizens or prosumers. As one participant observed, *“People see it as deliberate action by energy companies, so that people don’t appeal or protest... the bill doesn’t have to look like that—it’s ten pages in tiny print. It feels intentional, so that people don’t understand”* (Participant F). This perception of institutional complexity and lack of transparency reinforces low trust and alienation, disproportionately affecting those with less access to technical knowledge, including many women.

Taken together, these reflections illustrate that barriers to gender equality in the energy sector are not only a matter of workplace representation but also reflect deeply rooted societal norms, unequal confidence-building, biased institutional practices, and a lack of structural support for care and inclusion.

4.3 Context

The reflections shared by the workshop participants reveal that the barriers to gender equality in the energy sector are deeply rooted in broader political, social, and cultural structures that shape women’s opportunities, aspirations, and life choices in Poland. These systemic conditions extend beyond the workplace, influencing how gender roles are defined and reproduced across institutions, families, and the labor market.

At the political and institutional level, participants pointed to policy frameworks that reinforce traditional gender roles rather than promoting equal participation in the workforce. As one participant observed,

“Unfortunately, our legislation does not create an incentive for women to want to return to work, because it supports women’s childcare rather than the use of public places where such care could be provided, such as nurseries. Nurseries are not subsidized, new jobs in them are not created... It’s a social, systemic problem.” (Participant A).

This critique highlights how the state’s limited investment in institutional childcare and its continued emphasis on the mother’s role as the primary caregiver create structural disincentives for women’s economic activity. The absence of robust public care infrastructure not only restricts women’s career progression but also normalizes their long-term withdrawal from the labor market after childbirth—an issue particularly visible in sectors like energy, which demand continuity and full-time engagement.

At the cultural level, the participants described a deeply entrenched gender ideology that shapes people’s perceptions of which professions are “appropriate” for women and which are not. This cultural context normalizes occupational segregation and discourages women from entering technical and industrial fields. As one participant reflected,

“Where does this belief come from that there are professions that are not for women? ... I see how many women apply from India, and even though their society still has elements of caste divisions, education there seems to be more equal—if you want, you can study, if you want, you can work in that field.”

Where does this conviction come from in our society that certain fields are not for women?” (Participant B).

This comparison underscores that gendered professional stereotypes are not inevitable but culturally specific-rooted in local traditions, social expectations, and patterns of upbringing rather than natural differences in ability or interest.

Social norms and expectations were also identified as a powerful force shaping women’s professional decisions, even when they possess the qualifications and interest to work in the energy sector. Participant B described a recurring paradox: *“Girls from technical fields come to us for internships, they are good, and then they don’t take the job when they finish their studies... After all, they were just as good as everyone else. And then they don’t come to work.”* This phenomenon was understood as a consequence of both cultural conditioning and structural barriers—young women internalize the message that energy or engineering are “male” domains, and they anticipate difficulties in balancing such demanding careers with expected family responsibilities.

Taken together, these insights portray a wider context marked by conservative gender norms, a lack of supportive social infrastructure, and limited institutional accountability for equality. In such an environment, even when individual women break through educational barriers and gain technical competence, they face a broader social system that subtly directs them away from male-dominated sectors. The participants’ comparisons to other cultural contexts, like India, further reveal that Poland’s gender order is not simply a product of economic development or the specificity of the energy sectoral structure, but rather of persistent cultural narratives about femininity, work, and care. Addressing the gender imbalance in the energy transition, therefore, requires not only sectoral reforms but also a shift in societal values, family practices, and public policy priorities that together sustain gender inequality.

Table 3. Assumption and Contextual Change - TOC for Women in Energy Sector

- The energy industry is socially perceived as more suitable for men than for women.
- Energy law is complex, but it is possible to gain expertise in the energy field.
- Schools and households do not sufficiently foster women’s interest in STEM.
- There is a lack of women in top positions in the energy sector (glass ceiling).
- The energy system is stable and profitable as a professional field.
- Gender conflict can be harmful and counterproductive.
- A career in the energy sector often involves intense competition with men.

5. Pathway of Change: the logical sequence of actions leading to change

5.1 Inputs – What is needed to initiate action?

The starting point for this work was the analysis of existing data and reports concerning the **education curriculum** in relation to the **energy–gender nexus** in schools, as well as

insights gathered from **focus group discussions with students and academic staff** at higher education institutions. These sources helped to identify the fundamental problems related to gender equality in the broadly understood energy sector—covering industry, education, regulatory institutions, public organizations, as well as grassroots civic initiatives and entrepreneurship.

Based on these findings, several key challenges were recognized: lower presence of women in the energy sector, especially in managerial positions; barriers to career development for female employees; limited interest in STEM fields among female pupils; insufficient awareness of discrimination mechanisms; and low levels of energy literacy in society.

To initiate meaningful action, it is essential to strengthen the **starting resources**—namely, **energy literacy, self-awareness**, and a comprehensive **understanding of the importance of gender equality across all sectors of life**. These elements form the basis for empowering individuals, reducing structural inequalities, and fostering inclusive participation in the transition towards a sustainable and equitable energy future.

5.2 Activities – What specific actions will be undertaken?

The suggested activities aim to create lasting change in how women participate and advance within the energy sector. A key focus is on introducing **mentoring programmes** that support women during their studies and the early stages of their careers. By connecting students and young professionals with experienced mentors, these programmes help to strengthen confidence, expand networks, and open pathways toward leadership positions.

Encouraging women to **gain diverse professional experiences**—through internships, research projects, and participation in innovation or international initiatives—will further enhance their skills and visibility within the sector. Such opportunities are essential for building practical expertise and bridging the gap between education and employment.

Another important area of action is **raising awareness of gender stereotypes** and **training teachers** to address and overcome them. Education plays a crucial role in shaping aspirations, and equipping educators with the tools to challenge bias can inspire more girls to pursue STEM and energy-related fields with confidence.

Within organizations, **training for leaders in business and public institutions** will promote gender-sensitive leadership and inclusive management practices. These efforts help create workplaces where equality and diversity are recognized as drivers of innovation and performance.

Sustainable progress also depends on **strengthening the legal and policy framework** supporting gender equality. Introducing or refining regulations ensures that

the principles of inclusion and equal opportunity are embedded structurally across the energy ecosystem.

These interconnected activities aim to build a more inclusive and forward-looking energy sector—one that values women’s expertise, leadership, and active role in shaping the transition toward a sustainable future.

Table 4. Activities - TOC for Women in Energy Sectors

- Implementing mentoring during studies and early stage of career
- Encourage women to get new experience
- Build awareness of gender stereotypes and train teachers to overcome them
- Trainings for leaders in business organisations and public institutions
- Changes in the law supporting gender equality

5.3 Outputs – What will be produced as a result of these actions?

The activities aim to empower women to make informed and ambitious choices in education and career development within the energy sector. As a result, women become more aware of the broad spectrum of opportunities available to them and better prepared to take on leadership roles and responsibility in both academic and professional settings.

By strengthening the ability of individuals and institutions to recognize and respond to gender stereotypes, the initiative promotes more inclusive and supportive learning environments. At the same time, improved corporate and public policies ensure that equality principles are embedded in organizational culture and decision-making.

Ultimately, these changes foster greater confidence and motivation among women to take leading roles in energy communities, start-ups, and other grassroots initiatives, contributing to a more diverse, innovative, and equitable energy transition.

Table 5. Outputs - TOC for Women in Energy in Higher Education

- Women aware of wider spectrum of possibilities when choosing education and career paths
- Women prepared to take leadership and responsibility
- People able to react on the gender stereotypes
- Improved corporate and public policies
- Women more eager to take a lead role in energy communities, start-ups and other grassroots organisations

5.4 Outcomes – Short- and medium-term results

In the short and medium term, the initiatives are expected to lead to a noticeable increase in the number of women enrolling in energy-related higher education programmes and entering the energy sector, including management positions. Strengthened participation and visibility of women will also stimulate the growth of grassroots, transformative initiatives and community-driven projects. As diversity and inclusion expand, the sector will benefit from a broader range of perspectives, resulting in greater creativity and more innovative solutions for the energy transition.

Table 6. Outcomes – short and medium term results

- More women on energy programmes in higher educations
- More women in energy sectors (also in management board)
- More gras roots transformative. initiatives
- More innovations

5.5 Impact – Long-term effect of the change

In the long term, stronger participation and leadership of women in the energy sector will have a tangible impact on the sustainable transition. Their engagement will contribute to more efficient, inclusive, and flexible energy practices, better aligned with social and environmental goals. Ultimately, these developments will support the creation of a more **equal, resilient, and forward-looking society**, where gender balance and sustainability reinforce each other as drivers of lasting change.

Table 7 Impact – Long term effect of the change

- Women impact on sustainable transition
- More efficient and flexible energy practices
- Equal and resilient society

6. Recommendations and Next Steps

Based on the discussions and outcomes of the workshop the following recommendations are proposed. They are grouped into three main dimensions: business and professional development, policy and institutional frameworks, and social and cultural change.

6.1. Business and Professional Development

Mentoring in Business – Establish structured mentoring programs within the energy sector, pairing experienced leaders with young professionals and students. This will

accelerate knowledge transfer, career progression, and confidence-building among women entering the industry.

Cooperation with Schools and Universities – Strengthen partnerships with educational institutions to encourage girls and young women to pursue STEM subjects, with a special focus on energy-related fields.

Gender-Blind Recruitment – Introduce the practice of submitting CVs without gender identifiers as a standard recruitment tool to reduce unconscious bias in hiring.

Women-Centered Conferences – Organize conferences and networking events that highlight women’s success stories in the energy sector, serving both as role models and as platforms for visibility.

Boardroom Parity – Implement policies and internal guidelines that promote gender parity in management boards and supervisory bodies, especially within state institutions and publicly listed companies.

6.2. Policy and Institutional Frameworks

Legal Quotas – Advocate for the introduction of gender quotas in leadership and decision-making positions across the energy sector.

Shared Parental Leave – Promote reforms mandating shared parental leave, with obligatory paternity leave designed to balance childcare responsibilities between men and women.

Inclusive Language – Ensure that job advertisements, position descriptions, and institutional communication employ gender-inclusive language that does not reinforce stereotypes.

Pay Equity – Implement mechanisms for pay transparency and actively work toward eliminating the gender pay gap in energy companies and related institutions.

5.3 Social and Cultural Change

Strengthening the Social Fabric – Support initiatives that build community awareness and social solidarity around gender equality in the workplace and civil engagement.

Women in Politics – Encourage and support women’s entry into political life to ensure that their voices and perspectives are represented in energy policy-making.

Education for Equal Access – Ensure equal access to technical and scientific knowledge at all levels of education, with programs specifically designed to empower girls and women to pursue technical careers.

6.3 Conclusion

The recommendations provided above emphasize that achieving greater participation of women in the energy sector requires multi-dimensional action: from grassroots education to corporate policy, from social awareness campaigns to legislative changes. Progress will depend on the sustained cooperation of businesses, institutions, policymakers, and civil society.

Table 8. Recommendations - TOC for Women in Energy Sectors

- Mentoring in Business
- Cooperation of Business with Schools and Universities
- Gender-Blind Recruitment
- Women-Centered Conferences
- Boardroom Parity
- Legal Quotas
- Shared Parental Leave
- Inclusive Language
- Pay Equity
- Strengthening the Social Fabric
- Women in Politics
- Education for Equal Access

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6.2.3. United Kingdom

UK Academic Women’s Workshop Report (Yara Evans and Rocio Diaz-Chavez)

Theory of Change Designed by UK Academic Women in Energy in Higher Education

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the workshop

The workshop was convened to build a *Theory of Change (TOC) for Greater Participation of Women in Energy in Higher Education (HE)*. This entailed identifying the systemic barriers that limit women’s entry, retention, and progression in teaching and research in energy related issues and formulating measures capable of delivering lasting institutional change. It also entailed exploring how academic institutions can be transformed into inclusive environments that enable women to thrive across all career stages, inspiring and equipping them with the skills and opportunities necessary to build academic careers in energy, develop research, and assume leadership roles in both teaching and scholarly agendas.

The TOC was built through the articulation of pathways for making academia more gender-inclusive and equitable, with particular emphasis on supporting women’s progression into senior academic positions, fostering research leadership in gender-just energy transitions, and enhancing the visibility of women’s expertise in the sector. The TOC also incorporated the design of policy recommendations for recruitment, mentorship, promotion, and governance reforms to help align institutional structures with equity goals for pursuing gender just energy transitions. Grounding these aims in a long-term strategic framework aims to help drive systemic change that extends beyond individual institutions, shaping the norms, priorities, and practices of higher education’s engagement with the energy transition.

The workshop thus sought to generate a shared vision for embedding gender equity into the academic sphere, ensuring that women’s contributions to the energy transition are recognised, valued, and integrated into the core of HE practice. The workshop further aimed at gathering insights for designing an international masterclass on pedagogy and training on gender aspects of the energy transition, but this was not even attempted due to time constraints.

Brief presentation of the participants and context (e.g. sector, project, social issue)

Six academic women participated in the online workshop, held on 5 June from 14:00 to 16:30. They were recruited from staff working at UK universities, as lecturers and researchers on topics and disciplines encompassing energy. Recruitment was through e-mail communication by the two gEneSys partners working at Imperial College/UK, who also moderated the workshop activities. E-mails were sent, over several weeks, to over three dozen female staff at universities across the UK who matched the recruiting criteria. The target aimed for was a sample of eight participants, and while a higher number initially agreed to participate, only six attended in the end.

After the introduction to the workshop activities, introduced themselves, speaking about their academic background, their current work and the links to energy, as well as elaborating on what they understood by ‘energy transition’. Their anonymised profile is summarised in Table 1 (P, for participant, identified by a letter).

Table 1 Participant’s Profile

P	Background	Current Position and Work	Understanding of Energy Transition
A	She trained in Mechanical Engineering in 1981 aiming to contributing to renewable energy and sustainability. Over her career she has worked on a wide range of energy sources and technologies, including biomass, wind, solar, and geothermal, and was an early pioneer in framing transportation as an energy system alongside buildings.	She spent two decades teaching Energy Systems Engineering to mechanical engineers before moving to Heriot-Watt University in Scotland. There, she established the Island Centre for Net Zero, a government-funded initiative that works with communities, companies, and local councils to build capabilities for systemic change in energy use and planning. She is also the author of <i>Transition Engineering</i> .	She understands the energy transition as requiring systemic, ground-up change of existing infrastructures and practices. Rather than importing external solutions, she emphasises equipping communities and organisations with the capability to adapt, change, and actively shape their energy futures ('I actually think that's what we need now is a discipline of the doing of energy transition)'
B	Her expertise lies at the intersection of technology, ethics, and justice, with a particular focus on the role of AI and data practices in serving underserved communities	She is based at the Centre of Computational Science and Mathematical Modelling at Coventry University. Her recent research has moved into the energy sector, working with camp-based refugees in Rwanda and rural host communities. She investigates how renewable energy initiatives can be designed to maximise benefits for both groups, with an emphasis on equity and shared opportunities.	She views the energy transition through the lens of feminism, emphasising the need to foreground the lives of those historically excluded. For her, inclusive co-creation is central: systems must be designed 'with' marginalised groups rather than 'for' them, ensuring that if solutions work for the most disadvantaged, they will work for society as a whole
C	Her background is in energy access and off-grid electrification. Her doctoral research focused on Guatemala and Colombia, examining the relationship between gender and energy access in contexts of electrification	A Research Fellow at the University of Sussex, she is part of the university's Energy Demand Research Centre, where her work now concentrates on decarbonising housing in the UK. This includes case study research on private housing retrofits and energy efficiency upgrades, as well as investigations into community-based initiatives such as "warm spaces" in southern England.	She envisages the energy transition as an opportunity to centre questions of energy wellbeing and to engage with lived energy realities. Her approach foregrounds the social dimensions of transition, emphasising how changes in energy systems affect daily life and community resilience
D	She is originally from Greece and trained as a Chemical Engineer. Since 2007, her professional focus has been on energy from waste, with particular expertise in thermochemical treatments, such as pyrolysis, and calcification, as well as the design of experimental reactors.	After research posts including a period at Imperial College London, she joined the University of Hull in 2014, where she is now an academic leading her own laboratory and research team. Her recent work includes projects on industrial symbiosis, and she also serves as vice-chair of a European Union Action in the energy field.	She thinks of the energy transition as a process that must remain flexible and pragmatic. In her view, reliance on fossil fuels (plan A) cannot be abandoned abruptly; instead, the transition requires alternative strategies (plan B and plan C) to ensure adaptability, resilience, and responsible energy use.
E	A political scientist with a longstanding academic interest in gender and politics. Over time, her research trajectory has moved into the climate and energy space, where she applies a gender lens to questions of policy, participation, and equity.	Based at the Centre for Public Policy at the University of Glasgow, her projects include surveys examining women's underrepresentation in the green energy sector and comparative work on dynamics across fossil fuel and renewable industries. She also conducts research on deliberative democracy, including climate and citizens' assemblies, focusing on their potential to improve inclusion in climate and energy policy processes.	She approaches the energy transition through the lens of gender equity and inclusion. For her, the key concern is how climate and energy policies distribute costs and benefits across society, ensuring they do not reproduce or deepen existing inequalities. She emphasises that women's participation and representation are central to achieving a just and equitable energy transition.
F	She has a long-standing research interest in gender and energy. Her PhD focused on women's empowerment and energy in India, and she subsequently extended this work to study sociotechnical energy transitions in Africa	She is currently a Research Associate at the University of Manchester, working on a project that investigates gender and energy precarity. Her work consistently applies feminist perspectives to the study of energy transitions, with attention to social structures and inequalities.	She views energy transitions as requiring not only technical change but also deep cultural and structural shifts. This includes addressing gender and broader systems of inequality, while fostering resilience and supporting the agency of marginalised groups to develop their own agendas for change.

Source: Online Workshop with UK Academic Women (05/06/2025)

Methodological framework: how Theory of Change was applied during the workshop

No participants had any knowledge of TOC. The moderators introduced the TOC through a power point presentation, explaining its broad aims as a framework, and introducing its various stages and substages, noting the specific guiding questions for each stage. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate some of the key steps and the content for a possible TOC for Greater Participation of Women in Energy in Higher Education. These were shown to participants as a way to help them visualise a TOC and think through the key topics, aims, actions and initiatives when devising the TOC later together in the workshop.

TOC Example for Greater Participation of Women in Energy in HE

Figure 1

Figure 2

2. Description of the Workshop Process

The workshop was carried out online using the Teams platform over a period of two and a half hours with a ten-minute break midway. The workshop entailed undertaking three central activities for building the TOC, through the means of an online visual whiteboard accessed through Teams. The online whiteboard allows for groups to undertake a variety of collaborative and interactive tasks using diverse tools (e.g., writing on stickers) to record their contributions on the whiteboard (<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVIsEocf8=/>).

Participants first worked together on a whiteboard that prompted them to identify current challenges confronting women in energy related programmes in HE education, focusing on issues on entry, progression, retention and institutional practices (Frame 1, in the Appendix). This was followed by work on designing the TOC proper, where the whiteboard prompted participants to focus on the desired twin goals/outcomes of the TOC, namely: 1. Increase women's participation in HE, as students in energy-related programmes and as academic staff; 2. Empower them to contribute to/lead the energy transition. The whiteboard depicted each of the steps of the pathways and intrinsic questions in each, from assumption and context through to impact (Frame 2, in the Appendix). The last whiteboard prompted participants to put forward recommendations to help implement the TOC (Frame 3, in the Appendix). Participants were given ample freedom to speak and work on the different whiteboard frames, commenting and explaining their own contributions, which lead to lively and engaging conversations. The online workshop was video

recorded, so a transcription was obtained of participants' oral contributions which were then anonymised, synthesised and aggregated to the TOC devised whenever feasible. The content of each of the TOC steps is introduced and discussed next, in turn.

3. *Desired Change / Vision of the Goal*

Participants sought to promote structural and cultural change in academia to support greater participation and progression of women in energy-related teaching and research. A central aim was to establish conditions in which women could access, remain, and advance within these fields on an equal basis with men, with equitable opportunities to influence research agendas, teaching content, and leadership decisions. One proposal put forward by one participant and generally accepted was the development of a new *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline, designed from the outset to integrate interdisciplinary, systems-based, and socially responsive perspectives. This new field was envisaged as a space that could be inclusive in its design and practice, attracting a broader range of participants and producing research with direct relevance to societal challenges in the energy transition. In parallel, participants saw the need to strengthen professional networks, mentoring structures, and recruitment practices to reduce isolation and address barriers that disproportionately affect women's career progression in academia.

In addition to disciplinary development, participants called for embedding equity considerations into the standard policies and practices of HE institutions. This included making flexible working arrangements, transparent hiring and promotion processes, and fair workload allocation routine, rather than treating it as exceptional. They also sought to ensure that collaborative, interdisciplinary, and community-engaged work is appropriately recognised in performance evaluations. By fostering an environment in which gender equity is a consistent consideration in decision-making, participants thought it necessary to broaden the diversity of voices contributing to research and policy discussions on the energy transition. Over time, these changes were intended to contribute to a more representative academic workforce, to enrich the scope of research undertaken in energy-related fields, and to strengthen the alignment between higher education, industry needs, and societal priorities, thus helping fully reverse a trend observed by one of the participants at her own institution: *"for us here things are a little bit difficult because it is noticed ... [for] the first time that they're leaving, our women, and we become ... less and less and less in Engineering"* (B).

The envisioned future is a world where women participate fully and equitably in energy-related HE as students, researchers, and leaders. Academic environments would actively support their progression through transparent recruitment, fair workload distribution, and recognition of diverse scholarly contributions. Women's perspectives would help shape research, teaching, and policy on the energy transition, integrating technical expertise with social and environmental considerations. The dismantling of structural barriers and the cultivation of inclusive professional networks would foster collaboration across disciplines and sectors. In such a context, higher education and the energy sector could work in concert to embed gender equity as a cornerstone of innovation and socially responsive energy transitions. Realising this vision requires doing away with undermining behaviours and eradicating entrenched stereotypes about gender capabilities. These dynamics are illustrated in the experience of a senior academic who, despite having already served for five years as Research Director in Chemical Engineering within a prestigious industrial organisation, continued to face challenges to her leadership role: *"A guy from industry was telling me, 'I can't believe that you're a Research Director'. I said, 'Believe it or not, I'm a Research Director!' And then, after the discussion [he said again] 'I still cannot understand how you are a Research*

Director’. And I said, ‘Believe it or not, I’m a Research Director! So, sometimes you have to ... change your character, don’t take things personally, but it is very, very difficult” (D).

The TOC is grounded in values of equity, inclusivity, and social justice, recognising the need to dismantle entrenched cultural and structural barriers that limit women’s participation in energy-related academia. It prioritises creating transparent, supportive career pathways that acknowledge diverse trajectories, including those shaped by caregiving and non-linear progression, as well as changing the ways that career paths are structured, as observed by one participant: “rather than being something ... structured within specific hierarchies and goals and targets that need to be achieved in anyone’s career in order to progress ... that’s something that really needs changing in terms of ... challenging the structures” (F). Central needs include fostering environments where collaboration, mentorship, and interdisciplinary inquiry are valued alongside traditional research outputs; embedding gender-aware and intersectional perspectives into teaching, research, and policy engagement; and building networks that connect women across institutions and sectors. The change also seeks to normalise flexible working, equitable workload allocation, and fair recognition of contributions such as pastoral care and community engagement. Ultimately, it aims to ensure that women’s voices and leadership are integral to shaping energy transitions, thereby aligning academic and sectoral innovation with societal needs and the principles of a just and sustainable future. (The vision is summarised in Table 2)

Table 2 Vision - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Women participate fully and equitably in energy-related higher education as students, researchers, and leaders.

Academic environments enable progression through transparent recruitment, fair workloads, and recognition of diverse contributions.

Women’s perspectives shape research, teaching, and policy on energy transition, integrating technical, social, and environmental insights.

Structural barriers are dismantled and inclusive networks foster collaboration across disciplines and sectors.

Gender equity is embedded as a foundation for innovation and socially responsive energy transitions aligned with societal needs.

4. Assumption and Context

1. Assumption

Participants articulated a shared foundational belief that meaningful transformation for women in academia, particularly in energy-related disciplines, demands the deliberate creation of new intellectual and institutional spaces rather than the incremental adaptation of existing ones. They stressed that prevailing STEM structures remain deeply shaped by male-dominated traditions, perpetuating epistemic and cultural biases that limit the scope for inclusive innovation. A central proposition was the establishment of a new *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline that explicitly integrates feminist principles, systems thinking, and indigenous perspectives from its inception (“the possibility to create a new space and by design to have it be something that brings the female perspective back into the world”; A). This would be intentionally transdisciplinary, embracing non-

linear methodologies and rejecting the narrow, solutionist paradigms often dominant in conventional engineering domains, which are explained by two participants:

“the male dominated view of what engineering is and energy: the word ‘solution’. Try and talk for half an hour with a man or anybody actually about the energy transition without saying the word solution ... ‘it’s just to make a better boiler or something’. And you’re like ‘Yeah, but was the question? If that was the solution, what was the question?’ So, that’s what I mean by solutionism. It’s just this total focus on a gadget being the answer to whatever the question is” (A)

“I work with ... computer scientists and engineers, and I love engineers. They have a special spot in my heart because, but they are ... so solution-driven. When you talk about solutionism, that’s my biggest challenge with them. They think everything is a problem to be fixed, everything. And so sometimes having tried to get them to think differently, it’s like “Oh, well, is that a problem? Can I fix it?” Well, no, there’s some things that you can’t fix. You have to let it kind of sit. You have to sit with uncomfortable, you know, indecision” (B)

The underlying assumption was that inserting more women into structurally exclusionary environments cannot yield systemic equity; instead, structural redesign is necessary to value plural perspectives and alternative knowledge systems. This approach also reflects an understanding that empowerment is highly personal and shaped by intersecting factors such as race, gender, socio-economic background, and disciplinary identity. On the latter, as participant D observed: *“in Mechanical Engineering, traditionally very, very low [number of women] ... the same in Electrical Engineering, but in Chemical Engineering, more women. However, still in disciplines, there are some barriers. For example, a Mechanical Engineer cannot deal with Chemical Engineering” (D).*

The second major assumption emphasised the inadequacy of tokenistic interventions, such as quotas, when these are unaccompanied by broader structural reform. Representation, while necessary, was seen as insufficient to dismantle entrenched hierarchies. Participants stressed that deep cultural transformation must align with institutional changes in recruitment, promotion, and evaluation practices to dismantle exclusionary norms (*“what I’ve noticed is that it’s easier for men to have research only contracts rather than women, and this has to do with who is making the decisions ... who[ever] is making the panels up there don’t have the appropriate representation of female way of thinking ... [to break the] glass ceiling ... how to get to the top and have more women in order to have a balance”*; D). They highlighted the need to address gendered cultural patterns within academia, including the privileging of male-oriented leadership models and performance metrics. Central to this vision was committed leadership at both institutional and national levels; without sustained endorsement and modelling of inclusive practices by senior leaders, even the most progressive proposals risk remaining aspirational. This leadership dimension was not simply about authority but about the willingness to redistribute power, create opportunities, and legitimise alternative epistemologies.

The context in which these assumptions were situated was one of both opportunity and constraint. On the opportunity side, participants referenced policy developments in other countries, such as feminist-informed energy strategies in Spain, as evidence that systemic inclusion can be advanced through deliberate design. They also noted enabling signals from professional bodies as a potential legitimising force for innovative academic spaces (e.g., the Royal Academy of Engineering’s recognition of emerging disciplines). On the constraint side, they observed that entrenched masculine disciplinary cultures, narrow definitions of excellence, and persistent structural biases continue to resist transformation (*“a myopic view of energy, and it is the male view”*; A). Such

constraints are compounded by a lack of critical mass for women in certain technical fields, intensifying isolation and limiting their influence within networks and decision-making forums. As participant D considered: *“Have you ever seen a ULT [University Learning and Teaching] team, let's say, which is made by 80% females? No! ... Also, it's not enough to have one strong person at the top ... the problem is that there are not many women at the top” (D).*

Against this backdrop, participants envisioned the co-design of new disciplines and professional networks as a proactive strategy to reshape both academia and the energy field into more socially responsive domains. They stressed that if such spaces are deliberately inclusive from inception, they could act as models of how academic structures can evolve to embed equity as a structural feature, rather than as an add-on. This would require aligning institutional policies, values, and funding frameworks with inclusive principles, fostering environments where diverse contributions are recognised as central to technical excellence. Moreover, the deliberate formation of networks would help consolidate critical mass, enabling women to act collectively in influencing policy agendas and research priorities, although this would probably come up against entrenched assumptions regarding women's roles and capabilities (*“groups of women getting together really freak people out ... I mean, literally!”*; A). This vision rests on the belief that structural innovation, rather than piecemeal adaptation, is the most credible and promising pathway to fully realising women's potential in shaping both the academic landscape and the energy transition.

2. Challenges

Participants repeatedly emphasised that many of the barriers confronting women working in academia today remain strikingly similar to those reported in the 1980s, highlighting a lack of transformative progress in gender equity and equality in energy-related programmes (*“they are the same as they were in the 1980s ... we were thinking that there aren't many women ... it doesn't look like a place where women would go because there aren't women there ... a chicken and egg circular problem”*; A). The entrenched perception of STEM as a masculine domain continues to deter women particularly those inclined toward interdisciplinary, systems-oriented, or socially engaged approaches (*“we have won a lot of funding for women in STEM ... half of our students are female, we can't retain them ... they continually go into industry ... we just can't recruit them back into academia ... they don't want to be academics ... they want to go into industry”*; B). Fields with overtly militaristic or narrowly technical applications were viewed as especially uninviting to some women's interests or values in academia (*“as a complex thinker and systems thinker, why would I want to spend my time making weapons and widgets?”*; A). These narratives are reinforced by recruitment and promotion practices that often replicate the composition and cultural norms of dominant male groups. The absence of concerted efforts to redefine disciplinary identity and appeal means that these exclusionary patterns persist, limiting the diversity of talent entering and remaining in the field.

Structural barriers, rooted in wider societal power dynamics also played a central role in deterring women from working in energy fields within and beyond academia, with some interventions seen as tokenistic, as participant E elaborates at length:

“it all has to do with these ... well-entrenched power dynamics ... it's like adding in a little drip here... a little drip there... and there is nobody doing anything to change those power dynamics. And something that I've come up against a lot in my work around these issues is that when it comes to ... the power holders ... like policymakers, government strategies, there's plenty of worry and energy paid to the workforce deficits that are going to be preventing an energy transition from taking place.

These ... massive workforce deficits ... There's such a lack of women in these in these sectors, not so specifically higher education, necessarily, but in various sectors. Some of them have numbers. Some of them don't have numbers. We don't even know how big the gap is. But there's no connection at all being made about how that inequality is fuelling the workforce deficits ... we're not connecting the dots that those deficits could be addressed by bringing more women into these jobs ... if those connections aren't made ... it feels like ... tokenistic ... there's not enough women ... we have barely any women” (E)

Cultural biases also intersect with structural inequities in ways that deeply shape women’s academic experiences. Institutions frequently undervalue research that is collaborative, interdisciplinary, or community-engaged, favouring narrow definitions of excellence that privilege individualistic and technical outputs. Career pathways remain rigid, assuming uninterrupted trajectories that are incompatible with maternity leave, caregiving, or other non-linear life courses (“they don’t take into consideration ... changing circumstances that are actually gendered ... because of the structure of society ... [to make] career paths a little more flexible and adaptable to [accommodate] people’s lives and circumstance”; F). Short-term contracts heighten job insecurity, constraining long-term planning and limiting the scope for ambitious, high-risk research (“are you going to stay in a contract that’s going to last [only] nine months?”; B). Women are also disproportionately burdened with administrative responsibilities and pastoral care, often justified by gendered assumptions about competence in such roles (“we’re women, we’re mothers, the secretaries, we are pastoral care ... and this is ... not valued anywhere, it is not recognised ... still we’re ... the secretaries, the waitresses during our meetings”; D). This allocation of labour diverts time and resources from research outputs that carry greater weight in promotion criteria, entrenching disparities in advancement. As participant A illustrates: “I just mentored a young colleague. And I said, ‘Look, I will go talk to your Head of Department if you want’, because I see this every single time. They get given double the teaching load. They get given these pastoral things ... and she's just working so much more. And ... even if you have very active research, you get penalised because you're doing all the teaching” (A). Participant B concurred: “the teaching load ... makes it very difficult to do research ... I think the system isn't agile enough [to recognise] that teaching is very heavy ... it's really heavy and student demands are very heavy ... I can see why people get sort of stuck in that, you know, ‘can't publish’ ... and if you've got caring responsibilities ... I don't know what you do. I think you must give up sleep” (B).

The lack of critical mass in certain disciplines and departments compounds these barriers, intensifying professional isolation and reducing access to mentorship, peer support, and collective advocacy (“I’m the only female member of staff at my centre”; B). In such contexts, women may find themselves navigating professional spaces without allies. One participant explained how she addresses this: “Well, there's a strategy I came up with a long time ago, which there are men who can be anointed as honorary females. They, you know, they're wired a little differently. And if you can find one of those and, you know, partner with them, then you can work up, say, solutions for a problem the department's working on or something and, you know, work with them and then have them present it because then it'll be heard ... And if that person stands next to you and defers to you even once, then everything changes. This sort of Don Quixote and their ... friend, right? I hate to say it, but I got to get things done” (A). Sometimes women encounter unsupportive or hostile attitudes even from other women in senior positions (“when you get a woman who gets to the ... pro-vice chancellor or executive dean level or something like that, the propensity that they will be super hard on any women under them is shocking”; A). Intersectional barriers remain particularly acute for

women from racial and ethnic minorities, who may face compounded discrimination based on gender, race, and other identity markers which certain interventions may still not help bring down (“so, there were ideas of EDI ... giving some extra scholarships or things to attract women, but not attracting women to the same thing, and so, I don't think that's what worked ... the challenge is changing the field”; A). These intersecting challenges not only constrain individual career trajectories but also diminish the diversity of perspectives available to address complex challenges in the energy transition. Without structural reforms that account for both gendered and intersectional dynamics, institutional cultures risk perpetuating exclusionary norms under the guise of formal equity policies (“we pride ourselves on ... the appearance of being more equal ... but when I got into academia, I found that it was far more insidious ... it was far less about misogyny, but it underpins [it] still”; B).

3. Context

The broader social, political, and economic context frames these institutional challenges. Socially, entrenched gender norms continue to shape perceptions of capability, suitability, and belonging within technical fields, reinforcing feelings of exclusion among women in male-dominated environments. Politically, examples such as Spain's feminist-informed energy policies illustrate what is possible when political will aligns with equity goals, yet such approaches remain rare (“in Spain now there is a there is a law that, I'm not sure I think it's passed already, that is actually looking into incrementing and implementing feminist principles into energy transitions ... I think Sweden as well ... is doing the same thing”; F). Economically, the academic employment landscape is marked by precarity, intense competition for funding, and risk-averse management. As one participant elucidated: “We know that consistently women and ethnic minorities do not lead big [funding] bids. We lead smaller bids, but energy bids are invariably large bids ... in order to get a large bid, you have to win smaller bids ... and I'm not sure why women aren't leading these 10-million-pound projects ... Is it because they're making active choices not to? Is it because there isn't the critical mass of women to lead? Is it because they'd rather lead on a five-million-pound bid and ... because of their other responsibilities? I think that hasn't been uncovered ... it's very easy to say, “well, they lack ambition”; B). Such challenges disproportionately disadvantage women, particularly those whose careers include interruptions for caregiving, and these structural and cultural dynamics are self-reinforcing too: the insecurity and conservatism of the academic system limit the potential for innovation, while the absence of diverse leadership perpetuates inequitable norms. (Table 3 summarises the central issues assumption and context)

Table 3 Assumption and Context - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Structural redesign is required: inserting women into exclusionary systems is insufficient without creating new, inclusive academic and disciplinary spaces.

Tokenistic measures such as quotas are inadequate without deep institutional and cultural transformation in recruitment, promotion, and evaluation.

Prevailing STEM cultures, marked by solutionism and masculine norms, marginalise alternative knowledge systems, feminist perspectives, and intersectional approaches.

Systemic barriers, rigid career paths, continue to reproduce inequalities, undervaluing of teaching/pastoral work, precarity, and lack of critical mass, .

The wider context of entrenched gender norms, policy experiments, and structural precarity in academia frames both opportunities and constraints for change.

5. Pathway of Change: the logical sequence of actions leading to change

5.1 Inputs – What is needed to initiate action?

Initiating meaningful change towards women’s greater participation and progression in energy-related academia demands a combination of structural reform, leadership commitment, and cultural redesign. Central to this vision is the creation of new intellectual and professional spaces that are inclusive from their inception, most notably through the establishment of a Systems Transition Engineering discipline. This was proposed by participant A, who has already been working to mould such kinds of spaces, as she explained in detail:

“I've helped to create this field. I've written the book on it ... there's another way to look at it, we could make a long list of all the things, all the properties and all the benefits of this other way. And it would be the transdisciplinary ground-up, household-based, wellness-based. It would just make the make the big word salad of the things that you want and then say, is there any way that we could get that from the existing disciplines of energy engineering? Whether you're talking chemical, civil, mechanical. And the answer is no! So, let's create a new trans-discipline that is in an intersection of all those and social science. And, you know, it can move around. It's it really is a true trans-discipline. And let's build it so that it takes the perspective that will achieve these things. And so that's what I've been doing ... Sort of opening up this little portal into a different future. ... I've been given this little space to create a programme and to build a research centre around that ... I will look for this convergence effect, this way of going out and finding the people who have been thinking the same thing I've been thinking for the last 30 years ... So if we can find each other, we can actually create this this new way of looking at things. And when we start working that way, we will create amazing new benefits that then will be understood and recognised. But ... like I said, it's not only women. It's just there's a lot of women in this space, if we can find each other”.

Participants argued that such a field should be deliberately designed to attract and retain diverse participants, free from the entrenched biases of existing male-dominated and grounded in intersectionality, systems thinking, and social justice. The proposal rests on the belief that innovation in the energy transition requires trans-disciplinarity, bringing together technical, social, and policy perspectives in a way that values plural forms of knowledge (*“I have four female PhD students and lots of female colleagues from all across the university in different disciplines. We can see how intersection works. And I'm not recruiting women [only]. I'm not looking for women. I am creating the space within which the female perspective on how to deal with wicked problems and challenges and stuff can actually be used. And our ability to think transdisciplinary early. The men struggle with it”*; A). National-level leadership buy-in was considered essential for legitimising this discipline, securing resources, and establishing a robust foundation for its growth.

Beyond disciplinary innovation, participants stressed the importance of building professional networks that actively counteract the isolation often experienced by women in energy-related academia (*“for us, it's all about the networks you have”*; A), although that also requires overcoming certain barriers (*“in order to lead large [funding] bids, you need networks, you need to have those connections, and in order to have those connections, you need space to cultivate them ... there are times where I look and I think because of the caring responsibilities I have, I can't take out a week to go to a conference or I can't give up that time”*; B). In many institutions, women remain disconnected from peers who share their research interests, values, and perspectives. This lack of critical mass undermines opportunities for mentorship, skill-sharing, and collective advocacy. A reimagined network structure could connect academics across departments, institutions, and national

boundaries, fostering sustained knowledge exchange, the co-creation of research agendas, and more visible pathways into leadership roles. Such networks would not only amplify women’s voices within the sector but also increase their influence over strategic research directions.

For these networks to succeed, inclusivity must be embedded by design. Participants underscored the need to avoid reproducing the exclusionary cultures of existing academic and professional associations (“we need a culture where ... women can thrive rather than survive”; B). Alternative modes of engagement (e.g., informal, non-hierarchical, and empathetic), were seen as critical for enabling trust, collaboration, and mutual support. Such spaces would accommodate diverse working styles, career pathways, and research outputs, and would be co-designed with participants to ensure relevance and accessibility. This approach aligns with a broader institutional shift towards empathetic and inclusive values, moving beyond the reductive aim of ‘more women doing the male thing’ towards a model where women’s contributions help redefine disciplinary priorities and practices. As participant E explained about prevailing practices: “when you don't have a change in any sort of system, women who rise to the top have to be like men ... a lot of the time it's just a masculine trope that. And so, it's not only about that woman maybe using masculine tropes to get to a certain place, but, like, that's the reason a lot of these people make it to the top. It's like you only make it to the top if you act like a man ... you're getting put forward because you act like them”).

Complementary to these structural and cultural initiatives are targeted measures to support women’s individual progression and foster positive role models rooted in personal growth (“there are many issues that we need strong role models [for], and whoever decides to be up there, they must be strong, they need to be strong. But, of course, we sacrifice many things in order to do this”; D). Participants identified the need for training to boost confidence in high-pressure environments, clarity in career progression pathways, and access to coaching and mentoring. Opportunities for shadowing senior or mid-career staff were highlighted as valuable for developing leadership capacity. Recognising the intersection between gender and health (particularly in relation to menopause) was seen as essential, with calls for training, awareness, and supportive institutional policies. Normalising flexible working arrangements for all staff, rather than treating them as exceptions, was presented as a vital step in making academic careers compatible with diverse life circumstances. Together, these measures would create an enabling environment in which structural reform, cultural change, and individual empowerment reinforce one another. (Table 4 summarises the key actions)

Table 4 Inputs - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Establish new inclusive disciplines designed from inception to integrate intersectionality, systems thinking, and social justice.

Secure national-level leadership commitment and resources to legitimise and sustain structural innovation in academia.

Build professional networks that counter isolation, enable mentorship, and strengthen women’s collective influence over research agendas.

Embed inclusive and empathetic cultures in networks and institutions, rejecting masculine tropes and valuing diverse career paths and knowledge forms.

Provide targeted individual supports (role models, mentoring, leadership training, health and wellbeing awareness, flexible working) to foster women’s progression without personal sacrifice.

5.2 Activities – What specific actions will be undertaken?

To translate the identified inputs into transformative change, participants proposed a set of strategic and mutually reinforcing actions. Foremost among these was the creation of a flagship programme hosted by a leading university to co-design a proposal for a *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline. This initiative would bring together women from across leading institutions in a convergent, interdisciplinary process, ensuring that diverse technical, social, and policy perspectives are embedded from the outset. The explicit backing of influential experts, such as the President of the Royal Academy of Engineering, was identified as critical for lending legitimacy, overcoming institutional resistance, and securing a place for the new discipline in the academic landscape. The co-design process itself was envisioned as an exercise in inclusive governance, ensuring that the epistemological foundations of the discipline reflect a plurality of voices and experiences.

Parallel to disciplinary innovation, targeted mentorship programmes were prioritised as a means of addressing the structural and cultural barriers women face in energy-related academia. These programmes would offer structured support for early career researchers, providing them with guidance on navigating academic culture, building research portfolios, and advancing along clear career progression pathways. By fostering intergenerational solidarity, mentoring schemes would help to counteract the isolation that often accompanies being one of few women or the only woman in a department or research group. In addition, such schemes could create reciprocal learning opportunities, whereby senior academics are also exposed to new perspectives and evolving challenges within the sector.

Participants also articulated the need for activities aimed at embedding feminist-informed principles into institutional policies, research agendas, and everyday academic practices. This would involve developing curricula and training programmes that foreground gender equity, intersectionality, and systems thinking in energy-related disciplines, thereby normalising inclusive perspectives in both technical and non-technical contexts. Leadership engagement was considered essential, with proposed actions including structured dialogues between decision-makers and underrepresented groups, leadership training with an equity lens, and institutional audits of hiring, promotion, and fair workload allocation practices. These interventions were intended not only to address structural imbalances but also to catalyse broader cultural change.

Complementing these efforts, public engagement and network-building activities were seen as vital to shifting narratives and amplifying the contributions of women in energy research. Suggested actions included outreach campaigns, collaborations with civil society organisations, the creation of digital platforms for peer support, and the organisation of cross-disciplinary workshops and conferences designed to elevate underrepresented voices. By integrating curriculum reform, leadership engagement, mentorship, and public engagement, participants envisioned a coordinated strategy capable of disrupting entrenched norms and fostering an academic environment where women's participation and leadership are not exceptional but expected. (Table 5 summarises the activities)

Table 5 Activities - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Co-design a flagship Systems Transition Engineering discipline through a leading university programme, embedding diverse technical, social, and policy perspectives with high-level expert backing.

Establish targeted mentorship programmes to support early-career researchers, foster intergenerational solidarity, and provide reciprocal learning opportunities.

Embed feminist-informed principles in curricula, training, and institutional policies, including audits of hiring, promotion, and workload allocation.

Engage leadership in equity-focused actions, such as structured dialogues, inclusive training, and accountability mechanisms for cultural and structural change.

Promote public engagement and network-building through outreach, civil society collaborations, digital platforms, and cross-disciplinary events that amplify underrepresented voices.

5.3 Outputs – What will be produced as a result of these actions?

Participants envisaged that the proposed activities would yield a series of tangible, high-impact outputs capable of reshaping both the culture and the practice of energy-related academia. Foremost among these would be the establishment of innovative courses designed to equip students and professionals with the capabilities needed to address complex, ‘wicked’ problems in the energy transition. These courses would be academically rigorous yet rooted in interdisciplinary, systems-based approaches, enabling them to remain responsive to evolving societal, environmental, and technological challenges. In doing so, they would model a form of education that integrates technical expertise with inclusive values and critical perspectives.

A cornerstone of these outputs would be the formal creation of the *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline, built from its inception to prioritise diversity, collaboration, and transdisciplinary thinking. The discipline’s epistemological foundations would embed gender equity and intersectionality as central organising principles, ensuring that the knowledge produced reflects a plurality of perspectives. Research generated within this space would aim to be distinct from conventional outputs, producing transformative insights and solutions that deliver demonstrable benefits to communities, industry, and policymakers. The novelty and perceived societal benefit of this work would position the discipline as an attractive partner for industry, fostering collaborations that could amplify both its impact and visibility.

Beyond curriculum and research innovation, participants anticipated the emergence of concrete institutional reforms as key outputs. This would include the adoption of transparent recruitment and promotion processes, equitable workload allocation systems, and formalised mechanisms to address bias and discrimination. Such reforms would be codified in institutional policy documents, equality action plans, and progress reports, providing visible evidence of change and offering transferable templates for replication elsewhere. The presence of clear documentation would serve not only as proof of commitment but also as a resource for other institutions seeking to undertake similar transformations.

The outputs would also encompass the establishment of robust professional networks and mentoring schemes specifically designed to support women’s advancement in energy-related disciplines. This could include digital platforms for collaboration, recurring conferences and

symposia with equitable representation, and case studies showcasing successful women-led initiatives. Public engagement campaigns and cross-sectoral collaborations (with industry, policymakers, and civil society) were seen as additional outputs that could help reframe public narratives about gender and energy. Together, these deliverables would serve as both proof of concept and enduring structures that normalise inclusive practices, creating a self-sustaining ecosystem in which diversity is embedded at every level of academic and professional activity. Such networks would provide alternative, inclusive and enabling spaces, that contrast with prevailing ones, as explained by participant B: “we go to these conferences ... [where] a lot of the ‘after’ socialising is done ... I don't drink ... so, when the conference is finished, I go back to my hotel room, and I work ... a lot of the socialising ... that's done in spaces that I choose not to enter ... the argument is, well, I could go. Yes, I could go. But I'm choosing. I noticed that ... in our centre, which is very diverse, we have a lot of people from South Asia who are Muslims. They're having to do the same ... And I can't help thinking, is there some kind of pattern here that we're not in these social spaces?” (Table 6 summarises the outputs).

Table 6 Outputs - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Innovative interdisciplinary courses designed to equip students and professionals with the skills to address complex ‘wicked’ problems in the energy transition.

Formal creation of Systems Transition Engineering as a new discipline embedding diversity, collaboration, gender equity, and intersectionality in its epistemological foundations.

Institutional reforms codified in policy, including transparent recruitment, equitable workload allocation, and mechanisms to address bias and discrimination.

Robust professional networks and mentoring schemes (digital platforms, conferences, case studies) to support women’s advancement and leadership in energy-related academia.

Public engagement campaigns and cross-sector collaborations to reframe narratives on gender and energy and create inclusive, self-sustaining academic and professional ecosystems.

5.4 Outcomes – Short- and medium-term results

In the short to medium term, participants anticipated that the implementation of new approaches and institutional structures, particularly through the creation of the *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline, would demonstrate the tangible benefits of rethinking academic practice in energy-related fields. By moving beyond the historically narrow, male-dominated framing of energy, often centred on purely technical or market-driven logics, the discipline would foreground holistic, socially embedded perspectives that integrate technical, environmental, and socio-political dimensions. This reorientation was expected to reshape both research agendas and teaching content, expanding the field’s capacity to address household-level energy issues and the complex interdependencies between social and engineering systems.

The discipline’s early success would be measured by its ability to embed these alternative perspectives into mainstream academic practice, serving as a model for other fields. Participants viewed it as a critical platform for integrating diverse systems (social, environmental, and technical) into coherent frameworks capable of addressing the multifaceted challenges of the energy

transition. Over time, the discipline was expected to emerge as an influential voice in both academic and policy debates, offering robust evidence of how gender-inclusive and intersectional approaches produce richer, more effective solutions. These early achievements would serve not only to validate women’s leadership but also to build the case for structural and cultural reforms across academia.

Beyond the outputs themselves, participants envisaged deeper behavioural and cultural shifts as essential medium-term outcomes. They anticipated a measurable increase in the participation of women as students, lecturers, and researchers, reflecting both more inclusive recruitment strategies and the cultivation of a supportive academic climate. Such gains were intended to extend across lines of race, ethnicity, class, and disciplinary background, ensuring that intersectional representation becomes a defining feature of the field. Over time, this diversification would strengthen the intellectual and methodological range of energy research, enabling more innovative and socially relevant outputs. Indeed, acknowledging and addressing the diversity of gender-based intersectional experiences was imperative, as participant B argued: *“I was just thinking, you know, we talk as a woman is a universal category, but of course, that's not true ... if you're a woman of colour or you have a disability ... there are women who do have advantages and are not encountering the same levels of discrimination as other women. And I think we assume then that all women encounter the same discrimination, but different fields as well have different levels of discrimination ... I was just looking at the figures the other day ... on who's a Mechanical Engineer, but they are very few women in that field and consistently, whereas in other forms of engineering, there are more women. So even within fields of science, there are different ... kind of levels ... different forms of discrimination they encounter”*.

Equally important was the normalisation of inclusive leadership and decision-making processes. Participants envisioned governance structures in which women, including those from underrepresented groups, would play a central role in setting institutional priorities, mentoring emerging scholars, and modelling equitable practice. This shift would be accompanied by a mainstreaming of interdisciplinary and feminist-informed research, embedding systems thinking and cross-sectoral collaboration as core academic norms. As these practices became established, the field’s capacity to generate policy-relevant, socially attuned research would expand, enhancing the reputational standing of inclusive energy research and attracting further talent, funding, and institutional investment. (Table 7 summarises the outcomes)

Table 7 Outcomes - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

New disciplinary models demonstrate benefits, with Systems Transition Engineering embedding holistic, socially embedded perspectives that reshape research agendas and teaching content.

Inclusive frameworks validated, integrating social, environmental, and technical systems to address complex energy transition challenges and influence academic and policy debates.

Increased participation of women as students, lecturers, and researchers across intersecting identities (race, class, ethnicity, discipline), strengthening diversity and representation.

Cultural and behavioural shifts achieved through supportive climates, intersectional awareness, and more innovative, socially relevant outputs.

Inclusive leadership and governance normalised, with women in decision-making roles mainstreaming feminist-informed, interdisciplinary approaches and enhancing the reputation and reach of energy research.

4. 5.5 Impact – Long-term effect of the change

In the long term, participants envisioned that the establishment and maturation of the *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline would catalyse a fundamental transformation in how energy transitions are conceived, implemented, and evaluated (“*the impact we need to have is accelerated energy transition ... if the participation of women creates that impact, then we’ll have actually [achieved it]*”; A). By embedding gender-inclusive, intersectional, and socially responsive methodologies at its core, the discipline would not merely adapt existing structures but redefine the epistemological and cultural foundations of the field. This transformation would dismantle the inertia of ‘business as usual’ approaches, replacing them with convergent, transdisciplinary practices that respond to complex socio-technical challenges with innovation and equity at the forefront. Such a transformation was expected to deliver sustained benefits across multiple domains. Within academia, it would establish new benchmarks for excellence and inclusion, challenging entrenched hierarchies and diversifying the profile of those in leadership and decision-making roles. The proportion of women in senior academic and research positions would rise significantly, with these leaders actively shaping curricula, research priorities, and institutional cultures to reflect principles of inclusivity and justice. In turn, this would reinforce a cycle of attraction and retention, drawing more women and underrepresented groups into energy-related disciplines. Participant C noted, for instance, the positive impacts of working at a place that values inclusion: “*I feel like I’m really lucky to be part of a research centre where there is a real focus on inclusion. And I’m from a female lead who is very much about fore fronting that and those kind of values. And I think that that’s been really refreshing. And I feel, you know, it’s quite a contrast to what I hear within academia sometimes and from what my friends have experienced. So, it’s like ... a meeting starting with checking on people’s well-being or, you know, if the timings were right for people’s other commitments, that kind of thing*”.

A parallel dimension of impact lies in the restructuring of disciplinary norms and evaluative frameworks. Institutions would adopt success metrics that value collaborative, interdisciplinary, and socially engaged research alongside traditional markers of scholarly achievement. This shift would validate the integration of feminist, intersectional, and systems-based perspectives into

technical and policy work, demonstrating that diverse knowledge systems are essential for tackling the ‘wicked problems’ of the energy transition. Over time, such reorientation would strengthen the legitimacy, relevance, and public impact of energy-related research, both within academic circles and in wider policy and industry debates.

Beyond the boundaries of academia, the societal reach of this transformation could be considerable. Graduates trained in inclusive, interdisciplinary environments would enter industry, government, and civil society with the skills, critical perspectives, and collaborative mindsets needed to drive equitable and sustainable energy transitions. Their work would inform policy frameworks, technological innovations, and infrastructure projects that are more responsive to the needs of diverse communities, including those historically marginalised. Over time, such changes could advance equitable energy access, enhance the sustainability of infrastructure, and increase public trust in the energy sector’s ability to serve the collective interest. (Table 8 summarises the impact, whilst Figure 3 illustrates the key stages of the TOC)

Table 8 Impact - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Fundamental transformation of energy transitions, with Systems Transition Engineering redefining epistemological and cultural foundations through gender-inclusive, intersectional, and socially responsive practices.

New benchmarks for excellence and inclusion in academia, increasing the proportion of women and underrepresented groups in senior leadership and reshaping institutional cultures.

Restructured disciplinary norms and evaluative frameworks, valuing collaborative, interdisciplinary, and socially engaged research alongside traditional metrics.

Broader societal impact, as graduates trained in inclusive, interdisciplinary environments influence policy, industry, and civil society with equity-oriented approaches.

Advances in equitable energy access and sustainability, strengthening public trust in energy systems and ensuring transitions serve diverse communities and collective interests.

Figure 3

6. Indicators of Success

Participants identified a range of both quantitative and qualitative indicators to measure progress towards the transformative vision articulated in the TOC. Quantitatively, success would be reflected in sustained increases in the representation of women across all stages of academic careers in energy-related disciplines, from undergraduate enrolment to senior leadership positions. Disaggregated data would capture gains not only for women overall but also for those from underrepresented racial, ethnic, and socio-economic groups, ensuring that progress is genuinely intersectional rather than benefiting only the most privileged. Improvements in recruitment, retention, and progression rates would serve as clear evidence that structural barriers to entry and advancement are being dismantled.

On the qualitative side, indicators would focus on visible and sustained shifts in institutional culture and everyday academic experiences. This includes the normalisation of flexible working arrangements for all staff, ensuring that such practices are embedded rather than treated as exceptional accommodations (“there’s this lack of normalisation of flexible working, which I think if it was more of a norm that everybody did it ... when I wasn’t in academia, I worked for a company...we had our core hours, and everybody had the flexibility around that ... and so, we had all of our meetings during that time ... and I think that just sets up a much more ... kind of level playing field ... I thought that that was helpful”; D). The routine presence of gender-balanced and diverse hiring panels, reductions in the disproportionate assignment of administrative and pastoral workloads to women, and improved access to mentorship and sponsorship from senior colleagues would signal

meaningful change. Positive feedback from staff and students, captured through surveys, interviews, and focus groups, would reflect the development of a more inclusive and equitable academic climate in which discrimination is actively challenged and marginalised voices are heard and valued.

To operationalise these indicators, participants implied the necessity for systematic, longitudinal data collection at both institutional and sectoral levels. This could involve compiling gender-disaggregated statistics on recruitment, promotion, and retention, alongside documenting case studies that illustrate shifts in pedagogy, research priorities, and collaborative practices. Qualitative documentation would be essential for capturing more subtle yet critical cultural changes, such as evolving norms of leadership, increased interdisciplinarity, and the integration of intersectional perspectives into research design. Such evidence would enable ongoing evaluation and adaptive learning, ensuring that strategies remain responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities.

At the broader sectoral and societal levels, further indicators would capture the extent to which inclusive academic practices influence industry, policy, and civil society. Evidence of collaborative research initiatives, interdisciplinary partnerships, and policy changes informed by feminist and intersectional approaches would demonstrate the diffusion of these practices beyond academia. Over time, alignment between energy transition strategies and principles of equity and social justice would indicate that inclusivity has become a recognised driver of innovation and resilience, not merely a peripheral aspiration. These long-term indicators would also provide a feedback loop, sustaining momentum and reinforcing the legitimacy of the *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline as both a technical and social innovation. (Table 9 summarises the indicators)

Table 9 Indicators of Success - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Quantitative progress: sustained increases in women's representation across all academic career stages, with disaggregated data to ensure intersectional gains.

Structural improvements: measurable advances in recruitment, retention, and progression rates, evidencing the dismantling of barriers to entry and advancement.

Cultural shifts: normalisation of flexible working, gender-balanced hiring panels, fair workload distribution, and improved access to mentorship and sponsorship.

Qualitative feedback: staff and student surveys, interviews, and case studies reflecting inclusive climates, challenged discrimination, and recognition of diverse voices.

Sectoral influence: evidence of inclusive academic practices shaping industry, policy, and civil society, aligning energy transition strategies with equity and social justice.

7. Recommendations and Next Steps

Motivating women to enter and remain in academia with energy-related content

Participants stressed that senior leaders who 'get it' must actively deploy their influence to open pathways for women to study, teach, and research in energy-related fields. Two mechanisms were identified as central to this process: first, the creation of opportunities for like-minded individuals to find each other and converge their ideas; second, the establishment of sustained support systems for young pioneers once they emerge. The launch of a new *Systems Transition Engineering* discipline was regarded as a particularly powerful motivator, offering an intellectually exciting and socially impactful subject area that breaks from business-as-usual topics, often entrenched in male-dominated perspectives. Such a discipline would also provide the framework for building inclusive

networks that counteract the current dispersal of energy systems transition thinkers across disparate disciplines. Participants underscored the importance of networking spaces that are intentionally inclusive and alternative to conventional, often exclusionary, professional venues. These recommendations take on added significance amid growing concerns about workforce deficit, the persistent underrepresentation of women, and the recognition that homogeneous perspectives in energy systems limit innovation and responsiveness to societal needs.

Boosting women's progression in academia

The proposed discipline was widely viewed as a 'clean slate' for women's progression, an opportunity to establish fresh benchmarks and leadership roles unburdened by the legacy biases of older fields. Participants referenced the case of Biomedical Engineering, where a relatively recent establishment and healthcare orientation have helped create a female-majority field, suggesting that disciplines free from entrenched exclusionary cultures can be inherently more attractive to women. Designing the new field from the outset to be different to appeal to young women, offer equitable entry points, reject narrow "solutionist" approaches, and validate diverse perspectives was seen as essential. This would include embedding systems thinking and transdisciplinary integration as core features, as well as creating visible platforms to demonstrate the outcomes of inclusive practices. By doing so, the discipline would legitimise women's leadership not as an exception, but as a central component of its identity and success.

Building long-term institutional and cultural support

For the TOC to result in sustainable transformation, institutions must embed inclusivity into their structures, values, and operational processes. This entails implementing mentoring frameworks, inclusive leadership development initiatives, and recruitment practices that proactively address bias. Institutional values should be co-designed, empathetic, and inclusive, ensuring that equity is treated as a standard expectation rather than an optional enhancement. Policy reforms are also essential, including normalising flexible working arrangements, strengthening family-friendly provisions, and addressing intersectional challenges through targeted measures. Furthermore, redefining metrics of academic success to value mentorship, community engagement, and interdisciplinary collaboration alongside publications and grant income would support a broader and fairer conception of excellence. The Systems Transition Engineering discipline could function as a living laboratory for such institutional transformation, modelling practices that other fields could adapt to their own contexts.

Expanding influence beyond academia

Drawing on the broader themes of the TOC, participants also recommended that the new discipline leverage its networks and research outputs to actively shape industry, policy, and civil society practices. This includes forging long-term partnerships with professional bodies, governmental agencies, and community organisations to ensure that inclusive principles are embedded in real-world energy transition strategies. By cultivating visible cross-sector collaborations and producing policy-relevant research grounded in feminist and intersectional methodologies, the discipline could influence norms and decision-making far beyond university settings. Such outward-facing engagement would not only reinforce the discipline's relevance but also ensure that its inclusive ethos has measurable impact across the wider energy ecosystem. (Table 10 summarises the recommendations)

Table 10 Recommendations - TOC for Women in Energy in HE

- Motivate entry and retention: create inclusive pathways, networking spaces, and sustained support systems for women in energy-related academia, with Systems Transition Engineering as a key attractor.
- Boost progression: design the new discipline as a “clean slate” with equitable entry points, transdisciplinary integration, and visible platforms that legitimise women’s leadership as central, not exceptional.
- Institutional transformation: embed inclusivity into structures, values, and processes through mentoring, inclusive leadership development, family-friendly provisions, and redefined metrics of academic success.
- Cultural change: normalise equity as a standard expectation by fostering empathetic, co-designed institutional values and rejecting exclusionary norms and “solutionist” approaches.
- Expand cross-sector influence: leverage networks and research to shape industry, policy, and civil society, embedding feminist and intersectional principles into energy transition strategies.

Working Together to Achieve the Vision of the TOC for Women in Energy in HE

Collaboration emerged as both a strategic necessity and a deeply held value for participants, reflecting their conviction that collective action is indispensable for achieving the TOC’s overarching goal: increasing the participation of women as both students and academics in energy-related disciplines. This extends beyond numerical representation; it concerns the creation of environments where women actively support one another’s growth, share resources, and amplify each other’s voices. Central to this is the reinstatement of the power of women’s perspectives, as one participant explained: *“I believe the female perspective has actually existed before in cultures that it has flourished and it has had power. I believe it’s the Industrial Revolution and maybe capitalism ... that have eaten away at it. And now we are where we are. So, let’s do something!”* (Participant A). Participants saw collaboration as a means of creating the critical mass required to challenge entrenched norms and drive systemic reform, transforming not only who participates in the sector, but also how knowledge is produced and valued.

A recurring theme was the value of empathy and inclusivity as foundational to collaboration. Participants emphasised the need for alternative spaces and forms of networking that are explicitly inclusive places where women can share experiences, co-develop projects, and build supportive communities, free from the competitive and hierarchical norms often dominant in male-oriented academic cultures (*“the ability to connect when we’re each immersed in our disciplines and in our worlds, that we all know very well ... the possibility to find connections is not that great ... So, [take] any chance we get ... and then keep connecting ... do your best!”*; participant A). Such safe, collaborative spaces were seen as vital for fostering mutual support, reducing professional isolation, and enabling candid discussion of the unique challenges women face in energy-related academia. These environments, whether formal or informal, were understood as incubators for innovation, allowing women to take intellectual risks, test new ideas, and develop cross-disciplinary research agendas without fear of exclusion or dismissal.

The creation of the proposed Systems Transition Engineering discipline was widely regarded as a *‘huge opportunity for women to thrive’*. Participants framed its co-design not merely as a technical

or institutional project, but as an exemplar of collaborative practice that could unite women across institutions, sectors, and disciplinary boundaries. This new discipline would be deliberately shaped by intersectional, systems-oriented, and socially responsive values, embedding collaboration into its epistemological foundations. *As one participant explained: “women ... we never have time to be all together and support each other ... [but] ... it's not only empowering, but maybe it's the only way to go ... we should create that critical mass and don't give up on the way ... we shouldn't give up! For the benefit of all” (Participant D).* In addition, Systems Transition Engineering would prioritise transdisciplinary methods, recognising that solving complex energy challenges requires the integration of technical, social, and policy perspectives.

Cross-generational collaboration was described as a key enabler of sustained change. Mentorship, both formal and informal, was seen as essential for helping early-career researchers shadow and learn from mid-career and senior academics, facilitating the transfer of knowledge, skills, and confidence. Such intergenerational relationships were framed as a two-way exchange, where established academics also benefit from the fresh perspectives and innovative approaches of newer entrants. Over time, these relationships could help anchor women's presence in the field, preventing attrition and building a culture of solidarity.

Collaboration was also viewed as extending beyond the academy. Participants stressed the importance of engaging with industry, government, civil society, and professional bodies to amplify women's voices in shaping energy transition policy and practice. By forming cross-sector partnerships, women could pool resources for joint grant applications, share infrastructure, and strengthen their visibility in public debates. A unified voice in policy consultations, public campaigns, and technical committees would not only increase influence over decision-making processes but also reinforce the message that gender equity is central to effective and sustainable energy transitions.

Finally, participants were clear that collaboration must be more than a rhetorical aspiration: it needs to be structurally embedded in academic systems. This means recognising and rewarding collaborative achievements on a par with individual accomplishments, integrating cooperative criteria into promotion frameworks, and designing funding mechanisms that incentivise shared leadership. Participants acknowledged that collaboration is not without challenges. Building trust, sharing credit equitably, and navigating institutional politics require conscious and sustained effort. Nevertheless, they were unequivocal that the journey toward a more equitable academic and energy landscape must be a shared one, underpinned by a commitment to mutual support, inclusivity, and collective success.

Table 11 Collaborating for the TOC Vision for Women in Energy in HE

Collaboration as necessity and value: collective action is essential for increasing women's participation, amplifying voices, and building critical mass to challenge entrenched norms.

Inclusive and empathetic spaces: safe, non-hierarchical environments enable women to share experiences, co-develop projects, and innovate free from exclusionary cultures.

Systems Transition Engineering as exemplar: its co-design embodies collaborative, intersectional, and transdisciplinary values that model new ways of knowledge production.

Cross-generational mentorship: reciprocal relationships between early-career and senior academics sustain participation, transfer knowledge, and build solidarity.

Cross-sector partnerships: collaboration with industry, government, and civil society strengthens women's influence on energy policy and ensures gender equity is embedded in transition strategies.

8. Appendix

Workshop Whiteboard frames

Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition

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